

**The International Rice Research Institute
Annual Report 1969**

INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE Annual Report 1969

IRRI

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Contents

vi	BOARD OF TRUSTEES
vii	PERSONNEL
ix	ABOUT THIS REPORT
1	DIRECTOR'S INTRODUCTION
8	CROP WEATHER
9	CHEMISTRY
10	Grain protein
12	Protein metabolism
14	Rice quality
17	Starch synthesis
17	Biochemistry of planthopper damage
18	Seed germination
21	MULTIPLE CROPPING
22	Varietal selection
23	Crop management
27	Intensification of cropping
30	Weed control
30	Insect management
31	Economic evaluation
35	SOIL MICROBIOLOGY
36	Nitrogen fixation by rice
40	Nitrogen fixation by aquatic plants
41	Nitrogen fixation in legumes
41	Nitrogen transformation
42	Mineral transformations
44	Organic matter transformations
45	Pesticide residues
47	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS
48	Production of rice in Asia
48	Economic analysis of nitrogen response
51	Barriers to higher yield and farm income
57	Water management
66	Aggregate output growth
69	AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING
70	Field machinery
74	Drying and processing
79	Test and evaluation
81	Economics of mechanization
85	AGRONOMY
86	Nitrogen response in irrigated rice
90	Practices for irrigated rice
95	Rainfed paddy culture
101	Upland rice
104	Drought tolerance

105	Varietal adaptation to water conditions
107	STATISTICS
108	Estimating stem borer damage
112	Sampling in broadcast plots
113	Sampling to determine leaf area
115	Replanting dead hills
115	Determining yield in spacing trials
116	Soil heterogeneity
119	Growth durations and varietal comparisons
121	PLANT PATHOLOGY
122	Blast
123	Sheath blight
127	Bacterial blight
132	Vectors of virus diseases
133	Epidemiology of tungro
139	Improved tungro screening method
144	Screening for resistance to virus diseases
145	Combining disease resistance
147	VARIETAL IMPROVEMENT
148	Breeding program
158	Drought tolerance and upland yield
159	Rice germ plasm bank
160	Genetics and cytogenetics
163	ENTOMOLOGY
164	Varietal resistance to insects
170	Insecticides
179	Integrated control of insects
183	Insect ecology
188	Identification of rice insects
189	SOIL CHEMISTRY
190	Chemical kinetics of problem soils
194	Varietal resistance to injurious soils
199	Zinc deficiency
202	Nitrogen losses in flooded soils
204	Kinetics of hydrogen sulfide
207	PLANT PHYSIOLOGY
208	Effect of CO ₂ on spikelet formation
209	Temperature and growth
211	Photosynthesis
212	Screening test for drought resistance
215	Photoperiod
216	Screening for low temperature tolerance
217	Wind damage to leaves
218	Autecology of <i>Scirpus maritimus</i> L.
221	RICE PRODUCTION TRAINING & RESEARCH
232	OTHER ACTIVITIES
243	INDEX

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*Left during the year.

About this report

This is the 11th annual report of the International Rice Research Institute since it was founded in 1960. The major financial supporters of IRRI are the Ford Foundation, The Rockefeller Foundation, U.S. Agency for International Development, The Overseas Development Administration (U.K.), the International Development Research Centre (Canada), and the Japanese government. This report covers work done during the 1972 calendar year.

The thumb index on the back cover provides quick access to any research section. To use it, bend the book in half and follow the margin index to the page with the black edge marker.

Data in the report are given in metric units, e.g. "t/ha" means metric tons per hectare. Unless otherwise stated, control means untreated control, grain yield is calculated as rough rice at 14 percent moisture, and protein content is calculated as a percentage of brown rice at 14 percent moisture. A single asterisk (*) means significant at the 5 percent level, a double asterisk (**) means significant at the 1% level, *but* if value for a control is given, a single asterisk means significantly different from the control at the 5% level and a double asterisk means significantly different from the control at the 1% level.

The report frequently mentions three fundamental types of rice culture. Upland culture means rice grown without irrigation in fields without bunds. Rainfed paddy culture means rice grown without irrigation but in fields that are banded to impound rainfall. Irrigated or flooded culture means rice grown with irrigation in banded fields.

Director's introduction

The 1972 crop year was marked by an unusual combination of heavy rains and severe drought not only in the Philippines but also in many other rice-growing countries of Asia. In July and August, the Philippines experienced unprecedented rains and floods which damaged thousands of hectares of rice. The poor rainfall in October and November adversely affected rice production on rainfed lowland and upland fields. Drought also significantly reduced yields in India, Thailand, Bangladesh, and Indonesia. The general shortage of rice in 1972 shows that in spite of the availability of improved rice technology, the production on a large portion of the rice land in Asia continues to be greatly influenced by adverse weather conditions particularly drought.

The limited acceptance of IR22 and IR24 which possess a high yield potential and excellent grain quality demonstrated once again that disease and insect resistance is an indispensable characteristic which must be incorporated in new varieties to ensure their widespread dissemination. On the other hand, IR20, which has somewhat lower yield potential but possesses a broad spectrum of disease and insect resistance, rapidly spread to many new areas including the Philippines, South Vietnam, and Bangladesh, where it is now the most popular variety. In 1972, the Bangladesh government imported about 7,000 tons of IR20 seed from the Philippines, which is the largest consignment of rice seeds ever imported by any country. IR20 has also begun to make an impact in Ceylon and India. Although IR24 has the limitation of being susceptible to several diseases and insects, it produced 11 t/ha, the highest yield ever recorded in our experimental plots. It has good combining ability in cross-combinations and some of the most promising selections now being evaluated by IRRI inherit their high yield potential from IR24.

The institute will probably continue to name some selections as varieties if they show special promise in more than one country. Although the IRRI varieties with improved plant type have found acceptance over wide areas, even more important accomplishments of the institute, however, are the introduction of improved genetic materials into national research programs, the development of communication networks among rice scientists, the training of scientific staff, and the upgrading of research and extension programs in many countries throughout the world. In 1972 alone, more than 10,000 seed samples of institute's breeding lines and varietal collection were supplied to 69 countries. Many genetic lines developed at IRRI but not named by the institute were released as varieties in other countries. A total of 19 IRRI selections have now been named and released for commercial cultivation by different nations.

In spite of the high yield potential of new varieties only about 15 percent of the rice land in South and Southeast Asia is planted to high yielding varieties developed at IRRI and by national programs. The institute clearly recognizes that susceptibility to diseases and insects is a strong constraint to further extension of the new technology. Our crossing program was greatly expanded

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

in 1972 to combine diverse sources of resistance to major diseases and insects. A total of 1,000 new crosses were made during the year. Selections with improved plant type and excellent grain quality, which combine resistance to blast, bacterial leaf blight, tungro virus, grassy stunt virus, brown planthopper, and green leafhopper, are now available. Among selections in advanced stages of testing, IR1529-680-3 appears to be particularly promising. It gave the highest overall yield in replicated trials under lowland as well as rainfed conditions at several locations. It is a cross between IR24 and a progeny of Sigadis/2 × Taichung Native 1. IR1529-680-3 has excellent grain quality and is resistant to blast, bacterial leaf blight, bacterial streak, and green leafhopper, and is moderately resistant to tungro. It is susceptible to brown planthoppers, however. The seed of this selection was multiplied for extensive trials and possible release. Three other improved lines with special merits are IR1514A-E666, IR1541-76-3-3, and IR442-2-58. The IR1541 and IR1514A lines have higher resistance to diseases and insects than IR1529-680-3, and the IR442 line is adapted to growing under upland as well as deep water (up to 60 cm) conditions.

Preliminary evaluation of IRRI selections under a cooperative project in Egypt has shown exciting possibilities. The entire commercial rice crop grown in Egypt is of japonica type but the performance of IR22 and its sister line, IR579-48-1-2, was so encouraging that the Egyptian government has decided to begin an aggressive program for their commercial introduction in the country. IR667-98, which was named Tongil in Korea last year, was commercially grown during the year on 202,000 hectares, about 17 percent of the rice land in that country. The higher yield potential of Tongil compared with local japonica varieties is primarily due to its resistance to lodging. The development of Tongil has shown that the semidwarf plant type introduced in recent years in the tropics can also contribute to the improvement of the yield potential of temperate rice.

Lack of adequate and controlled water supply is another major barrier to attaining high yields. Farmers are hesitant to invest in inputs for rainfed rice because of the uncertainty of rainfall and of prospects of return on their investment. The applied research project on rainfed lowland and upland rice farms started in Central Luzon in 1971 in cooperation with the Philippine government furnished valuable information. The results of more than 100 trials on farmers' fields during 1972 confirmed that yields of 4 t/ha can be obtained under rainfed conditions by using an improved package of practices which include new high-yielding varieties, adequate fertilization, and insect and weed control. The varieties differed greatly in their performance under moisture stress and the improved package of practices greatly reduced the impact of drought on rainfed rice yields. For example, nitrogen application in combination with weed control was found to partially offset the adverse effect of drought. In addition to management practices, the availability of credit, improved mobility of extension workers, and training of extension workers were the other major contributing factors to increased yields under rainfed conditions.

The plant pathologists and entomologists continued to develop improved sources of multiple resistance to insects and diseases and to improve screening techniques for use in breeding programs. A simple method developed for field inoculation of plant material with bacterial leaf blight consists of clipping

leaves with a pair of scissors dipped in the bacterial suspension. This technique has facilitated rapid and large-scale screening of breeding material against this disease.

Detailed investigations on sheath blight, a disease which is becoming increasingly important in Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, and several other countries, showed that a high level of varietal resistance to the disease is available but the reaction is influenced by environmental factors and age of the plant. Varieties resistant in the seedling stage may not be resistant at the adult stage in the field. Therefore, resistance must be evaluated in the field. The discovery of the perfect stage of the causal organism in nature showed that the sclerotium may not be the only source of infection. Various methods of screening varieties for resistance have been evaluated and among them field inoculation with sclerotia appears to be the most efficient.

A major advance in the chemical control of insects was the development of the concept of placing insecticides about 3 cm below the soil surface near the roots of transplanted seedlings. In several experiments conducted during the year one such treatment protected the plants during the entire crop duration. That level of insect control can otherwise be obtained only by applying granular insecticides every 3 or 4 weeks. The prolonged effect of applying insecticide in the root zone apparently results from reduced exposure of the insecticide to sunshine, heat, and aerobic bacteria, and from reduced volatilization. A practical method of insecticide placement will have to be developed before it can be recommended for commercial adoption.

Studies by agricultural economists show that inadequate weed control methods on many farms sharply reduce the yield response to fertilizer and the economic benefits of high yielding varieties. Soil microbiologists found that the cheap herbicide 2,4-D which is rapidly becoming popular for controlling annual weeds in transplanted rice is biodegradable and nonpersistent both in lowland and upland soils. Probably the most significant results of herbicide research by the agronomy department was the identification of BASF 3510 (Bentazon) as a potentially inexpensive herbicide for controlling the perennial sedge *Scirpus maritimus* without visible toxicity to the rice plant.

Cereal chemists and plant breeders continued studies aimed at genetic improvement of grain protein and collected basic information on nutritive value of rices with varying protein contents. Various indices of protein quality showed consistent increases in percentage of utilizable protein with an increase in protein content in milled rices containing up to 10 percent protein. Also, increase in the protein content of the rice grain from the usual 7 percent to 9 or 10 percent did not have any adverse effect on the cooking and eating quality of rice. Among several thousand varieties analyzed for lysine, two varieties consistently showed 0.5 percentage point higher lysine content in grain protein in two crops.

Injurious soil conditions limit rice yields over vast areas. Some of the problems can be ameliorated by soil and water management and by heavy fertilization but the cost is often prohibitive. Soil chemists discovered striking differences in varietal resistance to such adverse factors as iron and phosphorus deficiency, manganese, aluminum, and iron toxicity, alkalinity, and salinity. Several selections and varieties have been identified that possess tolerance to one or more of these adverse soil conditions. Thus, a considerable amount of

basic information has been gathered to launch a breeding program to combine the resistance of these varieties to adverse soil conditions with other desirable characters to produce genetic lines that may be well suited to injurious soils.

Results further confirmed that zinc is becoming an important yield-limiting factor on large areas of soils well supplied with major plant nutrients and with water. Soil chemists diagnosed zinc deficiency as the yield-limiting factor on more than 47,000 hectares in Agusan del Norte, Philippines, which have long remained uncultivated. Dipping the seedlings in a 2 percent suspension of zinc oxide in water before transplanting—a treatment costing only about US\$1.00 per hectare—has enabled farmers to obtain yields of 4 t/ha without any fertilizers.

In continuation of previous work indicating greater nitrogen fixation activity in planted soils than in unplanted soils, microbiologists discovered that large amounts of molecular nitrogen were present in submerged soils planted to rice. Also, a nitrogen-fixing bacterium was isolated from the rhizosphere. These results suggest that the rice plant may transport atmospheric nitrogen to the rhizosphere for microbial fixation.

In work aimed at discovering new avenues of increasing the yield potential of the rice plant, studies in crop physiology confirmed that CO₂ enrichment before flowering increased yield by 30 percent by increasing grain number and grain weight and further demonstrated that the critical time for increasing grain number and hence grain yield ranges from 33 days to 14 days before flowering under Los Baños conditions. In the search for varieties that have high photosynthetic rates, more than 300 varieties were screened for net assimilation rate which is positively correlated with relative growth rate and leaf photosynthetic rate. The net assimilation rate varied by nearly 100 percent among varieties. Other data indicated that nitrogen content per unit of leaf area is the major internal parameter affecting photosynthetic rate of a single rice leaf and that this criterion might be used for differentiating varieties for photosynthetic rate.

Research on cropping systems led to the elucidation of significant principles regarding the effect of crop combinations on insect and weed populations. When peanuts were interplanted with corn under conditions of heavy corn borer infestation, the population of corn borer larvae was one-sixth of that in corn planted without peanuts. Similar findings in the area of weed control showed substantial increases in the grain yield of an early corn variety when mung bean was interplanted because mung bean successfully reduced weed growth without competing severely with corn.

More intensive cropping practices necessary to increase yields and incomes, particularly those of small farmers in the developing countries have increased interest in the mechanization of agriculture with small low-powered machines. Research in the engineering department indicates that many tasks in the production and processing of rice are suitable for small-scale mechanization, provided the proper machinery designs are made available to local manufacturers. A highlight of the year's activities in the engineering department was the release and rapid commercialization in the Philippines of the design for a small 5-hp to 7-hp power tiller. The machine can be manufactured with locally available materials. It has found wide acceptance among smaller farmers because of its simple design, ease of maintenance, and low cost. Commercial manufacturers produced more than 800 tillers in the Philippines during the last 4 months of the year. The tiller is now being evaluated in nine Asian countries under the institute's cooperative testing program. Other machinery designs which were

released for commercial production include an inexpensive bellows-type pump for low-lift irrigation, a multihopper seeder for lowland rice, and a 1-ton batch-type drier which can use either an oil burner or a rice hull furnace as the heat source.

A study is being conducted at the farm level in cooperation with institutes in six Asian countries to identify the constraints to higher yield and some of the socio-economic problems associated with the introduction of new technology. Preliminary results indicate that even in the better irrigated areas chosen for this study, there is a wide variation in the performance of the new rice technology. Yields in many locations fall well below what appears to be the potential based upon experimental results.

The institute continued to stimulate cooperative research and strengthen its links with national programs to further its goal of increasing rice production in different countries. Several new country projects were begun. A comprehensive project was started with the support of the U.S. Agency for International Development to assist with rice and multiple cropping research in Indonesia. Another project was initiated with USAID support to assist the Philippine government with its crop production program. A project on rice processing and storage in Ceylon and one on rice breeding in Egypt were undertaken during 1972. Both projects were funded by the Ford Foundation. A contract was signed with the government of Indonesia to strengthen research at Sukamandi Research Station in Indonesia. The continuing projects in India, Sri Lanka, and Indonesia made satisfactory progress. The project in Bangladesh which was interrupted by war in 1971 has been reactivated and negotiations are under way to expand the project.

The institute started a regional project for the collection and preservation of rice germ plasm. The institute staff participated in field collections in Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Khmer Republic and added more than 4,000 varieties to the institute's holdings.

Dr. R. R. Harwood joined as head of the multiple cropping program in February.

STAFF CHANGES

Mr. H. M. Beachell retired as head of the varietal improvement department and is now working in the USAID project in Indonesia. Dr. G. S. Khush, plant breeder, took over as head of the varietal improvement department.

Dr. T. H. Wickham joined as associate agricultural economist in January.

Dr. M. R. Vega joined the institute in March as assistant director, the position earlier held by Dr. D. S. Athwal, who is now the associate director.

Dr. Ralph W. Cummings succeeded Dr. Robert F. Chandler, Jr. as director in June but left IRRI in November.

Two Japanese scientists, Mr. C. Kaneda, a plant breeder, and Dr. Y. Ohno, a plant physiologist, whose services were provided to the institute by the Japanese government for a 2-year period, left during the year. Dr. Masaki Hara, a plant physiologist, who is also supported by the Japanese government, joined during the year.

Dr. K. A. Gomez was promoted from associate statistician to statistician and Mr. F. M. Salacup, treasurer, assumed the responsibilities of executive officer, as well.

The institute staff in international programs comprises 21 persons, 11 of whom joined this year. Their names are listed elsewhere in this report.

TRUSTEES Dr. Noboru Yamada completed his term of appointment.

FINANCES During 1972 the institute received cash grants amounting to \$4,214,910.

The Ford Foundation gave \$1,229,260. Of this amount \$750,000 was toward the operating and capital expenditures of the institute. The remainder was in support of the rice research and development programs in four countries: Ceylon—\$133,550 as part of a 6-year grant for the rice production project and another \$142,000 as part of a new 2-year grant for the project on rice processing and marketing; Indonesia—\$128,500 which is part of a 2-year grant for accelerated rice research program; India—\$44,000 which is part of a 13-month grant for the services of a plant pathologist; Egypt—\$31,210 which is part of a 2-year grant for the services of a project specialist with the Arid Lands Agricultural Program in the Middle East.

The Rockefeller Foundation contributed \$810,745 during 1972. This amount included \$750,000 for the operating and capital expenditure needs of the institute, of which \$606,676 was received in cash and the balance represented the value of the foundation's manpower contribution to the institute. The Rockefeller Foundation released \$23,400 as part of a 3-year grant in support of the experimental program to identify and demonstrate techniques for increasing the productivity of disadvantaged Asian rice farmers, \$19,620 as part of a grant for the collection of the world's germ plasm of rice, and \$17,725 as part of a grant in support of the joint Ph.D. training program with the Indian Agricultural Research Institute.

From various grants, the U.S. Agency for International Development released a total of \$1,532,237 in 1972. The institute received \$996,733 during the year for its operating and capital expenditures and \$271,298 in support of the project entitled "Research on Farm and Equipment Power Requirements for the Production of Rice and Associated Food Crops in the Far East and South Asia." Since 1967 a contract between the institute and USAID has supported a project for the acceleration of rice research and training program in India. During the year the institute received \$140,000 for this project. Since 1971 a contract with USAID has supported a project to help the government of Vietnam accelerate rice research for a 2-year period with a budget of \$150,000 in addition to a budget of VN\$1,800,000 which is managed by the USAID mission in Saigon. In 1972, \$43,916 was reimbursed to the institute. Since February 1972, a contract between the institute and the USAID has supported the accelerated development and utilization of improved technology in agriculture in Indonesia with a budget of \$398,000 in addition to a budget of Rp.400,000,000 which is managed by the USAID mission in Djakarta for a period of 18 months. In 1972, \$22,659 was reimbursed to the institute. Since July 1972 a contract between the institute and USAID supported an intensified crop production and extension program in the Philippines for 2 years with a budget of \$85,000 in addition to a budget of P92,400 which is managed by the USAID mission in Manila. In 1972, \$21,844 was released to the institute. USAID contributed toward the training program of the institute by supporting scholars from various countries where USAID has active programs. The institute received \$20,000 for this purpose this year. The USAID mission in Bangladesh provided \$26,000 to finance the training of staff from Bangladesh Rice Research Institute to be carried out at IRRI and at other institutions selected by IRRI. During 1972, \$15,787 was released to IRRI.

The Overseas Development Administration of the United Kingdom gave \$360,207 toward the institute's varietal improvement program.

The International Development Research Centre of Canada gave \$150,407. As part of a 2-year grant to the institute for the multiple cropping research in the Philippines in cooperation with the University of the Philippines, College of Agriculture, IDRC released \$110,200 in 1972. The Centre made another grant to the institute for research on changes in rice farming in Asia and released \$40,207 to the institute in 1972 for this purpose.

The Japanese government gave \$113,694 in 1972 toward the training program of the institute and toward the purchase of equipment required for the research activities of the institute.

In 1972 the Netherlands government gave \$90,950 as part of a 5-year grant for the institute's project for regional station development in Indonesia.

In 1967 the institute entered into a contract with the U.S. National Institutes of Health to study ways to increase the protein and essential amino acids of the rice grain through plant breeding. During 1972, \$49,803 was reimbursed to the institute.

The names of other donors along with the area supported and the amount received during 1972 are given below.

Imperial Chemical Industries, weed control, \$5,000.

Ciba-Geigy, herbicide research, \$4,000.

Potash Institute of North America, long term fertility experiments, \$1,100.

International Potash Institute, long term fertility experiments, \$1,100.

Stauffer Chemical Co., rice pest control, \$2,000.

Chevron Chemical International, entomology research, \$2,000.

Shell Chemical Co. (Phil.) Inc., applied variety-fertilizer trials, \$1,484.

Upjohn, Inc., herbicide research, \$1,200.

Hoechst Philippines, Inc., herbicide research, \$1,186.

Gulf Research and Development Co., herbicide research \$1,000.

Monsanto Co., herbicide research, \$750.

During the year the Australian government started the construction of a phytotron at Los Baños at an estimated cost of approximately \$900,000. Upon its completion the phytotron will be turned over to the institute.

Crop weather

During 1972, 2,474 mm of rain fell compared with a 6-year average of 1,895 mm. The most striking difference between 1972 and previous

years was the amount of rain in July and August. This year 825 mm of rain fell in July as against 342 mm in July 1971 and 224 mm for the 6-year average for the month. In August, 312 mm of rain fell in 1972 as against 61 mm in 1971 and 208 mm for the 6-year average. The July rainfall was 300 mm more than the previous record for July which was set in 1923.

October, November, and December had less rain than last year or than the average of the past 6 years.

As a result of heavy rains in July and August, widespread floods occurred in Central Luzon and delayed planting of rice. The drought conditions in October and December which occurred during the reproductive and ripening stages of the crop caused significant yield reductions in rainfed paddy rice. Most upland rice planted in late May or early June was not affected by flooding. Upland rice also escaped the drought because most upland varieties are early maturing.

Solar radiation values were generally lower in 1972 than the average for previous 6 years particularly during the ripening period (November and December) of the late-planted wet season crop.

A tropical depression occurred on July 25. It had a maximum velocity of 56 kph, but caused no significant damage to either the dry season crop which was harvested in May or June or to the wet season crop which was very young.

Solar radiation and rainfall (three-point moving weekly average) at IRRI, 1972 and 1966-71. Shaded area shows standard deviation of the 5-year rainfall average.

Chemistry

Various indexes of protein quality showed that in milled rices that have less than 10 percent protein consistent increases in percentage of utilizable protein occur with an increase in protein content. Divergent results occur in rices that have higher protein levels. Grains in the bottom branch of a panicle tended to have higher protein content than the rest of the grains on the same panicle. Among 38 varieties selected from the world collection of rice varieties by dye binding capacity, only two consistently showed 0.5 percentage point higher lysine content in brown rice over two seasons. □ In a study of nitrogen metabolism of rices differing in grain protein content, root glutamate dehydrogenase and percentage nitrogen of the leaf blades were highest 4 weeks after transplanting. Among rices with similar yields, high protein rice translocated more leaf nitrogen to the developing grains. Developing grains of high protein rice accumulated protein faster, regardless of yield. □ Criteria for processed rice products, such as flaked parboiled rice, fermented rice cake, and rice noodle, were studied to pinpoint factors that affect the eating quality of boiled rice. Amylose content was verified to be negatively correlated with the water content of steeped rough rice which in turn determined volume of puffed parboiled rice. □ In studies of starch synthesis the molecular weights of primed soluble starch synthetase from rice leaves, determined by disc electrophoresis and gel chromatography, indicated that this enzyme existed in at least two oligomeric forms. □ In studies of seed dormancy we found dormancy was consistently associated with a decrease in peroxidase activity, particularly in the hull fraction. Germination was accompanied by an increase in activity of phytase, lipase, and β -1,3-glucanase in the endosperm fraction.

GRAIN PROTEIN

About 20,000 rice samples from breeding and genetic studies were analyzed for Kjeldahl protein in 1972 as part of a cooperative program to improve the protein content of rice by 2 percentage points. A Udy cyclone mill was found suitable for grinding 2-g to 5-g samples from yield trials for protein analysis. We continued to use a Wig-L-Bug amalgamator for grinding 10 grains from the pooled harvest from individual plants in pedigree rows.

Protein quality. Nitrogen balance studies in young rats were performed on seven milled rices and one sample of brown rice by Dr. B. O. Eggum, Agricultural Research Laboratory, Copenhagen, Denmark. Protein content was calculated as $N \times 6.25$ to make the nitrogen level similar to that of other proteins. The rats were fed a constant amount of dry matter (10 g) and N (150 mg) every day. True digestibility (% of dietary N absorbed) was high in all samples (Table 1), and correlated with lysine content ($r = 0.966^{**}$). Biological value (% of absorbed N retained) tended to decrease with protein content, but was exceptionally high for BPI-76-1. Net protein utilization (true digestibility $\times$ biological value/100) was positively correlated with lysine content ($r = 0.832^*$). Utilizable protein (net protein utilization $\times$ protein content/100) was positively correlated with protein content ($r = 0.988^{**}$). The protein

content of milled rice and lysine content of protein were negatively correlated ($r = -0.785^*$).

The brown rice of IR480-5-9 had the same value for net protein utilization as the milled rice, but a lower true digestibility and a higher biological value.

Since the amount of utilizable protein (amount of protein multiplied by quality of protein) is ultimately the most important measure of the nutritive value of cereals, we compared the ability of four quality indexes to estimate utilizable protein (Table 2). Chemical score (lysine level in rice protein as a percentage of lysine content of 5.44 g/16 g N in the revised reference amino acid pattern) and the three other indexes of protein quality based on rat feeding trials gave similar values for samples with 10 percent protein or less. But relative nutritive value showed a levelling off of utilizable protein of milled rice above 10 percent protein. By contrast, nitrogen growth index and net protein utilization still reflected an increase in utilizable protein, with nitrogen growth index closest to the chemical score. The assay for nitrogen growth index was done by Dr. R. Bressani (Instituto de Nutricion de Centro America y Panama, Guatemala) on five male and five female rats fed *ad libitum* rice diets with protein levels of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 percent for 4 weeks. The growth response of the rats was linear with protein intake. The assay for net protein utilization by Eggum was done at a higher dietary protein level, 8.24 percent, but at a constant caloric intake. Presumably the reported dependence of net protein utilization on protein content may be reduced by using a restricted constant caloric intake.

Dr. D. M. Hegsted (Harvard University, U.S.A.) assayed relative nutritive value using diets with 28, 56, and 84 percent rice and five male rats per diet for a 3-week feeding period. The computed regression lines had different intercepts and lines had to be drawn with a common intercept. Relative nutritive value is the ratio of the slope of weight gain with protein intake for the rice sample to the slope of weight gain with protein intake for lactalbumin. Relative nutritive value of lactalbumin is 100 percent. The raw data indicated that rats fed the 84-percent rice diet had a less proportional weight

Table 1. Nitrogen balance in rats^a of milled rices differing in protein content (B. O. Eggum, Agr. Res. Lab., Denmark).

Rice sample	Protein ^b (%)	True digestibility (%)	Biological value (%)	Net protein utilization (%)
<i>Milled rice</i>				
Intan	5.9	100.1	75.2 ^c	75.3
IR8	7.3	96.2	73.1 ^c	70.3
IR8	9.5	95.4	68.4	65.2
IR22	10.1	98.5	69.7	68.7
IR1103-15-8	11.3	95.9	74.3	71.1
IR480-5-9	11.7	94.5	67.9	64.2
BPI-76-1	14.7	94.4	70.1	66.2
<i>Brown rice</i>				
IR480-5-9	10.6	90.8	70.8	64.2
LSD (5%)		1.90	2.17	2.54

^aCorrected for metabolic and endogenous N in feces and urine using a diet of 4% egg protein which is 100% utilized. ^b $N \times 6.25$.

^cCorrected for the lower N level in the diet.

gain than those fed lower protein diets. The resulting lower slopes of the growth curve when the 84-percent rice treatment was included may explain the levelling off in utilizable protein based on relative nutritive value of milled rices with more than 10 percent protein. By contrast, rats fed lactalbumin showed a linear growth response with protein intake up to a level of 10 percent protein. Bressani also found a similar lower growth response at high protein levels in the determination of nitrogen growth index. It may be preferable to run assays for relative nutritive values at similar protein levels rather than at similar rice levels for the different rice varieties to obtain results comparable with net protein utilization and nitrogen growth index since protein may not be the factor limiting growth in high protein diets.

Addition of 0.2 percent lysine and 0.1 percent threonine improved relative nutritive values but the increase was significant only in two out of three milled rice samples.

Protein variability within a panicle. We examined the protein content of individual grains from the top, middle, and bottom branches of two panicles of IR8 plants that received 0 or 120 kg/ha N. Grains in the bottom branch had higher protein content than those in the upper branches (Table 3). The grains from the fertilized plot had higher protein content than those from the unfertilized plot. The coefficient of variation among grains within a branch was 10.0 percent for unfertilized plants and 7.0 percent for fertilized plants. The absence of correlation between protein content and grain weight within a panicle, particularly in the fertilized plants (Table 3), indicates that a part of the starch was replaced by an equal weight of protein in the higher protein grains.

Lysine content of brown and milled rice. Our previous studies of low protein and high protein grain samples indicated that lysine content of protein tends to level off in samples that have more than 10 percent protein. To determine the exact nature of the regression equation, the lysine content of protein in brown and milled rices of about 10 samples of IR22 and of IR480-5-9 rices was assayed without replication. Protein content and lysine level in protein had a curvilinear relationship (fig. 1). Samples of the

Table 2. Utilizable protein of milled rices differing in protein content based on chemical score and on three protein quality indexes in rats.

Sample	Protein ^a (%)	Utilizable protein (%) based on			
		Chemical score	Relative nutritive value ^b	Nitrogen growth index ^c	Net protein utilization ^d
Intan	5.8	4.5	4.2	4.5	4.4
IR8	7.5	5.0	5.5	5.5	5.3
IR22	9.8	7.1	7.2	—	6.7
IR8	10.0	6.9	6.5	6.9	6.5
IR1103-15-8	11.3	7.7	7.2	—	8.0
IR480-5-9	11.5	7.6	6.3	—	7.4
BPI-76-1	14.9	8.8	7.4	8.3	9.6

^aN × 6.25. ^bSlope ratio assay with lactalbumin as 100%. Dr. D. M. Hegsted, Harvard Univ., U.S.A. ^cSlope rate assay with casein as 75%. Dr. R. Bressani, Instituto de Nutricion de Centro America y Panama, Guatemala. ^dValues from Dr. B. O. Eggum, Agr. Res. Lab. Denmark.

same variety that had similar protein levels showed a maximum range of lysine content of 0.3 g/16.8 g N in brown rice protein and of 0.5 g/16.8 g N in milled rice protein. The greater range in milled rice probably results from differences in degree of milling. Since the LSD (5%) for the mean of duplicate lysine determinations was 0.3 g/16.8 g N, the differences in lysine content above 10 percent protein are probably not statistically significant. Samples with more than 13 percent protein, however, tended to have increasing lysine contents as indicated by the regression curve (fig. 1). These samples have low grain weights so the higher lysine content may reflect a reduced contribution of endosperm protein to brown rice protein.

Our study also confirmed that brown rice protein has higher lysine content than milled rice protein. Studies last year showed that bran

Table 3. Protein content and weight of single grains of IR8 as affected by the branch position in two panicles of plants grown at two fertilizer levels.

Branch position	Grains (no.)	Brown rice protein (%)		Rough rice wt (mg)
		Range	Mean ^a	
<i>0 kg/ha N</i>				
Top	6.5	6.5 to 8.2	7.1 b	27.7
Middle	14.0	6.5 to 9.6	7.6 b	30.6
Bottom	3.5	7.8 to 9.5	8.5a	32.4
<i>120 kg/ha N</i>				
Top	8.5	7.9 to 9.3	8.6 b	29.2
Middle	11.5	7.3 to 10.0	8.5 b	29.9
Bottom	5.0	9.5 to 11.0	10.0a	29.9

^aAny two means under the same nitrogen level followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

1. Relation between protein content of brown and milled rices and the lysine content of the protein of IR22 and IR480-5-9.

protein (embryo and aleurone layers) had 5.5 to 5.8 percent lysine, which explains the differences in lysine content of the protein of milled and brown rices.

High lysine rices. Previously we identified 38 rice varieties in the IRRI world collection by dye-binding capacity as having high lysine content. This year, when we analyzed two crops of the 38 varieties for lysine by ion exchange chromatography, we found that only two, ARC 10525 and Kolamba 540, consistently had 0.5 percentage point higher lysine content in both crops than the other 38 varieties. The protein bodies of both varieties also were smaller (1.7 to 2.1 μ) than those of other varieties. Kolamba 540 had small, fine grains and the embryos of the grains contributed up to 4 percent of the weight of the brown rice. Analysis of the protein fractions in brown rice samples from the 1971 wet season showed that Kolamba 540 had a higher albumin content (20%) than IR8 and ARC 10525 (11 to 12%). The lysine content of the prolamin fraction of Kolamba 540 was also higher, 1.9 percent. Albumin of ARC 10525 had 6.1 percent lysine. Disc electrophoregrams of albumin and globulin indicated differences in

the number and mobility of the minor protein bands: 12 to 14 bands were obtained for albumin, and six to eight bands for globulin.

We are seeking variants of ARC 10525 and Kolamba 540 that have 5 percent lysine in brown rice protein by screening grains from about 100 plants by dye-binding capacity (DBC). Preliminary results of single-plant DBC analysis with IR480-5-9 and Kolamba 540 showed that brown rice protein of Kolamba 540 had a higher lysine content than that of IR480-5-9 (fig. 2). An increase of at least 1 percentage point would justify an effort to improve the lysine content of rice so as to be greater than the reproducibility of existing screening methods and the inherent variability in lysine content within a variety.

Protein and grain properties. We continued to study the effects of an increase in protein content on grain properties. Ash and total fiber contents of milled rice of two rices (after removing 10%, by weight, of the bran from brown rice) did not necessarily increase with an increase in protein content of 3 percentage points. Thickness of aleurone layers did not consistently increase either.

PROTEIN METABOLISM

Nitrogen absorption. We studied the nitrogen metabolism of four semidwarf rices differing in grain protein grown in the 1972 dry season in a flooded field fertilized with an application of 120 kg/ha N. The peak activity of root glutamate dehydrogenase in the plants occurred 4 weeks after transplanting when nitrogen absorption was high (fig. 3). A lower peak occurred during panicle formation 10 weeks after transplanting. The nitrogen content of the active leaf blade (the second fully expanded leaf blade) was also highest 4 weeks after transplanting. The activity of nitrate reductase in the leaf blades and roots was low and decreased after transplanting.

The results indicate that glutamate dehydrogenase is the key enzyme in nitrogen uptake in flooded rice, involving the reductive amination of α -ketoglutarate with ammonium ion. In 3-week-old seedlings of all varieties, the highest glutamate dehydrogenase activity per gram of tissue was in the roots, the leaf sheaths, and the leaf blades, in that order. By contrast, nitrate

2. Scattergram of dye-binding capacity and protein content of brown rice of single plants of Kolamba 540 and IR480-5-9.

reductase activity was higher in leaf blades than in roots and leaf sheaths.

Amino acid analysis of a hot 80-percent ethanol extract from IR480-5-9 roots 4 weeks after transplanting showed a three-fold molar ratio of glutamate to aspartate and a slightly higher ratio of glutamine to asparagine. The glutamine-to-glutamate molar ratio was 1.6 and the asparagine-to-aspartate ratio was 1.3, indicating that much glutamate produced by glutamate dehydrogenase was converted to glutamine by glutamine synthetase.

IR480-5-9 had a higher nitrogen content in the active leaf blade shortly after panicle initiation than IR8 (fig. 4). This occurred, however, mainly because the IR480 line accumulated dry matter more slowly. The amount of total dry matter of all four rices at maturity was similar as were rates of nitrogen uptake (fig. 3). Leaf nitrogen analysis, hence, cannot be used for screening rice seedlings for percentage or yield of grain protein. No trend was found between the nitrogen level of the second fully expanded leaf of seedlings 4 weeks after transplanting and grain protein content for 24 semidwarf rices differing in grain protein content.

Nitrogen translocation from leaves to grains. IR480-5-9 and IR160-27-3 had the same grain yield as IR8, while IR1103-15-8 had a lower yield. Brown rice of the IR480 and IR1103 lines had significantly higher protein content than brown rice of IR8. Among the three rices with similar grain yield, IR480-5-9 with 9.45 percent protein, tended to translocate more leaf nitrogen

3. Changes in total nitrogen per hill, root glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH), and nitrate reductase (NR) of leaf blades and roots of IR8, IR480-5-9, IR160-27-3, and IR1103-15-8 plants during growth under flooded conditions, 1972 dry season.

to the developing grains than IR8 which had 7.30 percent protein. The leaf blades of IR480-5-9 also had a lower rate of leucine incorporation during grain development, but higher protease activity than leaves of the rices with average protein content. IR1103-15-8 leaves had the fastest rate of leucine incorporation and the lowest protease activity. But the flag leaves of the four rices had similar rates of photosynthesis 10 days after flowering and of ribulose 1,5-diphosphate carboxylase activity at flowering.

Developing grains of the rices with high protein—IR480-5-9 and IR1103-15-8 (10.8% pro-

tein)—tended to have higher levels of soluble protein, free amino nitrogen, and protease, and a faster rate of leucine incorporation than grains of the IR8 rice with average percentage protein, regardless of grain yield. Presumably, rate of leaf nitrogen breakdown and translocation and rate of protein accumulation in the grain are not necessarily correlated, as indicated by the lower yielding, high protein line IR1103-15-8. Both processes are probably under separate hormonal control. Previous results indicate, however, that in samples from the same cross, nitrogen is translocated faster in high protein rices than in low protein rices primarily because the free amino acid levels in the sap going to the panicle are higher rather than because of a faster rate of sap movement.

Effect of herbicides on seedlings. IRRI agronomists have shown that herbicides, such as benzo-marc and simetryne, applied at sub-herbicial levels from panicle initiation to complete heading, increase grain protein content in fertilized IR22 plants without significantly reducing grain

yield. We are studying the mechanism of this phenomenon with IR22 seedlings. Preliminary results indicate that 2 weeks after being treated with 0.1 kg/ha simetryne or 0.25 kg/ha benzo-marc, 4½-week-old seedlings were greener, taller, and heavier than the untreated control plants under flooded fertilized conditions. The treated plants contained more nitrogen than the untreated ones. Higher levels of these herbicides stunted the growth of seedlings.

RICE QUALITY

Although amylose content is the major influence on the eating quality of milled rice, varieties within a limited range of amylose content may differ in eating quality. In 1971 we found that although boiled waxy rices have similar eating quality, waxy varieties used for rice cakes differ in quality. Since processed rice products offer a means of determining factors other than amylose which contribute to differences in eating quality, a survey was made of quality criteria for some Philippine processed rice products.

Parboiled rice flakes. A factory of *pinipig* or flaked parboiled waxy brown rice preferred Malagkit Sungsong to IR253-16-1 because of Malagkit's characteristic starchy aroma and the extreme tackiness of the hydrated *pinipig* made from it. IR253-16-1 is a waxy IRRI line which has partially replaced Malagkit Sungsong in farmers' fields. *Pinipig*-making consists of steeping rough rice in water, parboiling while continuously mixing the steeped grain in earthen pots over a fire, hand-pounding the parboiled grain, and separating the flakes from the hulls by winnowing. We arranged to have five waxy rices processed in the *pinipig* factory and then we assessed them for stickiness of the hydrated *pinipig* after storage for 3 months. Parboiled flakes from Malagkit Sungsong were much more sticky on wetting than those of all the other rices, except IR833-34-1 (Table 4); the flakes of Malagkit also absorbed more water. The starch-gelatinization temperature of the rices was low except that of Panpet 63 which was high. The brown rice of Malagkit Sungsong was less hard than that of the other rices.

Puffed rice. Caramel-coated puffed waxy and nonwaxy rice (*ampaw*) is a cottage industry in

4. Changes in nitrogen content of active leaf blade and total dry matter of IR8 and IR480-5-9 plants from panicle initiation, 1972 dry season.

Table 4. Properties of raw and flaked parboiled brown rice from five waxy rices.

Variety or line	Raw brown rice		Hydrated <i>pinipig</i>	
	Hardness ^a	Equilibrium water content ^b (%)	Stickiness (g/g hydrated rice ^c)	Water absorbed (g/g <i>pinipig</i>)
Malagkit Sungsong	22.3	35.2	885	5.0
IR253-16-1	35.2	34.3	148	3.5
IR833-6-2	30.2	35.1	423	4.5
IR833-34-1	35.4	34.0	835	4.6
Panpet 63	35.0	34.0	121	3.8
LSD (5%)	5.0	0.7	171	0.5

^aPercentage retained by 80-mesh sieve after 20 s grinding in a Wig-L-Bug amalgamator. ^bAfter steeping 18 h in water at 25 to 27 °C. ^cUsing the beam balance method of Kurawawa.

the Philippines. In recent years, only *pinipig* has been used for making gun-puffed rice. We subjected parboiled rices differing in amylose content to puffing at 250°C for 16 to 18 seconds. The lower the amylose content was, the greater the expansion in volume (Table 5). The reason may be that waxy and lower amylose rices have a higher equilibrium water content than high amylose rices. Parboiling of steeped grain was done in an autoclave for 14 minutes at 100°C. Since parboiling (*pinipig* making) involves toasting presoaked waxy rice with its absorbed water, waxy rices tend to be more parboiled and to have bigger puffed volume. Puffed volume was verified to be affected directly by degree of parboiling in IR20 and IR833-6-2 samples that were parboiled in sealed containers at different water levels (fig. 5). The higher water absorption of waxy rice may be related to the presence of micropores within the starch granules. Waxy starch granules have a lower absolute density than nonwaxy starch granules which reflects the presence of micropores. Steeped grain of "crumbly" rice, which is almost completely opaque due to loose packing of cell contents, had higher water content (32.7%) than predicted from the 20-percent amylose content (Table 5). Hence, water enters air spaces in opaque portions of nonwaxy rice during steeping and results in a higher water content than in rice with translucent grain.

Fermented rice cake. Several factories that make local yeast-fermented steamed rice cakes

Table 5. Effect of amylose content on water content of steeped brown rice and volume expansion of milled parboiled rice on puffing.

Variety or line	Amylose content ^a (%)	Equilibrium water content ^b (%)	Volume expansion ratio
Malagkit Sungsong	waxy	35.2	2.76
IR833-6-2	waxy	35.1	1.52
IR24	18	30.7	1.29
IR480-5-9	22	30.5	1.25
IR20	26	28.8	1.10
IR22	28	28.8	1.06
LSD (5%)	—	1.0	0.059

^aDry basis. ^bAfter steeping in water at 25 to 27 °C for 18 h.

(*puto*) require intermediate to moderately high amylose rices aged for at least a year. Manufacturers claim that varieties which are no longer commercially grown, like Elon-elon and Binirhen, are better than the presently used varieties like Intan, C4-63G, Wagwag, and IR20. Samples of Elon-elon and Binirhen have intermediate amylose content. A little Intan (intermediate amylose) must be added to C4-63G rice to obtain *puto* with the correct texture. Amylose content presumably affects the texture of steamed rice cake. A sample of wet-milled flour from C4-63G had 7.2 percent protein and 25.5

5. Water content of rough rice during parboiling in relation to volume expansion ratio of puffed milled rice of a nonwaxy (IR20) and a waxy rice (IR833-6-2).

percent amylose (dry basis). Yeast fermentation increased starch damage, as indicated by microscopy and reduced the amylograph peak viscosity of fermented flour compared with unfermented flour. In preliminary studies, the wet-milled flours from different varieties differed in viscosity and gas retention during fermentation.

Rice noodles. Rice was only an incidental ingredient of rice noodles (*bihon*) in a local factory. The main ingredients were cassava or corn starch and white corn grits or fully milled rice. The only requirement for milled rice was a white color, since most local varieties have intermediate to high amylose. Milled rice obtained from the factory had 7.6 percent protein, 28.6 percent amylose (dry basis), and intermediate gelatinization temperature. The wet-milled rice flour has 27.7 percent amylose (dry basis). A sample of rice noodle had 1 percent protein, 95 percent starch, and 35 percent amylose (dry basis). The corn starch had about 35 percent amylose and cassava starch had about 30 percent amylose. Both starches had less than 0.1 percent protein. Cassava starch was preferred since gelatinized root starch provides a more translucent paste than cereal starch. Cassava starch had intermediate gelatinization temperature and showed a high positive amylograph setback.

Digestibility of cooked rice starch. In India, feeding trials on adult humans reportedly showed that cooked Hamsa rice had better digestibility than IR8, as reflected by glucose level in the blood shortly after rice intake. We found that Hamsa has moderately high amylose (25 to 27%), while IR8 has high amylose (above 27%). High amylose rices have less water-soluble amylose in the starch-iodine blue test at 100°C than rices with moderately high amylose. Since it was important to check whether amylose retrogradation in the high amylose samples contributes to its reported lower digestibility, the *in vitro* digestibility of cooked rice of these varieties and of others differing in amylose content was studied using α -amylase from hog pancreas. Our results showed an almost identical digestion curve for Hamsa and IR8 rices as indexed by the reducing sugars released.

Survey of rice varieties. Among 15 Philippine varieties surveyed in the 1972 dry season crop, one was low in amylose content, four were intermediate, four were moderately high, and six were high. C4-63G, IR20, and BPI-76-1 were observed to have moderately high amylose. A survey of Wagwag samples in the local market indicated a range in amylose of 28 to 32 percent (dry basis) and a wide range of gelatinization temperatures. The survey confirmed the use of the term Wagwag in the trade to denote a grain type rather than a variety. Some of the Wagwag samples were probably IR20.

Six samples of rice imported by the Philippines in 1971-72 were analyzed for starch properties. The two samples from Thailand had 29% amylose content (dry basis); the sample from Burma (Emata), 27%; that from Italy, 21%; that from Japan, 22%; and that from China, 30%. All had low gelatinization temperature except the Chinese rice which had intermediate gelatinization temperature.

Samples of Australian rices had low to intermediate amylose content (18.6 to 23.6%) and intermediate or high gelatinization temperature. Samples from two successive crops of the Australian variety Kulu showed 21.7 percent amylose and high gelatinization temperature in the 1968-69 crop, and 23.6 percent amylose and intermediate gelatinization temperature in the 1969-70 crop. Although the latter crop had a lower ambient temperature during grain development than the earlier crop, it had more grains with opaque portions or white core. In Japan, opaque portions are usually associated with high nighttime temperature during grain development.

Screening methods for amylose content. Few breeding programs use the modified amylose test for screening lines for eating quality described in last year's report. Because of the importance of evaluating the eating quality of breeding lines from parents of diverse eating qualities, we are attempting to develop simpler screening tests applicable to breeding lines. The Wig-L-Bug amalgamator produces a powder of essentially amorphous or damaged starch. Damaged starch can absorb complexing agents faster than intact starch granules. Preliminary results

indicate that absorption of iodine, and possibly of Congo red dye, has potential as a screening method for amylose content. Both reagents complex in greater amounts with amylose than with amylopectin.

STARCH SYNTHESIS

Starch synthetase continued to be studied since it is a key enzyme in starch synthesis. The soluble form, although more unstable, is easier to characterize than the form bound to the starch granule which usually loses its activity during separation from its binding with starch. Isozymes of soluble starch synthetase were isolated from 2-week-old IR8 rice plants and purified at 2 to 4°C by homogenization and centrifugation, ammonium sulfate fractionation, diethylaminoethyl cellulose chromatography, and subsequent chromatography on Sephadex G-200 cross-linked dextran or amylopectin-cellulose (1:10 wt/wt). These procedures gave at least a 100-fold purification of the synthetase requiring maltose or maltosaccharide as primer. As shown by analytical polyacrylamide disc gel electrophoresis the primed enzyme was essentially homogeneous (one band) but existed in two active forms with molecular weights of 22 and 67×10^3 as measured by chromatography on Sephadex G-200. The enzyme aggregated during electrophoresis in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate which breaks hydrophobic bonds and mercaptoethanol which breaks disulfide bonds. Five distinct bands were obtained corresponding to molecular weights of 11.5, 20, 35, 50, and 69×10^3 . The molecular weights of these bands were integral multiples of one another within the limits of experimental error, which indicates aggregation of the polypeptide chains into oligomers. There is, therefore, a strong possibility that the enzyme consists of more than one polypeptide chain and that it exists in at least two active oligomeric forms of molecular weights 22 and 67×10^3 . Chromatography of either of these two fractions on Sephadex G-200 allowed the recovery of both oligomers.

Additional fractionation studies indicated that the primed enzyme was precipitated between 15 and 45 percent saturation with

ammonium sulfate, with the highest total and specific activities in the fraction precipitating between 25 and 35 percent saturation. ADP-glucose was found to be a better glucose donor than UDP-glucose for this enzyme. Oyster glycogen was a better primer than amylose, corn amylopectin, or maltose for the primed enzyme.

An enzyme that can synthesize starch in the absence of primer was also isolated from rice leaves and partially purified. It showed a similar aggregation phenomenon to that shown by the primed enzyme but it had a higher molecular weight. UDP-glucose was a better glucose donor for the unprimed enzyme than ADP-glucose. It is possible that the activities of these soluble starch synthetases (primed and unprimed) are controlled by the extent of enzyme aggregation which in turn is affected by factors like pH and concentration of metabolites.

In studies using ammonium sulfate fractionation of soluble starch synthetase of IR8 rice grains at the milky stage, the specific activity was higher in the protein precipitated between 0 to 20 percent saturation than in the protein precipitated between 20 to 40 percent saturation, while no activity was detected in the protein precipitated between 40 to 60 percent saturation.

BIOCHEMISTRY OF PLANTHOPPER DAMAGE

Resistance to brown planthopper. The entomologists and we are studying the biochemistry of resistance to the brown planthopper. We make extractions from resistant and susceptible plants and the entomologists conduct bioassays with the extracts. Initial work on aqueous extracts of leaf-sheath shreds of IR8 and Mudgo $\times$ IR8 plants showed that the active fraction was not a protein. Activity was highest in the neutral fraction, indicating that inhibitors were probably removed with the acid and basic fractions.

We attempted to find a simple way to prepare and extract large samples. The best method was air-drying at 28 to 30°C and grinding the dried material to a 100-mesh powder with a Udy cyclone mill. We compared benzene, petroleum ether (b.p. 40 to 60°C), chloroform, aqueous methanol, aqueous ethanol, aqueous acetone, and water as extractants. Bioassays indicated

6. Changes in the activity per grain of phytase, lipase, and β -1,3-glucanase in IR8 seeds during germination in the light.

that petroleum ether and 50-percent methanol were the best solvents. These two solvents extract different active fractions, since no active fraction soluble in petroleum ether was found in the 50-percent methanol extract. Mudgo $\times$ IR8 possessed the active fraction that is soluble in petroleum ether, but IR8 did not.

Hopperburn. Cooperative studies with entomologists were made on the effect of localization of feeding site of the brown planthopper on the symptoms of hopperburn in seedlings of Tai-chung Native 1. Hopperburn results in browning and drying of plants. Restricting the feeding site to a single leaf blade or to a leaf sheath resulted in the browning of that particular feeding site only, in contrast to the widespread browning that resulted when the whole plant was exposed, starting from the tip of the leaf blades downward to the leaf sheaths. When just the leaf blades or just the leaf sheaths were exposed, hopperburn symptoms were produced more slowly than when the whole plant was exposed to the same number of insects. Rice plants under water stress dried up with little loss in green color.

A 3-cm middle section of rice stem was exposed to the insects until hopperburn symptoms appeared, and the rate of flow of bleeding sap from the pruned stem (by successive cuttings above and below the feeding site of treated and untreated seedlings) was determined. We found that upward flow of sap tended to be slower, relative to the control, only in stems where the feeding site was intact. Presumably insect feeding impeded the upward flow of the sap. Considerable variation, however, was observed among plants in the same treatment. Non-destructive methods of analyses are therefore better for this type of study which involves changes occurring within a week of treatment.

SEED GERMINATION

Phytase, lipase, and glucanase. Earlier studies have shown that activities of phosphatase, esterase, and β -glucosidase in IR8 rice seed increase during germination. A study was made on the specificity of these enzymes to phytin, lipid, and glucan reserves localized in the bran layers of IR8 rice grains during germination in the light. Phytase increased progressively during the first week of germination (fig. 6). Lipase, assayed fluorometrically with 4-methylumbelliferyl butyrate as substrate, showed peak activity 5 to 6 days after germination. The β -1,3-glucanase activity, assayed with laminarin as substrate, showed a large increase by the seventh day of germination.

Grain dormancy. More studies were made on the loss of dormancy in rice grains. Of 10 factors studied, only peroxidase activity showed consistent results. It progressively decreased during loss of dormancy for three varieties. Seven isozymes of peroxidase from brown rice were separated by electrophoresis in 5 percent polyacrylamide gel. All seven decreased in activity during loss of dormancy. The hull contributed a greater portion of the total activity of the grain than the degermed brown rice and embryo in two varieties. In both varieties, peroxidase activity decreased in all grain fractions during loss of dormancy. Since dehulling partially breaks dormancy (regardless of whether or not the hull is included with the germinating brown rice) and pricking brown rice near the embryo

completely breaks dormancy, the hull, seed coat, and aleurone layers probably act as barriers to oxygen diffusion to the embryo by reducing the net oxygen diffusion to the embryo, thus preventing germination. The higher oxygen requirement of the covering structures in dormant grains than in nondormant ones may explain the lower respiration rate observed before visible germination occurs in nondormant grains of two out of three varieties. A high level of salicylhydroxamic acid (10^{-2} M), a known inhibitor of the cyanide insensitive respiration, inhibited the germination of nondormant grains.

Hulls of dormant and nondormant grains of three varieties had similar levels of water-

soluble phenols, but changes in the composition of the phenols were not investigated. Dormant and nondormant H 6 seeds had similar malic acid content. The possibility of diffusion of inhibitors from the embryo was studied with dormant brown rice with pricked portion above or under water. Both samples germinated completely.

Dormant and nondormant H 6 grains produced the same amount of ethylene before visible germination. Gibberellin A_3 even at 10^{-3} M had little effect in breaking dormancy of dormant seeds, while DL-abscisic acid at 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} M started to inhibit the germination of nondormant rice grains.

Multiple cropping

Individual crop varieties were evaluated for possible use in multiple cropping patterns.

Mung varieties that have a range of maturities and plant types and a high level of disease resistance are now available. A yellow-seeded mutant of the Philippine variety MG50-10-A was found which promises to have immediate acceptance in the Philippines for its high seed quality, early maturity, and high yield. □ The value of green vegetable soybeans as an early-maturing high protein crop in multiple cropping systems was demonstrated. Protein production of $9 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ was achieved in a dry season planting. The amount of solar radiation during the growing season had a marked effect on both dry matter production and total protein yields. The early maturing variety Shih Shih served as a model for photoperiod-insensitive types most useful in multiple cropping. □ Using interplanting combinations which are common in the tropics we found that total production was considerably higher when crops were intercropped. The combination of mung and corn not only gives high yield but has distinct advantages for weed control. Yield of corn increased from 2.6 t/ha to 3.1 t/ha when mung was used without any additional weed control. The combination of peanuts and corn markedly decreased corn-borer damage in corn. We have found that many intercropping patterns thus have a high degree of biological stability as well as high yield potential. □ The economic evaluation of rainfed cropping patterns illustrated a wide range of alternatives for farmers whose early rice crop is destroyed by disease or drought. Trials in farmer's fields showed the importance of water control in intensification of cropping. Unless good drainage is possible, upland crops have limited usefulness in low-lying areas during the growing season for rice. Irrigated systems illustrated the potential for increasing a farmer's income by intensification of cropping. At existing price relationships in the Philippines, a high correlation was found between marketable carbohydrates produced by a cropping system and profit.

Table 1. Grain yield of 14 varieties or selections in 12 provinces in the Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)												Mean
	Marin- duque	Panga- sinan	Isabela	Zamboanga del Sur	Pampanga	Leyte	Caga- yan	Sorso- gon	Kalinga- Apayao	Batangas	Tarlac	Laguna ^a	
PB76-TB188	2.0	5.8	2.0	2.8	4.6	6.8	3.9	2.8	4.2	4.9	4.8	5.7	4.2
BPI 121-407	0.7	5.8	1.9	4.3	5.0	6.8	5.5	2.5	6.0	4.3	3.1	7.1	4.4
C4-63 G	1.3	5.8	1.9	3.7	5.0	6.8	5.2	5.1	5.8	4.6	4.9	5.9	4.7
C4-137	1.6	5.8	2.1	3.9	4.5	6.3	3.3	4.9	4.6	4.5	5.2	6.7	4.5
C 12	1.6	5.8	2.2	2.7	4.1	6.3	1.8	5.7	5.3	4.5	4.5	4.9	4.1
IR8	0.9	5.9	2.2	4.7	3.6	7.1	4.3	2.1	5.3	2.8	3.5	6.8	4.1
IR20	2.2	4.6	2.1	4.2	4.2	6.0	3.2	6.0	5.3	4.7	4.4	7.1	4.5
Fortuna ×													
MA3-2b	1.5	5.8	2.1	2.9	4.7	6.1	4.0	5.7	5.2	4.3	4.9	4.9	4.3
IR1006-20-5	1.7	4.7	2.2	4.5	5.2	6.5	2.0	3.9	3.7	5.5	4.0	7.3	4.3
IR24	2.8	4.7	1.9	3.9	5.5	6.7	3.6	4.5	5.7	4.4	4.0	7.9	4.6
IR665-8-3	1.6	4.6	2.2	4.5	4.7	7.4	2.4	4.3	4.5	5.3	3.5	7.7	4.4
IR881-5-3	1.4	5.8	2.3	4.5	4.5	6.4	2.8	5.0	4.7	4.5	3.1	7.8	4.4
IR833-34	4.3	5.8	2.2	3.5	4.9	6.4	2.1	8.0	5.6	3.6	3.5	7.3	4.8
IR833-6-2	3.5	5.8	2.1	3.5	6.0	5.3	2.4	5.7	4.5	3.1	3.4	6.8	4.3

^aIRRI.

research trials on two groups of promising rice selections, on integrated pest control, and on new herbicides. The results of the herbicide trial are reported by the agronomy department.

New selections. The 1972 Farmers Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial was

conducted in both the wet and dry seasons, but data are not yet available for the wet season trial. Among the 12 locations from which reports were received IRRI had the highest yields. IR833-34 gave the highest mean yield for the 12 locations, 4.8 t/ha, followed in order by C4-63 and IR24 (Table 1). The low yield levels obtained at several locations suggest inadequate management and limit the usefulness of these data in evaluating new selections.

In a similar trial, seven new IRRI selections and varieties IR8 and IR20 were tested for yield performance and resistance to pest and virus diseases at four locations. Their yields in protected and unprotected plots did not differ significantly (Table 2), except at the IRRI farm, where the yield of the protected plot was significantly higher than that of the unprotected plot. The insect and disease problem apparently is more serious at IRRI than in farmers' fields. Results from one location are not reported because all except one plot lodged due to excess nitrogen from an unknown source. IR1529-680-3 had the highest mean yield in both the protected and unprotected plots.

Integrated pest control. Some insecticides which can be applied to paddy water, when used in combination with the new seedling treatment technique and on varieties tolerant to insect pests, can drastically reduce losses caused by insect pests and virus diseases. During the wet

1. Soil map. Rainfed and upland applied research project sites. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija provinces, Philippines.

superior to other yellow-seeded varieties. The yellow color and seed quality are preferred in marketing and usually bring a higher price. It has been released to the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture and to the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry for testing and possible release.

Sweet potato. Several lines of sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) introduced from Taiwan and from the U.S.A. were compared with local varieties for yield and quality of the lines. Those from Taiwan are very high yielding (Table 2) but are suitable only for processing or for animal feed. The Philippine varieties are dry in texture, having relatively high specific gravity, are smooth in shape, and have good eating quality. The U.S. varieties, Jewel and Centennial, have high carotene content but are of low specific gravity and are not preferred by Philippine consumers. In lowland areas or during periods of heavy rainfall the variety BNAS 51 yields better than most other varieties. Its yellow flesh and high specific gravity give it excellent quality. Its early maturity (80 to 90 days) may limit its use in intercropping, but it makes the variety highly desirable for the more intensive sequential plantings.

CROP MANAGEMENT

Vegetable soybeans. Soybeans are one of the most promising crops for use in multiple cropping. They produce more protein per hectare and per day than most other crops. Their tolerance of poor soil conditions make them an ideal crop to follow rice. We have used soybeans extensively in our intensive cropping patterns.

Little information is available on the characteristics of vegetable soybeans in the tropics so we studied the growth characteristics and time of harvest to clarify practices for growing the crop. Five varieties with different plant types and different degrees of photoperiod sensitivity were planted on four dates representing the growing seasons at IRRI.

The strongly photoperiod-sensitive variety L-114 showed a typical response to daylength (fig. 1). The other varieties, being less sensitive to daylength, showed a relatively greater response to temperature and light intensity.

Table 2. Yields of introduced and local sweet potato varieties. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Variety	Root yield (t/ha)	Yield of tops (fresh wt) (t/ha)	Eating quality
Hsinchu #1	22.3	48.3	Poor
Taichung 60	20.4	52.7	Poor
C53-83	15.7	33.1	Good
Tainung 27	14.2	35.9	Poor
Native (Bulacan)	13.9	32.8	Good
Jewel	13.9	28.8	Fair
Centennial	11.2	16.8	Fair

The best plant growth and highest yields were obtained from the February planting (Table 3). Yields were highly correlated with total solar radiation during the growing season. Protein production per day showed substantial variation with planting date and solar radiation. The highest protein yield was obtained in the February planting. The highest protein production per day was 8.9 kilograms for the variety Multivar 80 in the February planting when harvested 37 days after flowering. The average protein yield for all varieties in this planting was 7.8 kg/ha per

1. Fluctuation in daylength at IRRI and flowering response of five soybean varieties to four dates of planting.

Table 3. Yield of green shelled soybeans for different planting dates in relation to temperature and solar radiation (mean of five varieties). IRRI, 1971 and 1972.

Planting date	Solar radiation ^a (cal · cm ⁻² · day ⁻¹)	Mean temp. (°C)	Yield ^b		Highest protein production ^c (kg · ha ⁻¹ · day ⁻¹)
			t/ha	kg · ha ⁻¹ · day ⁻¹	
August 2	515	27	1.8	26.2	3.3
November 4	260	26	1.7	25.9	3.5
February 7	444	27	3.3	52.6	7.8
May 4	364	28	1.7	27.7	4.4

^a From planting until final harvest. ^b Average of six harvesting times for each date of planting. ^c Average of the highest production figures for each variety over the different times of harvest.

day. Soybean is thus an extremely high producer of protein during the dry season, but during the wet season it will not compete with mung bean. Multivar 80 had the highest yield of dry beans during the February planting, 2.0 t/ha, and the May planting, 1.3 t/ha.

The protein content of shelled beans measured as a percentage of dry weight showed little change with stage of harvest, varying only from 37.0 to 37.7 percent over the harvest period of 25 to 40 days after flowering. Planting date had a slight effect on protein content with the August, November, February, and May plantings—38.0, 37.7, 36.7, and 37.7 percent, respectively.

2. Yield of green pods and shelled beans of soybeans at different harvest times (average of four varieties and four planting dates).

There appeared to be a slight negative correlation between total yield and protein content but the effect was minor.

The optimum time of harvest varied with variety and season, but in general, harvesting between 31 and 37 days after flowering gave the highest yields of both green pods and shelled beans (fig. 2). Loss of yield after this period was due to moisture loss from the pods and to a lesser extent from the beans. The moisture content of beans at the time of maximum green bean yield is between 66 and 70 percent.

Protein yield of the shelled beans varied with time of harvest (fig. 3). The most rapid increase in protein occurred between 20 and 37 days after flowering. In general the varieties approached maximum protein yield at 37 days after flowering so that harvest at the late green bean stage did not cause much loss in total protein yield. Protein production per day dropped off markedly if harvest was delayed past 37 days. At about this time the pods and beans began to show yellowing and rapidly lost eating quality.

For most varieties the optimum harvest for use as a vegetable occurs 63 to 70 days after planting. Dry bean harvest requires 15 to 20 days more, depending on variety.

Rice. The IRRI multiple cropping project has been growing rice by direct seeding on unpuddled soil. The field is prepared using a small tractor for constructing alternate ridges and furrows 1 meter apart. The bottom of the furrow is 50 to 60 cm wide, leaving 40 cm for a 15-cm high ridge. The rice is drilled into the unpuddled furrow in three rows, 25 cm apart, at a seeding rate of 100 kg/ha. All subsequent

Table 4. The effect of planting pattern and nitrogen level on the grain yield of IR20 and IR127-80-1. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Planting arrangement	Yield (t/ha)							
	IR20				IR127			
	60 kg/ha N	100 kg/ha N	150 kg/ha N	Mean	60 kg/ha N	100 kg/ha N	150 kg/ha N	Mean
Drilled on furrows	2.6	3.3	3.6	3.2	2.4	3.1	3.7	3.0
Broadcast on furrows	2.8	3.6	3.5	3.3	2.2	3.0	3.6	3.0
Two rows and one skip	2.4	2.9	3.5	2.9	2.1	3.2	3.6	3.0
Three rows and one skip	2.5	2.7	4.0	3.1	2.2	2.9	3.4	2.8
Five rows and one skip	2.3	3.3	4.1	3.2	2.0	3.1	3.0	2.7
Continuous planting	2.9	2.6	4.2	3.2	2.1	2.5	3.0	2.5
Mean	2.6	3.1	3.8	3.2	2.5	3.0	3.4	2.8

field operations are conducted when the soil is dry enough to avoid puddling. The method permits intensification of the cropping pattern by maintaining the soil in good structural condition for crops grown before and after rice. The preceding and following crops can be planted on the ridge in relay with the rice crop to permit the growing periods to overlap and thus save time. The method requires high-level land preparation, weed control, and water control.

Planting patterns. During the wet season we conducted a series of experiments to test the response pattern of rice to several of the practices used in the method. The effect of the planting pattern was studied using two varieties, IR20 and IR127-80-1, representing high and low tillering types. For the ridge and furrow method we compared seed drilled in 3- to 25-cm rows in the 60-cm-wide furrow with seed broadcast in the furrow. For the flat seedbed method, 25-cm rows were seeded in combinations of two, three, or five rows of rice and one row skipped. A check of a continuous planting at 25 cm spacing was used. Nitrogen levels were 60, 100, and 150 kg/ha.

The difference between varieties was not significant. The effect of nitrogen and the interactions of variety with planting pattern and of nitrogen with planting pattern were significant. Both varieties responded to nitrogen application (Table 4). IR20, however, had a greater response to the high level of nitrogen in the continuous planting arrangement on the flat bed. The IR127 line showed the opposite effect,

having a significantly higher yield when planted in the furrow. The varieties behaved as expected in tiller response to row spacing. IR20 tillered more at all nitrogen levels when planted in the furrow or in a two-row bed. In three-row and five-row beds and in continuous plantings there were no differences in tiller numbers (Table 5). The difference in tiller number was thus not directly related to yield differences. The higher level of nitrogen affected mainly head filling and grain size.

3. Protein yield and rate of protein production of shelled beans of five soybean varieties at different harvest times for February planting and the average of four plantings.

Table 5. Effect of planting arrangement on total tiller numbers of IR20 and IR127-80-1 averaged over nitrogen levels.

Planting arrangement	Tillers (no.)			
	IR20		IR127	
	Per meter	Per square meter	Per meter	Per square meter
Three rows drilled in furrows	121	363	96	288
Two rows and one skip	150	400	120	320
Three rows and one skip	126	378	122	366
Five rows and one skip	116	386	117	390
Continuous planting	122	488	118	472

Table 6. Comparison of IR8 yields in response to soil condition and fertility level. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Unpuddled	Puddled
60	2.7	2.1
100	2.8	2.4
150	3.4	2.5

Table 7. Effect on rice yields of relay planting crops in the field before harvesting rice. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Crop combination	Length of overlap (days)	Rice yield (t/ha)
Rice alone		4.01
Rice and corn	21	4.28
Rice alone		4.12
Rice and sorghum	21	4.33
Rice alone		4.03
Rice and sweet potato	30	3.95
Rice alone		3.43
Rice and soybeans	21	3.91
Rice alone		3.97
Rice and cowpea	21	3.63
Rice alone		3.76
Rice and mung	21	3.55
Rice alone		3.38
Rice and radish	21	3.23

Table 8. Effect on sweet potato yields of relay planting into rice at different time intervals.

Length of overlap (days)	Sweet potato yields (t/ha)			
	Without rice		With rice	
	Tops	Roots	Tops	Roots
0	8.4	12.7	6.7	8.9
10	10.0	12.9	9.2	10.5
20	10.7	11.3	7.7	7.8
30	10.2	12.8	10.7	11.7
40	14.6	10.6	14.5	8.7

During the wet season with yields at 3 to 4 t/ha the practice of skipping one row in four thus has little effect on yield.

Puddling. Previous years' experiments showed little difference in rice yields between plots with puddled soil and plots where the soil was not puddled. In this year's trial the effect of unpuddled soil in a ridge and furrow condition with three rows in the furrow at 25 cm apart was compared with direct seeding on puddled soil with every fourth row skipped. Nitrogen levels were 60, 100, and 150 kg/ha. The puddled treatments had significantly lower yield regardless of fertilizer level (Table 6). This was caused by a heavy attack of bacterial leaf blight about 50 days after seeding following several days of rain. The rice plants in the puddled plots were considerably more vigorous and more advanced in growth which apparently made them more vulnerable to infection. The straw weight was greater in the puddled plots but there was no difference in total tillers or in the number of filled panicles.

Timing of nitrogen application. The use of the ridge and furrow method on puddled soil requires special attention to the timing of nitrogen application. In the wet season we planted IR20 and applied urea at 50, 100, 150, or 200 kg/ha N. At each level four patterns of application were used: all before planting (basal); one-half basal and one-half at panicle initiation (78 days after seeding); one-third basal, one-third at 30 days after seeding, and one-third at panicle initiation; and one-fourth basal, one-fourth at 30 days, one-fourth at 56 days, and one-fourth at panicle initiation.

There was a significant quadratic response to nitrogen averaged over all treatments. The difference between basal and split application was significant but the overall difference between the three types of split was not. The variation among the split application methods showed a significant interaction with the linear component, indicating that the pattern of response to each of the split applications was different. The entirely basal treatment gave the lowest yields at all levels of nitrogen (fig. 4). A plateau in yield was reached with each method of application except for the four-split treatment. Two times of application were best at low rates of

nitrogen but four times was better at higher rates. At low rates of nitrogen it appears desirable to apply a greater proportion early in the growth period. The four splits gave a linear response to 200 kg/ha N. Split application was always better than basal, with the high rates of nitrogen giving better yields with a greater number of splits. The value of split application should be even higher when water control is less ideal. With periodic flooding and drying, the nitrogen loss would increase.

INTENSIFICATION OF CROPPING

Relay planting with rice. As intensity of cropping is increased, the interactions between crops and the effects of management of one crop on the performance of another become more important. The ridge and furrow system for rice is designed to permit intensification of cropping by planting rice before harvest of the preceding crop or by planting a following crop before harvest of the rice.

In several experiments on the effect of seven crops relay-planted in a field of IR8 at different times before harvesting the rice, we found no effect on rice yield at the maximum time of overlap (30 days for sweet potatoes and 21 days for other crops) (Table 7). Tillage of the ridges in the rice, competition of the growing seedlings with rice, and the effect of the basal fertilizer rate of 30-50-50 (NPK) applied to the relayed crops before planting seemed to have little effect on the rice crop (the fertilizer rate for the rice was 150-50-50). Relay cropping in rice thus does not affect rice yield in this system.

But the relay effect on the crops that follow rice is more pronounced. Sweet potatoes are unusual in their tolerance to shading during the early growth stages. The early competition for light causes little difference in either top growth or root production (Table 8).

Interplanting. Previous work at IRRI has shown the benefits of interplanting for increasing annual production. A series of recent experiments has revealed additional benefits of several interplanting combinations.

Sweet corn and mung bean. During the dry season, planting patterns must be designed to allow for irrigation. With most crops a ridge and

4. Effect of level and time of application of nitrogen on yield of IR20 using the ridge and furrow system on unpuddled soil. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

furrow system is used: a 75-cm-wide ridge bordered by a 25-cm-wide irrigation-drainage furrow which is 10 to 15 cm deep. For hand tractors 1 meter is the optimum bed width. With this bed arrangement, for the least intercrop competition, corn can be planted in the furrows and the shorter crop can be planted on the ridges. The disadvantage of the system is that the crop growing in the furrow interferes with the irrigation and drainage. The system also prevents the use of the hand tractor for cultivating the furrow for weed control.

To compare the effects of planting configuration, we planted sweet corn both in the furrow and on the center of the ridge in a single row at 25 cm between plants (one plant per hill) and at 50 cm between plants (two plants per hill). One row of mung beans was planted near each edge of the ridge at a population of 350,000 plants per hectare. Corn and mung planted alone constituted the control. The mung was harvested in 55 days and the sweet corn in 67 days.

The sweet corn yield was 30,000 marketable ears per hectare regardless of the planting arrangement or whether or not mung was interplanted. The mung yielded 1,270 kg/ha when planted alone and 650 kg/ha when interplanted in sweet corn regardless of the corn planting arrangement (ridge vs furrow or 25 cm vs 50 cm

5. Effect of corn population on intercropping sweet corn and mung. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

within row spacing). It thus appears that the planting arrangement has little effect on the relationships of sweet corn and mung bean when planted together.

To further test the effects of corn populations on the yield of interplanted mung bean, corn was grown in rows 1 meter apart planted in the furrow at 10,000, 20,000, 33,000, 40,000, 50,000, and 60,000 plants per hectare. Mung beans were planted in a double row on the ridge at a population of 400,000 plants per hectare. The crops were grown separately and also interplanted for each treatment. Fertilizer levels were 40-40-40 (NPK) for the mung and 150-50-50 for the corn. When the crops were interplanted the fertilizer rates were added together. The mung variety MG50-10-A was harvested in 61 days and the sweet corn variety PH801 in 70 days.

Mung yield decreased sharply when planted with 10,000 and 20,000 corn plants per hectare (fig. 5). But higher corn population caused a more gradual reduction in mung yield. Mung, in turn, reduced the yield of corn at all levels of corn population. The mung interplanting reduced corn yield the most at a corn population of 50,000 per hectare.

A preliminary study of the fertility relationship of sweet corn and mung grown together

6. Yield of interplanted corn and peanuts (shelled seed) as affected by population and spacing (rows 1-m or 2-m apart) of field corn. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

showed that mung does not contribute nitrogen to corn (Table 9). The corn had poor growth with symptoms of severe nitrogen deficiency when grown with no added nitrogen. The interplanted mung bean seemed to contribute to the deficiency rather than to alleviate it.

When planted alone, mung bean did not respond to added fertilizer. When interplanted with corn the yield of mung was higher at low fertility than at high fertility because the relatively poor growth of corn reduced the competition.

Corn and peanut. Throughout Asia and Africa corn and peanuts are a common intercropping combination. In studying the productivity of this pattern we planted the early corn variety DMR-2 at the same time as CES 101 peanut. Two rows of peanut were planted in a 1-meter bed at a population of 160,000 plants/ha and the corn was planted in the furrows. The yield of

Table 9. Effect of mung on sweet corn yield (marketable ears) at two levels of fertility. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Cropping pattern	Sweet corn yield (ears/ha)	Mung yield (t/ha)
<i>110-60-60 NPK</i>		
Corn alone	26000	—
Corn and mung	25000	0.9
Mung alone	—	1.4
<i>0-40-20 NPK</i>		
Corn alone	6000	—
Corn and mung	5000	1.1
Mung alone	—	1.3

peanut decreased linearly as corn population increased (fig. 6). Peanut yields were slightly higher when the corn was planted at 2-meter spacing than when planted at 1-meter spacing. This difference was statistically significant. Peanut yields were significantly higher when the corn was harvested as green ears 75 days after planting than when harvested dry at 97 days at the same time as the peanut.

The yield of corn was likewise reduced at 2-meter spacing (fig. 6). It appears that the peanut affects corn yields by competing for nitrogen. High levels of fertilizer are required to get high yields from the interplanted corn. The peanut also influences the pattern of root development in the corn. When interplanted with peanut, corn tends to develop deeper roots and fewer shallow roots.

Another study combined peanut, sweet corn, and tomato. We planted 160,000 plants per hectare for peanut, 20,000 for corn, and 10,000 for tomato. The peanuts and tomatoes were planted on the ridges and the corn in the furrow at a 2-meter row spacing. The yield of peanut was reduced slightly by the corn planting (Table 10). Tomato had a somewhat greater effect, and the combination of corn and tomato reduced peanut yield by about 50 percent. The greatest gross return was from the combination of the three crops.

Sweet corn and sweet potato. Trials on the effect of sweet corn population on yield of interplanted sweet potato showed that corn (when harvested at 81 days) mainly increased top growth of sweet potatoes. Sweet potatoes produced 10.2 tons of tops when interplanted with corn and 6.8 tons with no corn. Corn population differences had little effect—10,000 plants per

Table 10. Effect of interplanting tomato and sweet corn on the yield of peanut. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Cropping pattern	Yield ^a			Value ^d (P/ha)
	Peanut ^b (t/ha)	Sweet corn ^c (ears/ha)	Tomato (t/ha)	
Peanut	2.7	—	—	4540
Peanut, sweet corn	1.9	29700	—	6230
Peanut, tomato	1.8	—	5.9	7250
Peanut, sweet corn, tomato	1.4	30300	5.4	9180

^a Harvest times (days after planting): Sweet corn, 68, 75; tomato, 69 to 84; peanut, 100. ^b Shelled nuts. ^c Marketable ears. ^d At a rate of P1.70/kg of shelled peanuts, P0.10/ear of corn and P0.70/kg of tomato.

hectare were sufficient to cause the increase. The effect of corn on tuber yield appeared slight, but yields were generally low because of heavy rains. Different amounts of fertilizer applied to the sweet potatoes had little effect on corn yield. The corn population response was similar to what could be expected from corn alone (Table 11).

Corn and soybean. Corn and soybeans are commonly interplanted in many parts of the world. The response to plant population was studied using the early varieties Shih Shih (soybean) and DMR-2 (corn). The soybeans were planted in 1-meter-wide beds with two rows per bed at a population of 400,000 plants per hectare. The corn was planted in the furrows at the same time.

Soybean interplanting had little effect on the yield of corn (fig. 7). Its population response was about the same whether interplanted with soybeans or not. Soybean yields were not high due to an early infestation of rust. The rust infection was heavier in the interplanted combinations

Table 11. Effect of population on sweet corn yield (marketable ears) when interplanted with sweet potato. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Population (10 ³ plants/ha)	Yield (ears/ha)
40 (1-meter rows)	34,600
40 (2-meter rows)	31,600
33	27,700
20	19,200
10	10,100

7. Yield response of corn and soybeans to interplanting with different population of corn. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

with higher corn populations. A more vigorously growing soybean variety might have a greater effect on corn yields.

WEED CONTROL

The predominant weed species in our plots are those which would be present in a region following several years of intensive cultivation. Most broadleaved species, being easier to control, have been eliminated.

We tested five crop combinations and six

Table 12. Effect of weed management on yield of five crop combinations. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Cropping pattern	Yield ^a (t/ha)			Butachlor (kg/ha a.i.)		
	Unweeded	Tractor ^b	Handweeded ^c	0.6	1.2	2.4
	<i>Corn yield</i>					
Corn	2.6	3.0	4.1	3.1	3.5	3.9
Corn, mung	3.1	3.6	3.3	3.2	4.0	3.3
Corn, cowpea	3.4	2.6	3.3	3.4	3.7	3.9
	<i>Mung yield</i>					
Mung	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
Mung, corn	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
	<i>Cowpea yield</i>					
Cowpea	0.8	0.8	1.3	1.0	1.0	0.9
Cowpea, corn	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3

^a Grain at 14% moisture. ^b One pass with a hand tractor with rotary cultivator. ^c Once, at 30 days after seeding.

weed control treatments to determine the response of intercropping pattern to weed control practices. The most common weeds present were *Portulaca oleracea*, *Echinochloa colonum*, *Eleusine indica*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, and *Cyperus iria*. The varieties used were DMR-2 corn, MG50-10-A mung, and E. G. Green Podded #2 cowpea. All are early-maturing.

Of the three crops grown, only corn showed a major reduction in yield when no weed control was used (Table 12). A single cultivation was not sufficient to give good control. The weed species present required a high rate of herbicide for good control. Yields of mung planted alone did not benefit from weed control. Cowpea yields had a moderate response to weed control. None of the three crops responded to weed control when interplanted. So, when no weed control was used, interplanting mung bean in corn increased the yield of corn by 35 percent (Table 12). All other factors (including fertility) were unchanged.

INSECT MANAGEMENT

In cooperation with the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture (UPCA), we are attempting to develop procedures for managing insect pests in multiple cropping systems. The procedures are based on studies by a UPCA scientist at IRRI of the influence of various crop combinations on the population of insect pests and their enemies.

Diamond-back moth. To verify the observation that cabbage plants in close proximity to tomato plants were less severely damaged by diamond-back moth (*Plutella xylostella* L.) than cabbage alone, we compared the abundance and oviposition activities of the moths in a 150-sq-m field of cabbage, an 80-sq-m field of tomatoes, and a 260-sq-m field planted to both cabbage and tomato in alternate rows. In the cabbage field the plant spacing was 75 x 40 cm and in the tomato field, 100 x 30 cm. In the mixed planting, any two rows of tomatoes were 125 cm apart with the cabbage row between them. To ensure that the moth's preferences for oviposition were not influenced by damaged plants, the fields were sprayed with Dipel, a commercial preparation of *Bacillus thuringiensis*, which

Table 13. Incidence of *Plutella* spp. on cabbage in a plot of solid cabbage (cab.) and cabbage-tomato (cab.-tom.) intercrop. IRRRI, 1972 wet season.

Days after transplanting	Adults (no.) on					
	Sticky traps		Plants ^a		Eggs on plants ^b (no.)	
	Cab. ^b	Cab.-tom. ^c	Cab.	Cab.-tom.	Cab.	Cab.-tom.
16 to 17	9	5	7	4	1381	1432
24 to 25	17	16	12	4	638	356
31 to 32	19	14	25	2	209	53
37 to 38	22	14	22	1	153	22
44 to 45	6	4	6	0	52	5
52 to 53	11	2	7	0	53	0
59 to 60	5	2	1	0	21	0

^aTotal number observed on 50 sample plants. ^bCollection of 14 sticky traps. ^cCollection of 16 sticky traps.

selectively kills feeding larvae but does not adversely affect the adults. Dipel was applied weekly at 10 g per 20 liters.

The solid planting of tomato (variety VC-48-1) was virtually free from *Plutella* spp. which is not surprising because tomato is not a natural host of the insect. Plots with cabbage plants (variety KK) interplanted with tomatoes had fewer adults and received fewer eggs than cabbage plants in the field without tomatoes (Table 13). The *Plutella* adults were apparently disturbed or repelled by the characteristic odor of tomato.

Corn borer. We have observed that intercropping corn and peanut greatly reduces the damage the corn borer (*Ostrinia furnacalis* Guence) does to corn. Since low plant densities are also less favorable for survival of corn borer than high densities, we evaluated the effects of population and row spacing of corn in combination with the effect of peanut in the corn. A field, 625 sq m, was equally divided into four plots. The plots were planted to corn alone or to a corn-peanut intercrop. The corn was planted at 20,000 plants per hectare (2 m between rows) or 40,000 plants per hectare (1 m between rows). In the two plots with the corn-peanut intercrop the peanuts, variety CES101, were planted in double rows, one row on each side of the row of corn, variety Glutinous Synthetic No. 22.

As expected, the plots with the high corn density were more severely infested than the plots with the low density (Table 14). But we also found that the presence of peanut reduced the corn borer infestation in both the high and low crop densities. Predators which may have been

provided a better habitat by the peanuts may have reduced the borer population.

ECONOMIC EVALUATION

Rainfed systems. Responding to drought-killed rice. In June 1971 a rainfed trial of rice planted at IRRRI was destroyed by severe moisture stress during a dry period in August. In September, following the loss of the rice crop, we planted several crop combinations under rainfed conditions to investigate what a farmer might do to recoup his loss from the rice crop. The plots were large to permit evaluation of each pattern for labor requirements and other inputs.

In half of each plot, 5 tons of rice straw was worked into the soil. A small rotary mower that fits the front of a hand tractor was used to cut the straw before working it into the soil. At P5/hour for the tractor and man, it required P30 to cut the straw. On the other half of each plot, the straw was cut and removed from the field. It required 123 man-hours at P62/ha to carry the straw off the field. Therefore, it cost P32/ha

Table 14. Comparison of corn borer infestation on corn with or without peanut intercrop in two cropping densities at 56 days after planting. IRRRI, 1972 wet season.

Corn population (plants/ha)	Peanut intercrop	Borer-infested plants (%)	Borers (no./plant)	Feeding or exit holes (no./plant)	Feeding tunnels (no./plant)
40,000	yes	30	0.4	0.5	0.4
40,000	no	86	2.6	3.1	2.7
20,000	yes	21	0.4	0.5	0.5
20,000	no	60	2.0	2.1	2.0

Table 15. Summary of costs and returns on rainfed cropping systems following a rice crop-failure caused by drought. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Crop	(P/ha)		
	Cost	Total return	Net return
Mung/sorghum	1200	2300	1100
Sorghum	900	3100	2200
Soybean/sweet corn/sweet potato	1700	8000	6300
Sweet corn/sweet potato	1100	5200	4100
Sweet potato/sorghum	900	3300	2400
Sorghum	1000	1900	900
Sweet potato	600	4800	4200

more to remove the straw than to plow it under.

Removing the straw or incorporating it made little difference in the net return for most crop combinations from most systems. With sweet potatoes the yield was occasionally higher if the straw was incorporated. This was presumably an effect of better soil structure and better aeration during the heavy rains of December.

The greatest net return was realized from the combination of soybean, sweet corn, and sweet potato (Table 15). Labor utilization was highest with combinations that included sweet potato and lowest with combinations that included sorghum. If the labor is considered to be extra

employment for the farmer or his family above the amount normally available to them, their actual return from the system would be higher than that indicated by net return.

Farm trials. Trials were established in four farmers' fields this year to evaluate the idea of planting upland crops before rice in typical rainfed rice paddies that have heavy clay and high organic matter content. The farmers' labor was used in all operations except those such as land preparation which involved a power tiller. The farmer received all of the production in return for his labor which was timed. In addition all inputs were recorded for nearby rice paddies which the farmer operated in his usual manner.

Heavy rains in early July flooded the plots of two farmers for 4 months and prevented them from growing upland crops. Poor drainage in paddies of the remaining two farmers reduced the yield of the upland crops (Table 16). Losses or small returns above variable costs were incurred on all crops. No cowpea was harvested because the expected yield did not justify expenses for harvesting. The low yield of cowpeas was due to waterlogged soil and low solar radiation (only $175 \text{ cal} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ for the 3 weeks before harvest date). Corn yields were low for the same reason.

Table 16. Comparison of multiple cropping and a single rice crop on typical rice paddies in 1972 at two barrios in Pila, Laguna.

Crop	Yield (t/ha)	Variable costs (P/ha)				Return (P/ha)	Net return (P/ha)	
		Labor ^a	Material	Tractor ^b	Total		per crop	per pattern
<i>Bukal</i>								
<i>Pattern 1</i>								
Cowpea	0.0	350	370	290	1010		-1010	
Rice	2.5	1260	370	60	1690	1440	-250	-1260
<i>Pattern 2</i>								
Sweet corn	13.9 ^c	430	580	320	1330	1390	60	
Rice	3.5	1000	440	120	1560	1960	400	460
<i>Pattern 3</i>								
Rice	5.4	560	300	1290	2150	3090	940	940
<i>Pansol</i>								
<i>Pattern 1</i>								
Cowpea	0.0	110	490	430	1030		-1030	
Rice	3.4	930	350	60	1340	1930	590	-440
<i>Pattern 2</i>								
Sweet corn	13.8 ^c	200	550	440	1190	1380	190	
Rice	2.4	330	450	220	1000	1360	360	550
<i>Pattern 3</i>								
Rice	5.0	630	170	1090	1890	2880	990	990

^a1 hour of labor: P0.75. ^b1 hour of tractor operation: P7.00. ^c1000 ears of corn.

The yields of rice in plots following the upland crops were low primarily because of high weed populations; in one plot, over 15 t/ha of weeds (green weight) were pulled out in the first 80 days. *Echinochloa colonum* and *Cyperus rotundus* were the major problems. In the first planting of upland crops, volunteer rice was a serious problem. The heavy rainfall made weeding with the power tiller impossible. Post-planting sprays of Machete at 1.2 and 1.5 kg/ha a.i. gave mixed results but generally did not control the weeds for more than 3 weeks. Directed sprays of paraquat and hand weeding were used as a last resort.

Compared with the multiple cropping systems, the traditional rice culture was much better able to withstand the adverse weather. Both farmers spent much time and money in preparing the soil for the upland crops. For the farmer at Bukal, soil preparation took 22 days from initial plowing to transplanting and cost over P1,000/ha. Weeds in the upland plots were minor problems after the thorough land preparation, however.

A hidden cost of the multiple cropping system was the disruption of the usual labor-sharing arrangements among neighbors. The high labor requirements of the upland crops meant that

our cooperators were not able to help their neighbors so they did not have a share in the neighbors' harvests. The farmer was then far more dependent on his own yields than before.

Thus in a typical paddy in a low-lying area having poor drainage, rice was the best crop to plant in the early rainy season. Upland crops cannot be planted near rice in an area where independent control of both irrigation and drainage is not possible.

Irrigated systems. We are evaluating the inputs and production of cropping systems grown under irrigation after rice. The agronomic practices followed were based on recommendations of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture except where special techniques were required for intercropping or relay interplanting. The criterion for making any decision was: Would the operation and the expense involved give a good return on the crop on which it was going to be applied?

Six cropping systems in order of decreasing net return are shown in figure 8 with yields outlined in Table 17. The intensity of the systems

Table 17. Crop production per hectare on six irrigated cropping systems.

Planting sequence ^a	Sweet corn ears (1000)	Other crops	
		Yield (t/ha)	Name
A1	30.0	—	—
2	17.0	11.0	Sweet potato
B1	—	0.3	Cowpea seed
2	34.0	—	—
3	—	1.0	Mung seed
C1	—	0.5	Soybean seed
2	12.0	6.0	Sweet potato
3	25.2	0.7	Mung seed
D1	—	7.0	Sweet potato
2	—	2.4	Cowpea pods
3	18.7	0.8	Cowpea pods
E1	—	0.4	Mung seed
2	—	2.2	Sorghum seed
3	—	3.1	Sorghum seed
F1	—	0.4	Soybean seed
2	26.5	5.6	Sweet potato
3	6.0	—	—

^a 1—First planting after rice, 2—second planting after rice, 3—third planting after rice.

8. Total and peak labor requirements per hectare for six cropping systems, listed in order of decreasing net return (arrows indicate peak labor requirements).

Table 18. Income and expenses for six irrigated cropping systems.

System	Expenses (P)	Net income (P/ha)		
		Total	Per day	Per hour of labor
A	2340	6580	28.70	4.90
B	3040	3630	13.90	2.20
C	4460	3650	13.00	1.50
D	3250	2890	10.60	1.70
E	2020	2270	8.20	2.10
F	3350	2520	9.40	1.40

Table 19. Cost of credit for six irrigated cropping systems.*

System	Amount borrowed (P/ha)	Weeks borrowed	Cost (P/ha)
A	640	10	16
B	1580	27	107
C	1560	16	62
D	550	14	19
E	560	23	32
F	1800	23	103

* Assuming total amount of credit needed is borrowed at beginning of season paying 13% interest per annum.

ranged from two to six crops planted. There was no relationship between intensity and net return.

The labor requirement for each system is not related to the net return either. Labor peaks of over 300 man-hours per hectare occurred whenever sweet potatoes were included. The other major causes of labor peaks were land preparation and handplanting of crops.

Net income per day followed a similar pattern to total net income (Table 18). Net income per hour of labor varied considerably. In evaluating cropping systems high net income may not give the farmer a high return on his labor. But with good water control all of these cropping systems were able to give a higher return per hour of labor than a laborer could earn at the minimum wage rate in the Philippines.

Table 20. Digestible nutrient production from six irrigated cropping systems.

System	Digestible protein		Non-protein digestible nutrient	
	Amount (kg/ha)	Marketable (%)	Amount (kg/ha)	Marketable (%)
A	920	29	14,900	39
B	670	64	6,600	47
C	1,260	40	11,800	38
D	720	29	6,700	32
E	810	63	17,000	24
F	770	61	10,200	37

Credit requirements for any cropping system are of major importance to any small farmer. Cropping system B, which had the second highest net income, had the worst credit requirements. The farmer would have had to borrow P1,580 for 27 weeks while a system with a lower net income would have required a small loan for only 14 weeks. There would be considerable justification for a poor farmer to choose the low-risk system (Table 19).

All of these systems were designed to produce a high net income for the farmer. Although protein production is of widespread concern, it unfortunately is not a factor in optimizing net income. Digestible protein production and net income are not related (Table 20). Marketable protein varied 122 percent in these systems. Less than half the protein produced could be sold and the rest was either waste or livestock food. Marketable non-protein digestible nutrient (basically carbohydrates) account for 87 percent of the difference in net income in these systems. It appears that a farmer who is planning to optimize his income from market sales should ignore protein and concentrate on marketable carbohydrates under the existing price structure.

Soil microbiology

In submerged soil atmospheric nitrogen fixation determined by the acetylene reduction method was much higher in the intact soil-plant system than in soil or plant roots. We found more nitrogen gas in planted soils than in unplanted soils in a submerged rice field. By using the autoradiographic technique we also demonstrated that carbon assimilated by the rice plant is excreted into the rhizosphere. An association between the soil and the rice plant in the rhizosphere appears to be a key factor for nitrogen fixation. Some aquatic plants also showed nitrogen fixing activity in rhizosphere. □ Several grain legumes were examined for symbiotic nitrogen fixation in the field by using the acetylene reduction method. Soybeans fixed more atmospheric nitrogen than cowpea, bush sitao, or mung bean. □ A tracer study showed that fertilizer nitrogen immobilized in the soil was persistent and remained in soil as organic nitrogen. A study of the transformation of fertilizer nitrogen in soil indicated no difference in total amount of nitrogen taken up by IR5 under upland conditions at different moisture tensions. But more nitrogen remained in straw and less nitrogen was translocated to grain as the moisture tension of soil increased. Rice plants grown in submerged soil took up more nitrogen, particularly soil nitrogen, than those grown under upland conditions. □ The A-value of sulfur varied from 18 to 170 ppm S in five submerged soils. The recovery of fertilizer sulfate by rice varies from 14 to 26 percent depending on the soil type. □ Ethylene was detected in submerged soil. Application of organic matter such as glucose and rice straw enhanced the evolution of the gas. □ Investigation of BHC residues in rice fields of Iloilo province showed less than 10 ppb in soil, zero to 350 ppb in rice plants, and negligible amount in water. The most abundant isomers found were α -BHC and β -BHC. □ The herbicides 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, and picloram were biodegradable and did not persist long in two Philippine soils tested both under upland and submerged conditions.

NITROGEN FIXATION BY RICE

Previously, using the acetylene reduction method, we found that the rhizosphere of the rice plant in submerged soil seems to be favorable for atmospheric nitrogen fixation. This year we examined the assay conditions of the acetylene reduction method in the soil-plant system to study nitrogen fixation in the rice rhizosphere *in situ*. The amount of nitrogen gas, excretion of organic carbon, and nitrogen-fixing bacteria which are factors that influence nitrogen fixation in rice rhizosphere were also examined.

Effect of air on the acetylene-reduction method.

Three germinated IR20 seeds were planted in a test tube (19.5 × 2.3 cm) containing 20 g of Maahas clay soil submerged under 2 cm of water. The lower half of the tube was covered with black cloth to prevent algal growth. The tubes were placed in a greenhouse and when the rice plants were 3 to 4 weeks old the assay was conducted. Test tubes containing only soil were used as control. After pouring out surface water

we evacuated the air in half the tubes with a vacuum pump and then flushed them with an argon-oxygen gas mixture (8:2). Then 30 percent of the argon-oxygen atmosphere was replaced with acetylene. In the other tubes air-tight syringes were used to replace 30 percent of the air with acetylene. The amount of ethylene produced was analyzed by gas chromatography. Five replicated analyses at 3, 5, 10, and 24 hours after incubation showed that the acetylene-reducing activity of the intact soil-plant system in the presence of molecular nitrogen in the air was comparable to the activity in the absence of molecular nitrogen.

To determine the effect of oxygen on the $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay, we assayed one set of tubes containing growing rice plants in an argon atmosphere and another set in the presence of oxygen (0.2 atm). During the first 5 hours of incubation the acetylene-reducing activity in the soil-plant system was lower in the anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay than in the aerobic assay (Table 1). After 10 hours of incubation, however, the acetylene-

1. Acetylene-reducing activities of intact soil-plant system, unwashed roots, and washed roots at different oxygen concentrations.

reducing activity in the anaerobic assay became remarkably high. The unplanted control tubes had very low activities.

An additional experiment was performed at different molecular oxygen contents: 0, 0.03, and 0.2 atm. Acetylene-reducing activity at 0.03 atm did not differ significantly from that at 0.2 atm in the intact soil-plant system (fig. 1). But the acetylene reducing activity at 0 atm increased greatly after about a 3-hour lag period. Washed rice roots showed lowest activity at 0 atm O_2 while unwashed roots to which soil was attached showed an intermediate activity at 0 atm O_2 . The activity of the washed roots, however, increased rapidly after 5 hours in the assay at 0.03 atm O_2 .

To examine the effect of preincubation on the anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay (0 atm O_2), the test tubes were placed in an incubator at 30°C for 24 hours in an Ar, N_2 , or argon-acetylene (0.01 atm C_2H_2) atmosphere before the assay. Preincubation increased the acetylene-reducing activity for the first 10 hours of incubation, but no significant difference in the assay was observed after 24 hours (Table 2). Preincubation treatments in Ar, N_2 , or Ar- C_2H_2 atmosphere gave about the same results as preincubation.

Anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay. The effect of acetylene concentration on the anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay (0 atm O_2) was further investigated. We found that the higher the concentration of acetylene, the shorter the lag period of acetylene-reducing activity. There was, however, no significant difference between 0.1 and 0.3 atm of acetylene in the amount of ethylene produced after 8 hours of incubation, or between 0.05, 0.1, and 0.3 atm of acetylene after 24 hours of incubation.

In another experiment, we compared the anaerobic acetylene-reducing activity of the intact soil-plant system with the activities of the plant separated from the soil and of the remaining soil. We used a 30 percent acetylene concentration in the assay for the intact soil-plant system and the separated plant, and a 5 percent concentration for the assay with soil itself. The lowest acetylene-reduction activity in the intact soil-plant system was at 3 hours of incubation and the highest after 10 hours (Table 3). The removed rice plant showed higher reduction

activity than the intact soil-plant system at 3 and 5 hours of incubation. Soil had the least activity. After 10 hours the acetylene-reduction activity of the intact soil-plant system was much higher than the total activity of roots and soil.

The experiment was repeated after preincubating the tubes for 24 hours at 30°C in an argon atmosphere. Preincubation in argon atmosphere increased the acetylene-reducing activity of the intact soil-plant system in the assay with incubation of 10 hours or less (Table 4). Preincubation had no significant effect on the acetylene reduction of the removed plant or the remaining soil.

Acetylene reduction and nitrogen fixation. The theoretical factor used to convert the amount of acetylene reduced to the amount of nitrogen

Table 1. Comparison between aerobic and anaerobic assay of intact plant-soil system in the acetylene reduction method.

Incubation time (h)	Cumulative ethylene formed (nmol/tube)			
	Planted		Control	
	Anaerobic	Aerobic	Anaerobic	Aerobic
3	10	75	0.3	0.5
5	38	176	1.5	2.1
10	509	375	2.4	3.1
24	2546	701	4.6	6.4

Table 2. Effect of preincubation (under Ar atmosphere) of intact soil-plant system on the acetylene-reducing activity in anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay.

Incubation time (h)	Cumulative ethylene formed (nmol/tube)	
	Preincubation	No preincubation
3	198	19
5	407	66
10	949	322
24	2195	2045

Table 3. Acetylene reducing activities of intact soil-plant system, plant removed and remaining soil measured by anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay.

Incubation time (h)	Cumulative ethylene formed (nmol/tube)		
	Intact soil-plant system	Plant removed	Remaining soil
3	8	29	11
5	29	42	13
10	406	70	19
24	2350	375	27

Table 4. Effect of preincubation (under Ar atmosphere) on the acetylene-reducing activity in anaerobic C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay.

Incubation time (h)	Cumulative ethylene formed (nmol/tube)	
	Preincubation	No preincubation
3	89	7
5	271	36
10	930	275
24	2407	1944

fixed is 3. But the factor may vary depending on samples assayed. To determine the factor more precisely, we measured the actual amount of nitrogen fixed in the rice rhizosphere and compared it with the amount of fixed nitrogen as estimated by the aerobic C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay.

At maturity five IR20 plants growing in a flooded rice field were pulled from an experimental plot with the rhizosphere soil attached. Each sample was placed in a polyethylene bag which was sealed with masking tape and taken to the laboratory. Soil samples were immediately taken from each plant, pooled, and thoroughly mixed. The roots were washed with water in beakers in which argon gas was bubbled to minimize contact with air. After dislodging soil and organic debris from the roots, equal amounts of roots from each plant were mixed together. Ten grams of root samples and 20 grams of soil samples were used for the experiment.

For the acetylene-reduction method the samples were placed in 25-ml Erlenmeyer flasks capped with rubber needle-puncture stoppers. A portion of the air in the flasks was replaced by acetylene inserted through a hypodermic syringe. The concentration of acetylene in the flask was 5 percent for the soil sample and 30 percent for the rice root sample. A previous experiment had shown that the C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay gave the same

Table 5. Acetylene-reducing activity of N₂ fixing bacteria isolates from rice rhizosphere.

Incubation time (h)	Cumulative ethylene formed (nmol/tube)	
	In agar slant	In solution
3	204	1
6	761	20
10	1450	210
24	3650	3550
34	5140	6460

results for roots whether the assay was conducted in the presence of air or argon-oxygen mixture (8:2).

The samples were incubated in an incubator at 30°C. Under the experimental conditions the acetylene-reducing activity of the samples showed a generally linear relationship with the incubation times for at least 10 hours. The assay of the samples was done after 5 to 10 hours of incubation.

For the isotope ¹⁵N method, 10 g of root samples or 20 g of soil samples were taken and placed in a 50 ml flask with a ground glass joint attached to its neck. A manifold with an inlet for the different gases, vacuum line, manometer, and sampling bulb was attached to the flask. Then the system was evacuated and filled with argon. The process was repeated three times. The stopcock for the argon and oxygen line was closed and the system was evacuated for the last time. The flask was then filled with 0.25 atm ¹⁵N₂, 0.2 atm O₂, and 0.55 atm Ar.

The atom percent excess of ¹⁵N of the gas phase and the sample was analyzed at the start and end of incubation. The root or soil samples were analyzed for total nitrogen by a Kjeldahl method which includes nitrate and nitrite. After titration the solution was acidified and dried with a steam bath for the ¹⁵N analysis.

The acetylene reducing activity of five rhizosphere soil samples ranged from 64.5 to 132.3 (81.6 average) nmol C₂H₄ · 20 g⁻¹ soil · day⁻¹. The amounts of ¹⁵N₂ fixed in the soils were 20.9, 22.1, 36.3, and 40.5 nmol in each of four replicates. The molar ratios of C₂H₄ to N₂ calculated by using the average value of acetylene reducing activity were 2.2, 2.3, 3.7, and 3.9 in each of four replicates. The acetylene reducing activity of each root sample ranged from 1.58 to 2.07 (1.71 average) μmol C₂H₄ · 10 g⁻¹ root day⁻¹. The amounts of ¹⁵N₂ fixed in the root samples were 0.53, 0.56, 0.67 μmol in each of three replicates. The molar ratios of N₂ to C₂H₄ calculated by using the average value of acetylene-reducing activity were 2.6, 3.0, and 3.3 in each of three replicates.

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria. A nitrogen-fixing bacterium isolated from the rice rhizosphere was examined for the acetylene-reducing activity. We found no significant difference in acetylene-

Table 6. Amount of nitrogen and methane gas in submerged soils at four locations at the IRRI farm.

Location	Rice variety	Spacing (cm)	Growth stage	Volume (cc/100 g dry soil)	
				N ₂	CH ₄
A	IR8	25 × 25	Maximum tillering	17.5*	7.8
	Unplanted	—	—	5.3	10.5
B	IR8	5 × 5	Panicle initiation	2.6	0.4
	IR8	40 × 40	Panicle initiation	1.8	0.6
C	IR747-B ₂ -6-3	10 × 10	Booting	6.8*	1.4
	Unplanted	—	—	1.6	5.0
D	IR20	25 × 25	Panicle initiation	6.0*	3.3
	Unplanted	—	—	2.0	7.3

*Significantly different from the unplanted field at the same location at the 5% level.

reducing activity between assay in air and assay in Ar-O₂ (8:2) mixture. The assay was therefore done by replacing a portion of the air with acetylene gas.

The bacterium was first grown for 3 days on nitrogen-free agar slants in test tubes. Then 5 ml of sterile distilled water was added to one set of slants and the bacteria were scraped into the solution, mixed, and transferred to 25-ml Erlenmeyer flasks which held 5 ml of a solution containing a nitrogen-free medium. The other set of slants was used directly for C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay. Acetylene was then injected into both sets of cultures at 0.05 atm and the ethylene formed was measured after 0, 1, 2, 3, 6, 24, and 34 hours of incubation. On agar slants the bacterium showed high acetylene-reduction activity (Table 5), but in solution the bacterium had a long lag period. The bacterium appeared to be of the facultative anaerobic type since its acetylene-reduction activities at 0, 0.03, 0.1, and 0.2 atm O₂ did not differ much.

Molecular nitrogen in soil. An essential condition for nitrogen fixation in the rice rhizosphere of a submerged soil is the presence of a source of nitrogen. Although the rice plant, through its air transporting system, supplies oxygen to its roots and even excretes some oxygen to the rhizosphere, excretion of molecular nitrogen to the rhizosphere of the rice plant has never been reported.

We analyzed the gases in a flooded rice field to estimate the amount of molecular nitrogen available for microbial nitrogen fixation. We collected and prepared gas samples from submerged soils with Koyama's apparatus, some-

what modified. The gases were analyzed with a gas chromatograph connected to a gas sampler with a manometer. In a preliminary study, we analyzed soil samples from several locations at the IRRI experimental farm. No fertilizer nitrogen was applied at any of the locations. We found that the submerged soils planted to rice had significantly more nitrogen gas than unplanted soils at all locations (Table 6).

In a subsequent experiment, we measured the change in the gas components during the growth of rice in a submerged rice field at one location. Plots, 4-m square, were prepared 2 weeks before transplanting. One plot was planted to IR20 at a spacing of 25 × 25 cm and another was left unplanted. Weeding and sampling were done without entering the plots to avoid disturbing the soil.

We found (Table 7) that the content of nitrogen gas in the planted soil increased at tillering (34 days after transplanting). At tillering, panicle initiation (48 days after transplanting), and heading (77 days after transplanting), the con-

Table 7. Volume of gases in a submerged field planted to IR20 and in an unplanted field.

Days after transplanting	Volume (cc/100 g dry soil)			
	N ₂		CH ₄	
	Planted	Unplanted	Planted	Unplanted
2	0.7	1.0	6.5	8.5
6	0.9	1.7	6.1	11.1
34	6.4*	1.4	1.4	16.2
48	3.8*	1.6	1.9	7.0
77	2.9	2.1	3.1	9.7

*Significantly different from the unplanted field at the 5% level.

2. Autoradiograph (left) of roots and rhizosphere of a rice plant 1 week after tops of the rice plant were treated with ^{14}C -labelled CO_2 . Right, the root development.

tent of nitrogen gas in the planted soil was higher than that in the unplanted soil. At 2, 6, and 77 days after transplanting, the content of nitrogen gas in the planted and unplanted soils did not differ significantly. More methane was found in the unplanted soil than in the planted soil during the period of plant growth. The planted soil had about 20 kg/ha N at transplanting but about 160 kg/ha N at tillering. Unplanted soil had 20 to 50 kg/ha N during the corresponding period.

Carbon exudates. Organic carbon provided by rice roots is another essential factor for atmospheric nitrogen fixation in the rice rhizosphere. Previously we demonstrated that the rhizosphere effect of rice was large in submerged soil conditions, particularly at later stages of rice growth. We attempted to examine carbon excretion by the rhizosphere using the radioisotope technique. An IR8 seedling was grown in submerged soil in a thin glass container and allowed to assimilate $^{14}\text{CO}_2$. An autoradiograph of the rice root zone made 1 week after treatment (fig. 2) showed that the extent of ^{14}C diffusion appeared to be large in the rhizosphere.

The excretion of ^{14}C assimilated by the rice plant was quantitatively examined in another experiment. At the tillering stage $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ was fed to the rice plant grown in water culture solution. Once a week the ^{14}C excreted from

roots but remaining in culture solution was measured with a liquid scintillation counter. One hour after the treatment, we found 96 percent of ^{14}C in stem and leaves and 4 percent in the roots. At maturity 66 percent of ^{14}C was in the straw, 18 percent in panicles, and 15 percent in roots. The cumulative amount of ^{14}C in the water culture solution was less than 1 percent of the total ^{14}C that remained in plant tissues.

NITROGEN FIXATION BY AQUATIC PLANTS

The ability of several edible aquatic plants other than rice to fix atmospheric nitrogen was examined using the acetylene-reduction method. The plants were the red and white variety of taro (*Colocasia esculenta*), kangkong (*Ipomoea aquatica*), lubigan (*Acorus calamus*), apulid (*Eleocharis dulcis*), and gabing uwak (*Monochoria vaginalis*). All plants were grown in submerged Maahas clay soil in pots.

The plants were uprooted and the roots were washed with running tap water. Three grams of roots were placed in a 50 ml flask and assayed for acetylene-reducing activity in atmosphere of $\text{Ar-O}_2\text{-C}_2\text{H}_2$ (5:2:3). All the roots showed acetylene-reducing activity. None of them showed natural evolution of ethylene. These aquatic plants thus may possess a mechanism

which enables them to fix atmospheric nitrogen as does the rice plant.

NITROGEN FIXATION IN LEGUMES

Symbiotic nitrogen fixation by legumes is one of the most important biological processes by which atmospheric nitrogen is made available for plant use. Legumes are grown extensively in the tropics as rotation crops or intercropped with cereal crops. The amount of nitrogen fixed by different legumes grown in Maahas soil was determined with the acetylene-ethylene technique. Two varieties of soybeans (CES434 and Shi-Shi), mung bean (CES55), bush sitao, and cowpea were planted in the field. The seeds were inoculated with inoculant obtained from the Philippines Bureau of Soils. The plant population consisted of 200,000 plants/ha for cowpea and 300,000 plants/ha for the other legumes.

From germination until harvest, using the $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ technique, the nitrogen activity of both soybean varieties and mung bean was measured weekly and that of the other legumes, biweekly. Twelve hills of each legume were randomly collected from 7:00 to 8:00 AM and the unwashed nodulated roots from each hill were placed in a 500-ml flask sealed with a rubber stopper with a serum cap. One-tenth atmosphere of C_2H_2 was introduced into the flask. The samples were kept in the laboratory for 1 hour. The gas in the flask was analyzed for ethylene by gas chromatography.

The total N_2 fixed was calculated from the acetylene-reducing activities at various sampling times (fig. 3). Cowpea fixed the most atmospheric nitrogen at the vegetative stage, followed by mung, bush sitao, and soybean in that order. Soybean fixed more nitrogen during its reproductive stage than cowpea or mung bean. Shi-shi soybean fixed the most nitrogen, the mung bean fixed the least: Shi-shi soybean, 123 kg/ha N; CES434 soybean, 99 kg/ha N; cowpea, 33 kg/ha N; bush sitao, 30 kg/ha N; mung bean, 12 kg/ha.

NITROGEN TRANSFORMATION

We continued the greenhouse experiment started last year to trace the fate of fertilizer nitrogen

3. Amount of nitrogen fixed by different legumes in a Philippine soil.

under three water regimes. Most of the fertilizer nitrogen immobilized in the soil during the first crop remained in soil as organic nitrogen through the second crop (Table 8). The nitrogen taken up by the second crop was 2.2 percent of the amount of fertilizer nitrogen applied in the previous crop in the submerged conditions, 3.1 percent in the upland conditions, and 1.5 percent in alternating wet and dry conditions. When rice straw was added to the soil, the nitrogen recovered by the second crop was 5.9 percent of the fertilizer nitrogen received by the first crop in the submerged conditions, 3.5 percent in upland conditions, and 2.0 percent in the alternating conditions.

In another experiment we studied the effect of different soil moisture tensions on nitrogen transformation, on grain yield, and on nitrogen uptake by the rice crop. Ten kilograms of air-dried Maahas clay soil were placed in porcelain pots. To create different soil moisture tensions, water continuously flowed from a water reservoir into the pots through a column of mercury whose height corresponded to the soil moisture

Table 8. Balance sheet of tagged soil nitrogen in rice plants and soils at harvest of a second crop under different water regimes and with and without application of rice straw in the greenhouse.

Water regime	Initial tagged soil N* (mg/pot)	Tagged N recovered (mg/pot)					Total	N recovery (%)
		Plant		Soil				
		Straw	Panicles	Ammonium	Nitrate	Organic		
<i>Control</i>								
Submerged	240	7.6	18.8	2.7	1.2	177	207	86.4
Upland	488	13.0	25.6	5.2	7.9	405	457	93.7
Alternating	327	6.9	10.5	5.4	1.6	257	282	86.2
<i>Rice straw added</i>								
Submerged	516	19.7	47.6	6.0	1.0	369	443	85.9
Upland	684	16.5	26.8	5.6	3.3	568	621	90.7
Alternating	611	10.1	14.0	4.5	11.5	479	519	84.9

*After harvest of the first crop.

tension. The soil moisture tensions were 0, 5, 15, 25, and 35 cm Hg (corresponding to 0, 6, 20, 33, and 47 centibars, respectively). All treatments were replicated three times. Ammonium sulfate was added at the rate of 100 ppm N. In two pots of each treatment tagged fertilizer was applied.

Ammonium sulfate, as a solution, was mixed thoroughly with the soil. Two germinated IR5 rice seeds were planted in each pot. For comparison, the soil was puddled with the fertilizer in three pots, then two 21-day-old IR5 seedlings were transplanted into each pot. The soil in these pots was kept submerged throughout the growth of the plants.

Soil samples were taken every 4 weeks and analyzed for exchangeable ammonium, nitrate, and organic nitrogen. The amount of exchangeable ammonium decreased rapidly within 4 weeks in the upland treatments (0 to 47 cb). The different soil moisture tensions did not greatly influence the decline in exchangeable ammonium. In the upland soil a rapid decrease in exchangeable ammonium was followed by a rapid increase in nitrate which lasted up to 8 weeks after planting. Almost no nitrate was found in the submerged soil.

At moisture tensions of 0, 6, 20, and 33 centibars, plants were almost the same height. They were tallest under submerged conditions and shortest at a soil moisture tension of 47 centibars. The soil moisture tensions did not affect panicle number. Dry matter weight decreased as soil moisture tension increased, but growth duration increased with soil moisture tension.

The nitrogen concentration, in both straw and grain at harvest, increased with soil moisture tension. But there was no difference in the total amount of nitrogen taken up by the rice plant. The amount of nitrogen in straw increased, while that in grains decreased, with increases in soil moisture tension (Table 9). Thus movement of nitrogen from the leaves to the panicles during the reproductive stage apparently was affected by the soil moisture tension, but the nitrogen uptake from the soil by the rice plant was not.

The submerged rice plants took up more nitrogen, particularly soil nitrogen, than upland plants. The amount of tagged fertilizer nitrogen recovered in the rice plant was higher (53.8%) in submerged plants than in upland plants (42.0 to 46.9%, depending on soil moisture tension).

MINERAL TRANSFORMATIONS

Iron-reduction. To develop an assay technique for iron-reducing activity in soil and in rhizosphere, we tested several iron oxides and hydroxide as sources of iron: goethite, lepidocrocite, limonite, and ferric hydroxide. To measure microbial iron-reducing activity, we added 100 mg of these iron compounds to a medium, inoculated a soil suspension of Maahas clay into each medium, and incubated them at 30°C. Limonite was reduced after a 1-day lag period, the other iron materials showed a 2-day lag period. When, however, instead of the soil suspension, we inoculated *Aerobacter aerogenes* or an isolate from rice rhizosphere, both of which

Table 9. Plant uptake of fertilizer and soil nitrogen at different soil moisture tensions.

Soil moisture tension (centibar)	Plant uptake (mg/pot)					
	Straw		Grains		Total	
	Fertilizer N	Soil N	Fertilizer N	Soil N	Fertilizer N	Soil N
Submerged	167	356	310	698	477	1054
0	122	203	250	425	371	628
6	157	241	255	381	411	623
20	162	255	229	362	390	617
33	193	308	198	317	391	625
47	291	443	124	197	416	640

are iron-reducers, into each medium, more iron in goethite and ferric hydroxide was reduced than iron in limonite.

We found that the iron-reducing bacteria convert potassium ferricyanide from yellow to colorless at concentration about 0.2 percent in an agar medium and convert it to green at concentration of about 1 percent in the medium under partially anaerobic conditions. The chemical was added to a bacterial medium to count numbers of iron-reducing bacteria in rice rhizosphere. Glucose-asparagine agar was prepared and potassium ferricyanide solution was added aseptically to give a final concentration of 1.0 percent. Soil suspension (10^{-4} or 10^{-5} dilution) was inoculated into the medium in a Petri dish. After the medium became solid, additional medium agar was poured to cover the surface to make anaerobic conditions. One week after incubation at 30°C, colonies of iron-reducing bacteria turned green.

Sulfur transformation. Using a tracer technique we studied sulfur transformation in Kimpo clay (from Korea), Maahas clay, Luisiana clay, and Pila clay, and a soil from Nueva Ecija (Philippines).

Three kilograms of soil were thoroughly mixed in a pot with 22.5 mg S as ^{35}S -labelled K_2SO_4 which corresponds to 15 kg/ha S. To examine the effect of organic matter on the availability of sulfur in a submerged soil, rice straw was applied at the rate of 0.3 percent. After the pots were submerged for 1 day, two 15-day-old Tongil (IR667-98) seedlings were planted in each one. Each treatment was replicated three times in the greenhouse. The rice plants were harvested at late maturity. Kimpo soil showed the highest A-value (a measure of

the amount of available S) and Pila soil the least (Table 10). Application of rice straw to the soil did not influence the A-values much. Depending on soil type, the rice plant recovered 14 to 26 percent of the fertilizer S.

Most plants absorb sulfur as sulfate, but in the submerged soil in which rice is grown, most sulfur compounds are in reduced forms such as sulfides. Three kilograms each of Maahas and Pila soil were weighed into glazed porcelain pots. A delivery tube for collecting soil leachate was attached to each pot. After 1 day of submergence in deionized water, half the pots were planted with 2-week-old Tongil seedlings; the other half were kept unplanted but supplied with deionized water as were the planted pots. At transplanting 50 ppm of sulfate-S was applied to each soil. At weekly intervals, the soil leachate was collected anaerobically from each pot for sulfate and sulfide analysis.

Two weeks after transplanting the soil leachate of neither the planted nor the unplanted Pila

Table 10. Total dry matter produced, A-value of sulfur, and uptake by rice in submerged soils with and without organic matter application.

Soil	Dry matter (g/pot)	A-value (ppm S)	Sulfur uptake by rice (mg/pot)	
			From soil	From fertilizer
<i>Control</i>				
Kimpo	32.6	134.0	104.9	5.9
Maahas	56.3	71.5	39.0	4.1
Luisiana	38.1	54.5	23.9	3.3
Gapan	36.9	50.6	22.5	3.3
Pila	42.1	18.9	13.6	5.4
<i>Organic matter added</i>				
Kimpo	34.6	167.0	71.1	3.2
Maahas	52.8	84.0	43.6	3.9
Luisiana	40.1	50.2	24.0	3.6
Gapan	36.2	40.6	22.6	4.2
Pila	45.2	18.6	13.0	5.2

soil contained sulfate. That suggests that rice plants can use either the reduced or the organic form of sulfur directly or after oxidizing them to sulfate in the rhizosphere. Maahas clay soil which has a high level of available sulfate retained sulfate for more than 9 weeks but when rice straw was added to it, sulfate in the leachate disappeared within 6 to 7 weeks after transplanting.

ORGANIC MATTER TRANSFORMATIONS

Among various gases which evolve in flooded soil after submergence, methane has been the only gaseous hydrocarbon known to accumulate in large amounts. Recently, however, some workers found that ethylene accumulates in anaerobic soil in amounts injurious to the roots of some plants.

We investigated ethylene evolution in two flooded soils: Ampayon clay (total nitrogen, 0.32%; organic matter, 6.1%; pH 6.7) collected from Agusan, Mindanao, and Maahas clay (total nitrogen, 0.14%; organic matter 2.0%; pH 6.6). We placed 50 g of each soil in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks and added 100 ml of distilled water to submerge the soil. To determine the effect of applying organic material on ethylene formation, 1 percent of glucose, cellulose, rice straw, or green manure (powdered *Sesbania* sp.) was added to the soil. The flask was closed with a stopcock connected to a manifold to manipulate exchange of gases. The flask was incubated at 30°C in the dark for 9 days. To obtain anaerobic conditions, the air in the flask was thoroughly exchanged with N₂. A 10 ml test tube containing 5 ml of 2 N KOH solution was placed inside the flask to absorb the carbon dioxide that evolved.

Table 11. Ethylene formation in Ampayon soil treated with various organic materials under anaerobic submerged condition.

Treatment	Ethylene formed (nmol/100 g dry soil)	
	Incubation time (days)	
	4	9
None	21	44
Glucose	75	101
Cellulose	36	53
Rice Straw	69	98
Rice root	30	50
Green manure	30	48

Four and nine days after incubation the flask was connected to an apparatus for absorbing ethylene. Then 1 or 2 ml of mercuric perchlorate which was used to absorb ethylene was placed in a 15-ml graduated centrifuge tube which was closed with a rubber needle-puncture stopper. Five milliliters of 4 N LiCl was injected through the stopper with a hypodermic syringe to evolve ethylene gas. The amount of ethylene was analyzed by gas chromatography.

Results in the Ampayon soil confirmed that ethylene is produced in submerged soils (Table 11). The amount of ethylene increased significantly when glucose or rice straw was added to the soil. Additions of cellulose, green manure, or rice roots to the Ampayon soil did not significantly increase ethylene formation. Less ethylene was formed in Maahas clay soil than in the Ampayon soil.

To investigate ethylene degradation by rice roots, IR8 plants were washed thoroughly with tap water to remove the soil from the roots. Three grams of leaves, straw, or rice roots were placed in 50-ml flasks which were sealed with rubber needle-puncture stoppers. The air in the flasks was evacuated with a vacuum pump through a hypodermic needle. The flasks were then filled with a mixture of oxygen-helium gas (2:8) several times using a gas-mixture apparatus. The flasks were incubated in the dark for 24 hours at 30°C. Portions of the air in the flasks were analyzed for ethylene.

The test of ethylene-degrading activity of rice plant in ethylene atmosphere showed that roots degraded most of the ethylene after 24 hours of incubation. Stems and leaves showed no activity.

The root tissue could not have physically absorbed the acetylene because roots which were autoclaved and treated with trichloroacetic acid did not cause a decrease in the ethylene concentration in the flask after 24 hours of incubation.

To investigate the microbial role in ethylene degradation, 20 g of rice roots were removed aseptically from 2-week-old rice seedlings grown under germ-free conditions. The roots were incubated at 30°C for 24 hours in a 25-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing ethylene. The amount of ethylene in the reaction flask did not decrease during 24 hours of incubation nor did

4. Degradation of 2,4-D in two Philippine soils under upland and submerged conditions.

the soils in which the rice plants were grown show any ethylene degradation during 24 hours. These results indicate that micro-organisms on rice roots may decompose ethylene.

PESTICIDE RESIDUES

Herbicides. We studied the degradation of 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, and picloram (4-amino, 3,5,6-trichloro-picolinic acid) under upland and submerged conditions in Maahas clay soil and Louisiana clay soil. Each herbicide was applied to 20 g of each soil in a large test tube. One set of

tubes was kept under upland conditions (80% of field capacity) and the other under submerged conditions with 3 cm surface water. After the tubes were incubated at 30°C for a time, the soil was analyzed for the herbicide residue by gas chromatography. The amount of 2,4-D in the soils was determined at 0, 2, 4, and 6 weeks after incubation. The amount of 2,4,5-T in the soil was determined at 0, 2, 4, 8, and 12 weeks after incubation. The amount of picloram in the soil was determined at 0, 3, and 6 months after incubation.

Little 2,4-D was found in Maahas clay under upland conditions after 2 weeks of incubation (fig. 4). Under submerged soil conditions 2,4-D remained relatively high during the first 2 weeks, but degraded fast until the sixth week of incubation. In Louisiana clay soil the amount of 2,4-D gradually decreased until 6 weeks of incubation, but there was not much difference in the rates between the upland soil and the submerged soil. More than 60 percent of 2,4-D was not recovered from the Louisiana soil at the sixth week of incubation.

The herbicide 2,4,5-T degraded fast in Maahas clay soil both under upland and submerged conditions (fig. 5). The amount that remained in submerged Louisiana soil was negligible by 2 months after submergence, but under upland conditions the herbicide degraded more slowly.

Picloram was more persistent in soil than 2,4-D or 2,4,5-T. It degraded faster in Maahas soil than in Louisiana soil (fig. 6). Six months after

5. Degradation of 2,4,5-T in two Philippine soils under upland and submerged conditions.

6. Persistence of picloram in two Philippine soils under upland and submerged conditions.

7. Degradation of 2,4,5-T in sterilized and nonsterilized soils under upland and submerged conditions.

incubation 74 percent remained in Luisiana soil under upland conditions while 45 percent remained under submerged conditions.

To assess the possible biodegradation of 2,4,5-T, the degradation in sterilized and nonsterilized Luisiana and Maahas soils was studied in both upland and submerged conditions. The amount of 2,4,5-T remaining in the soils was determined after 0, 2, 4, and 12 weeks of incubation. We found that 2,4,5-T remained stable in sterilized Maahas and Luisiana soil during incubation while in the control soils it degraded both under upland and flooded conditions (fig. 7). This result suggests that the degradation of 2,4,5-T is due to microbial activity in soil.

Insecticides. In a study of BHC residues in rice fields in Iloilo province, Philippines, soil, water, and plant samples were taken from the field in plastic bags and later analyzed for BHC by gas chromatography, using a column of 5 percent

Table 12. Residue analysis of BHC isomers in soil, plant and water of 15 rice fields in Iloilo province.

BHC isomer	Content ^a (ppb)	
	Mean	Range ^b
		<i>Soil</i>
α	5	2 to 9
γ	3	1 to 6
β	T	ND to T
δ	T	ND to T
		<i>Plant</i>
α	64	10 to 350
γ	32	10 to 167
β	70	ND to 100
δ	100	ND to 100
		<i>Water</i>
α	46	8 to 78
γ	13	5 to 22
β	22	ND to 28
δ	14	ND to 16

^aT = Less than 5 ppb for β , less than 1 ppb for δ . ^b ND = Not detected.

QF-1 on chromosorb W and a 1.5 percent XE on Gas Chrom Q. To confirm the results, thin layer chromatography was also conducted. In most samples only the α - and γ - isomers of BHC were detected quantitatively (Table 12). The plants had higher concentrations of BHC isomers than the soil and water. The residues of the α -isomer found in the plants ranged from 10 to 350 ppb, and of the γ -isomer, from 10 to 167 ppb. One location had unusually high concentrations of BHC isomers in the plants (α -BHC, 350 ppb; γ -BHC, 167 ppb; β -BHC, 100 ppb; δ -BHC, 100 ppb) compared with other locations. Probably that location had been treated with insecticide shortly before we sampled it.

Agricultural economics

Research concentrated on the identification of constraints to higher yield and farm income, and possible

measures to alleviate these constraints. Analysis of nitrogen experiments suggests that the level of on-farm fertilizer use is negatively influenced by the high degree of variability in yield response and returns to fertilizer from year to year. Studies in both Thailand and the Philippines indicate that poor weed control on many farmers' fields have dampened the potential of the new seed-fertilizer technology.

□ Low yields are frequently the result of inadequate water supplies. Studies on water management, this year, showed that the environment, the choice of variety, and the stage of growth of the crop all significantly influence the effect of stress upon rice yield. Crop loss due to stress in a given irrigation system could be reduced with relatively little cost by controlling water so as to ensure a more adequate supply in the far reaches of the primary distribution canals. □ Based on our projections in Central Luzon with the new rice technology, achieving self-sufficiency in Philippine rice production in the 1970's will require a growth in irrigated crop area of over 3 percent per year and a growth in nitrogen application of approximately 13 percent per year.

PRODUCTION OF RICE IN ASIA

The world food grain situation changed dramatically over the past year largely as a result of poor weather. A large decline in Russian wheat production coupled with lower Asian rice production due to drought and floods resulted in a 50-percent rise in the prices of the world's two major food grains in the last 6 months of 1972 (fig. 1).

The damage to the rice crop was most severe in India, Bangladesh, Indonesia, and the Philippines. The decline in rice production in 1972/73 from the previous crop year will range from 5 to 10 percent in these countries. There have been no production gains in other South and Southeast Asian countries to compensate for this loss.

As a result of crop loss and rising food grain prices, the cost of food grain imports will rise sharply in many countries. In the Philippines, for example, foreign exchange expenditures for food grain imports in 1973 are likely to be double that of the previous year and will approach 15 percent of total export earnings.

The four countries whose rice crops have been most severely affected have been in the forefront in the adoption of modern (high yielding) varieties. While the new technology has increased rice production, no answer has yet been found to the whims of weather. In the long run, the modernization of agriculture should help to mitigate year-to-year fluctuations in crop output

1. The export price of rice (Thai, 5% broken, f.o.b. Bangkok) and the export price of wheat (American, hard winter, f.o.b. Gulf Coast), 1960-1972.

due to weather. In the meantime, there is still much to be learned about the interaction between technology and environment.

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF NITROGEN RESPONSE

We estimated the optimum economic levels of nitrogen application by fitting quadratic functions to experimental data from four experiment stations in the Philippines. The data are from nitrogen response trials conducted by the IRRI agronomy department at IRRI, which is 60 km southeast of Manila, at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, located in Central Luzon, 150 km north of Manila, at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, located in southern Luzon, 260 km south of Manila, and at the Visayas Rice Experiment Station, located in the western Visayas, 450 km south of Manila.

Differences in yield level or in nitrogen response may be due to differences in local soil or climate (Table 1), or in the procedure for conducting the experiment, which may vary somewhat between stations. Solar energy was recorded but not rainfall, since water was not a limiting factor in these experiments. The soils at the four stations are in general well suited to rice production, although at the Bicol station the soil shows signs of deficiency in phosphorus and potassium, and in zinc as well. In 1972 all three of these elements were applied.

The nitrogen responses of IR8 and IR20 were chosen for analysis because a difference was anticipated. IR8 is the first of the modern rice varieties. It established a new yield plateau which has yet to be surpassed under optimum conditions in the tropics—that is, when low solar energy or insect and disease attacks are not restricting yield response. IR20 lacks the high yield potential of IR8 because it normally lodges when high rates of fertilizer are applied. But it has a broad spectrum of resistance to several major insects and diseases. It is at present the most widely planted modern variety in the Philippines.

The variation in yield response from one season to the next is shown for the IRRI

Table 1. The solar radiation and chemical properties of the soil at four experiment stations in the Philippines.

Station	Solar radiation ^a (kcal/sq cm)		Chemical properties of soil					
	Wet season	Dry season	pH	Organic matter (%)	Total N (%)	Extract-able P (ppm)	Exchange-able K (meq/100g)	Cation exchange capacity (meq/100g soil)
IRRI	17.5	25.1	6.0	2.0	0.14	12	0.8	45
Maligaya	17.4	23.8	6.9	1.5	.08	8	.5	36
Bicol	16.7	21.8	5.5	4.4	.22	3	.2	29
Visayas	17.8	25.5	7.0	3.3	.12	10	.9	59

^a Average of 1968-71 for 45 days before harvest.

experiments in figure 2. This same general pattern of wet and dry season response occurs at all four stations except that at IRRI the functions tend to be more closely bunched. This is probably the result of more rigid control over the

experiments at IRRI. Because of the low response during the wet season, the return to nitrogen and the level of nitrogen input associated with the highest return varies considerably from year to year. Weather and disease are

2. Variability in yield response of IR8 and IR20 to nitrogen by year. IRRI, 1966-72 wet seasons and 1969-72 dry seasons.

Table 2. Return to fertilizer, IRRI, 1966-72 wet season.

Year	Solar energy ^a (kcal • cm ⁻² • 45 days ⁻¹)	Net return to nitrogen (P/ha) ^b					
		30 kg/ha N	45 kg/ha N	60 kg/ha N	75 kg/ha N	90 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
<i>IR8</i>							
1966	16.7	220	248	230	158	40	0
1967	18.4	220	312	390	463	520	605
1968	19.3	370	517	635	728	795	850
1969	19.9	125	177	225	253	290	325
1970 ^{cd}	16.2	20	12	-10	-42	-90	-225
1971	14.4	15	42	85	148	220	410
1972	15.5	278	380	448	490	502	442
	Expected value ^e	206	274	320	342	342	333
<i>IR20</i>							
1969 ^f	19.9	45	-8	-115	-277	-490	-1070
1970 ^d	16.2	335	442	515	548	535	405
1971	14.4	30	27	10	-17	-40	-175
1972 ^f	15.5	325	442	525	578	600	545
	Expected value ^g	174	143	234	208	151	-74

^aDate of harvest and solar energy for 45 days before harvest based on IR8 only. IR20 harvest is usually a few days earlier than that of IR8. ^bAssumed prices: paddy = P0.50/kg, nitrogen = P1.50/kg. ^cYield affected by typhoon. ^dYield affected by bacterial leaf blight. ^eAvg. of 1966-70 and 1972. Excludes 1971 because function shows increasing returns. ^fYield affected by lodging. ^gAvg. of 1969-72.

associated with differences in annual wet season yield response (Table 2).

The highest expected return to nitrogen occurs at 75 kg/ha N for IR8 and at 60 kg/ha N for IR20 (Table 2), although for IR8 the difference in return between 75 and 60 kg/ha N is slight. In making these computations, we have assumed each annual production function is equally likely to occur. We do not know the

probability of occurrence on the experiment station (much less on the farmer's field). Hence, this procedure has no advantage over computing the optimum level based on the average function by pooling years.

The average function by pooling years was computed for the experiment stations other than IRRI (fig. 3). IR8 has a higher average response than IR20 during the dry season at two of the

Table 3. Optimum nitrogen level and net return to nitrogen by season, variety, location, and price ratio (3:1 or 6:1) based on average nitrogen response functions for Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station and Visayas Rice Experiment Station for 1968-72 wet season and 1969-72 dry season.

Station	Variety	Optimum nitrogen level (kg/ha)		Yield ^c (t/ha)		Return to nitrogen (P/ha)	
		3:1 ^a	6:1 ^b	3:1	6:1	3:1	6:1
<i>Wet season</i>							
Maligaya	IR8	68	51	4.4	4.3	208	119
Bicol	IR8	76	65	4.6	4.5	400	294
Visayas	IR8	96	77	4.3	4.2	373	242
Maligaya	IR20	83	74	5.3	5.3	590	473
Bicol	IR20	77	67	4.4	4.3	453	346
Visayas	IR20	90	83	5.8	5.8	897	767
<i>Dry season</i>							
Maligaya	IR8	117	106	6.6	6.5	918	750
Bicol	IR8	118	107	6.9	6.8	987	819
Visayas	IR8	144	129	6.3	6.2	1064	858
Maligaya ^d	IR20	93	81	5.5	5.5	519	388
Bicol	IR20	121	110	6.2	6.2	964	792
Visayas	IR20	126	116	6.6	6.5	1159	977

^aFarm price of nitrogen = P1.50/kg; Farm price of rough rice = P0.50/kg. ^bFarm price of nitrogen = P2.40/kg; Farm price of rough rice = P0.40/kg. ^cBased on optimum nitrogen level. ^dAverage of 1970-72 only.

3. Average production functions for IR8 and IR20 by location. Maligaya, wet season, 1968-72 and dry season, 1969-72; Bicol, wet season, 1968-71 and dry season, 1969-72, Visayas, wet season, 1968-72 and dry season, 1970-72.

three locations, while the reverse is true during the wet season. Based upon these response functions, optimum nitrogen input levels were computed for two ratios of nitrogen price to rice price, 3 : 1 and 6 : 1. The 3 : 1 ratio reflects the price situation facing those farmers in a relatively favorable situation in the Philippines — a low interest rate for credit, a low transportation cost, and a high rice price. Farmers located farther from market, however, frequently have a much less favorable price situation for all three, and this is reflected in the 6 : 1 price ratio. The optimum levels of fertilizer input (Table 3) do not vary greatly according to location, variety, or price ratio, although there is a pronounced difference due to season.

Some farmers in the Philippines apply fertilizer at close to the optimum economic levels suggested by these experimental results. The majority do not. One reason, of course, is that the environment and management on the farmers' fields, and hence the fertilizer response, may differ markedly from that of the experiment stations. In addition, farmers are responding to uncertain outcomes from one year to the next. If we want farmers to increase fertilizer use, ways must be found to reduce uncertainty of yield and farm income. Price supports and subsidies are techniques that have been widely

used with varying success. Achieving a more stable year-to-year production response through disease- and insect-resistant varieties and proper timing of planting to reduce weather damage are other approaches.

BARRIERS TO HIGHER YIELD AND FARM INCOME

Two studies were made to identify the constraints to higher farm level yield and income. A study undertaken in Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, employed farm surveys to examine the impact of the introduction of the modern varieties. A study conducted in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines combined close field surveillance with farm surveys to provide a detailed measure of the physical environment and crop condition during the growing period, as well as of inputs and yield.

Thailand. The modern varieties RD1 and RD3, developed in Thailand, and C4-63, developed in the Philippines, are being adopted in some areas of Thailand. A major question is how widely they have been and will be adopted, and how they have affected yield and net income.

Amphur Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, which lies on the western edge of the Central Plain of Thailand 200 km northwest of Bangkok, was

Table 4. Adoption of modern varieties in the three study villages. Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1971 wet season.

Item	Village		
	A	B	C
Farms sample (no.)	47	59	44
Area (ha)			
Of rice per farm	5.3	6.1	5.4
Of rice per village	252	358	238
Irrigated	247	285	0
In modern varieties	102	75	9
Farms (no.) growing modern varieties for first time in			
1970 dry season	7	1	0
1970 wet season	20	13	0
1971 dry season	11	5	0
1971 wet season	3	25	13
Total growing modern varieties	41	44	13

one of the first areas in which the high yielding varieties were introduced. For our study, all villages in Don Chedi were divided into three groups based on irrigation conditions. One group consisted of wholly irrigated villages, a second group was partially irrigated, and the third group was wholly rainfed. One village was chosen at random from each group. A

village in the subdistrict of Rai Rot (village A) represented the first group, a village in Nong Sarai (village B) represented the second group, and a village in Sa Krachom (village C) represented the third group.

Modern varieties were planted for the first time in this area in the 1970 dry season (Table 4). In the 1971 wet season 41 percent of the total rice area was planted to modern varieties in village A, 21 percent in village B, and only 4 percent in village C. Although the percentage of the area planted to modern varieties in village B is half that of village A, more than 75 percent of the farmers in village B have planted modern varieties. Nearly all of the land planted to modern varieties is irrigated. But not all of the irrigated area is planted to modern varieties which suggests that within the irrigated area there may be considerable variation in the suitability of the land for modern varieties.

Farmers who had grown modern varieties were asked to compare their performance with that of traditional varieties (Table 5). Most farmers considered the new varieties superior in yield and fertilizer response, disease resistance, resistance to lodging, ease of harvesting, price, and income. The new varieties were generally considered inferior in eating quality. Nevertheless, they command a higher price because of their superior export quality, although the price differential is not great.

Opinions about threshing and about resistance to drought and flooding were mixed. Most farmers had not experienced extreme flood or drought conditions during the period of adoption, but in village C, all but one farmer reported that the high yielding varieties perform poorly in deep water conditions. In 1972 this village was badly flooded, and there were no high yielding varieties grown during the 1972 wet season.

It is impossible to compare modern varieties with traditional varieties for the same environmental situation as is normally done under experimental conditions. So we asked farmers to recall their previous yields (1969 wet season) on land now planted to modern varieties. Most could not quantify yield differences due to soil or water control differences within their farms, but they were able to recall total farm yields.

Yield index of modern varieties

4. Yield index of modern varieties (yield of modern varieties divided by yield of traditional varieties × 100) in the three villages. Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1971 wet season.

Table 5. Comparison of modern rice varieties with traditional varieties by adopters of modern varieties. Don Chedi, Suphan, Buri, Thailand, 1971 wet season.

Characteristic	Farmers (%) in village A ^a who said modern varieties are				Farmers (%) in village B ^b who said modern varieties are				Farmers (%) in village C ^c who said modern varieties are			
	Better	Worse	Same	Don't know	Better	Worse	Same	Don't know	Better	Worse	Same	Don't know
Yield	71	20	7	2	84	5	11	0	61	31	8	0
Response to fertilizer	61	10	10	19	68	2	0	30	8	0	0	92
Resistance to disease	81	10	7	2	89	4	7	0	69	31	0	0
Resistance to flood	37	29	15	19	41	52	5	2	8	84	8	0
Resistance to drought	68	27	0	5	64	29	7	0	46	46	8	0
Resistance to lodging	93	5	2	0	100	0	0	0	85	15	0	0
Harvesting	98	0	2	0	100	0	0	0	77	23	0	0
Threshing	12	76	7	5	50	27	23	0	77	0	23	0
Price	83	0	12	5	82	1	11	5	39	8	15	38
Eating quality	7	78	3	12	5	86	2	7	0	62	8	30
Income	75	10	10	5	90	0	5	5	46	15	0	39

^a41 observations. ^b44 observations. ^c13 observations.

The farm yield averages for the villages were almost identical for traditional varieties in 1969 and 1971 (Table 6). Lower than usual rainfall in the 1969 wet season seems to explain the low yield level in village C which is rainfed. The yield of modern varieties was significantly higher than that of traditional varieties in all three villages. There were also significant differences among villages in the yield of both traditional and modern varieties. Village A, the fully irrigated village, had the highest yields.

Figure 4 shows that most farmers who grow both modern and traditional varieties get a better yield from the modern varieties. In addition a high relative yield for modern varieties is usually, but not always, associated with a high absolute yield. But despite the yield advantage gained by most farmers, 15 percent did worse with modern varieties than with traditional varieties. The proportion that did worse was approximately the same in each village. Another large group of farmers (18 percent) obtained no better yields with modern varieties than with traditional varieties.

The majority of farmers were partial adopters planting less than half of their area to modern varieties. One-third of the farmers reported that deep water was a factor preventing them from expanding the area planted to modern varieties. If sustained water depth were likely to exceed one-half meter, traditional varieties were preferred.

Only 10 farmers were full adopters of modern

varieties. Most full adopters did not achieve a significant gain in comparison with their yields before planting modern varieties. That suggests that yield declined with the size of area planted to modern varieties.

To test the impact of farm size on yield, we examined two relationships for each village: (1) yield of modern varieties in relation to the proportion of the farm area planted to modern varieties, and (2) yield of modern varieties in relation to the actual area planted to modern varieties.

Only in village A was the relationship between yield and area planted to modern varieties statistically significant. Yields varied widely among farms, however. In villages A and B,

Table 6. Grain yield of land planted to modern varieties and traditional varieties. Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1969 and 1971 wet seasons.

Variety type	Year	Farms (no.)	Area grown (ha/farm)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
<i>Village A</i>				
Modern	1971	40	2.4	3.2 a
Traditional	1971	39	3.6	2.4 b
Traditional	1969	47	5.1	2.4 b
<i>Village B</i>				
Modern	1971	43	1.7	2.4 b
Traditional	1971	57	4.3	1.6 c
Traditional	1969	59	5.1	1.6 c
<i>Village C</i>				
Modern	1971	13	0.6	1.8 c
Traditional	1971	44	4.1	1.1 d
Traditional	1969	44	4.0	0.9 d

^aYields followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Table 7. Modern varieties: area planted, fertilizer input, weeding labor, grain yield, and net return per hectare, two irrigated villages. Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1971 wet season.

Input level		Farms (no.)	Area planted (ha)	Chemical fert. ^c (kg/ha)	Weeding (man- days/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (baht/ha) ^d
Fertilizer ^a	Weeding ^b						
Low	Low	25	2.7	25	0.4	2.4	1571
Low	High	8	1.9	38	15.1	2.5	1524
High	Low	13	3.5	123	0.9	3.0	1746
High	High	13	1.4	170	15.2	3.9	2544

^aLow = 0 to 75 kg/ha; high = 75 + kg/ha. ^bLow = 0 to 3 man-days/ha, high = 3 + man-days/ha. ^cThe two common fertilizers used are 16-20-0 and 18-22-0. ^dBaht 20.8 = US\$1.00.

yields over 4 t/ha were achieved only on farms that planted less than 40 percent of their area to modern varieties and only on farms planting less than 2.5 hectares to modern varieties. In village C, yields in excess of 3 t/ha were achieved only on farms planting less than 10 percent of their area to modern varieties and on those planting less than 1 hectare to modern varieties. Thus, there appears to be an important relationship between area planted and yield.

The inputs other than water most closely associated with high yield were the quantity of fertilizer applied and the amount of labor used for hand weeding. Herbicides have rarely been used in this area. Thus, labor used for weeding is a good measure of the intensity of weed control. Farms in the two irrigated villages were classified into four groups according to whether they used a high or low level of fertilizer and a high or low level of weed control on the land planted to modern varieties. Before this classification was made, farms reporting a water control problem were eliminated.

The results (Table 7) emphasize the high degree of complementarity between weed control and fertilizer input in obtaining high yields and income. High levels of one or the other alone

result in an insignificant increase in yield and income. Here again, those farms applying inputs most intensively and getting a high yield and income response have a relatively small area planted to modern varieties.

Returns and costs per hectare were higher for modern varieties than for traditional varieties in all three villages with the exception of costs in village C which were about the same (Table 8). Returns and costs also differed for a given varietal type between villages. But the variable cost per ton of rice produced was not significantly different.

A comparison of returns of full adopters, partial adopters, and non-adopters of modern varieties (Table 9) shows the impact of modern varieties on total farm returns. In rainfed village C, the area planted to modern varieties is extremely small. Among the other two villages, partial adopters have shown about 10 percent increase in net income since 1969, and full adopters, who are relatively few in number and who started at a somewhat lower income level in 1969, made the largest gain.

Thus, the introduction of modern varieties in Don Chedi has achieved mixed success. Most farmers have tried modern varieties but

Table 8. Comparison of return above variable cost per hectare, variable cost per hectare, and variable cost per ton between modern varieties and traditional varieties in three villages, Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1971 wet season.

Village	Variety type	Farms (no.)	Land area (ha/farm)	Net return (baht/ha)	Cost (baht/ha)	Cost (baht/t)
A	Modern	40	2.4	1890	830	325
	Traditional	39	3.6	1416	624	286
B	Modern	43	1.7	1469	571	268
	Traditional	57	4.3	1010	350	282
C	Modern	13	0.6	1273	257	239
	Traditional	44	4.1	689	246	327

are still partial adopters. There appears to be a limitation to the full adoption on some farms as a result of flooding or deep water. But on the relatively large farms found in this area, farmers also tend to commit only a small additional amount of cash for production of modern varieties. Measures to encourage increased use of fertilizer and proper weed control over a wider area deserve consideration.

Philippines. Studies of the acceptance of improved varieties, input use, and resultant yields have been conducted in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines for the past 3 years (1969 and 1971 Annual Reports). This year we began a more detailed study of the relationships among environmental factors, management practices, and farm yields. One objective of the study is to determine how closely low yields are associated with environmental conditions which are largely beyond the control of individual farmers, as opposed to management practices which can be changed. We also intend to use the data to better understand the causes of low farm yields.

From each of three barrios in Gapan, 20 farms were selected randomly from all those intending to plant IR20, the dominant variety in the area. We then monitored the thoroughness of land preparation, weed competition, soil characteristics, insect and disease incidence, and nitrogen availability on one paddy from each of the farms. We used single paddies since they are relatively homogenous with respect to water and cultural management. All management of the crop was done by the farmer in his normal manner; the project was therefore conducted as a detailed survey rather than as a controlled experiment.

Data on water adequacy, rainfall, and solar radiation were collected for each paddy every day of the growing season. Exchangeable nitrogen (NO_3^- and NH_4^+) determinations were made at least four times during the season for each paddy, and weed incidence was measured by the dry weights of grasses, sedges, and broadleaved weeds twice for each paddy. Disease and insect incidence were assessed through observation of two sample areas of 4 square meters within each paddy at six periods of crop growth. Land preparation was evaluated

through measures of the depth and moisture content of the puddled layer, and the number of machine or carabao passes during harrowing and plowing. Crop performance was measured by tiller number and plant height at six periods, and by crop-cut yield sampling on the sample areas within the paddies. In addition, plant nitrogen content was measured for each sample area three times.

To compare the results from barrio to barrio, two of the 20 farmers in each barrio were chosen to receive a standard input package which consisted of 60 kg/ha N (split), carbofuran seedling root dip, and 2,4-D herbicide (0.8 kg/ha a.i.) applied 4 days after transplanting. Forty kilograms per hectare of P_2O_5 were applied to half of each standard paddy.

The project was carried out in the wet season in the barrios of San Nicolas and Malimba, which have irrigated farms, and in barrio Mahipon which has rainfed farms. The measurements will be continued with only minor changes in the two irrigated barrios during the 1973 dry season. Since complete analysis of the wet season data will take time, we are presenting only preliminary results.

Rainfall in all three barrios was very high for the first half of crop growth (fig. 5) due to the unprecedented floods of July. Paired values of rainfall (and solar radiation) for the same days were not significantly different in the barrios studied; however, the lack of irrigation on

Table 9. Return above variable cost per hectare on those farms that are full adopters, partial adopters, and non-adopters of modern varieties in 1971. Don Chedi, Suphan Buri, Thailand, 1971 and 1969 wet season.

Adopters of modern varieties	Farms (no.)	Area in modern varieties 1971 (%)	Net return (baht)	
			1969 ^a	1971
<i>Village A</i>				
Full adopters	8	100	903	1306
Partial adopters	31	35	1377	1544
Non-adopters	7	0	1579	1428
<i>Village B</i>				
Full adopters	2	100	954	2094
Partial adopters	41	27	1039	1178
Non-adopters	16	0	818	810
<i>Village C^b</i>				
Partial adopters	13	9	842	696
Non-adopters	31	0	369	696

^aNo high yielding varieties were planted in 1969.

^bNo full adopters.

5. Percentage of flooded paddies and mean daily rainfall for three barrios. Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

rainfed farms (Mahimpon) caused a delay in land preparation and transplanting, so that their cropping season was pushed back later in the rainy season. The delay of approximately 3 weeks meant that rainfed farms had significantly less rainfall at all growth periods and fewer flooded paddies during the second half of crop duration (fig. 5) than the irrigated farms (San Nicolas and Malimba). The chief value of irrigation for San Nicolas and Malimba is that it allows farmers to plant early in the season; once planted, those farms received more than enough rainfall to meet the crop's water requirement throughout almost all of the 1972 wet season.

Although the level of exchangeable nitrogen in the soil is related to time of nitrogen application, the exchangeable nitrogen level fell off quickly after transplanting in all three barrios

Table 10. Yields in three barrios, in relation to nitrogen application and dry weed weights. Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Nitrogen application level	Yield (t/ha)	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Weed wt ^a (kg/ha)
<i>San Nicolas</i>			
High	3.71	86	234
Low	3.47	51	112
<i>Malimba</i>			
High	3.32	66	282
Low	2.78	10	178
<i>Mahimpon</i>			
High	2.06	49	413
Low	1.88	19	286

^a35 days after transplanting.

(fig. 6). Mahimpon, in addition to its dependence upon rainfall, has soils with markedly less exchangeable nitrogen than the heavier, irrigated soils of the other two barrios, especially during early growth when nitrogen uptake is most important. Differences in soil type probably account for most of the difference in exchangeable nitrogen but, in addition, the floods of July probably caused considerable erosion of the higher paddies and carried much soil, and with it exchangeable nitrogen, to low-lying paddies such as those in Malimba.

In a preliminary examination of the relationship between nitrogen application, weed population, and yields, farms in each barrio were divided between those with above-average and those with below-average nitrogen application. High levels of nitrogen were more closely associated with high weed weights than with high rice yields (Table 10), which reflects the slight attention most farmers give to weed control. Yield response to nitrogen is clearly inhibited by high weed weights. Weeds are more serious in Mahimpon than in the other two barrios.

The standard input package was used on two farms in each barrio and the results were compared with those obtained by each farmer on an adjacent paddy, and with the average of all sample paddies in each barrio (Table 11). Application of phosphorus increased yields by about 0.5 t/ha in all three barrios. Phosphorus application caused the largest percentage yield gain in Mahimpon, because the soils in this area have very low levels of available phosphorus

Table 11. Nitrogen application and grain yield on paddies receiving a standard input package and on paddies adjacent to the paddies receiving the standard input package, as compared with the barrio average. Gapan, 1972 wet season.

Barrio	Observations	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Standard package paddies with phosphate^a</i>			
San Nicolas	2	60	4.6
Malimba	2	60	4.3
Mahipon	2	60	2.5
<i>Standard package paddies without phosphate^a</i>			
San Nicolas	2	60	4.1
Malimba	2	60	3.7
Mahipon	2	60	2.0
<i>Adjacent paddies^b</i>			
San Nicolas	2	81	3.5
Malimba	2	51	2.8
Mahipon	2	48	2.0
<i>Barrio average</i>			
San Nicolas	20	69	3.6
Malimba	20	35	3.1
Mahipon	20	26	2.1

^aTwo farmers in each barrio were helped in applying a standard package of inputs which consisted of a carbofuran root dip for seedlings and split application of urea with the first application at harrowing. In addition, half of each paddy received 40 kg/ha P_2O_5 and the other half received none. ^bPaddy which was managed by the farmer and which was adjacent to a paddy that received the standard input package.

(6.8 ppm, Olsen). Without phosphorus application, the other inputs of the standard package produced another 0.5 t/ha gain compared with the mean yield of the farmer-managed paddies in San Nicolas and Malimba, the irrigated barrios, but failed to make any difference in Mahipon, the rainfed barrio. Although the sample is too small for definitive conclusions, the soil and water conditions in Mahipon probably limited the response to the rest of the input package.

WATER MANAGEMENT

Our water management research involves assessing the impact of moisture stress on yields and using these findings to evaluate design and management alternatives for irrigation systems. Our analysis this year is based on experiments conducted on the IRRI farm and on the results of field investigations in existing irrigation systems.

Environment and moisture stress. We have reported experiments on the yield effects of applying water at rates from 4 to 8 mm/day throughout the season (1969 and 1970 Annual

6. Nitrogen fertilizer applied and exchangeable soil nitrogen at four crop growth stages. Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Reports). Although these trials were conducted uniformly and in the same plots on the IRRI farm, the yield responses were different in the 1969, 1970, and 1971 dry seasons. This year we analyzed the functional relationships for all 3 years to show how environmental and varietal differences modify the yield-stress relationship.

All three functions (fig. 7) show that IR8 yields are extremely sensitive to low levels of water input, but the critical level varies from season to season. Above the critical level yields approach asymptotic values.

For a given season, low yields are closely associated with the length of time during crop growth that soil moisture is seriously depleted (fig. 8). The 1969 dry season had more solar radiation during the last 45 days before harvest and less rainfall than either of the other seasons. The high solar radiation increased yields under the ample water treatments to levels higher than those in either 1970 or 1971. But under low levels of water application in 1969, the high solar radiation in combination with low rainfall appear to have depressed yields by accelerating the decline in soil moisture. Differences between the 1970 and 1971 relationships are more

7. Functional relations (logistics functions) between yield and water application intensity for IR8 (100 kg/ha N). IRRI, 1969, 1970, and 1971 dry seasons.

difficult to explain particularly for the ample water treatments. The greater rainfall and lower radiation in 1971 (fig. 8), however, are consistent with the higher yields that occurred in that year for the limited water application.

Thus, high solar radiation appears to be associated with high yields only where water is not a limiting resource. Under these conditions plant evapotranspiration can increase in response to high levels of solar energy. But with an insufficient supply of water, high solar energy causes greater moisture stress in the plants. For areas receiving limited water, therefore, higher yields can be expected in years when solar energy is lower, cloudy days are more frequent, and rainfall is greater.

Nitrogen response and moisture stress. Three varieties and lines were grown under three levels of nitrogen fertilizer in 1971 to determine varietal differences in the yield-stress relationships. The selections included IR5, a relatively tall variety with long growth duration; IR8, a short variety with medium growth duration; and

8. Soil moisture content in plots to which 5 mm/day of water was applied. IRRI, 1969, 1970, and 1971 dry seasons. (R = total rainfall, SR = incident solar radiation for 45 days before harvest.)

the line IR773A1-36-2, which is even shorter than IR8 and early maturing.

At zero nitrogen, IR8 and the IR773 line had essentially the same yields under all levels of water input and IR5 clearly outyielded both for all water treatments (fig. 9). At 50 kg/ha N, all yield levels were higher and IR8 started to reveal its potential. Under the ample water treatments, IR8 and IR5 had about the same yields. IR5 remained superior for the low water treatments and the IR773 line yielded the least under all water conditions. Nitrogen applications of 100 kg/ha further increased all yields. With high applications of both nitrogen and water, IR8 outyielded IR5, but under the low water treatments, IR5 remained higher yielding.

Whenever water input was low the IR773 line suffered from its inability to provide good crop cover. Conversely, the vegetative nature of IR5 may explain its remarkable performance under low levels of water input at all three nitrogen application rates. Maximum yields thus are achieved with plentiful water and nitrogen by efficient varieties such as IR8. When water is inadequate, taller and more vegetative varieties appear better able to conserve and make use of available moisture.

Economic performance of pumping systems. Should a pump be used to distribute a limited

Table 12. Net farm income and benefit-cost ratios for basic irrigation pumping systems (4-inch shallow tubewell with centrifugal pump financed through private bank loans).^a

Water applied (mm/day)	Experimental yield (t/ha)	Pump operated 10 h/day				Pump operated 14 h/day			
		Area irrig. (ha)	Net farm income (₱)	Pump benefit- cost ratio ^b	Farm benefit- cost ratio ^c	Area irrig. (ha)	Net farm income (₱)	Pump benefit- cost ratio ^b	Farm benefit- cost ratio ^c
5	4.65	4.8	330	1.0	1.0	6.0	670	1.4	1.0
6	7.30	4.0	4040	4.7	1.6	5.6	5930	6.5	1.7
7	8.74	3.4	4850	5.5	1.8	4.8	7010	7.6	1.9
8	8.83	3.0	4410	5.0	1.8	4.2	6450	7.0	1.9
9	8.88	2.6	3890	4.5	1.8	3.7	5680	6.3	1.9

^aBased on 1969 water response function (fig. 7) and cost and returns data from R. D. Reyes (unpublished). ^bDiscounted net farm income divided by investment cost of the pump. ^cDiscounted total farm income divided by total farm costs, including investment and operating cost of the pump.

amount of water over a wide area, or should the water be concentrated on a smaller area? We examined this question using the results of the 1969 dry season experiment shown in figure 7. We calculated net farm income, yield benefits, and costs for a 4-inch (10 cm) centrifugal pump operating from a shallow tubewell for 10 or 14 hours per day. The area that can be irrigated becomes less as the daily depth of water applied increases since we assumed the pump discharge to be constant at 6.6 liter/s throughout the season. That value was the mean discharge taken from a sample of 4-inch pumps in Nueva Ecija during the 1969 dry season.

The maximum net farm income occurs when 7 mm/day of water is applied (Table 12). Below that level, net income falls off due to sharply reduced yield; at higher levels, net

income drops because of the increased cost of operating the pump. But farmers' fields lose more water than our experimental fields, so we consider 9 mm/day a more reasonable rate for use in designing pump installations. At that rate 2.6 hectares of land can be irrigated with 10 hours of operation per day, or 3.7 hectares can be irrigated with 14 hours per day. The net income to the farmer would be ₱3,890 or ₱5,680, respectively.

We computed two benefit-cost ratios (Table 12) for each application rate. The pump benefit-cost ratio is a measure of expected profitability from investing in pumps. The farm benefit-cost ratio is a measure of the profitability of rice farming in the dry season with a pump. Investment in pumps shows high returns, but for the whole farm operation the benefit-cost ratios are

9. Functional relations (logistics functions) between rice yield and water application intensity for varieties IR8, IR5, and the line IR773A1-36-2 with 0, 50, and 100 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

much lower. We also calculated net income and benefit-cost ratios for a 5-inch (13 cm) centrifugal pump drawing from a shallow tubewell and for a 10-inch (25 cm) deep-well turbine and found that they are about the same as those for the 4-inch pump.

These results represent maximum economic returns that can be expected, since they are based upon high yields achieved under experimental conditions. To determine the sensitivity of the economic indices to yields, we computed the minimum yield required to provide a 2 : 1 return on the investment cost of a pump. For 10 hours operation per day and 9 mm/day water application, a yield of 6.4 t/ha is required. This yield results in a net farm income of ₱1,340 and a farm benefit-cost ratio of 1.2 : 1. At 14 hours operation per day and the same water application rate, the required yield is 5.7 t/ha, but the net farm income and farm benefit-cost

ratio are unchanged. Thus, with levels of operation up to 14 hours per day, the area that can be adequately irrigated from small pumps greatly depends upon the hours of operation and the water application rate. The yields required to obtain a 2 : 1 return on investment in pumps are higher than those attained by most farmers even with the use of improved cultural practices. The economic returns to the whole farm operation are favorable but much less than those accruing to pump investment.

Stress at different growth stages. Irrigation systems in the humid tropics usually lack storage facilities so the systems often do not have enough water to adequately irrigate the entire area they are supposed to serve. If rice varieties have different stages of growth which are more or less sensitive to drought, system managers could allocate the limited water supply to the crops at their most vulnerable stages. In the 1972 dry season we studied the yield response to comparable stress periods imposed at different stages of growth. In addition, we used two nitrogen treatments to explore possible interaction between nitrogen and stress. We also measured the amount of water applied to determine the effects of the stress periods on water use.

The experiment was conducted on a portion of the IRRI farm in which underground water movement was unlikely. Randomization of the water treatments was not attempted in order to minimize the chance that lateral seepage would destroy the treatment control. Two replications were used with plots of 144 sq m surrounded by bunds, metal levees, and larger plots to which the same treatments were applied.

The four treatments were *no stress*—continual flooding throughout crop growth; *early stress*—no irrigation for 1 month during the vegetative growth stage; *late stress*—no irrigation for 1 month beginning just before panicle initiation; and *late stress to harvest*—no irrigation from just before panicle initiation to harvest. Light rains fell during the treatments, so the stress periods were extended until pan evaporation for the additional days equalled the rainfall.

Continual flooding (no stress) gave the highest yields, followed in order by early stress, late stress, and late stress to harvest (Table 13).

10. Drained periods, soil moisture content, and rainfall at different growth stages, F = flowering; H = harvesting. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Table 13. Water use and grain yield of IR20 under four water treatments and basal or split applications of 100 kg/ha N. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Water treatment ^a	Days drained (no.)	Yield (t/ha)			Tillers (no./sq m)	Plant ht (cm)	Water use ^c (mm)	Yield productivity of water (kg/mm)
		Basal N application	Split N application ^b	Avg				
No stress	0	6.0	6.4	6.2	350	111	773	8.1
Early stress	38	4.5	4.4	4.4	336	94	788	5.6
Late stress	39	2.2	1.9	2.0	318	83	806	2.5
Late stress to harvest	54	0.8	0.2	0.5	298	72	338	1.5

^aNo stress = flooded throughout crop growth. Early stress = no irrigation from 43 to 81 days after seeding. Late stress = no irrigation from 63 to 102 days after seeding. Late stress to harvest = no irrigation from 63 days after seeding to harvest. ^bTwo-thirds basal; one-third at panicle initiation. ^cFrom transplanting to about a week before harvest. Includes all rainfall.

Early stress was significantly less damaging to yield than either of the late stress periods. The crop's appearance recovered quite well from moisture stress during the vegetative stage but it did not recover from stress that lasted into the reproductive period. In addition, the average soil moisture content during the early stress treatment was higher than that during the others (fig. 10). The soil puddling process just before transplanting saturates the soil with water, but this reservoir of water decreases with time even when the paddy is continually flooded. Late stress periods, therefore, begin with the soil having less available moisture. Tiller number and plant height were reduced as yields declined (Table 13). No significant difference in yield was found between the nitrogen treatments.

The water use data (Table 13) show that a savings in water cannot be expected where normal crop growth is interrupted by an extended drought. Large cracks develop in the soil and drain away a large portion of the water when it is first resupplied. Even after the soil is saturated again following the stress treatments, the amount of water needed daily to keep the plots flooded was considerably greater than before the stress period.

The same treatments were used in a 1-hectare field in Pila, Laguna, to test the results under farm conditions. Three replications were used and the variety planted was IR12-178. Two of the replications were unsatisfactory because underground water movement affected the stressed paddies. One replication, however, was high enough in elevation to avoid underground water supply. Yields from this replication were

lower than those on the IRRI farm, but the trend among treatments was similar. Yields from the continuously flooded paddies were 5.5 t/ha compared with 2.6 t/ha for the early stress treatment, 0.5 t/ha for late stress, and nothing for late stress to harvest. Because of the light soil at Pila, moisture stress reduced yields more than at the IRRI farm. The nitrogen treatments caused little difference in yields.

On the basis of these experiments, yield reduction can be expected whenever several weeks of drought occur. For IR20 the yield loss is approximately twice as serious if a month-long drought occurs during a period extending into reproductive growth, compared with a 1-month drought during early crop growth. Essentially no yield can be expected if water is withheld from the beginning of reproductive growth until harvest. Although splitting the application of nitrogen was not significantly better than a single basal application, farmers are nevertheless likely to use split application as a hedge against complete crop failure where severe droughts sometimes occur.

Estimating yield loss with stress days. We have analyzed data from a 1969-70 study by the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture (UPCA) and the National Irrigation Administration (NIA) designed to estimate yield benefits due to irrigation, and to identify water management practices which affect the benefits. The project was conducted in 11 sites averaging 25 hectares each within major diversion irrigation systems in the provinces of Nueva Ecija, Bulacan, and Laguna. Data on crop response to moisture deficiency and on water use were

11. Response of improved rice varieties to nitrogen fertilizer under farm conditions at three levels of moisture stress in the vegetative stage (early stress) and reproductive stage (late stress). Luzon, Philippines, 1969-1970.

obtained from essentially the same sites for both the wet and dry seasons. The data reflect farm conditions in that no attempt was made to influence the ways farmers managed their crops or handled water.

Crop response to moisture stress was established from 292 paddies on which a daily check of surface water was made. We defined "stress days" as the number of days in excess of three that a paddy was continuously without standing water. Crop-cut yield data for those paddies were then regressed on nitrogen, stress days incurred during vegetative growth, stress days incurred during the first month of reproductive growth, and the interaction of vegetative stress days and nitrogen. Stress days were separated into two periods to bring out the stress effect more clearly since the later stress period

had more effect than early stress on yields of the improved varieties. Half of these varieties were IR5, with the rest equally divided between IR8 and C4-63. For traditional varieties (mostly Binato and Intan), stress during the later growth stages was only weakly associated with yield loss. The improved varieties outyielded the traditional varieties by only 14 percent (3.3 vs. 2.9 t/ha) in the study sites.

To establish the combined effect of nitrogen and stress on the yield of modern varieties we computed, for the wet season, the equation

$$Y = 2790 + 41.5N - 0.50N^2 - 50.2S_1^{**} - 20.4S_2 + 0.76NS_1^{**} \quad (1)$$

$N = 126; R^2 = 0.21^{**}$

and for the dry season

$$Y = 3600 + 17.9N - 0.14N^2 - 35.2S_1 - 94.4S_2^{**} + 0.54NS_1 \quad (2)$$

$N = 92; R^2 = 0.49^{**}$

where Y is yield of rough rice in kilograms per hectare, N is nitrogen applied in kilograms per hectare; S_1 is early stress (number of days in excess of three that the paddy was drained within the period from transplanting to 60 days before harvest), and S_2 is late stress (number of days in excess of three that the paddy was drained within the period from 60 to 30 days before harvest). We used days before harvest rather than days after transplanting so that S_2 would specify the same physiological growth stage (early reproductive) in all varieties regardless of their vegetative growth durations.

Without stress the nitrogen response is higher in the dry season than in the wet season (fig. 11), but when stress occurs the yield reduction is considerably greater in the dry season, particularly when the stress occurs late. This finding supports the idea that when water is inadequate, higher yields are associated with reduced solar energy.

Early stress reduced yields much less when nitrogen applications were heavy. This is partly because substantial amounts of nitrogen are lost through drought, so the crop responds to subsequent applications. Furthermore, greater use of nitrogen encourages root development which expands the volume of soil from which the plant can draw moisture. Although nitrogen application seemed to offset most of the effect of early stress for improved varieties, it appar-

Table 14. Water use during land preparation. Luzon, Philippines, 1969-70.

Initial field condition	Duration (days)	Net irrig. (mm)	Rainfall (mm)	Drainage (mm)	Net use (mm)	Evaporation (mm)	Land soaking (mm)	Efficiency ^a (%)
Dry ^b	52	851	289	417	723	223	500	44
Moist ^c	56	526	182	339	369	198	171	24

^aLand soaking divided by the sum of net irrigation and rainfall.

^bMeans for nine sites in which land preparation began from dry fallow conditions.

^cMeans for five sites in which land preparation began soon after the harvest of a previous crop.

ently did not for the traditional varieties in our study. Nor did nitrogen application offset late stress for either variety group.

The effect of early stress on the grain yield of some improved varieties, especially IR5, was weak in part because it delayed panicle initiation. As a result, instead of inefficient plant development during stress, development stopped until water was resupplied. The growth duration of the improved varieties was therefore strongly affected by the length of early stress—every 6 days of early stress increased growth duration by 5 days.

Performance of canal irrigation systems. Equations (1) and (2) which relate stress days to yield can be used to estimate yield benefits due to irrigation provided that stress days can be determined from the effective depths of water supplied each day. To do this, all the water entering and leaving each site in the UPCA/NIA study was measured daily, and water balances were computed.

Water use. The average duration of land preparation—from the beginning of irrigation until the median date of transplanting—was 7 to 8 weeks in both seasons. During land preparation the sites received almost 1 m of water from rainfall and irrigation (Table 14). In dry sites—those not recently harvested—half the water was used to soak the land, while in sites just harvested about one-fourth was used for soaking. The rest of the water was lost to drainage and evaporation.

The wet season sites received almost 2 m of water during the growing period of the crop (Table 15). Net use (seepage and percolation into the soil plus evapotranspiration) amounted to nearly 40 percent of the total. The rest went off as surface drainage. In the dry season, net use increased by about 50 percent, but the field

efficiency rose to 68 percent, so that a smaller total supply was required to fill the increased need. Frequent heavy rain in the wet season is one reason efficiency is lower in the wet season than in the dry season. Farmers almost always try to keep their paddies flooded, so much of the rainfall in the wet season merely runs off. A second reason is that in the dry season some sites are so dry that little drainage occurs. Both rainfall, as a percentage of total water received, and the percentage of the site flooded were negatively correlated with field efficiencies.

Evapotranspiration was relatively uniform among the sites in each season. It was only a small part of the total water balance. Seepage and percolation was over 16mm/day for one-tenth of the sites, and over 7 mm/day for one-fourth of them. Excessive seepage and percolation occurs primarily because farmers attempt to irrigate marginal portions of sites next to creeks or rivers where the soils are light or there is a nearby drain for the seepage. High seepage and percolation rates also occur where small irrigated sites in the dry season are surrounded by unirrigated fields.

Table 15. Water use after transplanting by season (means of 11 sites). Luzon, Philippines, 1969-70.

Item	Water use (mm)	
	Wet season	Dry season
Net irrigation	1090	1475
Rainfall	850	210
Drainage	1210	537
Net use	730	1148
Net use per day	6.5	10.2
Evaporation per day	3.4	5.6
Efficiency ^a (%)	38	68

^aNet use divided by the sum of net irrigation and rainfall.

12. Mean effect of bund height on grain yield and water use efficiency for 10 synthesized rainfed sites in the wet season. Luzon, Philippines, 1969-1970.

A model for estimating yield benefits. To determine stress days, the water balance must be computed on a daily basis, rather than over whole seasons. To do this, we used rainfall and irrigation values recorded in the field, and estimates of evapotranspiration and seepage and percolation depending on recorded evaporation and other factors.

When the daily values of the negative terms (evapotranspiration and seepage and percolation) do not equal the positive terms (rainfall and irrigation), then the amount of water stored in the paddy, that is, the depth of water in the paddy, is changing. We hypothesized that when

this depth exceeded the effective height of the paddy dikes or bunds, the excess water was lost as surface drainage. Using this mechanism as our model, we computed drainage values for the sites which closely approximated measured drainage. During periods of low rainfall and little irrigation, the water level in the paddy fell to zero and even to negative values. Since this is analogous to the definition of stress days on a single paddy, the model could then be used to generate stress days from data on daily rainfall, irrigation, and evaporation, and from an estimate of the maximum seepage and percolation possible at each site.

This procedure was used in calculating the number of stress days which were then used in equations (1) and (2) to estimate yields. Using rainfall and irrigation data from each site, the model computed a mean yield of 3.23 t/ha for the wet season sites. This is within 4 percent of the mean crop-cut yield figure for the same sites. Stress was a barrier to higher yield levels for many of the sites because their irrigation supply was imperfect. The mean no-stress yield computed by the model was 3.46 t/ha.

Rainfed yields were also computed, by suppressing all irrigation inputs in the model to zero. Rainfall alone accounted for yields of 2.55 t/ha. Supplemental irrigation therefore gave a mean of 0.7 t/ha higher yields to the eight wet season sites largely planted to improved varieties (Table 16). This benefit was worth P460 (P0.68/kg of rough rice). Yields would have been 0.23 t/ha higher, however, if the amount of irrigation had met all the water requirements of the sites. The value of the lost yield was approximately one-third the size of the mean benefit of irrigation, and several times greater than the irrigation fee which farmers were asked to pay. The mean shortfall in the dry season was over 0.5 t/ha of rice, worth P375. Yield increases due to irrigation would be larger than those computed here if greater use of inputs such as nitrogen and weed control were assumed under conditions of better irrigation. Interviews showed that farmers are greatly concerned about the shortfall. Although these results were computed only from 1969-70 data, rainfall for these years was approximately the same as the average for the past 20 years in the areas studied.

Table 16. Summary of model predictions, means of eight wet and dry season sites planted to improved varieties. Luzon, Philippines, 1969-70.

Item	Wet season		Dry season	
	Yield (t/ha)	Gross value (P/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Gross value (P/ha)
Predicted yield				
No-stress conditions	3.46		4.06	
Actual stress conditions	3.23		3.51	
Shortfall	0.23	157	0.55	375
Predicted rainfed yield	2.55		—	
Production directly attributable to irrigation	0.68	460	3.51	2400

Bund height. Experimental studies have frequently concluded that farmers could make better use of scarce water supplies by building higher paddy bunds to store more water. The hypothesis is subject to test by the model.

We computed yields for different bund heights for all the wet season sites under simulated rainfed conditions. Increasing the bund height from 2 to 8 cm increases yield by only about 0.1 t/ha, and water use efficiency from 75 to 80 percent (fig. 12). The slopes indicate that bunds higher than 8 cm would give even smaller gains. The effective height of bunds in the sites we studied was only about 4 cm. These findings are not surprising because at the farm level seepage and percolation losses are often large and periods of water shortage are frequently long. The small amount of water stored on the paddy is then relatively unimportant.

Effectiveness of rainfall. Since rainfall often is poorly distributed, much of it runs off from the paddy and is not available for crop growth. The amount used relative to the total available is important in designing and managing irrigation systems. Although the model cannot be used directly to determine the effectiveness of rainfall, it can compute stress days and yields for crops served only by irrigation, for comparison with stress days and yields for crops served by irrigation and rainfall. The difference is a measure of the usefulness of rainfall in the irrigated sites.

We analyzed data from 10 wet season sites and found that rainfall added only 0.4 t/ha (12%) to the mean yield of 2.9 t/ha from irrigation alone. Almost all the gain came from three sites which had a shortage of irrigation water. It can be concluded that in the wet season, farmers rely principally on irrigation, and only secondarily on rainfall, just as they do in the dry season. This is consistent with the way in which diversion irrigation systems operate, for they cannot store excess river flow, and there is therefore no direct value to economizing in water use. Under such management the value of rainfall is small, and farmers act quite logically in using irrigation liberally. But managers of diversion systems to which storage reservoirs are being added will need to provide additional incentives to save water in the wet season for use in the dry season.

Water use efficiency and yield reduction. The

13. Relation between water use efficiency and yield reduction due to moisture stress on 21 crop sites. Luzon, Philippines, 1969-1970.

model also provides a framework for examining the relation between field efficiency (evapotranspiration plus seepage and percolation as a percentage of total water delivered), and the effects of water shortage on yields. The yield effects were computed for each site by taking the reduced yield due to stress as a percentage of yield without stress. Figure 13 shows that a serious sacrifice in yield occurs on sites whose water use efficiency reaches about 50 percent, a rather low value.

The negative association between efficiency and yields in existing systems is due in part to an inability to deliver water to all parts of the system during critical periods of the season. When the supply of water becomes seriously limiting much less is lost to drainage, and field efficiencies increase. Ways of improving water use efficiency without sacrificing yield must be found. Any significant improvement will require more intensive control of water flow within the systems.

At present it is unclear what direction this intensification should take. To help answer this question, we interviewed the farmers in the study sites and compared the responses of those who had farms served by the first half of distribution canals with those who had farms served by the

Table 17. Farmers' attitudes toward five water management problems in relation to farm location within irrigation systems. Luzon, Philippines, 1969 and 1970.

Question	Farmers answering "yes" (%) ^a					
	Along canal length			Distance from canal		
	1st half	2nd half	χ^2	Within 300 m	Beyond 300 m	χ^2
Is water supply adequate? ^b	80	59	10.9**	70	74	0.6
Willing to pay more for pump water? ^c	38	73	15.9**	56	51	0.4
Reporting conflicts over water use? ^c	11	24	3.8*	15	20	0.5
Is the water use fee too high? ^c	78	52	7.4**	58	77	4.1*
Willing to schedule irrigation deliveries? ^c	85	97	5.0*	95	86	3.3

^aChi-squared test conducted on number of yes responses in 2 × 2 contingency table ($d_f = 1$). ^bN = 231. ^cN = 104.

second half. A second breakdown was made based on whether the farm was located within or beyond an arbitrary line drawn 300 meters from the canal.

The proportion of farmers satisfied with the amount of water they received was significantly higher among those with farms served by the first half of the canal (Table 17). Farmers served by the second half reported significantly more conflicts, were more satisfied with the water use fee, were more willing to schedule water deliveries, and were more willing to pay extra for pump irrigation. The stratification according to distance laterally away from the canal showed little difference in any of the responses.

A major problem of water management therefore is getting enough water to the farther reaches of the primary distribution canals. The movement of water laterally away from the canal seems to be satisfactory even in the traditional systems we studied in which the density of farm ditches was not high. One reason is that the paddies close to the canal tend to be high in elevation and to have light soil texture, while

those farther away are closer to the water table and have heavier soil (fig. 14). As a result the farther paddies have a lower water requirement which compensates for their greater distance from the source of water.

These findings indicate that distribution of water along the full lengths of canals is a primary requirement for improved water availability and fewer stress days. The lateral movement of water from the canal appears to be reasonably satisfactory. Ultimately, improvements in both are likely to be important, but at present the paddy-to-paddy movement of water among farms does not seem to be a serious impediment to satisfactory water distribution.

AGGREGATE OUTPUT GROWTH

Two studies explore aggregate relationships in output growth and input requirements. One examines alternative ways of achieving a specific rice production target for Central Luzon in 1980. The second is part of a study of total agricultural growth and productivity in four countries

Table 18. Level of output and input requirement for the year 1980 based on three objectives. Central Luzon, Philippines.

Item	1970	1980 objectives		
		Max. net farm income	Max. net social income	Max. employment
Output (thousand t)	1200	1800	1800	1800
Effective crop area (thousand ha)	635	721	711	737
Yield (kg/ha)	2000	2400	2500	2400
Nitrogen (kg/ha)	9	25	28	35
Employment (man-day/ha)	65	70	71	72
Irrigated crop area added (thousand ha)	—	137	124	153
Irrigation investment added (mil. ₱)	—	408	215	453
Foreign exchange added (mil. \$)	—	38	21	44

14. Cross section of a typical rice landform.

(Japan, Korea, Taiwan, and the Philippines). Initial findings were presented in the 1971 Annual Report.

Rice production in Luzon, 1980. A linear programming model of the lowland rice sector of Central Luzon was formulated. We established a rough rice production target for 1980 of 1.8 million metric tons by assuming that the Philippines would be self-sufficient, that consumption requirements would increase at 3.5 percent per year, and that Central Luzon would continue to produce 25 percent of the national total as it did in the latter part of the 1960's. We further assumed that the land base is fixed, and therefore, that all growth in output must come from increases in land productivity. Land productivity is increased in the model by increasing inputs of labor and chemicals, by expanding irrigation in either the wet or dry season, or by some combination of these two.

Three objective functions were considered: maximization of net social income, of net farm income, or of employment. Net social income differs from net farm income in that it includes the full cost of gravity irrigation which in the Philippines is not charged to the farmer. Net farm income is a measure of net return above variable costs. It is determined by subtracting from the gross returns for rice production the cash costs for chemicals, irrigation, and hired labor, and the non-cash costs for payment in kind to hired labor. Fixed costs for land and family labor are not included in the computation. Finally, in maximizing the total employment, no

distinction was made between family and hired labor.

The objective functions we considered result in different demands for irrigation, nitrogen, and labor. In all three solutions, however, at least a third of the growth in output is achieved by a substantial expansion in effective crop area through increased irrigation (Tables 18 and 19). When net social income is maximized, the full cost of irrigation is charged and emphasis is placed on raising land productivity through more intensive use of fertilizer and other cash inputs. Of course, to expand use of fertilizer at 13.6 percent per year may require a greater extension effort or a fertilizer subsidy both of which involve additional social costs.

Table 19. Comparative annual rates of growth in selected items for 1960/62 to 1968/70 and projected for 1970 to 1980 based on three objectives. Central Luzon, Philippines.

Item	Annual growth rate (%)			
	1960/62-1968/70 ^a	1970/80 objectives		
		Max. net farm income	Max. net social income	Max. employment
Output	4.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
Effective crop area	2.2	1.3	1.1	1.5
Yield per hectare	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.0
Irrigated crop area	4.4	3.3	3.0	3.6
Nitrogen applied	—	12.8	13.6	16.5
Man-days employed	—	2.1	2.0	2.6
Net farm income	—	3.4	3.3	2.8
Net social income	—	2.8	3.0	2.1

^aBased on data from Philippine Bureau of Census and Bureau of Agricultural Economics.

Table 20. Annual compound rates of growth of agricultural production by commodities of selected inputs, and of total productivity, Philippines, 1949-1968^a

Item	Growth (%)					
	1949-1955	1955-1958	1958-1965	1965-1968	1955-1968	1949-1968
Total output	6.0	1.7	3.4	4.3	3.2	4.1
Rice	4.4	2.3	2.1	4.4	2.6	3.2
Corn	7.1	4.8	5.0	7.7	5.6	6.1
Coconuts	4.9	2.0	3.4	1.1	2.5	3.3
Sugar	10.4	4.0	3.7	1.0	3.2	5.4
Other crops	11.0	4.3	4.7	1.2	3.8	6.0
Livestock	5.1	-1.0	3.3	7.5	3.3	3.9
Total inputs	4.1	4.2	2.1	3.3	2.8	3.3
Employment	2.9	2.7	2.0	0.0	1.6	2.0
Cultivated land area	4.1	3.2	1.0	1.5	1.6	2.4
Crop area	4.8	3.9	1.6	2.2	2.3	3.0
Farm machinery	9.8	8.1	8.0	7.8	8.0	8.5
Fertilizer	12.7	22.0	4.8	18.0	11.6	11.9
Total productivity	1.9	-2.5	1.3	1.0	0.4	0.8

^a3-year average centered at the years shown.

Maximizing employment leads to the greatest expansion in both irrigation and nitrogen requirements, resulting in an inefficient use of total resources and a reduction in the income growth rate.

The growth rates in input use specified in these projections for 1980 do not seem unreasonable in the light of previous experience (Table 19). But the objective of maximizing net farm income, which is close to present government policy, requires 30,000 hectares of irrigation in addition to the 106,000 hectares now being developed by the Upper Pampanga River Project.

Philippine agriculture, 1948 to 1969. During the postwar period, Philippine agricultural output grew at the average annual rate of 4.1 percent (Table 20). Total input use increased at 3.3 percent per year, and total productivity (total output divided by total input) at 0.8 percent per year. Philippine agriculture during this period appears to have been in transition from dependence on traditional inputs—land and labor—to dependence on modern inputs—

Table 21. Relative contribution of area and yield to total growth in production of four major Philippine crops in two periods.

Crop	Annual growth in output (%)	Change (%) in output due to change in	
		Area	Yield
<i>1949 to 1959^a</i>			
Rice	3.7	115	-15
Corn	6.4	114	-14
Sugarcane	9.3	86	14
Coconuts	3.6	13	87
<i>1959 to 1968^a</i>			
Rice	2.3	-3	103
Corn	5.4	49	51
Sugarcane	2.2	140	-40
Coconuts	3.6	180	-80

^a3-year average centered at the year shown.

irrigation, fertilizer, new seeds—as the major source of growth in output and productivity.

The high growth rate up to 1955 resulted in part from the postwar recovery. In the late 1950's productivity declined as a result of changes in tariff rates on U.S. exports, an overvalued currency that discouraged exports, and unfavorable weather conditions.

The agricultural revival in the 1960's was led first by a boom in the export crop sector and then by a boom in the food grains sector. What distinguished the latter from the former was the reliance on growth in land productivity as the major source of output growth (Table 21). Coconut and sugarcane yields per hectare tended to decline after 1960, while rice and corn yields rose sharply.

In future years, feed grain, livestock, and "other crops" may take a larger percentage of agricultural production than they have in the past. The "other crops" sector might be dominated by exports such as bananas if the Philippines can take advantage of the situation created by the sharp rise in the cost of agricultural production in Taiwan. But the major challenge that faces agriculture is the need to sustain a high rate of output and productivity growth through the use of modern inputs.

Agricultural engineering

The IRRI 5-hp to 7-hp power tiller has been widely accepted in the Philippines. Two manufacturers

turn out more than 200 tractors per month, and other manufacturers are beginning production. An IRRI 1-ton batch drier is now being built locally and sold for half the price of comparable imported models. Refinements in the design of an axial-flow and a PTO-driven thresher also neared completion. □ Test and evaluation activities are determining the feasibility of improved transplanting methods. Locally built threshing designs were tested and reviewed as candidates for design improvement. Better machines now reach the market sooner because of IRRI's systematic testing of manufacturers' prototype equipment. □ Economic and technical research on present rice processing systems indicate considerable scope for improvement. The role of credit in the promotion and growth of mechanization was studied carefully. Marketing research indicates a need for an 8-hp to 14-hp walking tractor.

FIELD MACHINERY

5-hp to 7-hp power tiller. Two companies currently produce and market about 200 IRRI power tillers per month in the Philippines. Four other firms will soon begin production. The power tiller, complete with 5-hp to 7-hp gasoline engine, cage wheels, comb harrow, and mold-board plow, sells in the Philippines for approximately US\$500, or roughly half the price of comparable imported machines. The effect of this low-cost alternative in broadening the market is shown in figure 1. Only 16 hectares a year must be farmed to justify investment in an IRRI power tiller, compared with 28 hectares to purchase an imported tiller. As costs rise for imported equipment and maintenance of water buffalos, the relative advantage of the IRRI machine will increase.

Extensive testing of the second prototype machine indicated that several minor design changes would be desirable. We modified the input shaft of the power transmission unit (fig. 2), eliminating the cantilever arrangement of the pulley-driven shaft. We also replaced the light-duty ball bearings of the input shaft and the countershaft with a heavy-duty type. The axles

2. Original transmission of the 5-hp power tiller, left. Revised transmission, right.

were made thicker (3.2 cm) to reduce failures resulting from overloading. The thickness of the wall of the chain transmission housing was increased to 0.31 cm to minimize flexing and fatigue failure.

We tested manufacturers' initial production units and found the following defects: broken engine mountings, defective weld joints on the axle, cage wheel deformation and spoke failure, countershaft misalignment, and oil seal leaks. The test reports were submitted to the manufacturers who corrected these problems before beginning regular production. Each company offers a trailer and rubber tires as optional equipment for road travel as well as optional attachments for lowland tillage. We are developing a set of tools for upland cultivation.

8-hp to 14-hp power tiller. Examination of the Philippine tractor market revealed an expanding demand for 8-hp to 14-hp power tillers. Field interviews indicated that most farmers who now own 5-hp to 7-hp tillers want larger ones when they replace their present models. Imported double-axle tillers now available use diesel engines and are equipped with integrally

1. Total cost of land preparation with the IRRI 5-hp to 7-hp tiller compared with the cost of custom work and comparable imported tillers.

mounted rotary tillers. They are well suited for tillage in heavy soils. Such tractors are heavy, but individual steering clutches make turning easy.

We designed an 8-hp to 14-hp tiller (fig. 3) equipped with steering clutches and a three-speed transmission. Because multi-speed gear transmissions are difficult to manufacture, a standard automotive three-speed gearbox was used as the first-stage reduction unit and a chain and sprocket assembly enclosed in an oil bath was used for secondary reduction. The primary transmission is attached to the secondary transmission case through a bolted bracket, permitting different types of automotive transmissions to be used without major changes in the basic tiller design. This will make production of the machine in developing countries easier.

The secondary transmission (fig. 4) is a two-step reduction using No. 60 and No. 80 roller chains. The primary reduction shaft has two dog-type steering clutches. These clutches are normally spring-loaded in the engaged position during straight travel. While turning, each clutch can be disengaged individually with a lever on the tiller handle. The relatively low torque on the primary shaft permits easy engagement and disengagement under full load. Engine power is transmitted through two V-belts to the primary transmission. An idler pulley on the V-belts engages and disengages the power. The tractor's general design is similar to the 5-hp to 7-hp IRR I tiller. The prototype unit of the basic tractor is complete and work is under way on the integrally mounted tiller.

40-hp tractor. The market for four-wheel tractors in developing nations generally is small. Importing tractors from industrialized regions drains foreign exchange. But many countries in Asia import large numbers of automobiles and wide distribution and competitive markets have generally kept prices of automotive parts low. If tractors made primarily of locally available automobile components can be designed, then local production and increased market volume will lower tractor prices.

Figure 5 shows the preliminary design of such a tractor. It will use any standard four-cylinder automotive engine, gasoline or diesel. The power train consists of a primary jeep or car

3. Eight- to fourteen-horsepower tiller.

transmission, a secondary differential from a weapons carrier or truck, and two reduction housings at the wheels. It is designed to operate at 2.4 km/h in the lowest gear. Each rear wheel has an independent braking system with a separate hydraulic master cylinder which can be engaged individually by one of two pedals.

4. Transmission of the 8-hp to 14-hp double-axle power tiller.

5. Forty-horsepower tractor with automotive parts.

The pedals can be locked to simultaneously brake both wheels.

The power take-off is designed according to standards of the American Society of Agricultural Engineers and will provide 540 rpm at 2200 engine rpm. Its power is tapped through a special gearbox between the primary transmission and the engine flywheel housing, permitting use of the standard clutch while engaging and disengaging the PTO dog clutch. The tractor is equipped with a three-point linkage (ASAE Category II) with a simple external hydraulic system to raise and lower implements. The hydraulic pump is driven through a V-belt from the crankshaft pulley. The final reduction boxes at the rear axles use multistrand chains which are available in most developing countries. The transmission box, the rear axle drop housings, the chassis, and the sheet metal components must be built locally.

Multicrop, axial-flow thresher. The need for an economical throw-in-type thresher that has high output prompted development of the multicrop, axial-flow thresher.

The machine consists of a wire-loop threshing drum 35 cm in diameter and 127 cm long, with a concave screen enclosing the full length of the cylinder (fig. 6). A 6.5-hp aircooled engine powers the machine. Spiral baffles in the upper concave move the material in an axial direction. A blower, 20 cm in diameter, winnows the grain falling through the concave, removing lighter impurities such as chaff and dirt. A 7.6 cm auger

moves the winnowed grain to one end of the thresher. The grain drops onto a rotary cleaner which removes heavier impurities. Rubber flaps elevate the grain in a trough for delivery. The thresher has rubber wheels for easy mobility.

The cover can be easily opened to clean the concaves and thresher drum. The threshing output varies, depending upon crop yield and feeding rate, but has been higher than 1,000 kg/h of paddy in tests. Grain loss has been 2 to 3 percent in tests with freshly harvested paddy.

The machine is being tested and evaluated for other crops such as sorghum, soybean, and mung bean.

PTO thresher. The design for the threshing component of the PTO-driven thresher has been improved. Threshing output with freshly harvested crops has ranged from 1.1 to 2.0 t/h with 93 percent separation.

We attempted to reduce separation losses by retaining threshed materials in the rotary separator for a longer time. By changing the paddle angles on the central straw-throwing auger from 40° to 60°, we slowed movement of the threshed material in the inner cylinder. Addition of three wire rakes, slanted toward the straw thrower, better dispersed the straw lumps thus helping separate the grain.

We added a grain recycling cylinder made of sheet metal to the inner screen to improve cleaning. Total separation loss was 2 to 3 percent in tests, but the threshed grain was not adequately cleaned. Chaff that accumulated between the

6. Axial-flow thresher.

outer cylinder and the no. 2 screen prevented grain from passing through the no. 2 screen which increased grain loss. Air blown back from the straw-thrasher also interfered with the winnowing air from the centrifugal blower. To eliminate blow-back, we shortened the outer cylinder by 5 cm, creating a separate annular opening for the winnowing air. Chaff and light impurities no longer entered the straw-thrasher but were ejected through the annular space. Blow-back was further reduced by replacing the solid thrower paddles with paddles made of bars.

The modified thresher was tested with dry and freshly harvested paddy. Output with dry paddy was 1.2 t/h with 96 percent grain purity. Separation loss ranged from 2 to 3 percent.

The second prototype thresher (fig. 7) incorporated several desirable features: a feeding conveyor, an improved radial fan, a flat belt drive for the rotary separator, an improved lightweight frame, and a connected cylinder and straw thrasher which rotate at 540 rpm from the PTO shaft. We also reduced the angle of the PTO shaft from 24° to 14° to reduce wear. The new design permits easy servicing and maintenance of components.

Because perforated sheet metal, an imported item, is often not available in Asia, we are testing alternative screen designs using more common wire mesh and wire rod screens. Such screens can often be built locally.

Stripper harvester. Based on tests with the laboratory stripper harvester (1971 Annual Report), a four-row, self-propelled stripper

harvester (fig. 8) was designed, powered by a standard 7.5-hp power tiller. We mounted the power tiller on a high-clearance straddle chassis. The front-driven wheels were mounted on two pivoted chain-transmission housings. Power is transmitted through sprockets mounted on the tiller axles. A crankscrew arrangement pivots the two chain housings to raise or lower the front end of the straddle chassis. A swivel-mounted rear wheel permits steering with the power tiller's standard steering clutches. A stripper box mounted under the chassis houses the major components of the stripper harvesting mechanism: plant-gathering chain, threshing belt, and grain-straw separator. The chassis can be raised or lowered to adjust the stripper mechanism to the height of the crop. A slat chain conveyor separates grain from chaff. A cross auger at the rear of the stripper delivers the grain to an elevator which consists of a flat belt,

7. Second prototype of the PTO-driven thresher.

8. Second prototype of the stripper harvester.

7.6 cm wide, with rubber flaps which are enclosed in a sheet metal housing.

Poor mobility in soft fields was a problem during trials. A half-track system, added to the front-driven wheels, increased ground contact area. The effective surface area of the track is 0.194 sq m; that of wheels only 0.078 sq m. The half-tracks improved mobility in soft fields and while crossing levees. The maximum track width is 20 cm because usual row spacing in Asia is 25 cm. Thus, long half-tracks are necessary.

Another problem is that lodged plants do not enter the harvesting mechanism. We developed a simple chain mechanism to lift and feed lodged plants into the gathering bars. The fingers enter below the lodged plants and move up, lifting the plants with a combing action. A shield prevents the fingers from hitting the plants during the downward movement and acts as a crop divider. The fingers lifted lodged plants well in initial tests. One problem was that the fingers go around the small drive sprockets at a high velocity, cutting or breaking straw and losing the grain.

The relationship between the horizontal velocity of the upward-moving fingers and the forward speed of the machine is critical for proper lifting action. Laboratory testing showed that the optimal horizontal chain velocity is 1.5 times the machine's ground speed. With the chain at a

30° angle to the ground, a chain speed of 0.39 m/s was necessary at a ground speed of 0.22 m/s to give the fingers the proper relative horizontal velocity.

The 7.5-hp tiller is not powerful enough to harvest a four-row swath, especially with the crop-lifting fingers. We have not installed a more powerful engine, however, because this would necessitate many design changes. We will continue experiments with the four-row machine until problems with the harvesting mechanism are eliminated. When the design of the stripping-harvesting machine is completed, a larger engine with a new transmission will be installed.

Savonius rotor windmill. A Savonius rotor windmill (fig. 9) was designed using two 55-gallon (200 liter) oil drums. The rotor is made of two sections, each with two half-drums arranged at a 180° phase angle. This split-rotor arrangement allows the windmill to operate when wind blows from any direction, eliminating "dead spots" that plagued previous Savonius windmills. The rotor is coupled to a Sakia-type waterwheel. The unit is suitable for low-lift irrigation and it might be able to operate bucket-type waterwheels permitting higher water lifts. The windmill's power-generating capacity at various wind velocities will be measured. The windmill may have other uses, such as running small electrical generators.

DRYING AND PROCESSING

Heated-sand drying and parboiling. A grain drier which uses heated sand was designed at IRRI (1971 Annual Report) and found to gelatinize starch granules which hardens the grain and increases head rice yields. Paddy with an initial moisture content of more than 25 percent yielded 5 percent more head rice when dried by heated sand than when air-dried. Paddy below 25 percent moisture yielded less head rice than when air-dried.

We tested different post-drying treatments to see if they affected head rice recovery. We found that neither immediately sealing paddy in airtight containers nor spreading paddy on a concrete floor after the heated-sand treatment made any difference in milling recovery when the

initial moisture content was higher than 28 percent. Spreading samples with initial moisture content of 23 percent decreased head rice recovery. Soaking paddy for 24 hours, then exposing it to heated sand for as long as 40 seconds failed to remove all white bellies from the milled rice, probably because starch granules did not completely gelatinize.

Rice samples dried with heated sand yielded an average of 8.4 percent more head rice than conventionally dried control samples when equal amounts of bran were removed in test milling. When sand-dried and control samples were milled for equal times in a laboratory mill, an average of 4.9 percent more bran was removed from the controls than from sand-dried samples. Head rice recovery from the sand-dried samples was 16.4 percent higher than from the controls.

Sand-dried and commercially parboiled rice samples were compared. The presoaked paddy, treated at heated sand temperatures of 150° C to 180° C, was more desirable in appearance and translucency.

The drier has been further modified (fig. 10). We enlarged and reshaped the sandpan to increase sand-holding capacity. We installed fins on the sandpan to improve heat transfer and

9. Savonius rotor windmill.

insulated the firebox to reduce heat losses. In preliminary tests, we found that if presoaked paddy is fed at a rate of 146 kg/h dry matter, sand temperature stabilizes at 104° C which was considerably lower than the desired minimum of

10. Continuous-flow heated-sand drying and parboiling machine.

150° C. Moisture extraction at this stabilized temperature was 9.7 percent (dry basis) and thermal efficiency was 55 percent. The efficiency increases to 65 percent if moisture removed during cooling of the grain is included in the calculations. The moisture reduction of pre-soaked paddy treated within a temperature range of 150° C to 180° C averages 21 percent (dry basis) in a single pass through the machine.

We added a rotating conveyor to the machine. Tumbling grain is pre-heated in the conveyor by hot gases before reaching the drying-parboiling chamber.

Centrifugal huller. Two Japanese companies manufacture centrifugal-type paddy hullers. Because the machines are expensive and difficult to maintain, we built a laboratory model (fig. 11) to test the concept of centrifugal hulling. It was equipped with a standard 60-blade plastic impeller from a Japanese machine. The face of the impeller housing was transparent plastic so we

11. Laboratory centrifugal huller.

could observe the hulling. A sliding gate allowed the paddy feed rate to be varied. One-kilogram samples of IR24 paddy at 15 percent moisture (dry basis) were hulled at impeller speeds of 850 to 1,650 rpm and at feeding rates of 470 kg/h to 1,380 kg/h. We measured unhulled paddy, broken rice, and head rice from the samples. Increasing rotor speeds decreases the percentage of unhulled grain and increases broken rice. Raising the feeding rate increases the amount of unhulled grain and decreases the amount of broken rice (fig. 12).

We also attempted to determine how the number of passes through the centrifugal huller affected percentage of unhulled paddy and broken grains at feeding rates of 470, 720, and 970 kg/h. At each of these feeding rates tested, unhulled paddy decreased and broken grains increased with each successive pass (fig. 13).

We evaluated four-ply rubber belting, which is inexpensive and easily available in Southeast Asia, as a substitute for the centrifugal huller's costly urethane impact surface. We tested three settings of the polisher—at, above, and below the manufacturer's recommendations — with both rubber belting and the urethane impact surface. About 22 kg of IR24 paddy with 12 percent moisture content (dry basis) and 97 percent purity were used at a feeding rate of 950 kg/h in each test. The rubber impact lining reduced head rice yield by 6 percent and increased unhulled paddy by 3 percent compared with the urethane lining. We found little difference in total milling recovery between the two impact linings, although the flat belt lining gave slightly lower head rice recovery at the lowest polisher setting. We observed that fine broken rice was discarded along with the hulls during milling.

Batch drier. A low-cost batch drier that can be manufactured by small shops in Asia was designed this year. It has a minimum of imported parts. The drier consists of a burner, a vane axial blower 46 cm in diameter, and a rectangular bin with a plenum chamber (fig. 14). The gravity-flow kerosene burner, which can be cast by local foundries, was adapted from an imported design. A safety valve actuated by a counterweight vane in the blower passage terminates the fuel flow whenever the blower stops. The axial

blower is driven by a 3-hp gasoline engine and delivers an airflow of 50 m³/min against a static pressure of 2 cm of water. A canvas duct connects the blower outlet to the plenum chamber. The 5-sq-m grain bed has a perforated bottom of three individually framed sections. The drier is constructed primarily of iron sheets and angle irons. Its drying capacity is about 1 ton every 4 to 6 hours. Grain is unloaded through two doors on the side of the bin.

We conducted six trials, using paddy with initial moisture content ranging from 19 to 26 percent (wet basis). One ton of paddy at 22.5 percent moisture (wet basis) filled the drying bin to a depth of 30.5 cm. It was dried to 14 ± 1.5 percent (wet basis) in 4 hours. Drying air temperature was 43°C and airflow rate was 32m³ · min⁻¹ · m⁻³ of grain during this test. During

continuous drying the average moisture reduction per hour in the top layer was 1.1 percentage points, and in the bottom layer, 2.0 percentage points (Table 1). The engine used 0.7 liter/h of gasoline. Kerosene consumption by the burner was 2.1 liter/h.

Channeling the radiated and exhaust engine heat into the air stream raised the drying air temperature by 4.5°C which is equivalent to 28 percent of the burner's normal kerosene consumption.

Drawings of this drier have been released to two manufacturers for limited production in the Philippines. The estimated selling price, complete with engine, is about US\$400—half the price of comparable imported batch driers.

Hull furnace. Two furnaces to burn rice hulls (fig. 15) were designed and evaluated for use

12. Effect of impeller speed and feeding rates on percentage of unhulled paddy and broken rice using a laboratory centrifugal huller with a rubber-belt impact surface. IR24 paddy at 15% moisture content (dry basis).

13. Effect of impeller speed and number of passes on percentage of unhulled paddy and broken rice using the laboratory centrifugal huller with rubber-belt impact surface. IR24 paddy at 15% moisture content (dry basis).

14. Batch grain drier.

with the IRRI batch drier. Paddy is about 20 to 22 percent hulls by weight and the hulls contain about 3,000 kcal/kg of energy. Once removed by milling, however, hulls are usually waste products.

One furnace has a square metal column with a louvered combustion chamber which is open on all four sides. Hulls are stored in a hopper directly above the column. A grate with a set of vibrating louvers at the bottom of the column retains the burning hulls and controls the flow of ashes. The blower draws air through the burning hulls between the louvered openings

and the bottom grate. Any ash mixed with the hot air is separated by the trap. A sheet metal shroud around the furnace recovers radiated heat that would otherwise be lost. The combustion rate is controlled by the flow of air through the hull mass and the rate of ash discharge through the vibrating grate.

The second furnace is a rectangular chamber of fire brick installed in an angle-iron frame. Fire brick walls divide the chamber into combustion and settling sections. A vibrating feeder in the hopper continually feeds hulls to be burned. The blower draws air through an

Table 1. Evaluation of the IRRI batch drier.

Variety	Grain weight (kg)		Moisture content ^a (%)			Drying time (h)	Fuel consumption (liter/h)		Ambient condition	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final			Gasoline	Kerosene	Temp. (C)	RH ^c (%)
				Top ^b	Bottom ^b					
IR1529-571	838	740	23.2	14.4	12.9	6	0.5	1.5	32	70
IR24	888	770	25.8	20.5	10.8	7	0.8	2.6	27	70
C4-137	867	759	23.2	16.3	9.9	6	0.7	2.4	27	70
C4-137	838	758	21.1	15.3	11.0	5	0.8	2.2	26	80
C4-137	878	811	19.4	15.3	13.3	4	0.8	2.2	28	74
IR1529-571	1018	873	25.5	16.4	11.4	6	0.8	2.0	31	70

^aWet basis. ^bGrain depth in bin is 30 cm. ^cRelative humidity.

opening at one end of the settling chamber. Air enters through the combustion grate, goes partly through the hopper, and passes through the burning hulls to the blower. The settling chamber traps ash. The suction from the blower creates an air draft around the furnace, recovering heat lost through the furnace walls.

Both furnaces have eccentric idler pulleys on the fan belts that drive the vibratory hull-feeding and ash-removing systems. These systems ensure that hulls will flow continuously, and that ashes will be removed with minimum manual attention.

Attached to the axial-flow blower of the IRRRI batch drier, both furnaces consume hulls at 3 to 4 kg/h. They produce a drying-air temperature of 43°C at an ambient temperature of 29°C with an airflow rate of 45 m³/min against a static pressure of 1.9 cm of water. A maximum drying air temperature of 60°C was reached when hull consumption was raised to 8 kg/h at the same airflow rate. Hull combustion was more complete, however, at the lower feeding rate.

TEST AND EVALUATION

Rice planters. The performance of two mechanical transplanters was evaluated in 1972. One is a manual five-row unit which is locally manufactured. The manufacturer recommends that 20- to 25-day-old wetbed seedlings be used for transplanting.

The picking fingers often failed to grasp the 20-day-old seedlings and the tray holding them did not move uniformly or consistently. The result was both missed hills and too many seedlings planted per hill (Table 2). Before we tested the machine with 25-day-old seedlings, the

15. Two rice hull furnaces: a louvered columnar type, top, and a fire brick type.

manufacturer provided an improved set of picking fingers made of high-carbon steel. This change significantly reduced the previously excessive number of seedlings per hill and increased operator efficiency. The field capacity increased in successive trials because the operator became more skilled. With 30-day-old seedlings, roots often tangled, noticeably increasing the number of seedlings per hill.

Table 2. Evaluation of the two rice transplanters (unreplicated). IRRRI, 1972.

Seedling age (days)	Hills (no./sq m)	Missed hills (no./sq m)	Seedlings (no./hill)	Depth of planting (cm)	Distance between hills (cm)	Effective field capacity (sq m/h)
<i>Manual transplanter</i>						
20	13.4	2.6	14.3	5.1	33.5	333
25	12.3	2.6	6.5	5.2	33.5	571
30	12.8	1.6	13.3	6.3	33.5	820
<i>Japanese power-driven transplanter</i>						
10	13.6	3.4	3.4	3.6	18.1	952
15	14.4	4.4	3.6	4.0	17.2	952
20	15.6	3.8	3.3	3.7	17.2	952

Table 3. Cardiac tests with three sizes of low-lift bellows pump at three pumping heads.

Bellows size	Length of test (min)	Output (liter/min)	Energy used	
			kcal/min	cal/liter
<i>0.5-m head</i>				
Small ^a	75	135	6.9	50
Medium	58	152	4.3	30
Large I	61	143	5.9	40
Large II ^c	60	110	4.7	40
<i>1.0-m head</i>				
Small ^a	60	157	9.0	60
Medium	70 ^b	119	4.9	40
Large I	60	96	4.6	50
Large II ^c	60	106	4.7	40
<i>1.5-m head</i>				
Small ^a	60	98	7.8	80
Medium	66	88	4.6	50
Large I	60	64	3.8	60
Large II ^c	60	77	5.0	60

^aOne observation. ^bTwo observations. ^cModified to incorporate larger discharge orifice.

We also tested a two-row Japanese transplanter which is powered by an engine. The manufacturer specifies that seedlings used with this machine must be grown in special wooden trays. Special equipment is necessary to fill the trays, distribute seeds, and incubate the seedlings. According to the manufacturer the seedlings may be 15 to 25 days old. We could not make seedlings live more than 20 days under the manufacturer's specifications, however. Our inexperience in raising seedlings and operating the unit resulted in an excessive number of missed hills (Table 2).

Low-lift bellows pump. We tested the energy requirements for several modifications of the IRRI low-lift bellows pump to improve the design. Using cardiac monitoring equipment (1971 Annual Report) we measured how much energy three individuals used when operating three bellows sizes, with the static pumping head (height) varying from 0.5 to 1.5 m.

The medium-sized pump performed best overall in terms of efficiency of energy use (Table 3). The small pump had the highest output rate, but it required more pumping strokes per unit of output, and, thus, more energy. Operators said that the small pump did not provide enough resistance on the downward stroke to establish a rhythm during operation. The large pump, however, offered excessive resistance on the downward stroke, so the operator had to pause

as the water was slowly forced from the pumping chamber. We could not increase this unit's output, even after installing a larger discharge opening.

The output of the medium-sized unit was reasonably high over the entire range of pumping heads. Moreover, pumpers could establish a rhythmic pumping motion which reduced fatigue and energy expenditure per unit of output.

We also evaluated two prototypes of the IRRI pump built by local manufacturers. For rapid testing, we constructed a test fixture with a 0.5-hp electric motor that permitted continuous pumping against a 1-m head. The bolts that fastened the hinge shafts to the base plates of both pumps broke after less than 5 hours of operation. The outer canvas of the first bellows of one pump split along the width of the metal reinforcement plate after 7 hours and the outer canvas of the other pump's first bellows split after 37.5 hours. Both failures were caused by having stitching too close to the metal reinforcement. Similar failures occurred in the second bellows of each unit at 37 hours and 67.5 hours of operation. We continued testing one unit until the inner rubberized canvas developed a leak at 165 hours.

We recommended removing the stitching around the metal reinforcing plates and gluing the inner and outer fabrics together with waterproof adhesive. Strong waterproof thread, such as nylon, should be used for all stitching.

We tested other units with these modifications. Performance was satisfactory. One manufacturer now produces the bellows pump commercially.

Multihopper seeder. "Seed bridging," or clogging in the hopper of the multihopper seeder, was reduced by widening the seed-metering rollers to cover the full width of the hopper and by staggering the seed pockets along the axis (fig. 16). The rollers then picked up seeds from a wider area of the hopper. Staggered seed pockets on the rollers, however, scattered seeds in the row. To reduce this, we installed a guide plate under each seed roller. We rigidly fixed the drive wheel in the center of a sleeve which connects the two half-shafts, and widened the skid to increase flotation. The machine could be packaged more

16. Six-row multi-hopper seeder.

compactly after the skid was widened and divided into two pieces and the handle shortened. We reduced the size of the seed hopper, lessening the weight of the machine (18 kg without seeds), and improving flotation and handling.

The modified seeder was tested at seeding rates from 37 to 60 kg/ha, depending on seed germination time, root growth, and variety. Performance was acceptable. Additional modified seeders were ordered for field evaluation.

Field evaluation of the table thresher. Twenty IRRI table threshers were purchased from commercial manufacturers by the National Science Development Board and placed with cooperatives in Central Luzon for field evaluation during the 1972 wet and dry seasons. As part of a survey by the agricultural education department of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, in cooperation with IRRI, farmers participating in the project were asked their opinions of the table thresher to identify the variables affecting adoption.

Response to the table thresher varied from complete acceptance to total rejection. The main factors influencing the machine's acceptance were area cultivated, machine mobility, cost, machine capacity, and labor requirements. Large farmers preferred the McCormick-type

thresher because of its high output and relatively low labor requirements. Smaller farmers preferred the table thresher. Forty-five percent thought the table thresher was most economical, while 26 percent favored the McCormick thresher, with the balance preferring other methods.

ECONOMICS OF MECHANIZATION

Grain loss. We studied the nature and magnitude of grain losses during harvesting and threshing in the 1972 dry season at the IRRI farm. The effect of time of harvest on total and head rice yields was assessed. The benefits of mechanical drying were measured on yield samples drawn from the experiment. We used IR747B2-6-3, a line moderately susceptible to shattering, for the trials.

Yield samples were harvested at 3-day intervals, beginning 105 days after seeding. Half of each sample was reduced to 14 percent moisture (wet basis) by sun drying and half by mechanical drying.

The yield of the IR747 line increased up to 111 days after seeding and then gradually declined (Table 4). Postponing harvest for 12 days beyond the optimal date decreased yields by more than

Table 4. Milling quality in relation to mechanical and sun drying of IR747B2-6-3 samples harvested at different dates. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Time of harvest DS ^a	Moisture content at harvest (%)	Rough rice yield ^b (t/ha)	Yield index ^c	Mechanically dried			Sun-dried		
				Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)	Total milled (%)	Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)	Total milled (%)
105	22.8	5.9	91	63	9	72	57	16	72
108	22.7	6.2	95	64	8	72	54	18	72
111	20.4	6.5	100	62	10	72	46	25	71
114	19.1	6.2	95	64	9	72	59	13	73
117	18.8	5.4	83	63	9	72	54	18	72
120	17.9	5.2	81	58	14	73	55	19	73
123	17.2	5.1	78	45	27	72	42	31	73
126	17.5	5.4	83	44	28	72	38	35	73
129	19.2	4.4	68	40	31	71	17	52	70
132	20.9	5.1	77	34	37	71	14	55	69

^aDays after seeding. ^bAt 14% moisture. ^cYield at 111 days (6.5 t/h) = 100.

20 percent. As the plant dries, the pedicel becomes brittle and shattering increases.

Our results show that late harvest also decreases head rice recovery during milling. Panicle drying causes a temperature difference between the outer and inner portions of the grain. This, combined with intermittent drying during the day, followed by moisture condensation at night, causes internal stress in the caryopsis. Under these conditions, grain tends to crack during milling. With mechanical drying, moisture reduction can be uniformly controlled, reducing stresses and increasing head rice recovery.

Rice processing systems. About half of the rice grown in the Philippines is milled for home use in small Engleberg hullers. These hullers have a high power requirement and give a low grain recovery—generally less than 60 percent by weight, with head rice making up less than 50 percent of total milled rice. Bran and hulls are mixed.

Most rice that enters the commercial market is processed by cono-type mills. The cono gives a higher recovery rate (up to 68 percent by weight)

17. Distribution of milling capacity by mill size. Philippines, 1970.

18. Effect on total rice recovery of increased milling efficiency of an Engleberg huller from 60% recovery to 70% and a cono mill from 65% recovery to 70%.

than the Engleberg huller. Head rice recovery is also higher, bran and hulls are separated, and milling can be more closely controlled.

By a study of local rice processing, we hope to identify mechanical and economic factors that can be modified to improve efficiency. About 25 percent of the country's milling capacity is not used (fig. 17). Surveys of millers and manufacturers of mill equipment indicate that the efficiency of an Engleberg rice mill which processes 3 to 5 t/day rough rice can be substantially increased by upgrading equipment and facilities so that 70 percent recovery is achieved (fig. 18). Existing mills are being surveyed to determine criteria for improved equipment.

Credit programs. We examined the impact of two recent World Bank (International Bank for Reconstruction and Development) loan programs on growth and patterns of mechanization in the Philippines.

The first program began in 1965 with a US\$5 million credit line and was fully utilized by 1968. The second program began in June 1969 with US\$12.5 million and ends in March 1973. Both programs were designed to encourage mechanization on small farms by making funds available to purchase four-wheel tractors, hand tractors, irrigation pumps and engines, and other small-scale agricultural machinery.

From the first program, 2,400 farmers borrowed US\$4.9 million. Sixty-six percent of the funds was used for four-wheel tractors and implements, and 22 percent for power tillers and attachments. But the number of loans for power tillers was larger than the number for four-wheel tractors (Table 5).

The second credit line has been used more slowly than the first, probably because it be-

Table 5. Power unit sales prior to and during the 1965-73 credit programs of the Central Bank of the Philippines and the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development^a

Year	Tractors (no.)		Sales of power tillers	Loans (no.) released for	
	Imports	Sales		Tractors	Tillers
1960	297	—	—	—	—
1961	102	813	—	—	—
1962	262	994	—	—	—
1963	918	863	—	—	—
1964	859	950	—	—	—
1965	769	607	1505 ^b	—	—
1966	518	664	1932	72	126
1967	2203	1531	3058	560	724
1968	1443	1630	1837	265	228
1969	1390	1358	910	54	34
1970	982	978	475	150	42
1971	1065	1086	258 ^c	251	109

^aSources: Government of the Philippines, Bureau of the Census and Statistics, Agricultural Machinery Dealers Association, Radiowealth, Inc. ^bEstimated cumulative total of power tillers sold from 1960 to 1965. ^cJanuary to May.

came available just before the Philippine peso was devalued. Rising machinery prices and restrictions on imports discouraged purchases of agricultural machinery.

The extension of medium-term and long-term loans under the second credit line principally benefited larger farm owners rather than small holders or tenants. Loans are granted on the basis of collateral, rather than on the productivity of the investment. The result is that more than half the loan applications are denied each year, concentrating loans in the hands of those with land to offer as security. The program also encouraged farmers to continue relying on imported equipment; few incentives are offered to encourage the use of loan funds to purchase locally built equipment.

Agronomy Our major emphasis was on rainfed rice (upland and lowland). □ For upland rice, IR442-2-58 continued to look promising at IRRI farm and elsewhere. Techniques for screening rice varieties for drought tolerance are being developed. In greenhouse studies under a continual 75 centibars moisture stress IR442-2-58 had higher tolerance than C-22, the latest upland variety from the Philippines. Other promising lines are IR1487-372-4, IR1529-72-5, IR1529-677-2, and IR1721-11-6. □ Studies on rainfed lowland rice in farmers' fields indicate that IR442-2-58 has higher drought tolerance than IR20. □ Studies on moisture stress suggest that the relationship between moisture stress and stage of the crop may depend on growth duration of the variety, among other factors. □ Studies in fields and in tanks demonstrate that a single variety can be bred which would adjust its growth characteristics according to the moisture supply under the specific land and water management systems in rainfed areas (upland, rainfed lowland, and deep water). □ The herbicide bentazon was found to control *Scirpus maritimus*, a noxious perennial sedge found in some lowland rice fields, with no toxicity to the rice crop.

NITROGEN RESPONSE IN IRRIGATED RICE

Experiments were continued at the IRRI farm and in farmers' fields to study the nitrogen responses, growth characteristics, and field reactions to diseases of varieties or lines developed by IRRI and by breeders elsewhere.

Promising lines. Several promising lines from the IRRI breeding program were compared with IR8 and other varieties.

In the dry season, the two experimental lines, IR1006-20-5 and IR841-85-1 (Table 1), produced over 8 t/ha. The early maturing line, IR1561-243-5, which matured in 111 days, produced a grain yield of 7.7 t/ha at 150 kg/ha N. IR20 which is resistant to many insects and diseases continued to perform well because disease and insect incidence is high at the IRRI farm. The IR1103 lines have high protein content but they yielded poorly as they did in 1971. BPI 121-407 has not performed well in the last three cropping seasons.

In the wet season, the highest yield was 6.0 t/ha, obtained with IR841-85-1; however, yields

of IR20, the two IR1541 lines, IR1514A-E666, and IR1529-680-3 were statistically similar to the yield of IR841-85-1.

Grassy stunt often affects yields at the IRRI farm so we monitored it closely in the wet season. Based on a sample of 420 hills per plot, IR841-85, IR1006-20, IR1561-243, and IR1514A-E666 had only about 3 percent virus-infected hills. The IR1541 lines, the IR1529 lines, and the IR881 line had 6 to 7 percent virus. IR8 had about 11 percent. In cooperation with the plant pathology department, reactions to bacterial leaf streak were recorded 65 days after transplanting. Based on field observations, most entries were resistant or moderately resistant, but Peta was moderately susceptible.

International varieties. Among the 12 varieties from several countries tested at the IRRI farm, IR8 yielded the most in the dry season (Table 2). The other high yielders were Pelita I from Indonesia, Jaya from India, and Azral from Fiji, and IR20.

Without fertilizer nitrogen, Azral (IR480-5-9) had similar grain yield to other varieties in the

Table 1. Effects of levels of nitrogen^a on the grain yield of rice varieties and promising lines (avg of three replications). IRRI, 1972.

Designation	Maturity (days)	Dry season					Wet season					
		Yield ^b (t/ha)					Yield ^c (t/ha)					
		0	60	90	120	150	0	30	60	90	120	
IR833-6-2	117	4.0	5.3	5.8	7.3	6.3	117	4.0	4.1	4.3	5.1	5.5
BPI 121-407	123	4.0	5.0	5.7	6.0	5.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR1103-15-10	111	3.1	5.2	5.2	5.7	5.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR1103-1-3	130	2.9	4.3	4.8	5.0	5.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR1006-20-5	123	5.1	7.3	8.1	8.3	8.1	130	4.3	4.8	5.4	5.8	5.6
IR1163-153-2	123	4.9	6.6	7.4	7.7	8.1	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR841-85-1	130	4.8	7.1	8.2	8.0	7.7	131	4.1	5.3	5.3	6.0	5.5
IR881-5-3	123	4.9	5.8	7.4	7.3	7.6	130	4.1	4.3	4.9	4.9	4.8
IR20	118	5.1	6.2	6.9	7.9	7.6	131	4.0	5.1	4.9	5.9	5.5
IR22	111	3.8	5.0	6.5	6.8	7.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR1561-243-5	111	5.6	6.7	7.2	7.3	7.7	117	4.2	4.5	5.2	5.6	5.5
IR1364-37	123	5.0	5.5	6.9	7.5	7.5	137	4.3	5.0	5.2	5.5	5.4
IR5	139	4.4	5.9	6.4	6.2	6.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Peta	138	4.4	3.8	3.9	2.4	1.8	141	2.9	2.5	2.8	1.5	2.1
IR8	—	—	—	—	—	—	131	3.3	3.9	4.3	4.6	4.5
IR1514A-E666	—	—	—	—	—	—	123	4.0	4.2	4.9	5.6	5.6
IR1529-680-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	133	3.9	4.7	4.9	5.5	5.2
IR1529-382-4	—	—	—	—	—	—	133	4.3	5.3	5.2	5.3	5.5
IR1541-76-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	130	4.3	4.4	5.2	5.6	5.7
IR1541-102-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	123	3.9	4.6	4.8	5.7	5.1

^aIncludes 30 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation in dry season and 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation in wet season except for 0 kg/ha N treatment. ^bLSD (5%): 1.0 t/ha. ^cLSD (5%): 0.8 t/ha.

Table 2. Effects of levels of nitrogen^a on the grain yield of new varieties from several countries (avg of three replications). IRRI, 1972.

Designation	Dry season						Wet season					
	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					Maturity (days)	Yield ^c (t/ha)				
		0 kg/ha N	60 kg/ha N	90 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N	150 kg/ha N		0 kg/ha N	30 kg/ha N	60 kg/ha N	90 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
Pelita I	130	5.0	6.5	7.8	7.3	5.9	127	4.0	4.7	5.6	5.2	5.6
TN1	116	5.1	7.0	7.4	7.2	7.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
Jaya	116	5.7	7.4	7.8	7.6	7.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR8	130	5.2	7.3	8.0	8.3	8.1	131	3.9	3.8	5.0	5.7	5.8
IR20	116	5.6	6.6	7.6	7.4	7.7	136	4.4	5.0	5.0	5.6	5.4
IR22	111	4.1	5.7	6.4	6.6	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR5	130	4.8	6.9	7.0	7.3	6.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
RD1	130	5.5	6.8	7.2	7.6	7.0	131	3.1	3.8	3.7	4.0	4.6
Cica 4	116	4.6	6.8	7.2	7.2	6.9	123	3.0	4.3	4.6	4.4	4.8
C4-63G	130	4.5	6.1	6.5	6.7	5.0	141	3.5	4.5	4.5	5.1	5.1
Azral	116	4.6	5.7	6.8	7.4	7.6	120	3.4	4.0	4.5	4.5	4.6
Peta	138	4.0	3.0	3.9	2.5	1.5	144	3.5	3.5	2.9	2.2	2.8
BG 34-8	—	—	—	—	—	—	113	3.3	3.9	4.0	4.5	5.0
Tongil	—	—	—	—	—	—	113	3.0	3.0	3.4	4.0	4.9
Sinaloa	—	—	—	—	—	—	120	3.3	4.0	4.8	4.7	5.4
Vijaya	—	—	—	—	—	—	131	4.9	5.1	5.6	5.6	6.6

^aIncludes 30 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation in dry season and 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation in wet season except for 0 kg/ha N treatment. ^bLSD (5%): 0.9 t/ha. ^cLSD (5%): 0.7 t/ha.

dry season but at least 1 percentage point higher protein (9.1%) in the brown rice than all other varieties tested (7.1 to 8.1%).

In the wet season, the Indian variety Vijaya significantly out-yielded all other varieties (Table 2). The varieties were evaluated for their reactions to grassy stunt virus from samples of 360 hills per plot. IR8, Pelita I, and RD-1 (from Thailand) had over 17 percent virus. Sinaloa A68 from Mexico, Tongil from Korea, and Cica 4 from Colombia had about 13 percent. The Philippine variety C4-63G and Vijaya were intermediate in virus susceptibility. The Ceylonese variety BG 34-8 and IR20 had low incidence of virus. Azral had the lowest incidence of grassy stunt virus, 2.7 percent.

Without nitrogen fertilizer, the protein content of Azral was 9 percent as against 8 percent for Sinaloa A68 (Table 3). At 120 kg/ha N, Azral had 11.5 percent protein but Sinaloa A68 had only 10.6 percent protein, indicating Azral's superiority in protein content to Sinaloa A68.

Farmers' fields. As in previous years, experiments were conducted in farmers' fields to study varietal reactions to nitrogen fertilizers under management conditions that are within reach of most Asian farmers. In the dry season, IR24

produced the highest yield, 8.6 t/ha, followed by IR8 with 7.8 t/ha. Both IR20 and C4-63G matured 5 days earlier than IR8 and IR24 but they produced significantly lower yield than IR8 and IR24 (Table 4).

Long-term fertility experiments. The sixteenth and seventeenth crop in the long-term fertility experiment were grown at the IRRI farm in 1972. No variety showed significant response to phosphorus or potassium in either the dry or wet season (Table 5). In both seasons, IR20 produced similar yields to IR8. IR22 produced somewhat less.

Another series of long-term fertility experiments was begun in 1968 at the three experiment

Table 3. Grain yield and protein content in the brown rice of two varieties. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Nitrogen applied ^a (kg/ha)	Sinaloa A-68 ^b		Azral ^c	
	Yield (t/ha)	Protein (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Protein (%)
0	3.3	8.0	3.4	9.0
30	4.0	8.9	4.0	9.6
60	4.8	9.7	4.5	10.5
90	4.7	10.7	4.5	10.9
120	5.4	10.6	4.6	11.5

^aIncluding 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation. ^bIR160-27-4. ^cIR480-5-9.

Table 4. Effects of levels of nitrogen^a on the grain yield of irrigated rice in a farmer's field (avg. of two replications). Laguna, Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Variety	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)			
		0 kg/ha N	50 kg/ha N	100 kg/ha N	150 kg/ha N
IR8	128	5.4	7.7	7.8	7.8
IR20	123	5.1	5.5	6.1	6.6
IR24	128	5.1	8.6	7.8	7.8
C4-63G	123	4.1	5.7	6.5	5.1
IR5	132	5.9	6.2	7.3	6.3

^aIncludes 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation in dry season except 0 kg/ha N treatment. ^bLSD (5%): Difference between two variety means at same nitrogen level—1.1 t/ha; difference between two nitrogen means of same or different variety—1.7 t/ha.

stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry with the same objectives as the experiment at the IRRI farm. The experiment stations involved in this project are the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (soil: pH 6.9; organic matter, 1.5%; cation exchange capacity, 36 meq/100 g soil), the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station (soil: pH 5.5; organic matter, 4.4%; cation exchange capacity, 29 meq/100 g soil), and the Visayas Rice Experiment Station (soil: pH 7.0; organic matter, 3.3%; cation exchange capacity, 59 meq/100 g soil). All the three stations are located in important rice growing regions of the Philippines.

To monitor changes in capacity of rice soils to

Table 5. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, IR22, and IR20 in the 16th (dry season) and 17th (wet season) consecutive crops (mean of four replications). IRRI, 1972.

Fertilizer treatment ^a (kg/ha)			Yield ^b (t/ha)			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	IR22	IR20	Mean
<i>Dry season</i>						
0	0	0	4.2	4.0	4.2	4.1
140 ^a	0	0	8.0	7.0	7.7	7.6
0	30	0	4.8	4.4	4.5	4.6
0	0	30	4.8	4.0	4.3	4.4
140 ^a	30	0	8.0	6.8	7.6	7.5
140 ^a	0	30	8.0	6.3	7.5	7.3
140 ^a	30	30	7.9	6.7	7.7	7.4
140 ^{a,c}	30	30	7.8	6.9	7.6	7.4
<i>Wet season</i>						
0	0	0	4.3	3.9	4.0	4.1
60	0	0	5.2	5.3	5.5	5.3
0	30	0	4.2	4.0	4.2	4.1
0	0	30	4.4	3.8	4.2	4.1
60	30	0	5.3	5.1	6.0	5.5
60	0	30	5.5	5.1	5.3	5.3
60	30	30	5.5	5.0	5.6	5.4
60 ^c	30	30	5.5	5.0	5.5	5.3

^aIncludes 40 kg/ha N applied at panicle initiation. ^bAverage of four replications. LSD (5%): 0.5 t/ha in dry season and 0.6 t/ha in wet season. ^cCompost plus inorganic.

supply NPK over a period of intensive cropping, six fertility treatments were imposed with a randomized complete block design. The plots without fertilizer were the control. One treatment involved split application of potassium. Each treatment was repeated four times. Three

Table 6. Amount of increase in grain yield from application of phosphorus (60 kg/ha P₂O₅) with and without potassium to 10 successive crops at three locations (avg of three varieties):^a Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1968 to 1972.

Year	Yield increase (t/ha) from phosphorus								
	Maligaya station			Bicol station			Visayas station		
	With K	Without K	Difference	With K	Without K	Difference	With K	Without K	Difference
<i>Dry season^a</i>									
1968	0.43**	0.38*	ns	0.68*	0.66*	ns	0.81*	0.04	ns
1969	0.25	0.11	ns	0.48	0.86*	ns	—	—	—
1970	1.25**	0.66**	ns	1.14**	1.15**	ns	0.58**	0.57**	ns
1971	1.60**	1.37**	ns	1.85**	0.43	**	1.42**	1.04**	ns
1972	1.57**	0.65*	*	1.18**	-0.06	*	1.24**	1.14**	ns
Avg	1.02	0.63	0.39	1.07	0.61	0.46	1.01	0.70	0.32
<i>Wet season^b</i>									
1968	0.48**	0.32	ns	0.48*	1.06**	ns	0.39*	0.42*	ns
1969	0.72*	.15	ns	0.92**	0.65**	ns	0.62*	0.89**	ns
1970	0.22	.25	ns	—	—	—	1.47**	1.14**	ns
1971	0.49*	.23	ns	0.95**	0.40*	*	0.34	0.10	ns
1972	1.15**	.54*	ns	1.08**	0.96**	ns	1.24**	0.88	ns
Avg	0.61	.30	0.31	0.86	0.77	0.09	0.81	0.68	0.13

^aWith 140 kg/ha N. ^bWith 70 kg/ha N.

varieties were used to record any varietal difference in fertilizer response particularly to nitrogen. IR8 was used in all 5 years but the other varieties were changed to the best ones available for the year. The experiment was conducted in the dry and wet seasons for 5 consecutive years.

At all locations, the efficiency of nitrogen use was the highest in the first crop and then tended to decrease (fig. 1). This drop in nitrogen efficiency was most consistent for the dry season crops at the Bicol station. But in the first crop, efficiency was highest at the Visayas station (30 kg rough rice/kg N), followed by the Maligaya station (19 kg rough rice/kg N), and the Bicol station (13 kg rice/kg N). By the ninth crop, grown in the 1972 dry season, the Visayas station still had the highest efficiency (17 kg rice/kg N) followed by the Maligaya station (14 kg rice/kg N) and the Bicol station (1.4 kg rice/kg N). The marked drop in nitrogen efficiency at the Bicol station shows the importance of other nutrients to maximize nitrogen efficiency and grain yield.

For phosphorus, efficiency gradually increased (fig. 1). In the dry seasons, phosphorus efficiency reached its maximum at the seventh crop after which it declined, indicating that the continual application built up a phosphorus reserve for the succeeding three crops.

The efficiency of potassium varied greatly between stations. At the Maligaya station, the potassium efficiency was the lowest among the nutrients tested. With time, however, potassium response increased during the dry seasons (fig. 1).

The most striking results from potassium fertilization were obtained at the Bicol station. The increase in potassium response and the efficiency of potassium increased sharply over the years especially in the dry seasons. Potassium efficiency was only 13 kg rice/kg K_2O in the first crop in the 1968 dry season but it increased to 69 kg rice/kg K_2O in the 1972 dry season.

As in Maligaya, the potassium efficiency at the Visayas station was low compared with nitrogen or phosphorus efficiency. In the dry season crops, potassium response and potassium efficiency increased for few seasons, then they decreased gradually. In the wet seasons, how-

1. Changes in soil fertility, at three experiment stations located in the Philippines, as affected by intensive rice cropping for 5 years. IRRRI-BPI long term fertility experiments. 1968-1972.

ever, the drop in potassium efficiency was gradual and continued through the tenth crop (fig. 1).

In general, application of phosphorus made no appreciable difference in the average yield increase from location to location. At all locations phosphorus responses were more marked with K_2O than without it especially in the dry season (Table 6).

Table 7. Amount of increase in grain yield from application of potassium (60 kg/ha K₂O) with and without phosphorus to 10 successive crops at three locations (avg of three varieties). Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1968 to 1972.

Year	Yield increase (t/ha) from potassium								
	Maligaya station			Bicol station			Visayas station		
	With P	Without P	Difference	With P	Without P	Difference	With P	Without P	Difference
	<i>Dry season^a</i>								
1968	0.10	-0.12	ns	0.77*	0.83**	ns	0.40	-0.43	ns
1969	0.32	0.11	ns	1.19**	1.00**	ns	—	—	—
1970	0.06	-.06	ns	0.93**	1.03**	ns	1.97**	-.20	**
1971	0.64**	.42*	ns	2.20**	0.66**	**	1.16**	.20	**
1972	1.13*	-.04	**	4.13**	2.36**	*	-0.08	-.38	ns
Avg	0.45	.02	0.43	1.84	1.18	0.66	0.61	-.20	0.81
	<i>Wet season^b</i>								
1968	0.51**	0.27	ns	0.46*	0.66**	ns	0.26	-0.30	*
1969	.31	-.04	ns	0.42*	.20	ns	.42	-.02	ns
1970	.46	.22	ns	—	—	—	.36	.19	ns
1971	.63**	.45*	ns	1.36**	.79**	*	.16	-.20	ns
1972	.26	.07	ns	1.09**	.88**	ns	.12	-.10	ns
Avg	.43	.19	0.24	0.83	.63	0.20	.26	-.09	0.35

^aWith 140 kg/ha N. ^bWith 70 kg/ha N.

The application of potassium without phosphorus did not produce higher grain yield at either Maligaya or Visayas stations (Table 7). Occasionally, potassium application without phosphorus fertilization reduced grain yield. At the Bicol station, however, the positive yield response to potassium was usually significant with or without phosphorus.

Thus with adequate nitrogen supply, the response of rice to phosphorus or potassium, or both, is marginal in some areas under one-crop-a-year rice culture, but the response to these elements may become marked under intensive rice cultivation (two crops a year or more) over the years. If rice yields decline with nitrogen alone, phosphorus and potassium response should be checked. It is possible to build up a phosphorus reserve by occasional application. In potassium-deficient areas, potassium should be applied regularly since it is easily lost. Potassium deficiency is aggravated if rice straw is removed completely at harvest. Application of phosphorus or potassium should be advocated where and when the increased yields justify the cost of the fertilizer element.

PRACTICES FOR IRRIGATED RICE

Nitrogen sources. Large amounts of nitrogen from ammonium sulfate and urea are often lost

even under irrigation. Studies were continued to find alternative sources of nitrogen. Sulfur-coated urea with different release rates of nitrogen was compared with urea and ammonium sulfate. Two nitrogen sources with both ammonium and nitrate components were also included in the test. IR24 was grown broadcast and transplanted.

In the broadcast planting, three sulfur-coated ureas with release rates of 16, 20, and 28 percent produced significantly higher yields than urea, ammonium sulfate, and the two nitrate-containing sources (Table 8). With the slow-release fertilizer isobutylidene diurea, yields were similar to those with ammonium sulfate and urea. In the transplanted plots, sulfur-coated urea with 20 percent release rate gave significantly higher yields than all other fertilizers. But the yields with three sulfur-coated ureas (16, 20, and 28% release rates) were significantly greater than those with urea which is more prone to losses.

Early lodging in the broadcast-seeded plot lowered yields with urea and ammonium sulfate. Use of sulfur-coated urea delayed lodging. As a result, the advantage of using sulfur-coated ureas, in comparison with using standard fertilizers, was greater in the broadcast seeding.

When the grain yields were compared under 5 cm of continual flooding and under inter-

Table 8. Effect of different sources of nitrogen (150 kg/ha N) on the grain yield of broadcast and transplanted IR24 (avg of two water managements and two times of application). IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Nitrogen source	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	Broadcast	Transplanted
Sulfur-coated urea ^b		
28% R	8.6 ab	9.2 b
20% R	8.8 a	9.4 a
16% R	8.5 b	9.1 b
6% R	8.1 cd	8.9 bc
Ammonium sulfate	7.8 e	8.9 bc
Urea	7.9 de	8.8 c
Isobutylidene diurea	7.9 de	8.9 c
Ammonium sulfate nitrate	8.2 c	8.5 d
Calcium ammonium nitrate	8.2 c	8.2 e
Unfertilized control	5.4 f	5.4 f

^aFor the same time of application, any two source means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level using Duncan's multiple range test. ^bR = dissolution rate in 2 weeks.

mittent irrigation (irrigation to 5 cm whenever soil moisture tension was 33 centibars), split application of nitrogen produced significantly higher grain yields than single application (Table 9). Split application was beneficial with either planting method and under either water management practice. Under dense plant population with broadcast seeding, it is desirable to reduce nitrogen supply or apply it in split doses to minimize lodging.

Rotational irrigation. Rotational irrigation has not been widely adopted because it requires well-trained irrigation personnel and a high level of farmer cooperation, and water-measuring

Table 9. Grain yield of IR24 under two methods of planting as affected by the interaction between water management practice and time of nitrogen application. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Time of application ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Broadcast	Transplanted
	<i>Flooded^b</i>	
Single	7.6	8.4
Split	8.4	9.0
	<i>Irrigation at 33 centibars^c</i>	
Single	7.1	8.1
Split	8.7	8.7
LSD (5%)	0.5	0.5

^aSingle: all doses applied as basal; Split: equal dose applied at planting, at maximum tillering, and panicle initiation. Includes nine sources of nitrogen fertilizers. ^bTo 5 cm. ^cField capacity.

devices must be installed in canals. In addition, weeds are more difficult to control when the plots lack standing water. Nevertheless, the potential for using water more efficiently through rotational irrigation makes research on it highly desirable.

A project started during 1971 was continued during the 1972 dry season. IR5, IR20, C4-63, IR127-80, IR480-5, and IR1561-69 were used in the test. Granular 2, 4-D, which effectively controls common weeds with 5 cm of continual flooding, was tested with the different water management treatments.

The water use efficiency decreased as the growth duration and irrigation rate were increased regardless of irrigation interval (fig. 2).

Averaged over all irrigation intervals, the

2. Effects of irrigation level and interval on the water-use efficiency of rice varieties with different growth durations. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

3. Effects of irrigation levels and interval on weed control with 2, 4-D IPE in flooded rice. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

grain yields with 2, 4-D application followed by one hand weeding at the maximum tillering stage were slightly higher than the yields with 2, 4-D application alone (fig. 3). The slight increase with one hand weeding was due to the infestation of a perennial sedge, *Scirpus maritimus*, which was not controlled by 2, 4-D.

Weed control in transplanted rice. Two field experiments were conducted to evaluate promising herbicides for transplanted rice. One was conducted at IRRI with variety IR24 to compare nine promising herbicide treatments with hand weeding. In this experiment, C-288 gave excellent weed control for the second consecutive year and resulted in high grain yields (Table 10). The new herbicide USB 3153 from U.S. Borax, appeared promising when applied at 2.0 kg/ha a.i. Granular 2, 4-D gave about the

Table 10. Weed control in transplanted IR24 with granular herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Chemical ^a	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Toxicity ^c		Weed wt ^d (g/sq m)
			19 DT	83 DT	
2,4-D IPE	0.8	8.6 ab	2	0	46
MCPA-K (spray)	0.8	8.0 b	3	0	194
TCE-styrene/ 2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	8.6 ab	1	0	0
Butachlor	1.5	8.6 ab	0	0	0
USB 3153	2.0	8.4 ab	0	0	0
C-19490 + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	8.6 ab	1	0	0
Benthiocarb	1.5	8.2 b	0	0	0
C-288	0.8/0.2	8.5 ab	1	0	0
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	8.6 ab	1	0	0
Hand weeding	Twice	8.9 a	0	0	65
Control	—	0.0 c	0	0	1774

^a + = chemicals applied in immediate succession; IPE = isopropyl ester. ^bAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cDT = days after transplanting. Scale = 0 to 10: 0 = no toxicity; 10 = complete kill. ^dTaken at heading of *Echinochloa crusgalli* + similar species (other weeds virtually absent).

same grain yield as hand weeding twice. MCPA spray did not control grasses as well as granular 2, 4-D and it was toxic to IR24. This toxicity plus low temperature in early February significantly reduced grain yields with MCPA.

The second experiment was conducted in farmers' fields in Laguna and Quezon provinces in the Philippines in cooperation with the rice production training and research department of IRRI to evaluate promising herbicides at farm level. The varieties IR20 and C4-63 were grown with 0 and 100 kg/ha N.

The natural infestation of weeds in the farmers' fields was heavy. Averaged over both varieties and both nitrogen levels, use of most herbicides resulted in at least 1.6 t/ha higher yield than the untreated control (Table 11). The grain yields with herbicide treatments were similar to the yields from plots hand-weeded twice.

Clearly, 2, 4-D or MCPA, which are low-cost herbicides, can control weeds in farmers' fields and substantially increase grain yields when weed population is heavy. In fact, 2, 4-D and MCPA are the largest selling rice herbicides in the Philippines.

Weed control in broadcast rice. Two field experiments were conducted during the 1972 dry season to evaluate new chemicals for con-

Table 11. Effect of applying granular herbicides (applied 4 days after transplanting) on grain yield in farmers' fields. Laguna, and Quezon Provinces, Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Total mean
		C4-63		IR20		
		0 kg/ha N	100 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	100 kg/ha N	
C-288	0.8/0.2	4.4 a	6.4 a	4.2 a	6.1 a	5.3
Butachlor	1.0	4.3 ab	6.2 a	3.9 a	5.6 ab	5.0
Benthiocarb	1.5	3.8 c	6.1 a	4.1 a	6.2 a	5.1
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	4.2 abc	6.1 a	4.1 a	5.5 b	5.0
2,4-D IPE	0.8	4.1 bc	6.4 a	4.0 a	6.0 ab	5.1
MCPA-K salt	0.8	4.1 bc	6.0 a	3.9 a	5.4 b	4.8
Hand weeding	twice	4.4 a	6.2 a	4.2 a	5.8 ab	5.1
Control	—	3.2 d	4.4 b	2.5 b	3.4 c	3.4

^aAverage of two replications and six locations.

trolling weeds in broadcast-seeded flooded rice. In these experiments, barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crusgalli*) seed was sown in all plots at 2 kg/ha immediately after seeding the rice.

In one experiment, nine herbicides were tested at the IRRI farm. The variety used was IR24. The high weed population in the untreated control prevented the rice from producing any grain (Table 12). Plots treated with butachlor gave the highest grain yield, 11 t/ha. Butachlor is currently being marketed in India, Sri Lanka, Korea, Taiwan, and the Philippines. Benthiocarb continued to look promising for broadcast-seeded flooded rice. The herbicides C-19490 and C-288 from Ciba-Geigy, and A-820 from Amchem controlled all annual weeds and resulted in similar yields to those of the benthiocarb and butachlor treatments.

In the second experiment, three herbicides were evaluated for controlling weeds on broadcast-seeded flooded IR22 rice under various water management conditions. C-288 resulted in higher grain yields than butachlor or NTN 5006 with 2, 4-D under most water management conditions (Table 13). But in plots where soil was kept saturated from seeding to panicle initiation, all three herbicides controlled weeds. These results show that with the poor water control generally present in farmers' fields in tropical Asia, these three chemicals can control weeds in broadcast-seeded flooded rice.

Control of a perennial sedge. Farmers control annual weeds in rice fields in tropical Asia by hand pulling, rotary weeding, or chemicals. But when populations of annual weeds are low,

perennial grasses and sedges often predominate and reduce rice yields. One such perennial sedge, *Scirpus maritimus*, is a serious problem for rice growers in portions of several provinces in the Philippines. It is more common in irrigated rice fields than in rainfed rice fields.

During the 1972 dry season, we evaluated two herbicides in an area of the IRRI farm where natural infestation of the sedge is generally high. In one treatment, butachlor and MCPA were applied together and in the other treatment, butachlor was followed by MCPA 29 days later. Both herbicide treatments were evaluated with two varieties—IR305-4-12, a semidwarf, and C4-63G, a variety with intermediate stature—grown under two levels of nitrogen.

At either level of nitrogen, the herbicide-

Table 12. Grain yield of broadcast-seeded flooded IR24 rice as affected by granular herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage of grasses. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Butachlor	1.0	11.0 a
Benthiocarb	1.5	9.0 bc
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	9.7 abc
C-288 ^b	0.8/0.2	10.4 ab
C-19490	1.5	10.4 ab
C-19490 + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	10.6 ab
USB 3153 ^c (spray)	1.0	8.4 c
A-820 ^d (spray)	3.0	10.4 ab
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	9.0 bc
Control	—	0.0 d

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bS-(2-methyl-1-piperidyl-carbonyl-methyl)-0-0-di-n-propyl dithiophosphate and 2-(1,2-dimethyl-propylamino)-4-ethylamino-6-methylmercapto-s-triazine. ^cCoded compound, chemistry not disclosed. ^dN-secondary-butyl-4-tertiary-butyl-2,6-dinitroaniline.

Table 13. Effects of water management practices on weed control by three granular herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage of grasses for broadcast-seeded IR22 rice. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Water management ^a	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)			
	Butachlor ^c	C-288 ^c	NTN 5006/ 2,4-D IPE ^d	Control
5 cm (A-M)	6.5	7.1	7.2	3.3
2.5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (6-10) (11-20) (21-M)	6.2	7.5	7.2	1.3
1 cm + 2.5 cm (A-PI) (PI-M)	6.0	7.0	6.4	1.4
2.5 cm (6-M)	6.4	7.3	7.1	1.8
5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (6-10) (11-20) (21-M)	7.2	7.0	6.5	3.2
2.5 cm + 5 cm (6-20) (21-M)	6.2	6.9	6.9	4.3
1 cm + 5 cm (6-20) (21-M)	6.6	7.0	6.5	2.1
5 cm (4-M)	7.3	6.4	6.9	1.7
2.5 cm + 5 cm (4-20) (21-M)	6.6	6.9	6.8	2.6
2.5 cm (A-M)	6.7	7.0	5.4	1.2

^aFor each water management treatment, the first line indicates the depth of water and the second line in parentheses indicates the corresponding period (numbers indicate days) the water was maintained. A = day rice was sown; PI = panicle initiation; M = maturity. ^bLSD value at 5% level for comparing two herbicide means at each water management is 1.7 t/ha. ^c1.0 kg/ha active ingredient. ^d2.0/0.45 kg/ha active ingredient.

treated plots produced significantly higher grain yield than the untreated controls (Table 14). The highest grain yield, 7.2 t/ha, was obtained with IR305-4-12 at 120 kg/ha N when 2 kg/ha of butachlor was applied 3 days after transplanting followed by 1 kg/ha of MCPP at mid-tillering stage. At the same nitrogen level, C4-63G produced 6.9 t/ha. Without herbicide application, the yields were 2 to 6 t/ha lower. These yield reductions were due to severe weed competition from the perennial sedge as shown by high weed counts. Nitrogen application greatly increased the weed weight per unit area.

Without weed control, the IR305 line had more weeds than C4-63G regardless of nitrogen level. A relatively taller variety like C4-63G competes better with *S. maritimus*, than a semidwarf like the IR305 line.

In another experiment during the 1972 wet season, several new chemicals were identified which provide good control of *S. maritimus*. The most outstanding result was obtained with bentazon (3-isopropyl-1H-2, 1, 3-benzothiaziazin-4(3H)-one 2, 2-dioxide) when applied at 3 kg/ha active ingredient 15 to 20 days after transplanting. This chemical is safe for rice but provides excellent control of *S. maritimus*.

Table 14. Control of *S. maritimus* in transplanted rice varieties (C4-63G and IR305-4-12) under continuous flooding with butachlor (2 kg/ha a.i.) and MCPP (1 kg/ha a.i.). IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Weed control ^c		Toxicity ^d		Weed wt. (g/sq m) 50 DT	Weed count (no./sq m)			
		19 DT	Heading	19 DT	Heading		20 DT	40 DT	60 DT	83 DT
0 kg/ha N										
C4-63G										
Butachlor + MCPP	5.0	9	7	3	2	3	0	0	33	46
Butachlor fb MCPP	3.6	7	8	2	3	12	3	15	5	28
Control	2.6	5	3	0	0	140	65	247	293	298
0 kg/ha N										
IR305-4-12										
Butachlor + MCPP	3.6	9	7	2	2	13	2	17	48	68
Butachlor fb MCPP	3.7	7	8	1	4	10	2	30	35	42
Control	1.5	5	2	0	0	153	83	278	350	348
120 kg/ha N										
C4-63G										
Butachlor + MCPP	6.9	9	8	2	2	8	2	5	27	23
Butachlor fb MCPP	6.4	7	9	1	2	13	18	32	2	2
Control	3.2	4	2	0	0	250	63	300	415	378
120 kg/ha N										
IR305-4-12										
Butachlor + MCPP	6.0	8	5	2	2	8	0	8	33	70
Butachlor fb MCPP	7.2	7	9	1	3	12	22	42	2	2
Control	0.7	5	0	0	0	377	58	247	327	346

^afb = followed by. ^bLSD (5%) = 0.7 t/ha. ^cScale: 0 to 10, 0 = no control, 10 = complete control. ^dScale: 0 to 10, 0 = no toxicity, 10 = complete kill.

Other promising herbicides for *Scirpus* control are Alachlor, Fenoprop [2, -(2,4,5-trichlorophenoxy) propionic acid], MBR 8251 (4-Phenyl-sulfonyl-trifluoromethanesulfonyl-o-toluidide), and MC4379 (coded compound).

RAINFED PADDY CULTURE

Varietal differences. During the 1972 wet season, 81 varieties or lines were grown under rainfed paddy conditions and continual flooding (5 cm deep throughout the cropping season). Among the entries were the five IRRI varieties, 10 upland varieties, all promising IRRI lines, and several lowland varieties from India, Indonesia, Thailand, and the Philippines. IR1561-149-5, which was one of the earliest maturing lines (111 days) tested, produced the highest grain yield under both irrigated and rainfed conditions (Table 15). The IRRI varieties yielded about the same since there was no prolonged moisture stress at any time during the cropping season. Under rainfed paddy conditions, the upland variety Azmil 26 and the lowland varieties Pelita I from Indonesia and Vijaya from India produced over 5 t/ha. A few lines which performed particularly well under both irrigated and rainfed conditions were IR442-2-58, IR577-24-1, IR579-92-2, IR665-8-3, IR968-93-3, IR1110-43-3, IR1168-58-2, IR1529-72-5, and IR1529-680-3. IR1514A-E666 yielded better under rainfed conditions than under irrigation primarily because it lodged less under rainfed conditions.

Nitrogen response. Nine promising lines were grown at IRRI under rainfed lowland conditions at five levels of nitrogen. Land was prepared and seedlings were raised without use of any irrigation water. The crop was planted in August. The rainfall distribution during the season was good so the crop did not suffer from moisture stress. IR1529-430-3 produced the highest grain yield, 6 t/ha, followed by IR1529-680-3 which produced 5.5 t/ha. IR1514A-E666 and IR442-2-58 produced about 4.5 t/ha as did IR20, IR22, and IR24.

In another experiment at the IRRI farm we evaluated the effect of nitrogen application on the yield potentials and protein content of promising lines grown under rainfed conditions.

Table 15. Growth duration and grain yield of rice varieties under irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Irrigated	Rainfed
Azmil 26	119-127	3.5	5.1
C4-63G	127	3.7	4.0
C-12	127	4.7	4.6
Pelita-1	119-127	4.9	5.1
Peta	135	1.1	1.4*
Ratna	111	4.7	5.2
RD1	127	3.9	4.0
Sigadis	135	2.7	2.8
Vijaya	127	5.0	5.4
IR1514A-E666	119	4.6	5.7
IR5	127-135	4.7	5.0
IR8	127	4.4	5.2
IR20	127	4.3	5.0
IR22	119-127	4.6	5.1
IR24	119-127	4.6	4.8
IR442-2-58	119-127	5.2	5.3
IR577-24-1	127	5.0	4.9
IR579-92-2	127	5.7	5.4
IR665-8-3	119-127	5.1	5.6
IR788-21-3	127	5.6	5.3
IR937-55-3	127	4.9	5.1
IR968-93-3	127	5.2	5.4
IR1110-43-3	119	5.4	5.7
IR1168-58-2	127-135	5.8	5.5
IR1529-72-5	127	5.2	5.6
-382-4	127	5.1	5.1
-677-2	127	4.6	4.8
-680-3	127	5.2	5.1
IR1541-76-3	119-127	5.0	5.3
IR1561-38-5	111-119	5.6	5.7
-149-5	111	5.8	5.9
-228	111	5.5	4.7

*From one replication.

Except for two T442 lines, all entries had similar yields without nitrogen (Table 16). The protein contents of IR442-2-58 and IR1514A-E666, however, were higher than those of other promising lines. IR1529-680-3 was particularly low in protein without fertilizer nitrogen. With 80 kg/ha N, the highest grain yield was obtained with IR1541-102-3 followed by the two IR1529 lines and IR442-2-58. Even with nitrogen, the protein content of IR1529-680-3 was slightly lower than that of the IR442 lines without nitrogen.

In a farmer's field in Calamba, Laguna, we grew four promising lines under rainfed conditions. IR20 and IR8 were grown as controls. Insecticides and herbicides were applied at minimum level. In this experiment, the highest

Table 16. Grain yield and protein content of rice varieties at two nitrogen levels under rainfed condition. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (%)
IR20	0	4.6	8.4
	80	4.5	10.0
IR1514A-E666	0	4.8	8.8
	80	4.8	10.5
IR442-2-58	0	4.6	9.0
	80	5.2	10.6
T442-90	0	3.6	9.5
	80	3.6	12.1
T442-57	0	3.7	9.4
	80	1.6	13.1
IR1541-102-3	0	4.5	8.3
	80	5.7	10.1
IR1529-680-3	0	4.6	6.6
	80	5.4	8.8
IR1529-382-4	0	4.4	7.9
	80	5.3	7.7
LSD		0.9	1.1

Table 17. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield of flooded rice in a farmer's field (avg of two replications). Laguna, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Growth duration (days)	Yield ^a (t/ha)			
		0 kg/ha N	25 kg/ha N	50 kg/ha N	75 kg/ha N
IR8	136	4.2	4.3	4.0	4.9
IR20	136	5.4	5.8	5.4	5.3
IR1541-76-3	130	5.7	6.4	5.7	5.7
IR1541-102-3	128	5.6	5.2	5.3	3.9
IR1529-680-3	136	5.2	5.5	6.0	5.1
IR1529-382-4	136	5.4	6.0	5.2	4.4

^aLSD (5%): Difference between two variety means at same nitrogen level—1.3 t/ha.

Table 18. The water balance components of two sites in Nueva Ecija at different growth stages of rice. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Growth stage ^a	Rainfall (mm)	Drainage (mm)	Net water use ^b (mm)	Effective rainfall ^c (%)
<i>Gapan</i>				
T-MT	581	289	292	50
MT-PI	73	6	66	92
PI-M	106	30	76	73
Total	760	325	434	57
<i>Palayan City</i>				
T-MT	576	312	263	46
MT-PI	76	14	61	81
PI-M	16	0	16	100
Total	668	326	340	51

^aT = transplanting; MT = maximum tillering; PI = panicle initiation; M = maturity. ^bDeep percolation and seepage losses were assumed negligible. ^c(Rainfall—drainage)/rainfall × 100.

grain yield, 6.4 t/ha, was obtained with IR1541-76-3 at 25 kg/ha N (Table 17). IR1529-680-3 produced similar yields to those of IR20. Because of high soil fertility in the experimental field, the grain yields without fertilizer nitrogen were high and most varieties produced highest grain yields at 25 kg/ha N.

Water balance in farmers' fields. Field experiments were conducted in Palayan City and Gapan in Central Luzon to study water balance in relation to growth stages of rainfed rice. In these locations, rainwater flows from the highest to the lowest paddies and is finally lost as drainage. We collected rainfall data daily and monitored the water loss into the drainage outlet (lowest point in these locations) with Parshall flumes. The difference between the highest paddy and the lowest paddy was about 2.5 m in Gapan and 3 m in Palayan City. IR20, C4-63, and an experimental line, IR442-2-58, were planted.

There was no serious moisture stress at either site before the maximum tillering stage (Table 18). The amount of rainfall in Palayan City was about the same as in Gapan during the early vegetative period (transplanting to maximum tillering) but more water drained away so the net water use by the rice crop was lower. The water available from transplanting to maximum tillering was 8.3 mm/day in Gapan and 7.5 mm/day in Palayan City. These amounts are sufficient for normal tillering. From maximum tillering and panicle initiation at both locations, the crop received only 2.2 mm/day. This amount was insufficient for the crop. More rain fell in Gapan than in Palayan City during panicle initiation and heading.

Average grain yields were lower in Palayan City (3.4 t/ha for IR20, 4.5 t/ha for C4-63, and 4.2 t/ha for IR442-2-58) than in Gapan (4.1 t/ha for IR20, 4.5 t/ha for C4-63, and 4.8 t/ha for IR442-2-58). In both locations, grain yields were progressively higher the lower the paddy (fig. 4). In Palayan City, which had drier paddies than Gapan the highest paddies of IR20 had 2.8 t/ha less yield than the lowest paddies while the IR442 line showed a difference of only 1.7 t/ha, indicating that the latter has higher drought tolerance.

Water economy on puddled and nonpuddled soils. Puddling is the process of breaking down

4. Correlation between relative elevation of paddies and grain yields of two rice varieties. Gapan and Palayan City, Philippines. 1972 wet season.

soil aggregates into a uniform mass. It removes soil structure and makes the soil ideal for transplanting rice. But for direct seeding of rice, granulated soil is better and it permits some degree of mechanization. A field experiment was conducted in Maahas clay soil at the IRRI farm during the 1972 wet season to monitor water economy of rainfed rice on puddled and nonpuddled soil. The experiment was repeated in tanks without and with bottoms. Six treatments were rainfed and two were irrigated (controls). Water level was measured by hook gauge every morning. In the rainfed plots, tensiometers were installed at 10, 20, and 30 cm deep in the soil in tanks without bottoms.

With or without nitrogen, the grain yields of Tongil (IR667-98-1) in nonpuddled soil were significantly lower than in puddled soil (Table 19). Under rainfed conditions, its growth duration was longer on nonpuddled soil than on puddled soil. The protein content in brown rice of Tongil was also higher in puddled treatments.

In the irrigated treatments the cumulative evapotranspiration from plants in nonpuddled soil increased more rapidly than that in puddled soil (fig. 5), probably because row-seeded rice

grown on nonpuddled soil had a higher plant population than the transplanted rice grown on puddled soil. From the difference between cumulative water applied and cumulative evapotranspiration (water used), the amount of percolation and other losses was derived. Considerably higher losses of water through percolation were recorded in nonpuddled soil than in puddled soil (fig. 5).

The values of evapotranspiration in tanks without bottoms were calculated from regression

Table 19. Growth duration, grain yield, and protein content of rainfed Tongil (IR667-98-1) rice grown on puddled and nonpuddled soils at two levels of nitrogen (tanks without bottoms). IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Method of planting	Puddled	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (%)
<i>0 kg/ha N</i>				
Transplanted	Yes	96	3.01 de	8.2 c
Broadcast	Yes	88	3.52 bcd	8.4 c
Row-seeded	No	108	2.25 f	8.0 c
<i>75 kg/ha N</i>				
Transplanted	Yes	96	4.02 abc	10.5 a
Broadcast	Yes	88	4.10 ab	9.9 ab
Row-seeded	No	108	2.82 ef	8.9 bc
Transplanted*	Yes	96	4.56 a	10.6 a
Row-seeded*	No	95	3.44 cd	9.8 ab

*Continual flooding (with irrigation) at 5 cm.

equations derived from values obtained from tanks with bottoms as affected by environmental factors and days after planting: for puddled soil

$$\hat{Y} = -3.63 + 0.003X_1 + 0.005X_2 + 0.008X_3 + 0.561X_4 + 0.108X_5 - 0.006X_6 - 0.069X_7$$

$$R^2 = 0.779^{**}$$

and for nonpuddled soil

$$\hat{Y} = -8.03 + 0.004X_1 + 0.007X_2 + 0.067X_3 + 0.045X_4 + 0.192X_5 + 0.002X_6 - 0.140X_7$$

$$R^2 = 0.798^{**}$$

where X_1 is gross solar radiation, X_2 is actual sunshine, X_3 is mean air temperature, X_4 is relative humidity, X_5 is mean wind speed, X_6 is days after planting, and X_7 is rainfall.

In rainfed treatments in tanks without bottoms, Tongil suffered from a 2-week drought at panicle initiation. Soil moisture tension reached 70 centibars (cb) at 10 cm in nonpuddled soil compared with 25 cb in puddled soil. At 30 cm, tensions reached 45 cb in nonpuddled soil compared with 15 cb in puddled soil. Soil moisture tensions at 20 cm (fig. 6) were intermediate between those at 10-cm and 30-cm soil depths.

Cultural practices. During the 1972 wet season an experiment was conducted to study the feasibility of cultural practices for broadcast-seeded rice developed at IRRI for rainfed areas. IR24 was broadcast or transplanted and grown with one of three water treatments: continual flooding to 5 cm, irrigation to 5 cm every 15 days, or rainfed. One type of land preparation tested was zero tillage. For weed control under zero tillage we applied a mixture of Dalapon (3 kg/ha a.i.) and 2, 4-D amine (0.5 kg/ha a.i.) 12 days before planting. Seven days later we applied Paraquat spray at 1 kg/ha a.i. The second type of land preparation was one plowing and one harrowing and the third was one plowing and two harrowings which is considered the standard practice. Sixty kilograms of nitrogen per hectare was applied basally during land preparation, in equal split doses during land preparation and at panicle initiation, or in equal split doses during land preparation, at maximum tillering, and at panicle initiation. The control had no nitrogen application. We used a split-split plot design with water management as main plot, combinations of nitrogen level and land

Cumulative amount of water (mm)

5. Comparison of cumulative water applied, evapotranspiration, and percolation loss in puddled and nonpuddled soils continually flooded at 5 cm. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

preparation as subplots, and method of planting as sub-subplot. There were three replications.

The different water management treatments had no significant effect on yields because frequent heavy rains kept even the rainfed plots from developing any moisture stress. The yield from zero tillage was 1.3 t/ha less than that from one plowing and one harrowing and 1.5 t/ha less than that from standard land preparation (Table 20). Yields from one plowing and one harrowing were about the same as yields from standard land preparation.

Plots without nitrogen had much lower yields than any of the fertilized plots, but yield differences between the fertilized plots were not significant. The transplanted plots produced 0.47 t/ha more than the broadcast-seeded plots, a significant difference.

Yields with zero tillage were lower than with plowing and harrowing primarily because of heavy infestation of *Paspalum* spp. The infestation of weeds was worse in rainfed plots than in continually flooded plots.

Because zero tillage provides inconsistent results, it should not be advocated for farmers particularly those in rainfed areas. Moreover, although one plowing and one harrowing gave statistically comparable yield to one plowing and two harrowings, under farm conditions in rainfed areas it is desirable to harrow two or more times to suppress weed growth.

Fertilizers. More nitrogen is lost from rainfed paddies than from irrigated paddies. Thus, slow-release nitrogen fertilizers might be valuable for rainfed fields. In the wet season we compared slow-release fertilizers with standard fertilizer

Soil moisture tension (cb)

6. Soil moisture tensions at 20 cm depth in puddled and nonpuddled soils under rainfed conditions. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

sources like urea and ammonium sulfate. IR24 was the test variety.

The grain yields were generally high for a wet season crop. The highest, 7.8 t/ha, is perhaps the highest yield ever obtained with rainfed paddy rice at the IRRI farm (Table 21). Sulfur-coated urea with a release rate of 21 percent gave significantly higher grain yields than all other fertilizers, confirming results obtained with irrigated rice in the dry season. It appears that sulfur-

Table 20. Grain yield of broadcast and transplanted IR24 under three water management treatments and three types of land preparation^a IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Land preparation	Broadcast yield (t/ha)			Transplanted yield (t/ha)			Mean ^d
	Rainfed ^b	Intermittent irrigation ^c	Continuous irrigation	Rainfed ^b	Intermittent irrigation ^c	Continuous irrigation	
Zero tillage	2.56	2.77	3.19	3.23	3.30	3.59	3.11 b
One plowing and one harrowing	4.29	4.00	4.21	4.36	4.96	4.51	4.39 a
One plowing and two harrowings	4.35	4.41	4.61	4.78	4.81	4.88	4.64 a
Mean ^e	3.73	3.86	4.00	4.12	4.36	4.33	

^aData are averaged over four nitrogen levels and three replications. ^bDalapon/2,4-D followed by paraquat. ^cEvery 15 days. ^dAny two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^eTreatment means are not significantly different from each other.

Table 21. Sources of nitrogen for broadcast-seeded and transplanted rainfed IR24 with single or split application (80 kg/ha N). IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Nitrogen source	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)				Mean
	Broadcast		Transplanted		
	Single	Split ^b	Single	Split ^b	
Ammonium sulfate	7.0	7.2	6.2	6.8	6.8 b
Urea	7.1	7.5	6.5	6.5	6.9 b
Sulfur-coated urea ^c					
6% R	7.1	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9 b
17% R	6.9	6.7	7.1	6.9	6.9 b
21% R	7.8	7.3	6.9	7.5	7.4 a
26% R	7.2	7.2	6.7	7.0	7.1 b
Isobutylidene diurea	6.9	7.2	6.9	6.9	7.0 b
Unfertilized control	5.5		5.2		5.4 c

^aAny two source means followed by at least one common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bThree equal split doses (basal + at tillering + panicle initiation). ^cR = dissolution rate in 2 weeks.

coated urea with a nitrogen release rate of about 20 percent has a definite advantage over other slow-release and standard nitrogen sources, but it should be used only where the yield increase justifies the price of fertilizer.

Phosphorus deficiency in rice often is more apparent under rainfed conditions where the paddies dry up intermittently than under continual flooding. In a rainfed experiment conducted at San Rafael, Bulacan, Philippines (soil: pH 4.0; Bray No. 2, extractable P, 3.7 ppm) to compare rock phosphate sources, the highest yield was obtained with rock phosphate from Morocco but there were no significant differences among the sources (Table 22). Added phosphorus caused a significant increase in yields, however.

Weed control. The goal of our herbicide screening trials is to find new effective herbicides

to give the farmer a choice among several products. When several effective herbicides are on the market the farmer can choose the most economical one.

For the first time we screened new herbicides entirely under rainfed conditions. Until the 1972 wet season, all new chemicals were first tested at the IRRI farm under continual flooding.

New chemicals which were found promising under transplanted rainfed conditions are MBR 8251 from 3M Company, USA; AC 92,390 from American Cyanamid, USA; S-18510 from Gulf Oil, USA; CRD 70-3469 from Pépro, France; and Tribunil [1,3-dimethyl-3-(2-benzothiazolyl) urea] from Bayer, Germany (Table 23). Due to heavy weed infestation, the untreated control did not produce any grain yield.

In another experiment all chemicals were tested in broadcast-seeded IR24 rice under rainfed lowland conditions. MON 0385, experimental herbicide from Monsanto, USA, looked highly promising for direct-seeded rice when applied at 1 kg/ha a.i. at the one-leaf to two-leaf stage of grassy weeds (Table 24). A chemical (Molinate) which is extensively used for rice in USA and Australia looked promising in combination with a broadleaved weed killer. This combination herbicide is called Ordram B. Other promising new herbicides are M-3432 from Montecatini, Italy; GS 14260/C-19490, from Ciba-Geigy, Switzerland; MC 4379 from Mobil Corp., USA; and HOE 16410 from Hoechst, Germany. HOE 16410 is somewhat toxic to the broadcast-seeded crop. Most herbicide treatments shown in Table 24 produced yields similar to the standard herbicide treatments, butachlor

Table 22. Effects of phosphorus fertilization (25 to 200 kg/ha P₂O₅) on the grain yield of rainfed IR20. San Rafael, Bulacan, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Source	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Mean
	25 kg/ha	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	200 kg/ha	
Triple superphosphate	3.9	4.1	4.4	4.2	4.2
Idaho rock phosphate	3.8	4.1	4.0	4.0	4.0
N. Carolina rock phosphate	4.1	3.9	3.6	3.9	3.9
C. Florida rock phosphate	3.6	4.2	4.0	4.1	4.0
N. Florida rock phosphate	3.7	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.1
Morocco rock phosphate	3.8	4.0	4.5	3.8	4.0
Tennessee rock phosphate	3.4	3.9	3.8	4.1	3.8
Mean	3.8	4.0	4.0	4.0	

^aAverage of four replications. Control without P₂O₅ yielded 3.3 t/ha. Any treatment mean exceeding 4 t/ha is significantly higher than the control.

Table 23. Grain yield of transplanted rainfed IR24 rice as affected by promising new herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting (before weeds emerge) and 10 days after transplanting (after weeds emerge). IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Chemical	Formulation ^a	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Yield (t/ha)	
			4 DT ^b	10 DT ^b
AC 92,390	L	1.0	—	4.22
CRD 70-3469	L	0.5	5.00	—
CRD 70-3469	L	1.0	—	4.72
GS 14260/C-19490	L	0.75	4.13	4.39
MBR 8251	WP	2.0	4.60	—
MBR 8251	WP	6.0	—	4.04
MON 0385	L	1.5	—	5.07
Ordram B	G	2.0/0.57	4.76	—
S-18510	L	2.0	4.25	—
Tribunil	WP	1.0	4.08	4.23
2,4-D IPE	G	0.8	3.71	—
Control	—	—	0	0

^aL = liquid, WP = wettable powder, G = granular. ^bDays after transplanting.

and benthocarb. MON 0385, Ordram B, and GS 14260/C-19490 also gave good results in the trials with transplanted rice.

UPLAND RICE

Varietal differences. During the 1972 wet season, 72 promising lines or varieties including several upland varieties from the Philippines and Africa were grown under upland conditions in four locations in the Philippines. These locations represent different soil and climatic conditions. In Batangas, a farmer's field was used; the other three locations were experiment stations. The better yielding entries are shown in Table 25. The superior yielding ability of IR442-2-58 under wide range of conditions makes it highly promising for upland rice. IR930-2-6, IR1487-372-4, and two IR1529 lines also yielded well in these trials. Among the Philippine upland varieties, C-22 is perhaps the best, but it is more susceptible to lodging than IR442-2-58 or IR5. None of the African varieties (OS4, OS6, and E425) yielded well because of their low tillering capacity and susceptibility to bacterial leaf blight and stem borers.

IR442-2-58, a semidwarf line, appears to be the most promising line for upland rice. Averaged for 4 years, its grain and that of IR5 were the same (Table 26). Both IR5 and IR442-2-58 yielded 1.8 t/ha more than M1-48, one of the

Table 24. Grain yield of broadcast rainfed IR24 rice as affected by promising new herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage and two- to three-leaf stage of grassy weeds. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Yield (t/ha)	
		1 to 2 leaves	2 to 3 leaves
GS 14260/C-19490	0.75	5.8	5.6
M-3432	2.0	4.8	5.2
M-3432	4.0	—	6.1
MC 4379	3.0	—	5.3
MON 0385	1.0	5.8	—
Ordram B	1.5/0.43	5.9	—
Ordram B	2.0/0.57	—	5.4
HOE 16410	1.0	—	4.6
Benthocarb	1.5	—	6.0
Butachlor	1.0	5.6	—
Control	—	0.8	0.8

Table 25. Upland rice yield trials at four locations in the Philippines. 1972 wet season.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	IRRI	Batangas ^a	Maligaya	La Granja	Avg
Azmil 26	2.3	4.6	2.4	1.0	2.6
Azucena	2.4	2.9	1.9	1.4	2.2
Dinalaga	2.7	4.2	2.9	1.4	2.8
Palawan	1.7	4.2	2.3	2.0	2.5
M1-48	2.4	3.9	1.8	1.3	2.4
C-22	3.0	4.1	3.7	3.2	3.5
OS4	2.2	3.1	2.5	^b	2.6
OS6	2.7	2.2	1.8	0.9	1.9
E425	2.1	1.8	2.8	^b	2.2
IR8	2.9	3.8	2.8	2.9	3.1
IR5	3.2	4.3	2.0	2.3	3.0
IR442-2-58	4.5	5.0	3.7	2.9 ^c	4.0
IR930-2-6	3.7	5.5	4.7	3.2	4.3
IR1487-372-4	3.3	4.7	4.2	2.1	3.6
IR1529-677-2	3.8	4.5	4.6	3.2	4.0
IR1529-72-3	4.1	5.4	3.8	3.1	4.1
IR20	3.4	3.9	4.1	2.1	3.4

^aFarmer's field (non-replicated). ^bNo harvest due to severe rat damage. ^cYield of one replication only, the other plots were damaged by rats or eroded by heavy rains.

Table 26. Grain yields of three rice varieties grown under upland conditions during four wet seasons (1969-1972).

Date of seeding	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	IR5	IR442-2-58	M1-48
June 1969 ^a	5.2	4.6	2.2
June 1970 ^a	4.8	4.6	3.5
August 1971 ^a	4.0	3.4	1.6
June 1972 ^b	3.0	4.0	2.4
Avg	4.2	4.2	2.4

^aAt IRRI farm. ^bAverage of four locations (IRRI, Batangas, Maligaya, and La Granja).

Table 27. Grain yield and some plant characters and yield components of five varieties grown under upland condition. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./sq m)	100-grain wt (g)	Growth duration (days)
IR5	3.2	96	216	2.54	140
IR442-2-58	4.5	98	204	2.44	123
M1-48	2.4	121	110	2.40	118
OS6	2.7	129	140	3.31	113
C-22	3.0	115	198	2.28	122

recommended upland rice varieties in the Philippines.

The plant height, growth duration, and grain yield of the two upland varieties, M1-48 and C-22 from the Philippines, of OS6 from Africa, of IR5 and of IR442-2-58 were compared in an experiment conducted at the IRRI farm during the 1972 wet season. In this experiment, IR5 and IR442-2-58 were about the same height, but 15 to 20 cm shorter than the Philippine upland varieties and about 30 cm shorter than OS6 (Table 27). IR442-2-58 was 17 days earlier than IR5 but similar in maturity to C-22.

The IR442 line has clear translucent grains with small white centers but no white belly. M1-48, C-22, and OS6, and the IR442 line had higher head rice recovery than IR5 (Table 28). The highest head rice yield was obtained with IR442-2-58. IR442-2-58 and M1-48 had considerably better grain appearance than OS6 and IR5. The protein content (brown rice) was the highest in IR442-2-58 (Table 28).

Although many upland varieties are resistant to blast, C-22 and IR442-2-58 are susceptible (Table 29). Field observations at Batangas indicate that when the crop was planted early (no later than June) as most farmers do, the IR442 line did not suffer from blast. When planted late IR442-2-58 matured in the cool months of November or December and suffered from blast.

Table 28. Milling quality and protein content of five rice varieties grown under upland conditions. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)	Chalky kernels (%)	Brown rice protein (%)	Head rice yield (t/ha)
IR5	64	45	19	5	7.0	1.4
IR442-2-58	69	58	11	6	7.7	2.6
M1-48	68	59	9	6	6.9	1.4
OS6	70	59	9	6	7.4	1.6
C-22	67	53	14	13	7.4	1.6

IR5 and IR442-2-58 are resistant to green leafhopper while all upland varieties tested are susceptible (Table 29).

Weed competition. Unchecked competition between upland rice and weeds throughout the growing period reduces grain yield. During the 1972 wet season, we conducted an experiment at the IRRI farm to measure yield reductions due to two groups of weeds. We compared plots containing (1) no weeds, (2) annual broadleaves and sedges, (3) perennial nutsedge (*Cyperus rotundus*), and (4) a combination of annual and perennial weeds. In plots with perennial nutsedge, despite constant removal, some *Cyperus iria*, an annual sedge, was also present. IR5 was broadcast seeded or row seeded.

In the broadcast-seeded crop, grain yield was reduced by 82 percent when all weed species were allowed to compete with rice (Table 30). Annual grasses and broadleaved weeds reduced grain yield by 70 percent. *Cyperus rotundus* alone reduced grain yields by 41 percent. Similar yield reductions occurred in the row-seeded crop.

The 82 percent reduction in grain yield was due to fewer tillers and panicles, and lower leaf area index and light transmission ratio.

Weed control. Except for water supply, inadequate weed control is perhaps the greatest barrier to higher yields of upland rice. Since more than one weeding is needed to remove all weeds, chemical weed control is essential if upland rice is to be grown successfully.

In a trial conducted under simulated upland conditions during the 1972 dry season at IRRI, several new chemicals such as USB 3153 and USB 3584 from U.S. Borax, and U-27267 from Upjohn Company, USA, appeared highly promising for upland rice (Table 31). Butachlor applied at 2 kg/ha 2 days after seeding continued to be effective in upland rice.

In the wet season we evaluated seven chemicals

Table 29. Differences^a in the resistance to diseases and insects of varieties for upland conditions at IRRI.

Designation	Blast ^b	Bacterial leaf blight ^c (IRRI field)	Green leafhopper ^c (Greenhouse)
Azmil	3 to 4	S	S
Azucena	3 to 4 ^d	S	S
Dinalaga	1	S	S
Palawan	3 to 4	S	S
M1-48	1	MS	S
C-22	5	S	S
BPI-76 (n.s.)	1 ^e	S	R
OS4	3	S	S
OS6	1 ^e	S	S
E425	3 to 4	S	S
IR8	5	S	R
IR5	4 ^f	S	R
IR442-2-58	6	MS	R

^aReadings made by the plant pathology and entomology departments. ^bLesion scale: 1 = highly resistant, 7 = very susceptible. ^cR = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^dSome plants had scale 5 lesions. ^eSome plants had scale 3 lesions. ^fFew lesions.

in comparison with hand weeding in a farmer's field in Batangas. IR5 was used as the test variety. The major weed species present in the experimental site were the grasses *Echinochloa colonum*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Eleusine indica*, and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*; the broadleaved weeds *Mimosa invisa*, *Vernonia cinerea*, and *Commelina benghalensis*; and the sedges *Cyperus rotundus*, *Cyperus compressus*, and *Cyperus iria*. The weed infestation was so heavy that the untreated control yielded only 1 t/ha (Table 32).

All treated plots gave significantly higher grain yields than the untreated control. The highest grain yield, 4.9 t/ha, was obtained with C-288 and with hand weeding two times. Butachlor controlled weeds adequately except in one replication where a severe infestation of *Mimosa invisa* reduced the grain yield substantially. Nevertheless, the grain yield with butachlor was not significantly different from that of the best treatment (Table 32). Fluorodifen at 3 kg/ha continued to look promising. U-27267 (3,4,5-tribromo - N,N α - trimethylpyrazole - 1 - acetamide) caused severe toxicity to the crop throughout the entire growing period.

In another experiment in the 1972 wet season, herbicides found promising in earlier experiments at the IRRI farm were tested in cooperation with the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center. These were compared with hand weeding twice to remove weeds completely.

Table 30. Effect of weed densities and weed competition on grain yield of upland rice (IR5) under two methods of seeding. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Weed community	Drilled		Broadcast	
	Weed wt ^a (g/sq m)	Yield (t/ha)	Weed wt ^a (g/sq m)	Yield (t/ha)
Weed free	20	4.7	14	4.9
Annuals (broadleaved and grasses)	765	1.2	645	1.6
Perennial nutsedge ^b	508	2.7	520	2.4
Perennial nutsedge and annuals	928	0.8	908	0.9

^aTaken at flowering of grassy weeds. ^b*Cyperus rotundus* L. and some *Cyperus iria*.

Table 31. Promising liquid herbicides for rice (IR442-2-58) grown under simulated upland conditions. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Herbicide	Application		Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DS ^a)	
Fluorodifen	3	3	2.7 ^c
Butachlor	2	3	4.1
USB 3153	1	3	4.8
USB 3584	1	3	4.5 ^c
U-27267	2	3	3.8
Propanil	3	15 ^d	4.5 ^c
Hand weeding	twice	15 & 30 ^d	3.8
Control	—	—	0.4

^aDays after seeding. ^bAverage of two replications. ^cOne replication. ^dDays after rice emerged.

The test variety was IR5. The treatments were repeated four times in randomized complete block design.

The major weed species in the experimental site were the grasses *Echinochloa colonum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eleusine indica*, and *Paspalidium flavidum*; the sedges *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cyperus iria*; and the broadleaved weeds *Commelina benghalensis*, *Portulaca oleracea*, and *Eclipta alba*.

The infestation was not as heavy as in the farmer's field in Batangas. The untreated control plots produced grain yield of 2.6 t/ha (Table 32). Plots treated with fluorodifen at 2 kg/ha a.i. produced 4.3 t/ha which is significantly higher than the yield from the untreated plots and comparable to yield from the hand-weeded plots. Benthocarb and C-288, two highly selective chemicals under IRRI conditions, caused severe crop toxicity at Maligaya which was sustained throughout the entire growth period, resulting

Table 32. Promising liquid herbicides for upland rice (IR5) tested at two locations in the Philippines. Farmer's field Batangas, and Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Herbicide	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
		Batangas ^b	Nueva Ecija ^c
Benthiocarb	2	4.4 abc	0.8 d
Butachlor	2	3.5 abc	3.2 bc
C-288	2	4.9 a	0.6 d
Fluorodifen	2	3.1 bc	4.3 a
Fluorodifen	3	4.7 ab	3.9 ab
A-820	2	4.6 ab	—
U-27267	2	2.8 c	—
USB 3153	2	4.2 abc	—
Hand weeding	twice ^d	4.9 a	4.3 a
Control	—	1.0 d	2.6 c

^aMean of four replications. At one location any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bHerbicides applied 6 days after rice emerged. ^cHerbicides applied 5 days after rice emerged. ^dAt 20 and 40 days after rice emerged.

in yields of less than 1 t/ha. Butachlor, another selective herbicide, also caused severe initial toxicity to the crop. Although the plants were able to recover somewhat, plots treated with butachlor had significantly lower yields than plots treated with fluorodifen.

Liquid butachlor (Machete) is the only herbicide available for upland rice, in the Philippine market. At our recommended rate of application, 2 kg/ha a.i., it costs farmers US\$16/ha. This is expensive for weed control in upland rice. In the Philippines, however, a 300 kg/ha increase in rice yield would pay for the use of butachlor. In most of our experiments use of butachlor or fluorodifen gave at least 2 t/ha higher yield. So chemical weed control at \$16/ha is worth considering if improved varieties are grown with modern cultural practices and if the farmer is not willing to spend at least 400 to 500 man-hours/hectare to hand weed two times or more.

Suitable control measures must be developed for persistent weeds like *Cyperus rotundus* (nut-sedge) before upland rice culture can become commercially attractive.

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Lowland rice. In an experiment during the 1972 dry season, 30 varieties or lines were grouped according to their growth durations under irrigation and were subjected to soil moisture ten-

Table 33. Grain yield of varieties and lines grouped by growth duration and subjected to soil moisture stress (50 centibars) during the vegetative stage (early stress) or during the reproductive and ripening stages (late stress) as compared with yield with continual flooding 5 cm deep (no stress). IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Designation	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)		
		Early stress	Late stress	No stress
<i>Early maturing^a</i>				
IR1561-38-5	114	5.7	6.0	7.4
IR790-28-1	121-131	5.7	6.0	6.8
IR1110-43-3	121-138	5.2	6.0	7.9
IR1561-149-5	99-114	5.0	5.7	7.8
IR1561-69-6	99-114	5.4	5.6	7.3
Ratna	99-114	4.2	5.0	6.9
IR841-5-1	121-131	5.3	4.3	7.0
IR480-5-9	121-131	5.0	4.8	6.3
IR747B ₂ -6-3	99-103	3.6	4.3	5.9
Padma	99-114	5.1	3.8	4.5
Mean		5.0	5.1	6.8
<i>Intermediate^a</i>				
IR579-92-2	131-138	7.5	5.8	7.4
IR841-99-1	121-138	6.9	5.0	7.2
IR262-43-8	114-131	6.0	4.6	6.3
IR665-8-3	114-131	6.7	4.5	6.7
IR667-142-2	131-138	5.6	4.1	6.2
TN1	121	6.8	4.0	6.3
CR 36-148	114-131	6.8	3.9	6.0
IR1093-148	131-142	6.1	3.0	5.7
IR478-68-2	131-138	4.9	3.0	5.0
M1-48	114	4.6	1.1	2.1
Mean		6.2	3.9	5.9
<i>Late maturing^a</i>				
IR24	131-138	4.7	5.6	7.7
IR8	131-138	5.5	5.5	8.2
IR937-55-3	131-138	5.0	5.5	7.8
IR20	121-131	6.2	4.8	7.5
Jaya	121-138	5.1	4.7	6.6
IR22	114-131	5.2	4.6	6.7
C4-63 G	138-142	4.4	4.3	4.2
IR1531-93-3	131-138	5.3	3.7	7.0
IR127-80-1-10	114-131	4.4	3.3	7.0
IR1531-73-5	131-138	3.7	2.6	4.4
Mean		5.0	4.5	6.7

^aGrouping based on growth duration under continual flooding.

sion of 50 centibars (cb) throughout either the vegetative or reproductive stages of the crop or to 0 cb (continual flooding).

Stress affected the growth durations (Table 33). In the early maturing group, IR790-28-1 and the three IR1561 lines tested produced high yields in all moisture treatments. The average grain yields of all early varieties and lines at either the vegetative stage or the reproductive and ripening stages were significantly different from yields of the continually flooded plots, showing the effect of moisture stress.

The grain yields of varieties with intermediate

7. Relative growth of IR1561-149-5, IR442-2-58, and the upland variety C-22 when subjected to continual moisture stress of 75 cb.

growth duration were significantly reduced only by moisture stress during the reproductive and ripening stages. The experimental lines which suffered least due to moisture stress during the reproductive and ripening period were IR579-92-2, IR665-8-3, and IR841-99-1 (Table 33).

The late maturing lines behaved the same as early maturing lines—moisture stress reduced grain yields irrespective of when it occurred. The four IRRI varieties tested and IR937-55-3 were among the better performers in the late maturing group.

Although our results, obtained in the dry season with controlled irrigation, may not be valid for the wet season, they indicate that interaction between moisture stress and growth stage of the crop may be affected by the growth duration of the variety. But the relationships between growth durations of rice varieties and resistance to soil moisture stress will depend on the nature of rainfall distribution for a particular season. If the rainfall distribution is more uniform during the first 90 to 100 days during the wet season, the early maturing varieties should have advantage over later varieties. On the other hand, if the rainfall distribution is erratic during the early part and more uniform during the later part of the rainy season, the medium to late maturing varieties should perform better than the early varieties. Until a variety is developed which is drought tolerant at all stages of growth, farmers should consider planting at least two varieties with different growth durations to avoid a complete crop failure when prolonged moisture stress occurs.

Upland rice. We are attempting to develop a reliable method for screening rice varieties for drought tolerance. In 1972, we tested the upland variety C-22 and IR442-2-58 and IR1561-149-5 which are considered promising lines for upland rice, with soil moisture tensions of 0, 33, and 75 cb in the greenhouse. Figure 7 shows that when the varieties were subjected to a relatively continual moisture tension of 75 cb, IR442-2-58 produced more tillers than C-22 or IR1561-149-5 indicating that the IR442 line has better drought tolerance than the others.

VARIETAL ADAPTATION TO WATER CONDITIONS

Different rice varieties have been bred for upland, lowland, and deep water areas in Asia. Since 80 percent of the rice growing area is rainfed, development of rice varieties adapted to a wide range of water supply conditions could have profound effects on the production of rainfed rice. In other words, if a variety could adjust its growth characteristics to the moisture supply, it would be of great significance since it is impossible to predict the distribution of rainfall.

We conducted an experiment during the 1972 wet season using rice varieties which are well suited for specific water and land management systems—IR8, a typical high yielding lowland variety; C-22, the latest Philippine upland variety; Leb Mue Nhang, a traditional variety in deep water areas of Thailand; T442-57, an improved semidwarf which has performed well in water 130 to 150 cm deep in Thailand; and IR442-2-58 which we consider the most promising line for upland rice. The varieties were grown under upland and rainfed paddy conditions, and under three irrigation levels. The irrigation treatments consisted of continual flooding to 5 cm deep (control), to 30 cm deep, and to 92 cm deep. In the 30 and 92 cm treatments, continual flooding to 5 cm was maintained until 20 days after transplanting. The water depths were then increased by 3 cm every day until the desired depths were reached. The desired depths were maintained until the crop matured. The point of the 30- and 92-cm treatments was to determine varietal response to moderate deep water conditions which occur in some areas of the tropics.

8. Yields of rice varieties under different water management conditions. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Deep water made the plants grow taller. In the 92-cm treatment T442-57 had the greatest increase in height, 61 cm, compared with the control plants but was only 9 cm taller than IR442-2-58. C-22 had the least increase, 5 cm (Table 34). IR8 showed limited capacity to elongate beyond 30 cm of water: it was completely submerged in 92 cm deep water.

Tillering capacity was greatly reduced in all varieties at 92 cm of water except in T442-57, confirming results from Thailand that it is the best suited semidwarf for moderately deep levels of water.

The grain yields of IR8 and IR442-2-58 under 5 cm of continual irrigation were about the same (fig. 8). When the water depth was increased from 5 cm to 30 cm, however, the yield of IR8 dropped 1.7 t/ha while that of IR442-2-58 was only 0.3 t/ha lower. The other entries had low yields in both 5 cm and 30 cm deep water. At 92 cm of water, T442-57 and IR442-2-58 had about the same yield, which was substantially higher than the yield of the other varieties. IR8 was drowned. Despite the better stand and higher tiller number of T442-57 at 92 cm of water, the yield of it and the IR442 line were similar primarily because T442-57 had more bacterial blight.

Table 34. Growth duration and plant characters of rice varieties grown under several water treatments. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Water level	Growth duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./sq m)
<i>IR8</i>			
Upland	124	70	407
Rainfed lowland	130	96	241
Irrigated			
5 cm	130	101	288
30 cm	126	119	197
92 cm	0	0	0
<i>C-22</i>			
Upland	124	114	301
Rainfed lowland	130	142	194
Irrigated			
5 cm	130	138	138
30 cm	130	165	203
92 cm	136	143	81
<i>IR442-2-58</i>			
Upland	124	88	311
Rainfed lowland	126	113	206
Irrigated			
5 cm	126	127	237
30 cm	126	135	212
92 cm	130	161	112
<i>T442-57</i>			
Upland	126	94	297
Rainfed lowland	130	109	234
Irrigated			
5 cm	130	109	228
30 cm	136	134	178
92 cm	140	170	160
<i>Leb Mue Nhang</i>			
Upland	126	183	199
Rainfed lowland	136	208	116
Irrigated			
5 cm	136	185	119
30 cm	136	189	182
92 cm	136	236	131

Under upland and rainfed lowland conditions, IR8 and IR442-2-58 yielded substantially more than all other varieties (fig. 8). T442-57 yielded poorly under upland and rainfed lowland conditions because of lodging and bacterial blight. IR442-2-58 appears to be the most promising line for most rainfed areas.

These results substantiate the idea of identifying or breeding a variety which could adjust its growth characteristics depending on the land and water management systems (upland, lowland, and moderately deep water) in areas that are rainfed. To develop drought-tolerant varieties for most rainfed areas, deep water varieties should be extensively used in breeding programs since they are often grown under drought conditions for the first 4 to 6 weeks after seeding.

Statistics

This year's experiments revealed that: For measuring stem borer incidence, the "modified screening technique" reduces bias caused by induced tillering. Percentage yield loss is a better indicator than absolute yield in assessing yield loss caused by stem borer damage through regression technique. In experiments involving different plant spacings, area rather than number of hills should be the basis for plot yield determination. Soil heterogeneity in a succeeding planting can be increased by applying different levels of nitrogen or by planting varieties differing in growth duration. Fertility patterns in rice fields persist for as much as 10 crop seasons. A square wire frame placed before seeding is best for demarcating the sampling area in broadcast rice plots.

ESTIMATING STEM BORER DAMAGE

Measuring percentage of dead hearts and white heads. Estimates of incidence of dead hearts and white heads made with the screening technique are biased because of induced tillering in infested hills (1971 Annual Report). This bias can be avoided by determining the number of tillers not only in infested hills but also in uninfested hills, possibly through sampling. In this way the total number of tillers in the sample area, and thus the percentage of incidence, can be determined accurately. Since counting tillers in both uninfested and infested hills is time consuming, we investigated an alternative procedure based on the usual screening technique but using a different computational formula. In this modified screening technique the percentage of incidence is computed as follows:

$$I = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i}{N} \right) 100$$

where I is the incidence (%) of dead hearts or white heads, p_i is the proportion of infested tillers in the i -th hill, n is the number of infested hills, and N is the total number of hills in the sample area.

Using data from surveys made in Nueva Ecija in 1970 and 1971, we compared estimates from the usual screening technique and the modified screening technique with estimates from complete enumeration. While the screening technique gave significant underestimation of incidence at all plant growth stages, the modified

Table 1. Incidence of dead hearts and white heads in farmers' fields based on complete tiller count as compared with estimates from the screening technique (ST) and the modified screening technique (MST). Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1970-1971.^a

Time of sampling ^b	Dead hearts and white heads (%)			Bias (%)	
	Complete count	ST	MST	ST	MST
<i>1970 wet season</i>					
50 DT	3.88	3.76	3.92	-3.1**	1.0
90 DT	1.61	1.56	1.62	-3.1**	0.6
Maturity	2.26	2.14	2.24	-5.3**	-0.9
<i>1971 dry season</i>					
50 DT	1.91	1.83	1.87	-4.2**	-2.1**
Maturity	2.08	1.94	1.94	-6.7**	-6.7**

^aFrom 32 farms in the wet season and 16 farms in the dry season, each farm consisting of four sampling units. ^bDT = Days after transplanting.

screening technique gave bias-free estimates of the wet season incidence (Table 1). In the dry season, the biases were larger than in the wet season, nevertheless the modified screening technique still gave smaller biases than the screening technique. Based on results of the 1971 and 1972 Laguna surveys, estimates from the modified screening technique were also larger (Table 2), indicating reduction of the bias from the original screening technique.

We therefore suggest using the modified screening technique to estimate percentage of dead hearts and white heads. When high precision is desired, however, the tillers in a sample of uninfested hills must be counted to get a more accurate estimate of the number of tillers in the sample area.

Distribution of incidence in the field. Information on the distribution of infested hills in the field is essential for establishing sampling procedures. In the 1972 dry season, we made a complete count of all infested hills in six randomly selected paddies in Laguna which ranged in size from 336 to 756 sq m. These paddies had 1 to 8 percent dead hearts and 1 to 4 percent white heads. Figure 1 shows a typical distribution of hills damaged by stem borers. The white head incidence in this field was 4 percent. The infested hills were usually widely and uniformly distributed throughout the field. In general, the degree of incidence in each hill was not large. At both stages of observation, about 90 percent of all infested hills had less than 30 percent incidence (fig. 2). No consistent trend of incidence in relation to the center or the periphery of the paddy was found.

Table 2. Estimates of dead heart and white head incidence in farmers' fields based on the screening technique (ST) and the modified screening technique (MST). Laguna, Philippines, 1971 and 1972.

Time of sampling	Dead hearts and white heads (%)		Difference (%)
	MST	ST	
<i>1971 wet season^a</i>			
50 DT	1.12	1.08	3.7**
Maturity	0.58	0.54	7.4**
<i>1972 dry season^b</i>			
50 DT	2.55	2.49	2.4**
Maturity	2.09	1.99	5.0**

^aNine farms with 728 sampling units. ^bSix farms with 571 sampling units.

Assessing yield loss. Previous studies based on multiple regression technique revealed that percentage yield loss caused by stem borers differed among varieties with different yielding abilities (1971 Annual Report). This year we made surveys in Laguna to develop suitable techniques for establishing functional relationships between grain yield and stem borer damage under different farm conditions.

In each of nine sample paddies surveyed in the 1971 wet season, we selected 100 hills infested with stem borers. For each hill we determined grain yield, plant height, number of white heads, number of virus-infected tillers, and total number of tillers. Grain weight and percentage of white heads per hill had a logarithmic relationship rather than the linear pattern that is usually

hypothesized (fig. 3). In other words, the reduction in grain yield due to stem borer was not proportional to the percentage of incidence. Although the correlation coefficients were significant for seven of nine paddies, they were not large (between 0.303 and 0.699). The small correlation coefficients indicate that one or more major factors, other than percentage of white heads, caused the yield variation among hills. When percentage of virus incidence, total number of tillers, and plant height were included in the regression, the multiple correlation coefficients increased markedly: the range was 0.760 to 0.931, with an average of 0.873 (Table 3). To accurately assess yield loss caused by stem borers based on a single-hill unit, therefore, the number of tillers and plant height should be

1. Distribution of hills with white heads in a paddy measuring 330 sq m. Laguna, Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Table 3. Estimated multiple regression coefficients and multiple correlation coefficient^a (R) between percentage of white heads and yield with virus incidence, tiller number, and plant height included as independent variables based on single-hill units, from nine farms. Laguna, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Farm no.	Constant	Regression coefficients				R
		Percentage white heads	Percentage virus	Tiller no.	Plant ht	
1	-0.593	-0.104	-0.072	1.190**	0.007**	0.926**
2	-.585	-.144	-.030	0.891**	.012**	.877**
3	-.273	-.256**	-.123	0.849**	.009**	.925**
4	-.646	-.193**	^b	0.784**	.015**	.867**
5	-.486	-.229**	.112	0.988**	.009**	.901**
6	-.352	-.151**	-.088**	0.724**	.014**	.802**
7	-.825	-.090**	-.056	1.055**	.012**	.931**
8	.344	-.308**	-.122**	1.079**	.001	.867**
9	-.641	.096	-.144	1.276**	.004**	.760**

^aExcept for plant height, all other variables including yield are in logarithmic scale. ^bNo virus incidence.

included to compensate for differences in plant vigor among hills in same field. Incidence of diseases and pests other than stem borers should also be considered.

In the 1972 dry season, we made a complete enumeration of dead hearts at 50 days after transplanting and of white heads at maturity in six sample paddies. Grain yields were measured from 5-sq-m units throughout the paddy, excluding a few border rows.

The incidence was not generally severe. Incidence of dead hearts ranged from 1.1 to 8.3

percent, and of white heads from 0.6 to 4.0 percent. Three of the six farms had rat damage.

Multiple regression analysis based on 5-sq-m units showed that little yield variation was due to dead hearts and white heads. When rat incidence and number of stem-borer-infested hills per square meter were included as variables, multiple correlation coefficients increased although the values were still generally low (Table 4).

The significant contribution of number of stem-borer-infested hills per square meter as an

2. Frequency distribution of percentages of dead hearts and white heads from a complete enumeration in a paddy. Laguna, Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Table 4. Multiple regression coefficients and multiple correlation coefficient (R) in the estimation of grain yield of rice based on incidence of dead hearts and white heads in farmers' fields based on 5-sq-m units. Laguna, Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Paddy no.	Constant	Regression coefficients					R
		Percentage dead hearts	Percentage white heads	No. of hills per sq m infested with stem borers		Percentage rat incidence ^a	
				50 DT	Maturity		
1	498.9	4.25	-26.81	-2.29	-2.61	-11.2**	0.385*
2	361.4	-5.73	-12.65	2.88	9.41	-4.9**	.743**
3	428.6	-7.27	-23.94**	15.07*	13.96	—	.434*
4	377.3	-23.36*	-10.50	20.34*	4.39	—	.368*
5	434.7	-2.48	-6.68	1.40	7.26	-102.9	.304
6	713.8	-17.90*	-9.76	12.49	4.96	—	.196

^aMeasured at 50 DT for paddy no. 1 and 5; and at maturity for paddy no. 2.

additional variable in the regression shows that percentage of incidence is inadequate as the sole indicator of yield loss. In other words, under the same percentage of incidence the magnitude of yield loss depends on whether dead hearts and white heads are spread widely among many hills

(low incidence in each infested hill) or concentrated on a few hills.

These attempts to establish a direct relationship between incidence of dead hearts and white heads and absolute yield seemed unsuccessful even in plots of the same variety, whether we

3. Relation of grain weight to percentage of white heads based on single-hill units in four paddies. Laguna, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

4. Relation between percentage of yield loss and percentage of white heads based on a 2-sq-m unit, from 14 farms planted to IR20. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1971 dry season.

used a single-hill unit or a 5-sq-m unit. Therefore, from a survey of the 1971 dry season crop in Nueva Ecija involving farms growing IR20 (1971 Annual Report), we attempted to establish a simple relationship between percentage of white heads and percentage of yield loss. Data were collected on 2-sq-m units. Logarithmic relationships were derived separately for two levels of dead heart incidence (less than 2% and more than 2%) as well as one ignoring the

Table 5. Bias of the U-shaped frame for sampling in broadcast rice plots: based on estimates^a of tiller number of IR127-80-1 and IR22 (unfertilized) at different growth stages. IRRRI, 1971 dry season.

Time of sampling (DS ^b)	Control	Cuts at closed-end		Cuts along side	
		Estimate (no./sq m)	Bias (no./sq m)	Estimate (no./sq m)	Bias (no./sq m)
<i>IR127-80-1</i>					
50	267	307	40	341	74
80	224	270	46	291	67*
Maturity	199	243	44*	246	47*
<i>IR22</i>					
50	534	516	-18	730	196*
80	422	388	-34	568	146**
Maturity	421	450	29	485	64

^aData are averages of seven replications each having two to five samples. ^bDays after seeding.

degree of dead hearts (fig. 4). Although the slopes of the lines did not differ significantly, the position of the lines differed between the two levels of dead hearts. That is, even with the same percentage of white heads, the percentage reduction in yield was smaller with lower incidence of dead hearts. For example, with 3 percent white heads, yield loss is estimated at 6.1 percent for less than 2 percent dead hearts and 9.6 percent for more than 2 percent dead hearts.

SAMPLING IN BROADCAST PLOTS

Sampling techniques for measuring various rice characters in experimental plots have been developed, but these are primarily for transplanted rice. In broadcast rice the non-uniform plant density causes difficulty in identifying and demarcating sampling units. We began a study in 1970 to develop tools for demarcating the sampling area in broadcast rice plots.

We tested a U-shaped wire frame especially designed for marking off several subcuts at different positions of the frame (fig. 5) on broadcast plots of fertilized (120 kg/ha N) and unfertilized IR22 and IR127-80-1. Since the major problem was the uncertain demarcation of the sampling area, we used tiller number as the indicator character. Tillers were counted at 50 days after seeding, at 80 days after seeding, and at maturity.

In unfertilized plots (Table 5), perimeter cuts (cuts along the sides or the closed end of the frame) tended to give overestimates. No consistent trend was found in fertilized plots however. The bias from cuts at the closed end of the frame was probably caused by the tendency of the enumerator to push the frame close to the plants while setting the frame in the field. This practice tended to reduce the empty space or gap at the closed end of the frame thus increasing the number of plants per unit area. A larger bias could be expected if plant density were lower. In fact, the bias at the closed end of the frame occurred only in IR127-80-1, the low-tillering selection, and not in IR22, the high tillering variety.

The bias from cuts along the sides of the frame probably stemmed from the enumerator's tendency to include more plants than needed when

5. U-shaped frame designed for sampling study in broadcast rice plots.

placing the frame's two arms in the field. Bias at the sides was greater than that at the closed end and it occurred in both low-tillering and high-tillering varieties.

Because of the bias that results and the difficulties encountered when the U-shaped frame is used with growing plants, we evaluated the use of a square wire frame (fig. 6) that can be placed in the field immediately before or after seeding. We also tested circular and triangular wire frames. Although the shapes of the wire frames did not affect the magnitude of the estimates, the sampling variances differed slightly (Table 6). The circular frame gave relatively small variance but it is inconvenient to use because it easily loses its shape when handled. There was no consistent or appreciable difference in variance between square and triangular frames.

No difference was found in the estimates or variances from sampling frames placed before and after seeding (Table 6). Because it is difficult to place the frame in the field after seeding without trampling the crop, we recommend placing the sampling frames immediately before seeding.

Analysis based on the relationships between variance and cut size (fig. 7) showed that the optimum size of frame is between 0.15 and 0.25 sq m.

Although in transplanted rice a higher variation occurs in fertilized plots than in unfertilized plots, we observed the reverse in broadcast rice. Hence, for broadcast rice, a larger sample size is required in unfertilized plots. Sample size, or number of sampling cuts (each 0.25 sq m) per

6. Square wire frame designed for sampling study in broadcast rice plots.

plot, needed for varying degrees of precision are given in Table 7. A sample size larger than that indicated in Table 7 may be required, however, when plants lodge or when measurements are made at early growth stages.

SAMPLING TO DETERMINE LEAF AREA

Previous studies on variation in leaf area showed larger variation among leaves within tillers than among tillers and among hills (1971 Annual Report). We therefore recommended the use of the tiller instead of the leaf as the unit of measurement. Since leaf area is also closely related to the height of individual tillers, variability among tillers in a hill is large. Hence, sampling by taking tillers at random from selected hills is not desirable.

Table 6. Effect of shape and time of placement of wire frame (0.1 sq m) on the estimates and sampling variances of tiller number in broadcast rice plots measured 50 days after seeding. IIRI, 1971 wet season.

Shape of frame	Placement in relation to seeding	Tillers			
		IR127-80-1		IR22	
		Estimate (no./sq m)	cv (%)	Estimate (no./sq m)	cv (%)
<i>0 kg/ha N</i>					
Square	After	400	27	624	33
Square	Before	411	37	582	21
Triangular	Before	392	17	560	25
Circular	Before	364	16	612	15
<i>80 kg/ha N</i>					
Square	After	421	19	652	9
Square	Before	415	18	754	14
Triangular	Before	404	32	712	26
Circular	Before	479	17	738	17

7. Relation between sampling variation and size of sampling frame for estimating tiller number of IR22 and IR127-80-1 (unfertilized and fertilized) in broadcast rice plots. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

able because it requires a large sample size. Although stratifying tillers in a hill according to their individual heights before sampling tillers may improve precision (Table 8), it is tedious and time consuming. We, therefore, examined the possibility of finding a specific tiller, or a combination of several tillers, in a hill that would adequately represent the entire hill.

Among the different tiller positions examined (based on height of individual tillers in a hill),

Table 7. Estimated standard error of plot mean for determining tiller number in broadcast rice plots with 0.25-sq-m wire frame, for varying numbers of sampling units per plot.

Sampling units (no./plot)	Standard error of plot mean (%)	
	Fertilized	Unfertilized
2	11.8	17.7
3	10.2	15.5
4	9.4	14.2
5	8.8	13.4
6	8.4	12.9
8	7.9	12.1
10	7.6	11.7

the middle tiller generally gave estimates of leaf area closest to the actual value (Table 9) with a mean error of about 10 percent. A mean error of 5 percent, or a reduction by half, can be obtained by counting all leaves in the sample hill rather than tillers alone. But the additional work involved in counting leaves must also be

Table 8. Relative efficiency of stratifying tillers in a hill according to their individual heights, in sampling to determine leaf area.

Time of sampling (DT ^a)	Relative efficiency (%)					
	IR22			IR662-2-7		
	0	60	120	0	60	120
	kg/ha N kg/ha N kg/ha N kg/ha N kg/ha N kg/ha N					
	<i>Dry season</i>					
30	349	287	149	174	201	204
45	291	277	257	328	272	232
75	124	122	153	208	364	258
	<i>Wet season</i>					
30	229	280	341	232	133	228
60	207	246	186	220	181	163
75	141	154	195	192	136	258

^aDT = days after transplanting.

Table 9. Estimates of leaf area of IR22 and IR662-2-7 (fertilized and unfertilized) based on different positions of sample tiller, measured at two growth periods.

Time of sampling (DT)	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Actual leaf area (sq cm/hill)	Estimates ^a of leaf area (sq cm/hill) based on				
			Topmost tiller	2nd tiller	3rd tiller	4th tiller	Middle tiller
<i>IR22</i>							
45	0	493	776**	683*	658*	499	483
	120	585	1033**	831**	699*	758*	635
75	0	468	573	524	526	461	481
	120	1150	1286	1288	1290	1191	1090
<i>IR662-2-7</i>							
45	0	436	631**	643**	516**	504	452
	120	979	1473**	1320*	1231**	1344	1057
75	0	674	787*	878**	754	783	740
	120	1960	2446**	2416**	2395**	2275	2216

^aLeaf area of the sample tiller multiplied by number of tillers in the hill. *Significantly different from the corresponding actual leaf area at the 5% level. **Significantly different from the corresponding actual leaf area at the 1% level.

considered when deciding whether to reduce sampling error by increasing sample size (the number of hills per plot) or to reduce measurement error by using estimates based on leaf count. But when plants can be removed and a measurement technique involving dry weight of leaves is used (1971 Annual Report), no counting of tillers or leaves is needed.

Coefficients of variation among hills under varying conditions ranged from 7 percent to 74 percent with an average of 30 percent (Table 10). Variation was slightly higher in the fertilized plots. Hence, a larger sample size is required for fertilized than for unfertilized plots. The sample size for determining leaf area with varying degrees of precision desired can be chosen from estimates given in Table 11.

REPLANTING DEAD HILLS

Previous trials showed that dead hills that occur at early growth stages should be replanted to protect the surrounding hills (1971 Annual Report). We suggested that replanting material should be thinned from hills of the outermost row bordering an unplanted alley. Because this source of replanting material is limited in quantity, we examined the possibility of improving the performance of other sources by replanting with a higher number of seedlings per hill.

Regardless of type of replanting material used and time of replanting, the replanted hill performed differently from the normal hills (Table 12). The smallest reduction in yield of replanted hills occurred when replanting was done with

four seedlings per hill (each normal hill had two seedlings) and with seedlings taken from those left at ends of rows. Of five methods tested, only two—replanting material taken from the outermost hill and replanting material from end rows at four seedlings per hill—gave good protection to the surrounding hills at all times of replanting. The other methods only protected the surrounding hills up to 3 weeks after transplanting.

Therefore dead hills should be replanted with seedlings taken from hills bordering an unplanted alley or from hills left at ends of rows. If the latter procedure is used, the number of seedlings planted to a dead hill should exceed those used in the normal hills.

DETERMINING YIELD IN SPACING TRIALS

In experiments involving several plant spacings, a common question is whether plot yield should be determined from the same area or from the

Table 10. Coefficient of variation among hills within plots for leaf area measurement under varying conditions.

Time of sampling (DT)	cv (%)			
	IR22		IR662-2-7	
	0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
<i>Dry season</i>				
30	20.8	73.6	24.7	46.3
45	38.7	30.1	46.9	33.0
75	21.5	31.3	33.9	44.2
<i>Wet season</i>				
30	25.7	22.8	19.2	38.4
60	7.1	28.9	38.1	19.6
75	45.8	19.3	14.7	24.0

Table 11. Estimated standard error of plot mean for determining leaf area for varying numbers of sample hills per plot.

Hills (no./plot)	Standard error of plot mean (%)	
	Unfertilized	Fertilized
2	20	24
3	16	20
4	14	17
5	13	15
6	12	14
7	11	13
8	10	12
10	9	11
12	8	10

same number of hills. The best choice is the one that provides maximum information and a uniform level of precision among different plant spacings.

In the 1972 dry and wet seasons, six varieties were grown in plots measuring 4 × 4 sq m with four plant spacings, 10 × 10 cm, 20 × 20 cm, 25 × 25 cm, and 30 × 30 cm, in three replications. Several subcuts were harvested from each

Table 12. Grain yield of a replanted hill and hills surrounding the replanted hill as affected by time of replanting and the number and source of seedlings in the replanted hill (IR747B₂-6-3). IRRI, 1972 dry season. (Data are averages of eight replications).

Time of replanting (DT)	Yield ^a (g/hill)			
	Two seedlings in replanted hill		Four seedlings in replanted hill	
	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills
<i>Replanted hills from seedbed</i>				
15	8.0**	24.1	9.1**	25.0
18	3.8**	18.8	4.6**	21.0
21	2.0**	22.7	2.1**	25.6
24	3.0**	26.0	2.5**	24.4
28	1.1**	28.8*	1.6**	27.5*
<i>Replanted hills from row end^b</i>				
15	12.6**	24.2	19.0	23.4
18	10.4**	24.1	13.8**	21.4
21	6.8**	25.2	11.2**	20.0
24	6.4**	27.0*	7.4**	21.3
28	3.6**	27.9*	5.2**	21.6
<i>Replanted hills from outermost rows^c</i>				
15	11.0**	26.1	—	—
18	8.4**	24.1	—	—
21	8.1**	24.1	—	—
24	4.5**	26.3	—	—
28	4.6**	22.4	—	—

^aControl yielded 22.5 g/hill. ^bEight to ten seedlings were left in a bunch at row ends. ^cAdjacent to an unplanted alley. *Significantly different from the control at the 5% level. **Significantly different from the control at 1% level.

plot. The subcuts were combined to provide different sizes of harvest area as well as different numbers of hills in the harvest area.

Experimental error decreased exponentially with increase in size of harvest area per plot (fig. 8). Plant spacing had no appreciable effect on the error variance, except for harvest areas under 1 sq m in which 30 × 30 cm spacing gave a much higher error variance than the rest.

On the other hand, the rate of reduction in error variance with increase in number of hills harvested per plot differed with plant spacing (fig. 9). The slow rate of reduction of error variance in the 10 × 10 cm spacing reflected the slow rate of increase in size of harvest area with increase in number of hills at close plant spacings. The observed relationship between experimental error and number of hills harvested resulted primarily from the change in size of harvest area. That is, at a given number of hills harvested per plot, the error variance differed from one plant spacing to another.

Thus, to ensure homogeneity of error variance, the size of harvest area per plot, rather than the number of hills, should be the basis for determining plot yield.

SOIL HETEROGENEITY

Residual effect of nitrogen. Previous trials indicated that residual nitrogen is present in experimental fields, especially when the rate of nitrogen applied was high (1971 Annual Report). This year we attempted to find out whether the effect

Table 13. Residual effects of 120 kg/ha N applied in 1971 wet season on various characters of IR20 in the 1972 dry season, with and without fertilization. IRRI, 1972 dry season. (Data are averages of 20 replications.)

N applied in 1971 wet season (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Plant ht (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (%)
<i>No N applied in 1972 dry season</i>					
0	4.42	175	84	132	12.4
120	4.83	194	84	131	13.1
Residual effect	0.41**	19	0	-1	0.7
<i>120 kg/ha N applied in 1972 dry season</i>					
0	7.14	287	96	134	15.8
120	7.22	289	97	133	16.2
Residual effect	0.08	2	1	-1	0.4

8. Experimental error in relation to size of harvest area per plot, under varying plant spacings. IRRI, 1972.

of residual nitrogen varies with crop season, whether it can be reduced by fertilization, and whether it persists for more than one crop season. When nitrogen was applied, residual nitrogen significantly increased grain yield by 0.41 t/ha, which is about 15 percent of the yield

Table 14. Residual effects of 120 kg/ha N applied in 1972 dry season on various characters of IR20 in the 1972 wet season, with and without fertilization. IRRI, 1972 wet season. (Data are averages of 20 replications.)

Nitrogen applied in 1972 dry season (kg/ha N)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Plant ht (cm)	Dry matter production (g/sq m)
<i>No N applied in 1972 wet season</i>				
0	3.68	200	97	752
120	4.07	220	99	860
Residual effect	0.39	20*	2	108*
<i>120 kg/ha N applied in 1972 wet season</i>				
0	4.99	271	106	1061
120	5.02	281	107	1080
Residual effect	0.03	10	1	19

response to application of 120 kg/ha N (Table 13). When 120 kg/ha N was applied, on the other hand, no effect of residual nitrogen was observed. Similar results were obtained when nitrogen was applied in the 1972 dry season and residual effects were measured in the 1972 wet season (Table 14). The effect of residual nitrogen apparently can be alleviated by a uniform application of a high rate of nitrogen in the succeeding planting.

Table 15. Second-crop residual effects of nitrogen (120 kg/ha N) applied in 1971 wet season on various characters of IR20 grown without fertilization in 1972 wet season. (Data are averages of 20 replications.)

Nitrogen applied in 1971 wet season (kg/ha N)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Plant ht (cm)	Dry matter production (g/sq m)
0	3.76	206	97	773
120	4.00	214	99	839
Residual effect	0.24	8	2	66

9. Experimental error in relation to number of hills harvest per plot, under varying plant spacings. IRRI, 1972.

There was a slight indication of a second-crop residual effect of nitrogen in unfertilized plots (Table 15), but the differences were not significant.

Growth duration and soil heterogeneity. To determine if planting varieties widely different in growth duration increases the heterogeneity

Table 16. Grain yield and other plant characters of IR20 (fertilized and unfertilized), grown under two planting schemes in areas previously planted to varieties varying in growth duration. IRRI, 1972 wet season. (Data are averages of five replications.)

Varieties* planted in previous crop	Yield (t/ha)		Dry matter production (g/sq m)		Panicles (no./hill)		Plant ht (cm)	
	0 kg/ha N	80 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	80 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	80 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	80 kg/ha N
<i>Same planting date</i>								
IR878B ₄ -220-3	4.09	4.69	829	942	8.8	10.0	96	104
IR8	4.54	4.77	882	955	8.8	9.9	97	101
IR22	4.31	4.72	859	962	8.9	9.7	91	97
IR1561-288-3	4.23	4.60	808	926	8.4	10.5	94	100
<i>Same harvest date</i>								
IR878B ₄ -220-3	3.47	4.18	542	843	7.1	8.6	98	103
IR8	3.55	4.43	678	924	8.1	9.7	96	104
IR22	4.31	4.57	789	892	8.1	9.9	94	100
IR1561-288-3	4.31	5.28	800	951	9.0	10.4	94	108
LSD (5%)	0.56	0.56	123	123	1.1	1.1	13	13

*Growth durations: IR878B₄-220-3, 137 days; IR8, 127 days; IR22, 117 days; IR1561-288-3, 109 days.

Table 17. Correlation matrix for rice uniformity yield data^a from 10 successive crops on the same site (768 sq m). IRRI, 1968 to 1972.

Crop season	1968 WS ^b	1969 DS ^c	1969 WS	1970 DS	1970 WS	1971 DS	1971 WS	1972 DS	1972 WS
1968 dry	0.896	0.621	0.589	0.861	0.664	0.835	0.628	0.722	0.821
1968 wet		.667	.607	.675	.624	.638	.675	.671	.716
1969 dry			.788	.830	.670	.821	.775	.805	.764
1969 wet				.835	.782	.800	.712	.796	.815
1970 dry					.694	.888	.656	.893	.850
1970 wet						.802	.636	.688	.850
1971 dry							.635	.836	.847
1971 wet								.632	.704
1972 dry									.890

^aBased on unit measuring 16 sq m. All correlations are significant at the 5% level. ^bWet season. ^cDry season.

of a soil, four varieties were grown under two planting schemes in the 1972 dry season. In one scheme the varieties were sown and transplanted at the same time; in the other, they were planted at different dates so that they would be harvested at the same time. In the succeeding wet season, IR20 was grown uniformly throughout the area.

There were some differences in grain yields in the areas planted to the four varieties in the previous season, although they were significant only among the varieties in the same-harvest-date planting scheme (Table 16). Yields of IR20, whether fertilized or not, were significantly higher in plots in which early maturing varieties had been grown previously. Since soil heterogeneity can be expected to increase in an area planted to varieties differing in growth duration by more than 10 days, appropriate remedial measures should therefore be taken in succeeding crops to control such variation.

Persistence. Results of uniformity trials in the same area for six successive crop seasons showed that the pattern of soil heterogeneity in lowland paddy soil remains fairly constant over time (1970 Annual Report). After 10 successive crop seasons, the conclusion still holds. The correlations between grain yields from one crop to another were still high and significant (Table 17). With the fertility pattern persisting until the 10th crop, it seems that the use of uniformity data to control variability due to soil heterogeneity in field experiments is worth considering.

Uniformity data are also commonly used in determining the optimum plot size and shape based on the estimated soil heterogeneity index (1968 Annual Report). For such estimates to be meaningful, however, their values should not

vary with the test conditions. Our estimates of the soil heterogeneity index based on 10 uniformity trials conducted in the same area, with different varieties, are quite consistent (Table 18). The values ranged from 0.235 to 0.402 with an average of 0.274. The results seem to indicate a high persistence in both fertility pattern and soil heterogeneity index estimated from uniformity data in rice.

GROWTH DURATIONS AND VARIETAL COMPARISONS

In preparation for a study of how planting varieties widely different in growth duration affect soil heterogeneity, we grew four varieties under two planting schemes (Table 19). The results indicated not only significant differences between mean yields obtained from the two

Table 18. Persistency of Smith's soil heterogeneity index (*b*) with time. Data are averages of 10 successive crops (IR8, IR22, IR20) of uniformity trials (unfertilized). IRRI, 1968 to 1972.

Year	Season	Mean yield (t/ha)	cv ^a (%)	Estimate of <i>b</i>
<i>IR8</i>				
1968	Dry	7.33	13.0	0.235
	Wet	4.92	9.4	.273
1969	Dry	4.80	11.7	.263
	Wet	5.20	9.3	.272
<i>IR22</i>				
1970	Dry	5.02	10.1	.242
	Wet	4.35	9.5	.274
1971	Dry	4.75	10.8	.246
	Wet	4.47	7.5	.402
<i>IR20</i>				
1972	Dry	3.68	10.1	.282
	Wet	3.16	12.8	.254
	Avg	4.77	10.4	.274

^aBased on basic unit measuring 1 × 1 sq m.

Table 19. Grain yield and other agronomic characters of four rice varieties differing in growth duration grown under two planting schemes. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Variety ^a	Solar radiation (kcal · cm ⁻² · 45 days ⁻¹)	Yield (t/ha)	Dry matter production (g/sq m)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Plant ht (cm)	Virus incidence (%)
IR878B ₄ -220-3 ^b	24.0	4.49	976	138	82	9.3
		<i>Same planting date^c</i>				
IR8	22.8	5.92	993	221	85	4.1
IR20	20.7	4.72	826	238	79	4.2
IR1561-288-3	19.2	6.04	802	446	80	0.0
		<i>Same harvest date^d</i>				
IR8	24.0	7.89	977	302	92	0.0
IR20	24.0	6.53	974	346	90	0.0
IR1561-288-3	24.0	7.66	783	431	87	0.0
LSD (5%)		0.48	92	38	3	—

^aGrowth duration: IR878B₄-220-3, 137 days; IR8, 127 days; IR22, 117 days; IR1561-288-3, 109 days. ^bPlanted Jan. 18, 1972; harvested May 15, 1972. ^cJan. 18, 1972. ^dMay 15, 1972.

planting schemes but also significant interactions between variety and planting scheme. The latter indicates that the relative comparisons among varieties differed between the two planting schemes. IR8, IR20, and IR1561-288-3 had higher grain yield under the same-harvest-date scheme than under the same-planting-date scheme, mainly because solar radiation was

higher during the 45 days before harvest under the former scheme. The difference between each of the three varieties and IR878B₄-220-3, which has the longest growth duration, varied from one planting scheme to the other. The result indicates that differences in critical climatic conditions must be considered in tests involving varieties widely different in growth duration.

Plant pathology

Additional data from the international blast nurseries further confirmed the broad spectrum of resistance to blast of rice varieties identified earlier.

An experiment showed that stabilizing selection cannot be demonstrated in blast fungus because of the great pathogenic variability within each culture. □ The basidial stage of the causal organism of sheath blight disease was discovered in the field, suggesting another possible means of disease dissemination besides sclerotial bodies. Special lobated mycelium produced by the fungus were found to cause disease lesions. Besides temperature and humidity, other factors, such as age of the rice plant and nutrition of the fungus, were found to affect the development of sheath blight disease. □ Efficient methods were developed for screening large plant populations for resistance to bacterial blight. A high level of resistance to bacterial blight was obtained by crossing two or more resistance have doubled its capacity. Of the thousands of that no significant strain differences exist since the resistance of several varieties holds up under severe disease pressure. □ Improvements in the mass screening technique for tungro resistance have doubled its capacity. Of the thousands of lines screened, several are resistant to both tungro and grassy stunt, and many are resistant to one or the other. A new vector, *Nephotettix malayanus*, was found to transmit tungro and yellow dwarf.

BLAST

Varietal resistance. Ninety-five test results from 23 cooperating countries were obtained during the last 2 years from the international blast nurseries. The total number of tests is now 280. The data continue to show that varieties such as Tetep, Nang chet cuc, C46-15, Tadukan, Trang cut L. 11, Mamoriaka, Carreon, Huan-sen-goo, and Dissi Hatif have a broad spectrum of resistance.

Stabilizing selection. A greenhouse experiment was performed to test the hypothesis that a virulent race of fungus pathogens is less fit to survive on a host variety lacking resistance genes than a less virulent race, using the races of the blast fungus. Two races of *Pyricularia oryzae*—P38, which infects two of the 12 Philippine differential varieties, and P150, which infects all 12 varieties—were inoculated separately and mixed in equal proportions to caged seedlings of variety Khao-teh-haeng 17, which is equally

susceptible to both races. When the seedlings had been infected and the lesions were sporulating profusely, a new set of seedlings was introduced to each cage every week.

After five successive generations on Khao-teh-haeng 17, the relative population of P150 was determined by direct lesion inoculation: placing individual lesions in close contact with leaves of three varieties, Tetep, Katakara DA2, and CI 5309, which are susceptible to P150 but resistant to P38. Isolates from single lesions from each cage were inoculated to differential varieties to determine the races. Few isolates of race P150 were recovered from the mixed culture of races P150 and P38. But even in the pure P150 culture the rate of recovery was low, less than 10 percent. Fifty-four races were present in 155 single-lesion isolates from the mixed culture and only three isolates belonged to race P150 and three to race P38; 17 races were present in 50 isolates of P150 culture and only four isolates belonged to P150; 13 races were found in 50

Table 1. New races of *Pyricularia oryzae* based upon the Philippine differentials.

Philippine differential variety	Reaction* on differential varieties									
	P 201	P 202	P 203	P 204	P 205	P 206	P 207	P 208	P 209	P 210
Katakara DA2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	S	S
CI 5309	●	●	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	S
Chokoto	●	●	●	S	S	S	●	●	S	S
Co 25	●	S	S	●	S	●	●	●	S	S
Wagwag	S	●	S	S	●	S	S	S	●	●
Pai-kan-tao	S	S	●	S	S	S	●	●	S	●
Peta	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●
Raminad Str. 3	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Taichung T.C.W.C.	S	●	●	S	●	S	S	●	S	S
Lacrosse	●	S	●	●	●	S	●	●	S	S
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	S	S	●	S	●	S	S	S	●	●
Khao-teh-haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

	P 211	P 212	P 213	P 214	P 215	P 216	P 217	P 218	P 219
Katakara DA2	S	S	●	●	●	●	●	S	S
CI 5309	S	S	S	●	●	●	S	S	S
Chokoto	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S
Co 25	S	S	●	●	●	S	●	●	●
Wagwag	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Pai-kan-tao	●	●	●	●	S	S	S	S	●
Peta	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Raminad Str. 3	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●
Taichung T.C.W.C.	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S
Lacrosse	●	●	●	●	●	S	●	S	S
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Khao-teh-haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

* ● = resistant, S = susceptible.

isolates of *P38* culture and none of the isolates were of race *P38*. We concluded that the apparent decrease in population of *P150* in the mixed culture was caused primarily by the great variability of the fungus. So-called stabilizing selection was not demonstrated in *P. oryzae*.

New races. Nineteen new races of *Pyricularia oryzae* were identified by the 12 Philippine differentials, bringing to 219 the total number of Philippine races (Table 1).

SHEATH BLIGHT

Lesion formation. When rice leaves or leaf sheaths are infected by sheath blight, the mycelium covers the entire infected areas. But the lesions are rather oblong, variable in size, scattered or aggregated, and distinct from each other. When artificially inoculated with sclerotia, the mycelium grows from the sclerotia and the lesions are formed usually some distance from the point of inoculation.

We found that the fungus produces two types of mycelium: the straight running type and the lobated type (fig. 1). The straight running mycelium creeps on the surface of plant tissues and does not produce any lesions; the lobated type infects the tissue and produces lesions. The

lobated mycelium is produced in patches of varying sizes and shapes which determine the size and shape of the lesion. All lesions we have examined were covered with lobated mycelium and the adjacent healthy tissue had straight mycelium (fig. 2). A lesion is the result of multiple infection by abundant lobated mycelium produced from the straight mycelium. Lobated mycelium also occurred in culture on petri dish covers or on test tube walls.

Perfect stage. The basidial stage of the sheath blight fungus rarely has been reported to occur on rice in the field. Conventionally the sclerotia has been considered the sole source of inoculum.

We discovered the basidial stage of the fungus in our sheath blight nursery. It appears as a white powdery or frosty layer on healthy leaf sheaths and occasionally on leaves near the infected tissues under extremely moist conditions. The basidia usually measure 11 to 15 μm $\times$ 8 to 9 μm ; the sterigmata, 7 to 10 μm $\times$ 2 to 3 μm ; and spores, 9 to 12 μm $\times$ 5 to 7 μm (fig. 3). They closely resemble *Thanatephorus cucumeris*. Based on this finding, the fungus should be called *T. cucumeris*, rather than *Corticium sasakii* according to present-day nomenclature.

Specimens taken in daytime had few mature basidia when the atmosphere was dry, but the

1. Straight and lobated mycelia of *Thanatephorus cucumeris*.

2. Portion of a sheath blight lesion showing lobated mycelium on the lesion and straight mycelium on adjacent healthy leaf tissue.

specimens taken at night or during a daytime drizzle had many. The basidia were short-lived and collapsed in dry atmosphere. They released basidiospores at night (fig. 4).

Our discovery of the basidial stage changes our concept of the epidemiology of sheath blight in the tropics. Occasionally a few isolated lesions are found on rice leaves in the field although no sign of the disease exists on the lower portion of the plant. That suggests that air-borne basidiospores started the infection.

About 180 single-basidiospore cultures have been obtained. They differ greatly in cultural characters (fig. 5) and are heterozygous. They also differ in pathogenicity.

Survival. Naturally infected straw, cultures on straw, and sclerotia produced in culture were separately buried about 10 cm deep in soil of different moisture conditions—air dried, upland, and submerged soils—in the field and in large pots. Samples were taken at 2-week intervals and transferred to medium (PDA) to recover the fungus. Up to 16 weeks, a large percentage of the fungus was recovered from most of the samples. Mycelium in the infected tissues seemed able to survive as long as the sclerotia under upland conditions.

Sclerotia may float on water for several weeks and produce mycelia in water and secondary sclerotia on the water surface.

Host range. A sheath blight disease similar to rice sheath blight was observed on corn, sorg-

3. Basidium and basidiospores of *I. cucumeris*.

hum, and sugarcane near the IRRI farm. The lesions were larger than lesions on rice. Sclerotia from these hosts and from rice infected each other readily. A wild grass, *Roettboelia exaltata*, was also infected and the sclerotia from it also infected rice. The fungus has a wide host range; it is also important on corn and sorghum.

Varietal resistance. Distinct resistant and susceptible reactions were observed in rice seedlings tested in a sheath blight nursery (fig. 6). When mature plants of the same varieties were tested in the field, however, their reactions did not always agree with those of the seedlings. A series of experiments were conducted to identify factors that affect disease development and to determine the proper method of inoculation for screening for varietal resistance.

Types of inoculum. Two methods were tested for inoculation. One method consisted of inserting one sclerotium into the leaf sheath of a tiller. Two tillers were inoculated for each hill. In the other method, three pieces of sterilized straw cultures about 8 to 10 cm long were placed among the tillers of a hill and the entire hill was wrapped with paper which touched the irrigation water. About 134 varieties, three hills each, were inoculated. Disease development was measured with a standard disease index. The disease developed

4. Diurnal basidiospore release of *T. cucumeris*.

equally well by both the sclerotia and straw methods. But both methods are laborious so we are still trying other ones.

Disease index. The simple disease index for sheath blight calculated by dividing the number of infected leaf sheaths by the total number of

5. Variation in cultural characters of single basidiospores of *T. cucumeris*.

6. Sheath blight nursery with resistant and susceptible varieties at seedling stage.

leaf sheaths is inadequate because different degrees of infection occur on each sheath. We developed a modified disease index based upon percentage of infected area on each leaf sheath. Usually three representative tillers from each hill are examined.

Disease spread. The disease spreads within hills as well as among hills in the field. On sus-

ceptible varieties, under moist conditions, it reaches the flag leaves within 6 to 7 days. On more resistant varieties it spreads more slowly. In a field of susceptible varieties the disease spread faster to neighboring hills than it did in a field of resistant varieties (fig. 7). In another experiment, the disease spread from one inoculated hill to seven neighboring hills of one variety and to 16 hills of another variety. It spread faster in the 20-cm $\times$ 20-cm spacing than in the 25-cm $\times$ 25-cm spacing.

No varieties so far tested were immune or highly resistant to sheath blight. All varieties produced lesions when inoculated. The spread of the disease both within hills, particularly upwards, and among hills may be considered a major aspect of disease resistance.

Nutrition. We found that the nutrition of the fungus greatly affects the development of the disease. Sclerotia that had been dipped in nutrient solution before being inoculated on rice leaves produced many lesions within 2 days while sclerotia dipped in water produced only a few lesions in 4 to 5 days (fig. 8).

Age of plant. Two experiments involving 77 varieties were conducted to assess the development of the disease at early and late stages of growth in the field. The results were compared with those of the seedling stage test. Ten to fifteen hills of each variety were inoculated early (34 days after transplanting) and late (62 days after transplanting). The development of the disease was measured on the basis of percentage of infected leaf sheath area at 2-week intervals for 8 weeks for one experiment and at 3-week intervals for 6 weeks for the other.

The disease developed much faster as the plants grew older because plants were most susceptible after they had flowered and were approaching maturity. Thus early maturing varieties appear to have more disease at a given time. Resistance must therefore be evaluated at maturity. For 37 varieties inoculated early the overall disease index after 3 weeks was 12 percent and after 6 weeks, 19 percent. When inoculated late, however, the disease index was 19 percent after 3 weeks and 54 percent after 6 weeks. In the other experiments the increase in the overall disease index of 40 varieties at the earlier stage of plant growth was from 10% to

7. Spread of sheath blight in different varieties and lines at maturity.

25%, and at the later stage, from 16% to 57% (fig. 9).

The reactions at the adult stage did not always agree with those of seedling inoculation. Some varieties are resistant or susceptible at both stages, some are resistant at the seedling stage but susceptible at the adult stage, and some are susceptible at the seedling stage but resistant at the adult stage (fig. 10 and 11).

Varietal screening. Over 1,000 varieties were screened in sheath blight nurseries. Three hundred varieties were further tested in the field at the adult stage by straw inoculation. Scores were taken at maturity of each variety. Among the Assam varieties, eight were resistant at both the seedling stage and maturity: ARC 12208, ARC 12248, ARC 12256, ARC 12417, ARC 12547, ARC 12622, ARC 12637, and ARC 12655. Some varieties and promising lines that were resistant at maturity:

PTB 18	IRATOM 20
T442-148-29	IR533-1-89
BG34-11	IR8/4 × Zenith
IR442-2-58	IR1330-3-2
CS-2	IR1917-3-17
IR1360-87-1	OS4
Ratna	Sinaloa A68
Colombia 1	CP SLO
IR1093-148-3	Mehran
Carreon	Bahagia

Variety Ta-poo-cho-z showed resistance at both seedling and adult stages, while Kataktara DA2 was resistant at seedling stage but only moderately resistant in late stages.

Since sheath blight is greatly affected by several environmental factors, heritable resistance is difficult to ascertain.

Chemical control. In a preliminary study on chemical control, six chemicals were sprayed at weekly intervals starting 1 week after inoculation (about panicle initiation) on two varieties in 10-m × 10-m plots. A total of four sprays were made on three replications. The experiment was affected by bacterial blight. Most chemicals nevertheless increased the yield of the susceptible line IR883-6-2 but not that of the moderately resistant variety IR22 (Table 2). Several of these chemicals also controlled blast. They can be applied about the time when both diseases are present.

8. Effect of nutrition on development of sheath blight lesions; left, sclerotia dipped in nutrient solution before inoculation; right, dipped in water.

BACTERIAL BLIGHT

Inoculation technique. A new clipping technique has been developed for the inoculation of bacterial blight. Scissors are dipped in a bacterial suspension and then used to clip off tips of rice leaves (fig. 12). Five plants at maximum tillering stage can be serially inoculated after each dipping

9. Development (avg. of 40 varieties) of sheath blight after inoculation at early or late growing stages (staggered planting; inoculated on the same day).

10. Patterns of development of sheath blight in four varieties.

of the scissors in bacterial suspension containing at least 10^9 cells per milliliter. Disease readings can be taken 14 days after inoculation under most environmental conditions.

Compared with the pinprick method, the clipping method of inoculation gives significantly lower variance in disease scores on both susceptible and resistant varieties. It is also more efficient since many leaves can be simultaneously inoculated. Scoring diseased leaves is easy since the cut tip is a good reference point for measuring lesion spread.

Table 2. Effect of chemical control of sheath blight on grain yields of IR833-6-2 and IR22.

Chemical	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	IR833	IR22
Benlate + D.P.	3.4**	3.4
Hoe 17411	3.4**	3.7
NF-44	3.1**	3.0
BSAF 3050	3.1**	3.6
Hinosan + D.P.	3.0**	3.4
Hinosan	2.9**	3.3
Calexin	2.4	3.4
Control	2.4	3.2

11. Correlation of reactions of 191 varieties to sheath blight at seedling stage and at maturity.

Either a leaf extract inoculum or a pure culture of the bacterium can be used. Leaf extract inoculum taken from young developing lesions gave bacterial populations of approximately 10^9 cells per milliliter when the leaves were allowed to soak 15 minutes in the water (fig. 13). The maximum infection frequency and highest disease scores resulted if the bacterial suspension was no older than 2 hours. In older suspensions, the population of *X. oryzae* declined and the saprophytic bacterial population increased, giving poor rates of infection.

We attempted to determine whether results from clipping inoculation correlated well with disease reaction under natural field conditions. Epidemic conditions of bacterial blight in the field were induced throughout the year with an overhead sprinkler irrigation system. For the field evaluation, various plot layouts were tested: microplots of 16 plants, two rows of 1 meter each, and single hills. Disease readings from the plants inoculated by clipping correlated well with the visual readings from the naturally infected plots. The two-row plots had the most advantages. They were easier to transplant than the microplots and it was quite simple to take natural disease readings from them. Single hills consisting of several plants spaced 50 cm from

12. Clipping method for bacterial blight inoculation.

other entries also gave reliable results both for the inoculation by clipping and for natural infection when rows of a susceptible variety were also planted in the plot to spread the disease. For preliminary screenings of many entries the single hill layout is convenient, but for routine field screening under natural conditions the two-row layout is the most satisfactory.

Varietal testing. A screening system for evaluating breeding material was devised cooperatively with the varietal improvement department. All breeding material is first tested in the breeders' plots by clipping inoculation 60 to 80 days after seeding. The first six to 10 plants in the pedigree nursery rows and 10 plants in the border rows of the yield trials are inoculated. All F_2 plants are inoculated. Under this system many resistant plants are selected in early generations and retested each season to confirm their resistance. In addition, the overall percentage of lines and selections resistant to bacterial blight

is determined for each season. This information is important for assessing the progress of breeding programs for resistance and for maximizing the long-term effective use of resistant germ plasm.

A total of 2,470 yield trial entries, 15,900 breeding lines, 3,600 miscellaneous entries, and 25 F_2 populations from the breeding program were tested. Semidwarf progeny of Sigadis, TKM 6, IR22, W1263, Syntha, and DZ192 continued to show high resistance to the Philippine isolates of *X. oryzae*. Although the inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight is not completely understood, the genes for resistance have been easily transferred to the semidwarf plants, suggesting a simple mode of inheritance. The breeders now have many good semidwarf progeny lines at various stages of development.

Several varieties such as Zenith, Wase Aikoku, Malagkit Sungsong, and B589A4 appear to have only adult plant resistance (fig. 14). Young

13. The effect of aging on leaf extract inoculum.

seedlings of these varieties were moderately susceptible when inoculated by clipping but adult plants were resistant. Similarly, their semidwarf progenies had good resistance at 90 days after seeding, but at 30 days they were susceptible. As they matured they developed good field resistance. Although their resistance is not equal to that of Sigadis, TKM 6, or IR22, it appears adequate under most farmers' conditions in the Philippines.

The varietal testing program was adjusted, however, by inoculating progeny from those with adult plant resistance just prior to flowering. In addition, all advanced-generation breeding material and resistant donor parents were evaluated for field resistance by inoculating border rows on the windward side of a field plot 60 to 75 days after seeding. Distance and intensity of secondary disease spread across plots were evaluated 4 weeks later. In the replicated yield trials during the dry and wet seasons, all entries showing resistance by clipping inoculation were also resistant to secondary disease

Table 3. New sources of resistance to bacterial blight in the Philippines, based on a screening of 5,700 varieties from the world collection.

IRRI acc. no.	Variety	Origin
12133	ARC 5793	India
12122	ARC 5758	India
12180	ARC 6018	India
12259	ARC 6230	India
12260	ARC 6231	India
12356	ARC 7291	India
12359	ARC 7303	India
12376	ARC 7347	India
12567	ARC 10674	India
12682	ARC 10952	India
12686	ARC 10959	India
12690	ARC 10968	India
13530	Benong	Indonesia
11484	Chinsurah Boro II	India
13714	Djelita	Indonesia
636	Dular (R)	India
3581	Hakchang Fow	Indonesia
12969	Hom Thong	Laos
13512	Ketan Gadjih	Indonesia
12904	Khao Lo	Laos
13010	Ngane Tia	Laos
13843	Patong 32	W. Malaysia
13518	Seksek	Indonesia
14622	Sri Kuning	Indonesia
10302	Syntha	Indonesia
13746	Tao-thabi (M-163)	India
13836	Tolil 14	W. Malaysia

spread. But five semidwarf entries, derived from Zenith, B589A4, Malagkit Sungsong, and Wase Aikoku which were moderately susceptible to the clipping test were resistant to secondary disease spread.

Some varieties being used as sources of resistance in breeding programs are not highly resistant to a few virulent isolates of the bacterium. We tried to increase the level of resistance of these varieties by crossing two or more of the following varieties: IR20, IR22, BJI, Zenith, Laka, Malagkit Sungsong, TKM 6, Nagkayat, and Wase Aikoku. The F₂ and F₃ populations of 12 such crosses included many progeny that were more resistant than their individual parents when inoculated with the virulent isolate Pxo 25.

Additional sources of resistance. In a screening of 5,736 entries from the world collection, 27 new sources of resistance to bacterial blight were identified. The varieties resistant in two tests are listed in Table 3.

Most entries from the collection of wild rice

14. Effect of plant age on varietal reaction to bacterial blight.

were screened again. Some species gave the same reactions as reported in the previous test (1964 Annual Report), but a few others gave a different disease reaction from those reported earlier (Table 4). *Oryza punctata* was highly resistant to bacterial blight. Some entries of *O. latifolia*, *O. minuta*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perennis*, and *O. redleyi* were moderately resistant while other entries were either susceptible or were mixtures of susceptible and resistant plants.

Virulence of Philippine isolates. Isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* have been found to be variable in virulence. It is, however, not clear whether this variation is inherent in naturally occurring strains or is a result of isolating and maintaining the bacterium on pure culture and of the defects in methods for testing virulence.

In studies with 40 newly isolated cultures from six locations on the island of Luzon (Philippines) we found only minor variation in virulence between isolates. Varieties Wase Aikoku, Malagkit Sungsong, and Zenith best differentiated the isolates. Only one isolate, Pxo 10, was distinctly different. Pxo 10 had very low virulence, the colony morphology was non-fluidal, and the color was dark yellow.

In cooperation with the varietal improvement department we conducted disease screening nurseries at four locations in the Philippines. Disease reactions were generally similar at all locations. IR22, TKM 6, Sigadis, and W1263 and their progenies were resistant at all locations, indicating that the prevalent strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* naturally occurring in these four regions of the Philippines were similar. So

screening for bacterial blight resistance with naturally occurring strains in one location should be generally representative of the entire country.

Studies on yield loss. We continued studies on yield loss caused by bacterial blight with a controlled experiment in large clay pots in cooperation with the statistics department. IR24 was the test variety and treatments consisted of two dates of inoculation (1 and 2 weeks after heading),

Table 4. Reaction of wild *Oryzae* species to *Xanthomonas oryzae*.

Species	Disease score ^a	IRRI acc. no.
<i>O. latifolia</i>	MR	100165
	MR	100169
	MR	100172
	MR	100966
	MR	100891
<i>O. minuta</i>	MR	100887
	MR	101086
	MR	101096
	MR	101097
<i>O. officinalis</i>	MR/S ^b	101086
	MR	100948
	MR	100953
	MR	101112
<i>O. perennis</i>	MR	101117
	MR	101149
	MR	100600
<i>O. punctata</i>	R	100125
	R	100884
	R	100892
	R	100937
	R/S	100954
<i>O. redleyi</i>	R/S	101439
	MR	100877

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.
^bMixture of resistant and susceptible plants.

Table 5. Effects of bacterial blight on yield components of IR24 when different number of leaves per tiller are inoculated.^a

Leaves inoculated (no.)	Leaf infection ^b (%)	Panicle wt. (g)	Unfilled grains (g)	1000-grain wt. (g)
0	0 a	4.5 a	10.6 a	25.0
1	32 b	4.1 b	16.2 b	24.3
2	62 c	3.6 c	23.5 c	23.7
3	92 d	3.6 c	26.5 c	24.2
All	87 d	2.9 d	31.2 d	23.4

^aData are averages over three dates of inoculation, each having six replications (except for "all leaves" where there were two replications). Any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bReading made on three leaves.

three groups of leaves inoculated (top single leaf, top two leaves, and top three leaves), and controls with no inoculation and one with all leaves inoculated.

The yield component most directly affected by increased percentage of infected leaf area was the percentage of unfilled grains (Table 5). Under these conditions, the 1,000-grain weight was not greatly affected by increased disease infection in contrast with earlier tests under field conditions in which the 1,000-grain weight was adversely affected.

Although the leaf area infected was similar for the two inoculation dates, the inoculations made 1 week after heading gave the highest percentage of unfilled grains (Table 6), indicating that early infection reduces yield more than does late infection.

Studies on selective medium. Among 28 antimicrobial agents tested for tolerance to *X. oryzae*, only six were potentially useful in a selective medium for *X. oryzae*. The antimicrobial agents consist of 2.5 ppm Neomycin sulfate, 2.5 ppm Tyrothricin, 2.5 ppm 8-hydroxyquinoline, 150

ppm Cycloheximide, 0.1 g sodium taurocholate, and 0.05 g of sodium thioglycollate in 1 liter of medium. Incorporating this group of antimicrobial agents into WF-P or the modified Silva-Buddenhagen medium (MSB) as basal media resulted in different colony recovery and growth reduction of *X. oryzae* and rice leaf saprophytes. On MSB, these agents caused 60 to 100 percent growth reduction in *X. oryzae* and 0 to 50 percent in saprophytes. Growth of both saprophytes and *X. oryzae* on WF-P is fluidal even with low levels of carbon thus hampering recognition of colonies. The reaction of two test isolates to this group of antimicrobial agents also differed.

VECTORS OF VIRUS DISEASES

New vector of tungro and yellow dwarf. *Nephotettix malayanus* (fig. 15) was described as a new species by Ishihara and Kawase in 1968. Its major characteristics are crown a little longer medially than next to the eye (i.e., the cephalic margin is rather rounded), crown has no sub-marginal black band or has traces of it only behind the ocelli, tegmina have or have no central black spots, aedeagus is constricted about the middle, and the lateral paraphyses project obliquely and are sword-shaped.

This species has been collected from weeds in Santa Rosa, Laguna and reared in the greenhouse. *Leersia hexandra* was a better host than the rice plant. On *L. hexandra*, the insect lived longer and more progeny reached the adult stage.

Studies on the transmission of tungro by *N. malayanus* revealed that when the insects were allowed to acquire the virus from diseased plants for 4 days, 42 percent became active transmitters of the disease. The number of infective insects

Table 6. Effects of bacterial blight on unfilled grains from panicles on plants on which different numbers of leaves were inoculated 1 or 2 weeks after heading.

Leaves inoculated (no.)	1 wk after heading		2 wk after heading	
	Unfilled grains (%)	Increase compared with control (%)	Unfilled grains (%)	Increase compared with control (%)
0	9.6	—	9.8	—
1	19.8	106**	13.4	37
2	25.0	160**	22.5	130**
3	35.4	269**	24.5	150**
All	34.4	258**	34.1	248**

gradually increased as acquisition feeding period was increased from 1 to 4 days. The longest retention period was 3 days. The percentage of infective insects decreased tremendously with number of days after acquisition feeding. Thus, the virus-vector interaction seemed similar to that of *N. virescens*.

In a study of transmission of yellow dwarf by *N. malayanus*, even an acquisition feeding period of 10 days did not enable the insects to become infective immediately. The shortest incubation period of the virus in the insects was 23 days. Once the insects became infective, most transmitted the disease almost until they died without any additional acquisition feeding. The longest retention obtained was 10 days, limited by the life span of the insects on Taichung Native 1 seedling. The virus-vector interaction seemed similar to that of *N. virescens*.

Colony of grassy stunt transmitters. A colony of *Nilaparvata lugens* collected from *L. hexandra* in the field has been reared on *L. hexandra* in the greenhouse because it propagated well on *L. hexandra* but not on Taichung Native 1. The colony had a high percentage of active transmitters of grassy stunt.

Vectors in the Philippines. The names of some of the insect vectors of rice viruses have undergone several changes as a result of either progress in taxonomic research or personal preference. An increasing number of species have been demonstrated to be vectors of rice viruses. To eliminate confusion, the current and previous names of rice virus vectors in the Philippines are listed in Table 7 together with the rice viruses they transmit.

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF TUNGRO

The severe outbreak of tungro disease in the Philippines in 1971 underscored the limited knowledge available on tungro epidemiology—the outbreak and spread of infection—although many observations on tungro disease have been made in the field and in the greenhouse. The incidence of tungro is determined principally by four factors—availability of virus source, population and activity of insect vector, susceptibility of the rice variety to the virus and to the insect vector, and environmental conditions. These

factors interact. The study of the epidemiology of the disease is hampered by the lack of a reliable method, the difficulty of separating the complex factors, and the instability of the factors. We have attempted to increase understanding of the epidemiology of tungro by studying factors related to disease incidence.

This year we began using insect cages, 52 × 51 × 73 cm, covered by metal screen, for studying the factors affecting the percentage of infected seedlings. The cage accommodates 16 pots, each 12 cm in diameter. Virus source, number of insects, rice variety, and plant age can be varied, regulated, and selected as desired for determining the effect of factors on the disease incidence.

Insect preference for diseased plants. If insects prefer to move to diseased plants, the number of viruliferous insects should increase. We measured the number of insects of *N. virescens* on healthy and tungro-diseased plants in a cage at various time intervals after the insects were introduced into the cage.

Within 2 hours after they were introduced into the cage, 40 to 60 percent of the insects moved to the plants (Table 8). The percentage increased with time, but rarely reached 100. The insects seemed to prefer to move to the diseased plants when the tests were made under

15. *Nephrotettix malayanus*, a new vector of tungro and yellow dwarf.

Table 7. Current and previous (indented) names of vectors of rice viruses in the Philippines and the viruses they transmit.

Name	Author and year	Name	Author and year
<i>Tungro and yellow dwarf</i>			
<i>Nephotettix malayanus</i> (Ishihara & Kawase)	Ishihara & Kawase, 1968		
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål)	Ghuri, 1971		
<i>Nephotettix apicalis</i>	Ishihara, 1964	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Matsumura & Ishihara, 1945
<i>Nephotettix apicalis apicalis</i>	Linnavuori, 1960	<i>Hikona formosana</i>	Matsumura, 1935
<i>Nephotettix apicalis</i>	Ishihara, 1953	<i>Nilaparvata oryzae</i>	Esaki, 1932
<i>Nephotettix bipunctata</i>	Mercalf, 1946	<i>Delphacodes oryzae</i>	Esaki & Hashimoto, 1931
<i>Nephotettix bipunctatus</i>	Thompson	<i>Liburnia oryzae</i>	Kuwana, 1930
<i>Nephotettix bipunctatus apicalis</i>	Esaki & Hashimoto, 1932	<i>Liburnia sordescens</i>	Dammernan, 1929
<i>Nephotettix apicalis</i>	Melichar, 1903	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	Muir & Giffard, 1924
<i>Nephotettix nigropicta</i>	Matsumura, 1902	<i>Nilaparvata sordescens</i>	Muir, 1922
<i>Nephotettix nigropicta</i>	Matsumura, 1902	<i>Delphacodes sordescens</i>	Muir, 1919
<i>Thamnoettix nigromaculata</i>	Kirby, 1891	<i>Delphacodes parysatis</i>	Muir, 1917
<i>Thamnoettix nigropictus</i>	Lethierry, 1888	<i>Delphacodes ordovix</i>	Muir, 1917
<i>Thamnoettix nigro-picta</i>	Stål, 1870	<i>Delphacodes anderrida</i>	Muir, 1917
<i>Pediopsis nigromaculatus</i>	Motschulsky, 1859	<i>Delphax oryzae</i>	Matsumura, 1907
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	Motschulsky, 1859	<i>Dicranotropis anderrida</i>	Kirkaldy, 1907
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	Ishihara & Kawase, 1968	<i>Delphax parysatis</i>	Kirkaldy, 1907
<i>Nephotettix impicticeps</i>	Ghuri, 1971	<i>Delphax ordovix</i>	Kirkaldy, 1907
<i>Nephotettix apicalis</i>	Ishihara, 1964	<i>Nilaparvata greeni</i>	Distant, 1906
<i>Nephotettix apicalis bipunctatus</i>	Nielson, 1962	<i>Kaipa aculeata</i>	Melichar, 1903
<i>Nephotettix bipunctata</i>	Ma, 1933	<i>Liburnia sordescens</i>	Motschulsky, 1863
<i>Nephotettix bipunctatus</i>	Esaki & Hashimoto, 1932	<i>Delphax sordescens</i>	Stål, 1854
<i>Nephotettix bipunctata</i>	Yusope, 1920	<i>Delphax lugens</i>	
<i>Senocephalus virescens</i>	Distant, 1908	<i>Orange leaf and tungro</i>	
<i>Nephotettix bipunctatus</i>	Distant, 1908	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i> (Motschulsky)	Nielson, 1968
<i>Nephotettix apicalis</i>	Kirkaldy, 1907	<i>Inazuma dorsalis</i>	Ishihara, 1953
<i>Nephotettix bipunctatus</i>	Matsumura, 1902	<i>Sanctarius dorsalis</i>	Oman, 1949
<i>Thamnoettix bipunctatae</i>	Stål, 1870	<i>Togacephalus dorsalis</i>	Matsumura, 1940
<i>Cicada bipunctata</i>	Stål, 1869	<i>Thamnoettix dorsalis</i>	Matsumura, 1907
<i>Cicada Zpuncata</i>	Fabricius, 1803	<i>Thamnoettix storatus</i>	Ikuma, 1903
	Fabricius, 1803	<i>Deltocephalus fulgurialis</i>	Matsumura, 1902
	Fabricius, 1803	<i>Thamnoettix sellata</i>	Matsumura, 1899
		<i>Deltocephalus dorsalis</i>	Motschulsky, 1859

Table 8. Effect of test conditions on the preference of *Nephotettix virescens* caged on healthy and tungro-diseased Taichung Native 1 plants.

Light condition	Duration (h)	Trials (no.)	Insects (no.)	Insects on plants ^a (%)	Insects (%) on		X ² test	
					Healthy plants	Diseased plants	1:1 ratio	Homogeneity of trials
Natural	2	8	3028	60	38	62	**	**
Natural	8	12	4213	98	41	59	**	**
** Natural and dark ^b	16	12	4094	96	42	58	**	**
Dark	2	11	4015	49	52	48	ns	**
Dark	16	4	1044	92	50	50	ns	ns
Green	2	8	2898	43	46	54	**	ns
Yellow	2	8	2827	39	57	43	**	**

^aThe rest of the insects were in the cage. ^bFrom 1600 to 0800 hours.

light alone or from afternoon to the following morning. Diseased plants had significantly more insects than healthy plants regardless of the length of testing time. But the departure from a 1:1 ratio became smaller as testing time increased.

In the dark (the cages were covered with black cloth in daytime) diseased and healthy plants had almost the same number of insects regardless of the length of testing time. The main reason why different results were obtained under light and dark conditions may have been that the insects were attracted to the yellow color of the diseased plants, but in the dark they could not distinguish the yellow plants from the green healthy plants.

To verify this finding we covered the cages with colored cellophane. In the cages covered with green cellophane, diseased plants had significantly more insects than healthy plants although the difference was only 8 percent. But in the cages covered by yellow cellophane the number of insects on healthy plants was significantly higher (14%) than that on diseased plants. The results reveal the sensitivity of the insects to green and yellow. The insects may be highly attracted only to a certain intensity of the color between green and yellow. Possibly the preference of the insect for a particular rice variety may be related to the color of the variety and its intensity.

The results of most tests (Table 8) were inconsistent from one trial to another, implying that some factors were not properly controlled. Nevertheless, the insect is capable of moving to the diseased plant under various conditions. Movement of the insects to the diseased plants

is the first step in disease transmission. If they do not move to the diseased plants, they cannot become viruliferous.

Acquiring tungro virus. Acquiring the virus from the diseased plants is the second step in disease transmission. We tried to determine how placing different proportions of healthy and tungro-diseased plants in a cage affects the proportion of infective insects. The proportion of infective insects should reflect the movement of the insects to the diseased plants as well as the acquisition of the virus from the diseased plants.

After being confined in the cage for a time, the insects were sampled and tested individually for infectivity. About 20 percent of the insects became infective when the ratio of diseased to healthy plants was 1:3 (Table 9). The percentage of infective insects increased as the ratio of diseased to healthy plants increased. It seemed that the insects were not evenly distributed on the test plants but that more were on diseased plants when the confinement period was 1, 7, or

Table 9. Percentage of infective insects of *Nephotettix virescens* 1 to 14 days after being introduced into a cage with different proportions of healthy and tungro-diseased plants.

Pots in cage (no.)		Infective insects ^a (%)						Avg.
Healthy	Diseased	1 day	2 days	4 days	7 days	14 days		
3	1	21	18	16	26	40	24	
2	2	36	33	39	58	60	45	
1	3	56	39	44	51	51	48	
0	4	63	70	75	68	71	69	
Avg.		44	40	44	51	56		

^aAvg. of two trials with a total of 3161 insects.

Table 10. Movement of *Nephotettix virescens* from healthy or tungro-diseased plants (TN1) to healthy and diseased plants in cage after 1 to 3 days.

Original no. of insects (range)	Total insects ^a (no.)	Duration (days)	Insects ^b (%) on		
			Original plants	Healthy	Diseased
<i>Healthy original host plant</i>					
287 to 386	1372	1	80.2	10.0	8.6
356 to 394	1468	2	49.0	28.9	21.9
286 to 411	1381	3	39.3	37.9	22.4
<i>Diseased original host plant</i>					
193 to 324	1080	1	82.9	7.6	8.7
268 to 342	1256	2	54.7	27.5	17.4
323 to 395	1406	3	31.5	38.1	29.9

^aFour trials. ^bThe sum is not 100 percent since some insects were not on plants.

14 days. In contrast, more insects were likely to be on healthy plants when the confinement period was 2 or 4 days. Consequently, the percentage of infective insects did not increase steadily as confinement increased from 1 to 4 days, except when the cage contained no healthy plants.

Testing the infectivity of insects at various lengths of times after their confinement on diseased plants is identical to determining the effect of length of acquisition period on the percentage of infective insects. These results confirm studies we made a few years ago which showed that the percentage of infective insects gradually increases with increasing length of acquisition feeding period from 2 hours to 4

days, after which it decreases slightly (1965 Annual Report).

Insect movement. The spread of tungro disease is determined by the movement of viruliferous insects. Movement refers to the number of insects caged on healthy or diseased plants that move to other plants (healthy or diseased) in the same cage after a period of time. Tests were made by introducing insects into a cage containing either a pot of diseased plants or a pot of healthy plants. After the insects had settled on the plants, one pot each of healthy and diseased plants were placed in the cage. Every day thereafter for 3 days the insects on each plant were counted. This test could not reveal the frequency of insect movement, nor could it specify the number of

16. Distribution of tungro-infected seedlings in cages containing IR8 or Taichung Native 1 (16 pots per cage) after 200 viruliferous insects of *Nephotettix virescens* introduced to the upper left corner of each cage were allowed to feed for 1 day.

insects that had moved out and then returned to the same plant during a given period.

Some insects always left their host plants regardless of whether the plants were diseased or healthy. With 200 to 400 insects per cage we found that 20 percent of the insects moved out after 1 day, 50 percent after 2 days, and 65 percent after 3 days. Thus, for 3 days the number of insects leaving their host plants increased with time. But the rate at which they moved out was not proportional to the number of days of confinement. There was no striking difference between the number of insects leaving diseased plants (43.8%) and the number of insects leaving healthy plants (43.6%) (Table 10).

Not all the insects that moved from either the healthy or the diseased plants reached another plant. About 0.6 percent of the test insects were not on the plants at the time they were counted. The rest were either on their original host plants or on other plants. Twenty-six percent of the insects on healthy plants moved to other healthy plants, 18 percent moved to diseased plants. Twenty-four percent of the insects on diseased plants moved to healthy plants and 19 percent to other diseased plants. In other words, whether the insects were on healthy or on diseased plants, more moved to healthy plants. This result differs from that obtained in the preference test (Table 8). The greater number of insects moving to healthy plants might be one reason for the low percentage of infective insects when the insects were confined in a cage with various proportions of healthy and diseased plants for 2 or 4 days (Table 9).

Infected seedlings. The percentage of infected seedlings should be mainly determined by number of viruliferous insects, movement of insects, susceptibility of the plants, and duration of inoculation. We attempted to determine how these factors interact, with IR8, IR20, and Taichung Native 1 as test varieties. All three are susceptible to tungro virus, but Taichung Native 1 is the most susceptible and IR20 is more susceptible than IR8. Taichung Native 1 is susceptible to the test insects, while IR8 and IR20 are resistant. We placed 16 pots of seedlings in a cage. Fifty or two hundred insects were introduced to the pot in a corner of the cage, then, 1 day later, the seedlings were moved out of the

Table 11. Infected seedlings of IR8 with Taichung Native 1 and of IR20 with Taichung Native 1 in a cage with 50 or 200 tungro-viruliferous insects of *Nephotettix virescens*.

Variety	Infected seedlings ^a (%)	
	50 insects	200 insects
	<i>IR8 and TN1</i>	
IR8	6.2	12.3
TN1	20.3	30.4
	<i>IR20 and TN1</i>	
IR20	9.1	29.5
TN1	13.0	32.0

^aAvg. of two trials.

cage. The insects were removed, and the plants were kept in the greenhouse while symptoms developed.

When 50 insects were introduced, 3.8 percent of IR8 seedlings were infected; when 200 insects were introduced, 7.1 percent were infected. The corresponding figures for IR20 were 7.3 and 10.0 percent, and for Taichung Native 1, 9.9 and 16.3 percent. Most of the infected seedlings were in the pot where the insects were introduced and in adjacent pots (fig. 16). There seemed to be no striking difference among the three varieties in the distribution of infected seedlings. Hence, the insect-resistant varieties did not cause more scattering of the insects in the cage. Nevertheless, the most susceptible variety showed the highest percentage of infected seedlings.

Although the percentage of infected seedlings, regardless of variety, increased as more viruliferous insects were introduced into the cage, when the number of insects was increased by four times (from 50 to 200), the percentage of infected seedlings increased only 1.6 times.

When the seedlings of two varieties were alternately arranged in a cage and the viruliferous insects were introduced above the seedlings in the center of the cage the varieties differed in percentage of infected seedlings (Table 11). Since the insects were scattered, the percentage of infected seedlings, regardless of variety, was generally higher than when the insects were introduced at one corner of the cage. Similarly the percentage of infected seedlings increased regardless of variety when more viruliferous insects were introduced into the cage. But when the insects were increased from 50 to 200, the percentage of infected seedlings increased 2.3

17. Distribution of tungro-infected seedlings in two cages containing IR8 and Taichung Native 1, after 200 viruliferous insects of *Nephotettix virescens* introduced to the upper left corner of each cage were allowed to feed for 1 day.

times, indicating that the rate of increase in percentage of infected seedlings may not coincide with the rate of increase in number of viruliferous insects in the cage.

Changing the arrangement of seedlings of IR8 and Taichung Native 1 or of IR20 and Taichung Native 1 in a cage did not alter the difference in susceptibility of the varieties to tungro disease. In other words, the more susceptible variety always had the higher percentage of infected seedlings regardless of number of viruliferous insects in the cage. The highest percentage of infected seedlings usually occurred in the pot where the insects were introduced. The seedlings in adjacent pots had the next highest percentage. The farther the seedlings were from the pot where the insects were introduced, the lower the percentage of infected seedlings. A more susceptible variety, however, even far from the point where insects were introduced into the cage, might have a higher percentage of infected seedlings than the variety nearer the pot where the insects were introduced (fig. 17). Furthermore, the percentage of infected seedlings, regardless of variety, increased as the number of viruliferous insects increased.

A different result was sometimes obtained when the insects were confined in the cage for 7 days (fig. 18). The difference was that the percentage of infected seedlings of IR8 was remark-

ably low in the pot where 200 viruliferous insects were introduced and in adjacent pots. Thus, the difference in number of infected seedlings between IR8 and Taichung Native 1 was drastic. This difference did not occur when only 50 viruliferous insects were used. Although the cause of the difference is unclear, one possibility may be the irregular arrangement of the cages in relation to the direction of sunlight in the greenhouse because insects tended to move toward the light a few minutes after they were introduced into the pot.

Transmission. When healthy and diseased seedlings were confined with virus-free insects, some of the healthy seedlings became infected. The longer the insects were confined in the cage, the more seedlings became infected but the number of dead seedlings also increased. Similarly, the more insects in the cage, the higher the percentage of infected seedlings. These are preliminary results.

Vectors in farmers' fields. To determine the possibility of predicting an outbreak of tungro disease by testing the infectivity of insect vectors in the field, insects were collected from 15 fields in six provinces (Laguna, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pangasinan, Tarlac, and Pampanga) at monthly intervals. Collection was begun in February but was interrupted in August and September due to typhoons and floods.

18. Distribution of tungro-infected IR8 and Taichung Native 1 seedlings in two cages after 200 viruliferous insects of *Nephotettix virescens* introduced to the upper left corner of each cage were allowed to feed for 7 days.

The average incidence of tungro disease was low. *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* were found in almost all the fields every month, but *N. virescens* were more numerous.

We tested 1,663 insects of *N. virescens*. The averages of infective insects from the different fields ranged from about 1 percent (Urdaneta, Pangasinan) to 37 percent (Santa Cruz, Laguna). The averages of infective insects were 46% in February, 17% in March, 19% in April, 0.5% in May, 0% in June and July, 2% in October, and 1.5% in November.

At eight locations, none of the 611 insects of *N. nigropictus* collected were infective. The collections from Santa Cruz, Laguna, had the highest percentage of infective insects (4%). The averages of infective insects were 1.1% in February, 3.4% in March, 3.0% in April, 1.2% in May, 0% in June, July, and October, and 0.6% in November.

IMPROVED TUNGRO SCREENING METHOD

The mass screening method for testing varieties for resistance to tungro (1965 Annual Report) has a theoretical maximum testing capacity of 5,840 entries a year, which was satisfactory for several years. Recently, however, demand for testing has increased greatly. The capacity of the mass screening method can only be enlarged

by rearing more insects or by inoculating more seedlings per insect. Since we did not have the additional facilities, such as insect cages, required for rearing more insects, we attempted to find ways to inoculate more seedlings per insect. These studies showed that the inoculation period could be shortened to 2.5 hours so that the insects could be used for inoculating seedlings twice a day. In other words, the capacity of the screening method was doubled.

In the improved method the viruliferous insects are used for inoculating seedlings every day from 800 to 1030 and from 1400 to 1630. To keep the insects infective they are confined on diseased plants between inoculations for re-acquisition feeding (fig. 19).

The distribution of viruliferous insects on the seedlings in an inoculation cage is a key factor determining the uniformity of inoculation. Although the insects can be disturbed artificially to ensure their uniform distribution on the test seedlings, the insects are naturally attracted to light. Their characteristic tendency to move toward the light is therefore used to facilitate the even distribution of the insects on test seedlings in the inoculation cage.

A new style of inoculation cage was fabricated. The four sides and the top of the cage consist of a metal screen under a wooden sliding door. The metal screen is for confining the insects in the

19. Improved mass screening method for testing varietal resistance to tungro disease.

age. The adjustable sliding door regulates the light entering the cage. In other words, the distribution of the insects in the cage is controlled by regulating the opening of the sliding door. We found the new inoculation cage convenient to use.

In tests of rice varieties and selections for their reaction to tungro disease by the mass screening method, it is better to have both resistant and susceptible checks. If the checks are included in every inoculation, the capacity of the screening method is reduced by one-eighth because each inoculation cage accommodates only 16 pots. A test was therefore developed for checking the infectivity of the insects in each inoculation cage for every inoculation. Forty insects were simply

sampled from each cage immediately before each inoculation and tested individually for their infectivity.

Inoculation period and transmission. One influence on the success of inoculating a seedling with a viruliferous insect is the inoculation feeding period or the time interval between introduction of an insect to a seedling and its removal from the seedling. Obviously, if the inoculation feeding period is shorter than the minimum time it takes the insect to introduce the virus to the seedling, the seedling cannot become infected, and a low percentage of infected seedlings results. On the other hand, excessively prolonging the period causes the percentage of infected seedlings to be limited by the percentage of active transmitters of the insect vector. Hence, within a certain time range, prolonging the inoculation feeding period would increase the percentage of seedling infection, but beyond that range, the inoculation feeding period should not affect the transmission of tungro virus.

The number of seedlings inoculated per insect per day can be increased only by shortening the inoculation feeding period. The question is how short the inoculation feeding period should be. We found that the percentage of seedling infection increases gradually as inoculation feeding period lengthens from 1 to 9 hours (Table 12). The increase is greater, however, from 1 to 3

Table 12. Effect of inoculation feeding period on the transmission of tungro virus by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens*.

Inoculation feeding period (h)	Seedlings	
	Inoculated (no.)	Infected* (%)
1	513	54
2	512	60
3	513	70
4	497	69
5	498	71
6	516	71
7	500	73
8	500	73
9	502	74

*Avg. of 13 trials.

hours than from 3 to 9 hours. For screening, considering both the time interval and the percentage of infection, shortening the 8-hour inoculation feeding period to around 3 hours would mean the least sacrifice of infection percentage.

Number of inoculations in a day. Since the inoculation feeding period can be reduced to about 3 hours, two or three inoculations a day can be made by the same insects. Experiments performed to verify this point (Table 13) indicated that the percentages of infected seedlings from the second and the third inoculations were always lower than the percentage from the first inoculation on the same day even when the second inoculation feeding period was longer than the first inoculation feeding period.

Maintaining infectivity. To maintain their infectivity, the insects must have a reacquisition feeding between inoculations because the tungro virus does not persist in the vector. In mass screening rice varieties for reaction to tungro with one inoculation feeding a day the insects are given a daily reacquisition feeding lasting 16 hours. But when mass screening involves two inoculations a day, reacquisition feeding must be provided to the insect between the first and second inoculations to keep the insects infective for the second inoculation.

Studies on reacquisition feeding confirmed that more seedlings were infected after the first inoculation than after the second inoculation (66.5% versus 59.2%). But when the inoculation feeding period was 2 hours and the reacquisition feeding period was 4.5 hours between the two inoculations, the percentage of infected seedlings from the second inoculation was higher than that from the first inoculation 71.0% versus 61.3%). When the inoculation feeding period was 2.5 hours and the reacquisition feeding period was 3.5 hours between the two inoculations, however, the two inoculations gave almost identical percentages of infected seedlings (64.3% versus 64.2%).

Another experiment (Table 14) showed that the 8-hour inoculation feeding period gave greater infection than the 2.5-hour inoculation feeding but confirmed the consistency of the 2.5-hour inoculation as mentioned above. Thus, the insects could be used in the morning for the

Table 13. Percentage of infected seedlings inoculated by the same viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* at different times in a day.

Inoculation time	Inoculation period (h)	Seedlings	
		Inoculated (no.)	Infected (%)
<i>Two inoculations a day^a</i>			
0800 to 1030	2.5	2094	63.3
1030 to 1530	5.0	2096	54.4
<i>Three inoculations a day^b</i>			
0830 to 1100	2.5	1696	62.1
1100 to 1330	2.5	1661	58.0
1330 to 1600	2.5	1649	53.0

^aAvg. of 23 trials. ^bAvg. of 50 trials.

first inoculation from 0800 to 1030 and in the afternoon for the second inoculation from 1400 to 1630. From 1030 to 1400 and from 1630 to 0800 the following morning, the insects can be confined on diseased plants for reacquisition feeding.

Serial transmission. In the mass screening the insects are used repeatedly for inoculation. To determine their ability to transmit the virus twice a day we measured the infectivity of the insect by daily serial transmission with reacquisition feeding between two inoculations. The insects remained infective almost until they died regardless of number of inoculations per day (fig. 20). Furthermore, there seemed to be no striking difference in percentage of infected seedlings between inoculating once a day and inoculating twice a day, nor between the first and the second inoculation in a day.

Number of insects per seedling. *N. virescens*, used in mass screening, is the most efficient vector of tungro virus. But the proportion of

Table 14. Percentage of infected seedlings inoculated by the same viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* at different times in a day with reacquisition feeding between two inoculations.

Inoculation time	Inoculation period (h)	Seedlings	
		Inoculated (no.)	Infected ^a (%)
<i>One inoculation per day</i>			
0800 to 1600	8.0	1807	55.1
<i>Two inoculations per day</i>			
0800 to 1030	2.5	1968	49.9
1400 to 1630	2.5	1881	50.0

^aAvg. of 26 trials.

20. Serial transmission of the tungro virus by individual leafhoppers of *Nephrotettix virescens* permitted reacquisition feeding after each inoculation.

active transmitters varies according to the method and conditions of testing. It rarely reaches 100 percent in a large sample. Hence, when one insect per seedling is used, it is impossible to consistently get 100 percent infected seedlings, even with a very susceptible variety. For screening rice varieties at least one *infective* insect per seedling should be used, therefore, more than one insect per seedling is needed. If the inoculation feeding period is long enough for the insect to transmit the virus, the probability that a seedling will have one infective insect can be calculated, $P = 1 - (1 - a)^n$, where P is the

probability, a is the percentage of infective insects, and n is the number of insects per seedling (formula derived by the statistics department). For a 2.5-hour inoculation feeding period, we determined the percentages of infected seedlings inoculated by various number of insects. The percentage increased with increasing number of insects per seedling (Table 15). But the percentages were generally lower than the calculated figures even if the calculation was based on percentage of infective insects obtained from an inoculation feeding period of 2.5 hours. We therefore use five to six insects per seedling in mass screening.

Table 15. Percentage of tungro-infected Taichung Native 1 seedlings inoculated by one to five viruliferous *Nephrotettix virescens* for 2.5 hours.

Viruliferous insects (no./seedling)	Inoculated seedlings (no.)	Infected seedlings (%)	
		Actual ^a	Calculated ^b
1	458	73.6	73.6
2	449	88.2	93.0
3	451	95.5	98.2
4	448	96.0	99.5
5	427	97.8	99.9

^aAvg. of 12 trials. ^bFrom $[1 - (1 - 0.736)]^n$ where n is the number of insects per seedling.

Virus source. Last year we reported that on Taichung Native 1, a susceptible variety, the insect recovered less virus from green leaves of an infected plant than from yellow leaves (1971 Annual Report). Based on periodic observation of diseased plants this year, the intensity of yellowing of infected plants varied not only from plant to plant but also from time to time from seedling stage to maturity, although all plants were inoculated by the same number of viruliferous insects for a similar time period and

at similar age. This led us to suspect that, in addition to biological variation, the virus concentration may not be identical in all infected plants at all stages of plant growth. In preliminary studies, we allowed insects to feed on five plants that had been inoculated 2 to 12 weeks earlier. After the feeding, the insect infectivity ranged from 66 to 88 percent.

Variation in infectivity results not only when insects feed on plants inoculated at different times but also when they feed on different varieties. In a study of the percentage of infective insects in relation to varieties from which they acquired the virus, we placed about 400 insects on diseased plants which had been inoculated 6 weeks before. On Taichung Native 1, 82% of the insects became infective; on IR22, 73%; on IR5, 25%; on IR20, 22%; on IR8, 20%; on IR24, 18%; and on C4-63G, 16%. The reason for the variation is unclear.

It is unlikely that the nitrogen level in the soil would reduce the ability of diseased plant to act as a virus source. The percentage of infective insects was not greatly reduced when a higher amount of nitrogen was applied to the soil of diseased plants. Commercial ammonium sulfate was used as source of nitrogen and Taichung Native 1 as test variety. The fertilizer was mixed with soil (Maahas clay) at 0 to 10 g/kg soil. Virus recovery tests were performed 2, 4, and 6 weeks after inoculation. An average of 48 percent of the insects were infected in the treatment with no ammonium sulfate and 59 to 73 percent with the 2 to 10 g/kg soil treatments.

Insect damage. *N. virescens* can retard plant growth especially just after feeding (1969 Annual Report), so a seedling infected by tungro virus suffers from damage caused by both the virus and the insect. Since the tungro virus can only be inoculated to a seedling by an insect vector, there is no way of completely eliminating the insect damage from the inoculated seedlings. The damage can be reduced, however, by using fewer insects per seedling or shortening the duration of the insect feeding. The improved mass screening method has shortened the duration of insect feeding from 8 to 2.5 hours so the insect damage is reduced (Table 16).

Blank test. One hundred sixty pots of Taichung Native 1 seedlings were tested by the improved

Table 16. Average height of 35 Taichung Native 1 seedlings 0 to 5 weeks after being infested by five green leafhoppers (*Nephotettix virescens*) per seedling for 2.5 and 8 hours.

Duration of infestation (h)	Plant ht (cm)				
	0 wk	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk
0.0 (check)	21.0	34.3	53.4	73.9	77.7
2.5	20.6	32.3	51.9	70.1	78.4
8.0	20.8	29.6	49.8	67.7	79.7

mass screening method for 5 consecutive days. Each pot had 70 to 100 percent infected seedlings for the first inoculation and 60 to 100 percent for the second inoculation in the same day. The coefficients of variation were 10.2, 4.4, 4.4, 9.0, and 6.0 percent for the first inoculation on five consecutive days, and 8.2, 5.0, 5.3, 7.1, and 11.6 percent for the second inoculation. Therefore five pots are needed to keep the standard error of the mean under 10 percent unless the extreme cases can be avoided. On the whole, however, the overall means of the infected seedlings of the two inoculations did not differ appreciably (93.4% versus 93.9%). No consistent trend was observed for each day either.

Data from screening tests. From August to December we tested about 540 entries a month for tungro resistance by the improved mass screening method. Inoculations were made only 5 days a week, so the rate is lower than the theoretical maximum, 704 entries a month. About 135,000 seedlings were inoculated and about 87,000 seedlings were infected. The percentage of infective insects differed appreciably between the two replications and between months. The difference could be due to the sample size used in testing the infective insects in the inoculation cage or the variation of the virus source. The mean percentages of infected seedlings in the two replications did not differ appreciably regardless of the month.

Large variations were observed on certain days. The differences in percentage of infected seedlings between two duplicates of an entry are shown in Table 17. In two entries the difference in percentage of infected seedlings between their two duplicates ranged from 51 to 60 percent. But duplicates of 83.2% of the entries in August, of 94.6% in September, of 92.1% in October, of 95.3% in November, and of 87.2% in December

infected seedlings in two trials. None of four seedlings of Pacita became infected. C4-137 had 30 percent infected seedlings and IET 1039 had 29 percent.

Of the 25 other resistant selections, 19 came from IR1737 (IR24/4 × *O. nivara*), three came from IR1721 (IR24/3 × *O. nivara*), and one each from IR789 (IR8 × Muey Nahng 62M), IR946 (H105 × [Dgwg × H4]), and IR1917 (IR20/3 × *O. nivara*).

COMBINING DISEASE RESISTANCE

To accelerate breeding for disease resistance, we attempted to introduce resistance from many more donors to standard varieties, to build up the level of resistance by crossing among resistant varieties, and to combine resistance to several diseases in single lines.

Three families, IR22/3, × Tetep, IR8/3 ×

Columbia 1, and (IR8 × Dawn) × (IR8 × Kataktara) showed resistance to both blast and bacterial blight under severe disease pressure. Progeny of (IR8/4 × Pankhari 203) × IR24/4 × *O. nivara* are resistant to both tungro and grassy stunt viruses. Crosses involving IR841, Mudgo × IR8, IR8 × *O. nivara*, and IR24 × *O. nivara* show resistance to grassy stunt, to brown planthopper, to green leafhopper, and some resistance to tungro, also. All the lines are semidwarf with good plant type.

Some crosses also involve many sources of resistance. The F₁ plants of one cross involving IR22, Zenith, M. Sungsong, IR20, *O. nivara*, IR8, Pankhari 203, Dawn, and Kataktara and of a cross involving IR8, Pankhari 203, Dawn, Kataktara, *O. nivara*, IR20, BJI, and Nagkayat were inoculated with tungro, grassy stunt, blast, and bacterial blight. Many of them were resistant to all four diseases.

Varietal improvement

Considerable progress was made in combining resistance to major

diseases and insects with improved plant

type and superior grain quality. Many breeding lines and traditional varieties were screened for tungro resistance under heavy disease pressure in the field. Several with excellent level of resistance to the virus were identified. Many promising lines resistant to other diseases such as blast, bacterial blight, and grassy stunt and to insects such as leafhoppers, plant-hoppers, and stem borers were identified. Several selections with multiple disease and insect resistance were evaluated in replicated yield trials. Two promising selections, IR1529-680-3 and IR1541-76-3, are being evaluated in large-scale trials. □ High levels of protein were detected or reconfirmed in a few breeding lines that have improved plant type and emphasis was placed on combining these traits with disease and insect resistance. Using these lines as sources, a modified recurrent selection scheme was undertaken to reinforce genetic factors for high protein content. For grain quality improvement emphasis was shifted to developing varieties with intermediate amylose content. □ Progress was made in transferring the drought tolerance and early maturity of upland varieties into plants with intermediate height. New crosses were made to recombine drought tolerance with tillering ability, disease and insect resistance, and high productive capacity. □ Several nations in Asia collaborated with us in conserving indigenous rice germ plasm. About 2,500 seed samples were collected and assembled from the remote areas of Sri Lanka, Indonesia, and the Khmer Republic.

BREEDING PROGRAM

More than 1,000 crosses were made in 1972, many of them multiple crosses involving two F_1 hybrids or an F_1 hybrid and a fixed line. Many of the crosses combined resistance to the major diseases and insect pests with such important traits as high protein content, earliness, and desirable grain quality.

Tungro. During 1972, we screened more than 8,000 breeding lines and varieties and F_2 populations from 27 crosses, consisting of 100,000 plants, for tungro resistance under heavy disease pressure in the field. The tungro screening nurseries were planted during both the dry and wet seasons at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur. At Maligaya infection was low in the dry season but high in the wet season; in Bicol, infection was extremely high during both seasons.

Hundreds of advanced breeding lines were screened. Lines with high levels of tungro resistance (Table 1) derived from several sources, such as TKM-6, Gam Pai, W 1263, HR 21, BJ 1,

Pankhari 203, and PTB 18, were identified. Gam Pai 15 and PTB 18 combine well with the dwarf plant type. Some tungro-resistant lines, which are also resistant to other diseases and pests, are being used extensively in the hybridization program.

Pedigree nurseries of early generation lines, mostly F_3 and F_4 , were planted at Maligaya and in Bicol for tungro screening. The dry season tungro nursery in Bicol consisted of 1,600 lines. The test entries came from three crosses involving an excellent tungro-resistant line with improved plant type, IR1364-37-3. These crosses were made to combine tungro resistance with resistance to other diseases such as blast and bacterial leaf blight, and to such insects as green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers. We concurrently tested these lines at IRRI for blast, bacterial leaf blight, green leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers and saved selections with multiple resistance.

We tested 5,000 selections from 16 crosses in the wet season at Maligaya. The resistant parents involved were IR833-6-3, IR1364-37-3, IR1330-5-3, C4-63, and TKM-6. These selections were simultaneously evaluated at IRRI for resistance

Table 1. Dwarf selections and varieties identified as tungro resistant at Pili and Maligaya, Philippines, tested for resistance to other diseases and insects at IRRI, 1972 dry and wet seasons.

Designation	Cross	Resistance ^a to				
		Blast	Bacterial blight	Grassy stunt	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR1541-76-3	IR24 × TKM-6	R	R	S	R	R
-102-6		MR	S	S	R	R
IR1514A-E666	IR20 × TKM-6	R	R	S	R	R
IR833-6-2	(Peta/3 × TN1) × Gam Pai 15	MR	S	S	S	R
IR1330-5-3	(17-1 Lt × IR8) × W 1263	S	MR	S	R	R
IR1364-37-3	(Peta/3 × TN1) × HR 21	MR	S	S	MR	R
IR1365-83-2	(Peta/3 × TN1) × BJ 1	S	MS	S	S	R
IR825-11-2	(IR8 × Pankhari 203) × (Peta/6 × TN1)	S	S	S	S	R
IR1702-22-3	IR24 × PTB 18	MR	MS	S	S	R
-31-2		MR	MS	S	R	R
-74-3		MR	S	S	R	R
-87-2		S	S	S	R	R
-134-2		MR	S	S	R	R
-158-4		MR	S	S	R	R
-171-2		MS	S	S	R	R
IR1721-14-6	IR24/3 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	S	R	S	R
CS 3	Gam Pai/2 × TN1	R	S	S	S	R
Ratna	TKM-6 × IR8	S	R	S	S	S
RD 2	Gam Pai/2 × TN1	R	S	S	S	R
CR 94-13		S	S	S	R	R
Triveni		S	S	S	S	S

^aR = Resistant, MR = Moderately resistant, MS = Moderately susceptible, S = Susceptible.

to other diseases and insects and for grain quality. Lines with multiple resistance were selected.

Tungro-resistant F₂ populations from single, top, and double crosses were also grown at Maligaya during both seasons. Tungro-susceptible segregates were removed at the flowering stage and resistant plants selected for further testing.

Several tall varieties were tested. Those with high levels of resistance are listed in Table 2. Pankhari 203, Habiganj D.W. 8, HR 21, and Ram Tulasi had been previously identified as resistant by IRRI pathologists; Latisail Aman, Kamod 253, Ambemohor 159, Ambemohar 102, and Kataribhog were identified as resistant by Indian scientists.

Grassy stunt. In cooperation with the plant pathologists, we evaluated selections from *Oryza nivara* backcrosses to IR24 and IR20 for resistance to grassy stunt. Many IR24 backcross lines are resistant to grassy stunt virus, have good grain quality and yield potentials equal to the recurrent parent. They are of excellent plant type, with sturdy stems that make them resistant to lodging. IR20 backcross lines, however, have weak stems and are susceptible to lodging.

Most IR24 backcross lines resistant to grassy stunt are also resistant to blast (Table 3), a trait that must be inherited from *O. nivara*, because IR24 is susceptible. One line has a good level of tungro resistance while others are moderately resistant. Most are resistant to green leafhoppers. Entomologists tested two IR24/3 × *O. nivara*

Table 2. Traditional varieties that showed high levels of resistance to tungro disease in tungro nurseries. Maligaya, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Origin
Pankhari 203	5999	India
Malagkit Sungsong	599	Philippines
Nagkayat	584	Philippines
W 1263	11057	India
PTB 10	67	India
PTB 18	6105	India
Hashikalmi	3397	Surinam
Basmati 6129	9037	Pakistan
Latisail Aman	9893	Bangladesh
Kamod 253	—	India
Ambemohor 159	5896	India
Ambemohor 102	—	India
Kataribhog	12765	India
Habiganj D.W. 8	11751	Bangladesh
HR 21	663	India
BJ 1	256	India
Brondol Putih T 43	5338	Indonesia
ADT 25	5151	India
Co. 21	6396	India
Gam Pai 30-12-15	831	Thailand
Ram Tulasi	181	India
H 8	11071	Ceylon
Mong Chim Vang A	219	Vietnam
ARC 5752	12119	India
ARC 7010	12313	India
ARC 10844	12654	India
ARC 7105		India
ARC 7110		India
ARC 7118		India
ARC 7120		India
ARC 7125		India
ARC 7140		India
ARC 10226		India
ARC 10531		India
ARC 10980		India
ARC 11254		India
ARC 11264		India

Table 3. Promising lines that are resistant to grassy stunt and that have high levels of resistance to other diseases and insects.

Designation	Cross	Resistance to				
		Blast	Bacterial blight	Tungro	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR1704-3-2	IR24/2 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	S	—	S	S
-13-3		R	S	—	S	S
IR1721-2-7	IR24/3 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	S	MR	S	R
-7-1		R	S	MR	S	R
-11-4		R	S	MR	S	R
-11-5		R	S	MR	S	R
-11-8		R	R	MR	S	R
-14-6		R	S	R	S	R
IR1737-19-6	IR24/4 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	S	MR	S	R
-41-3		R	S	MR	S	R
IR1917-3-17	IR20/3 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	R	MR	S	S
-3-19		R	R	MR	S	R

Table 4. Promising lines that are resistant to bacterial blight and that have high levels of resistance to other diseases and insects.

Designation	Cross	Resistance to				
		Blast	Tungro	Grassy stunt	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR1330-3-2	(17-1 Lt × IR8) × W 1263	S	S	S	R	R
IR1480-116-3	IR790-28 × IR825-28-4	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1487-194-5	IR127-80-1 × IR442-2-50	MR	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-53-2	(Sigadis/2 × TN1) × IR24	R	MR	S	S	R
-382-4		R	MR	S	S	R
-680-3		R	MR	S	S	R
IR1626-71-2	IR24 × IR22	MR	S	S	S	R
-88-2		S	S	S	S	R
IR1614-168-2	IR22 × (Mudgo × IR8)	S	S	S	R	R
-389-1		S	S	S	R	R
IR1541-102-3	IR24 × TKM-6	S	R	S	S	R
IR1694-3-2	IR8/3 × Wase Aikoku	S	S	S	S	R
IR1697-237-2	IR8/4 × Wase Aikoku	S	S	S	S	R
IR1698-237-2	IR8/4 × Zenith	R	S	S	S	R

Table 5. Promising lines that are resistant to blast and that have high levels of resistance to other diseases and insects.

Designation	Cross	Resistance to				
		Bacterial blight	Tungro	Grassy stunt	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR759-133-1	IR8 × (Peta/3 × Dawn)	S	S	S	S	R
IR879-24-1	IR8/2 × (Peta/3 × Dawn)	S	S	S	S	R
IR944-102-2	(TN1 × Malagkit Sungsong) × IR8	MR	S	S	S	R
IR1360-87-1	IR8 × Kambaungan	S	S	S	S	R
IR1416-131-3	(Peta/4 × TN1) × Tetep	S	S	S	S	S
-128-1		S	S	S	S	S
IR1544-238-2	IR24 × Tetep	S	S	S	S	R
-340-6		S	S	S	S	R
IR1905-27-1	IR8 × Tetep	S	S	S	S	R
IR1542-30-2	IR24 × Carreon	S	S	S	S	R
-43-2		S	S	S	S	R
IR1698-237-2	IR8/4 × Zenith	R	S	S	S	R

Table 6. Promising lines that are resistant to green leafhoppers or brown planthoppers and that have high levels of resistance to other insects and diseases.

Designation	Cross	Resistance to					
		Blast	Bacterial blight	Tungro	Grassy stunt	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR4-93-2	H-105 × Dee-geo-woo-gen	R	S	S	S	R	S
IR747B2-6	TKM-6/2 × TN1	MR	R	S	S	R	S
IR946-33-2	IR4-93-2 × H-4	R	S	S	S	R	R
IR1154-243	IR8/2 × Zenith	MR	R	S	S	R	S
IR1539-111-2	IR24 × (Mudgo × IR8)	S	S	S	S	R	R
-823-1		S	S	S	S	R	R
IR1330-3-2	(17-1 Lt × IR8) × W 1263	S	R	S	S	R	R
IR1541-76-3	IR24 × TKM-6	R	R	R	S	R	R
IR1514A-E666	IR20 × TKM-6	R	R	R	S	R	R
IR1614-110-1	IR22 × (Mudgo × IR8)	S	R	S	S	R	R
IR1628-353-1	IR24 × IR1154-243	R	S	S	S	R	R
IR1702-74-3	IR24 × PTB 18	MR	S	R	S	R	R
IR1712-195-1	IR747B2-6 × IR665-40	MR	R	S	S	R	R

lines and found one that had a good level of stem borer resistance. Other backcross lines are being screened for resistance to stem borers.

We combined grassy stunt resistance with the blast resistance of Tetep in the crosses IR1818, IR2031, and IR2035, with the blight resistance of IR22 in the crosses IR1825, IR2030, and IR2032, with brown planthopper resistance in the crosses IR1824, IR2034, IR2035, and IR2039, and with tungro resistance in the crosses IR2061, IR2076, and IR2151.

Bacterial blight. Plant pathologists developed an improved screening technique for bacterial blight and helped in screening all the breeding materials. Several sources of resistance have been used in the breeding program. IR22, TKM-6, Zenith, Wase Aikoku, Sigadis, and W 1263 combined well and produced resistant lines with good plant type (Table 4). Resistance to bacterial blight was combined with blast resistance in the crosses IR1480, IR1529, IR1698, IR1833, IR2030, IR2037, IR2061, and IR2151 with tungro resistance in the crosses IR1541, IR2046, IR2053, and IR2054 and with resistance to green leafhopper and brown planthopper in the crosses IR1614 and IR1707. Several new sources of resistance to bacterial blight, such as Hashikalmi, Semora Mangga, and BJ 1, were brought into the crossing program.

Blast. Blast-resistant lines were selected from several crosses (Table 5) with Dawn, Kambaungan, Tetep, Carreon, and Zenith as the main sources of resistance. Blast-resistant lines were also obtained from *O. nivara* backcrosses. New sources of resistance, such as Memoriaka and Kataktara, were used in the crossing program. Blast resistance was combined with bacterial blight resistance, tungro resistance, and resistance to green leafhopper and brown plant-

hopper in several crosses such as IR2031, IR2034, IR2039, IR2061, IR2071, and IR2151.

Leafhoppers and planthoppers. We made considerable progress toward combining resistance to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers with disease resistance and improved plant type (Table 6). We used two distinct sources of resistance to the leafhopper and two to the planthopper. Thus, resistance to brown planthopper is governed by the recessive gene, *bph 2*, in IR4-93-2, IR946-33-2, IR1154-243, IR1628-353-1, and IR1702-74-3. In IR747B2-6, IR1539-111, IR1539-823, IR1330-3, IR1614-110, and IR1712-195, however, resistance is conveyed by the dominant gene *Bph 1*. Resistance to the green leafhopper in IR1702-74-3 is conveyed by *Glh 1*, while *Glh 3* is present in the other resistant lines. Resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers and resistance to major diseases have been combined in the crosses IR2031, IR2034, IR2039, IR2061, IR2071, and IR2151.

Stem borers. Entomologists have screened rice varieties for stem borer resistance under field conditions for years, but only varieties with moderate levels of resistance have been found. Several of these have been used in the breeding program.

Entomologists screened about 200 dwarf selections and varieties that have improved plant type for stem borer resistance. Several semidwarf selections were identified which were as resistant as the tall parents (Table 7). These lines inherited their resistance from Siam 29, TKM-6, Tadukan, BJ 1, Tetep, and *O. nivara*. Resistance seems to be polygenic. Because the resistant parents are unrelated, we may assume that they have different genes for resistance.

We began a cooperative breeding program with the entomologists to consolidate genes from

Table 7. Promising lines that are moderately resistant to stem borers.

Designation	Cross	Resistance to					
		Blast	Bacterial blight	Tungro	Grassy stunt	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
IR6-156	Siam 29 × Dee-geo-woo-gen	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR1514A-E666	IR20 × TKM-6	R	R	R	S	R	R
IR1561-228-3	(IR8 × Tadukan) × (TKM-6/2 × TN1)	MR	R	S	S	R	S
IR1365-83-2	(Peta/3 × TN1) × BJ 1	S	MS	R	S	S	R
IR1416-131-3	(Peta/4 × TN1) × Tetep	R	S	S	S	S	S
IR1721-11-13	IR24/3 × <i>O. nivara</i>	R	S	MR	R	S	R

different sources into one or two lines, building up the level of stem borer resistance. We are using a diallel selective mating scheme using several semidwarf lines listed in Table 7. We expect that the genes for resistance to other major diseases and insects will be carried along in the selection process, allowing us to develop varieties with high resistance to stem borers as well as to other insects and diseases.

Multiple resistance. Sources of resistance to various diseases and insects have been combined with plants of improved type. Many of the resulting lines have good grain quality and high yield potential. These lines have been intercrossed to combine resistance to major diseases and insects. Early generation lines from the newer crosses will be tested for yield next year.

Many advanced generation lines were evaluated for yield and disease and insect resistance during the year. Table 8 shows agronomic traits, grain quality, and yield potential of promising advanced lines. IR1529-680-3 is a high-yielding line with sturdy stems and resistance to lodging. It resembles IR8 in plant type, and has translucent grains with excellent appearance. It is resistant to blast, bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, and green leafhopper, and is moderately

resistant to tungro virus. In trials in farmers' fields during the 1972 wet season, it showed some drought tolerance.

Other promising selections being tested are IR1541-76-3, IR1541-102-7, and IR1514A-E666. They are more resistant to diseases and insects than IR1529-680-3, but have a lower yield potential. They resemble IR20 in plant type and in size, shape, and appearance of grain. These selections are resistant to blast, bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, tungro virus, green leafhopper, and brown planthopper. Another promising selection of excellent plant type and grain quality is IR1480-116-3. It is resistant to blast, bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, and green leafhopper, and is moderately resistant to tungro.

Protein content. We have taken several steps to improve the protein breeding program. To minimize environmental variability, we standardized the evaluation systems so that all plant spacing used in all nurseries is now 20 × 20 cm. All fertilizer is applied as basal in four equal parts to assure uniform distribution. The observational yield trial was replaced by multiple-row pedigree nurseries (three rows for F₃, four rows for F₄, and five rows for F₅ and subsequent

Table 8. Agronomic traits, grain quality, and yield of some promising selections and varieties grown in replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1972 (D) and wet (W) seasons.

Designation	Cross	Grain yield (t/ha)		Maturity ^a (days)		Plant ht (cm)		Tillers (no.)		Wet Season lodging (%)	Gel. temp. ^b	Amylose (%)
		D	W	D	W	D	W	D	W			
IR8	Peta × Dee-geo-woo-gen	7.8	5.7	135	130	98	92	13	11	0	L	27
IR20	(Peta/3 × TN1) × TKM 6	7.7	5.0	125	130	100	106	13	12	100	I/L	27
C4-63	Peta × BPI-76	6.5	4.7	135	135	120	122	11	10	100	I/L	24
IR759-133-1	IR8 × (Peta/3 × Dawn)	7.1	4.4	130	135	90	92	13	10	0	L	29
IR1093-148-3	IR8 × Intan	7.8	4.5	135	135	103	110	11	10	75	L	27
IR1416-131-5	(Peta/4 × TN1) × Tetep	8.0	4.4	135	140	89	92	17	13	40	L	28
IR1364-37-3	(Peta/3 × TN1) × HR 21	8.9	4.6	130	140	92	100	14	11	18	I	29
IR1480-116-3	IR790-28 × IR825-28-4	—	5.2	—	125	—	112	—	11	—	L	26
IR1487-194-5	IR127-80-1 × IR442-2-50	7.6	5.0	130	125	85	94	14	13	0	I/L	27
IR1539-823-1	IR24 × (Mudgo × IR8)	8.3	5.1	135	135	106	105	11	11	0	L	29
IR1529-430-3	(Sigadis/2 × TN1) × IR24	8.6	5.3	130	125	92	97	12	12	0	L	20
-680-3		8.3	5.9	130	130	87	99	10	11	0	L	29
-949-3		9.0	5.4	130	135	97	103	13	10	0	L	29
IR1514A-E666	IR20 × TKM-6	7.3	5.4	120	120	92	96	17	14	33	I	28
IR1541-102-6	IR24 × TKM-6	8.1	5.4	125	125	92	94	15	13	50	L	27
-76-3		—	5.4	—	125	—	103	—	12	10	I/L	27
IR1561-228-3	(IR8 × Tadukan) × (TKM 6/2 × TN1)	8.1	6.0	110	110	81	91	18	15	0	L	29

^aSeeding to harvest. ^bI = intermediate, L = low.

generations). Three to six plants are taken from selected lines and certain uniform lines are bulk harvested. Both the plant selections and bulk seed are analyzed and those extremely low in protein are discarded. The bulk selections then go to carefully managed, replicated yield trials and the plant selections are grown in the next pedigree nursery. Promising lines are used in the crossing program and concurrently screened for disease and insect resistance. The agronomy department evaluates exceptionally promising lines at several fertility levels.

Potential high-protein materials are produced in three ways. The first is a conventional crossing program in which promising protein lines are crossed to other promising lines as well as to the best disease- and insect-resistant materials.

The second is a backcrossing program designed to incorporate disease and insect resistance into the high-protein material in the shortest possible time. The best high-protein lines are used as recurrent parents and the best lines for disease and insect resistance as donor parents. IR480-5-9 has been used as the recurrent parent in this program.

The third is the use of diallel selective mating populations (N. F. Jensen, Cornell Univ.) formed by making all possible crosses among several (usually five) high-protein breeding lines and then making all possible crosses among the subsequent F_1 hybrids. Individual plants with

high protein content from such populations are intermated through several cycles as a form of recurrent selection to concentrate different genetic factors for protein.

In the high-protein yield trials in the 1972 wet season, we evaluated 138 lines and discarded 98. All those retained had significantly higher protein content than IR8; 19 of them yielded comparably. A few lines outperformed IR480-5-9, the standard high-protein check variety, in both protein content and yield.

Lines such as IR480-5-9, IR160-27-3, IR1103-15-8, and IR1163-153-2, which have previously appeared high in protein, continued to show some advantage (Table 9), but they yielded somewhat less than IR8.

The promising new lines include EPJ1-13-B-10 and EPJ1-13-B-55 from Bangladesh. IR1126-39-3, IR1550-16-2, and IR1552-57-2 were also noteworthy although yields of the latter two were not satisfactory. None of these lines are resistant to the major diseases and insect pests of the Philippines.

Grain quality. We are now emphasizing the development of varieties with intermediate amylose content. Such varieties seem to be preferred in tropical Asia. Crosses of high amylose types with low amylose types do not yield true breeding intermediates. So we are using varieties such as BPI 121-407, a radiation-induced dwarf developed by the Philippine

Table 9. Brown rice protein and grain yield of varieties and breeding lines in replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1972.

Designation	Cross	Dry season				Wet season			
		Protein		Yield		Protein		Yield	
		%	Index ^a	t/ha	Index ^b	%	Index ^a	t/ha	Index ^b
L4, (1915)-12	IR8 mutant	8.0	107	5.6	73	8.1	109	4.6	92
EPJ1-13-B-10	IR8 × DA31	9.2	124	6.7	88	9.6	120	5.0	96
-13-B-55		9.7	131	6.2	81	10.2	128	4.7	90
IR160-27-3	Nahng Mon S-4 × TN1	7.7	103	6.8	89	9.3	116	5.0	95
IR1103-15-8	IR8 × Chowsung	10.3	139	5.6	69	10.2	142	3.8	72
IR1126-39-3	Khao Med Lek/2 × (Peta/3 × TN1)	9.8	131	5.6	74	8.8	122	5.2	99
IR1163-153-2	IR8/2 × BPI-76	8.5	116	7.3	93	8.4	114	4.5	89
IR1550-16-2	(Nahng Mon S-4 × TN1) × DV 133	—	—	—	—	8.6	124	4.3	88
IR1552-57-2	(Nahng Mon S-4 × TN1) × Crosa 2	—	—	—	—	9.2	124	4.4	88
IR480-5-9 ^c	Nahng Mon S-4/2 × TN1	8.6	116	6.0	79	9.3	126	4.1	81
IR8 ^d	Peta × Dee-geo-woo-gen	7.4 ^e	—	7.6 ^e	—	7.4 ^e	—	5.0 ^e	—
IR20 ^d	(Peta/3 × TN1) × TKM 6	8.3	112	7.8	102	8.9	103	5.0	88

^aProtein content in relation to protein content of IR8 grown in same trial (protein content of IR8 = 100). ^bYield in relation to yield of IR8 grown in same trial (yield of IR8 = 100). ^cHigh protein check. ^dCheck. ^eMean of six trials.

Table 10. Agronomic characteristics and grain yield of early maturing selections. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Cross	Maturity ^a (days)	Tillers (no.)	Height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
IR747B2-6	TKM 6/2 × TN1	101	15	96	4.1
IR833-6-2	IR262-43 × Gam Pai 15	108	10	96	4.9
IR1561-228-3	IR579-48 × IR747B2-6	108	15	91	6.0
-243-5		108	14	92	4.9
-250-2		108	14	98	5.0
IR1712-80-1	IR747B2-6 × IR665-40	105	14	99	4.7
-95-1		105	13	86	4.3
-100-1		109	12	88	5.3
-217-2		109	19	94	5.9
IR8 (check)	Peta × Dee-geo-woo-gen	130	11	95	5.3
IR20 (check)	(Peta/3 × TN1) × TKM 6	125	11	104	5.1

^aSeeding to harvest.

Bureau of Plant Industry. BPI 121-407 has high yield potential and intermediate amylose content, but is susceptible to diseases and insects. We crossed it with resistant lines and selected many lines with intermediate amylose content and resistance to blast, bacterial blight, green leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers. More crosses are being made to incorporate tungro resistance into these lines.

Other sources of intermediate amylose content being used in the crossing program are C4-63 and IR480-5-9.

Growth duration. Photoperiod-insensitive semidwarfs with growth durations of 120 to 125 days adapt well to areas with good water control, but not to large river deltas where farmers plant traditional varieties which have long growth durations (more than 160 days) and are generally sensitive to photoperiod. Such varieties flower in late October and are harvested after the water recedes in November or December. Water which stands in the field for 5 months or more prevents the harvesting of early, photoperiod-insensitive varieties.

We are trying to develop photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties with improved plant type, disease and insect resistance, and superior grain quality. We are crossing resistant lines with photoperiod-sensitive semidwarfs. These lines (IR793 and IR1060) were developed from crosses between IR8 and Wagwag, a Philippine variety with high grain quality.

Many areas with good water management need early, high-yielding varieties with growth durations of 100 to 105 days. We have selected and tested short duration types from crosses involving TKM-6, Tadukan, Zenith, Khao

Dawk Mali, and other varieties for several years. Early maturing selections that produce many tillers in the early stages of growth yield as well as high-yielding dwarfs that mature in 120 to 130 days.

We compared several early selections with IR8 and IR20 (Table 10). The best selections came from IR1561 and IR1712; they have excellent grain quality and considerable disease and insect resistance. Their chief weakness is susceptibility to virus diseases.

One early maturing IR1561 selection was crossed with an IR1737 line (IR24/4 × *O. nivara*), which is resistant to grassy stunt. The F₁ was crossed with IR833-6-3, a waxy line that matures early and is tungro resistant. The early maturing waxy and non-waxy lines from this cross are resistant to both the viruses and their vectors, as well as to blast and bacterial blight.

Cold tolerance. Cold irrigation water (snow melt) or low ambient temperatures can adversely affect the rice plant at almost all stages of growth. Symptoms include poor germination, seedling discoloration, reduced seedling vigor, poor tillering, stunting, delayed heading, partial panicle exertion, degeneration of panicle tips, sterility, and delayed maturity.

Farmers in many rice-growing areas at higher latitudes and elevations still depend on traditional rice types because high-yielding dwarf varieties are not tolerant to cold. Breeding progress has been slow because of the lack of a reliable method of artificial screening for cold tolerance, inadequate supervision of natural screening nurseries because of their geographic locations, and the poor combining ability of the source material used.

Table 11. Composition of the first International Rice Yield Nursery

Designation	Cross	Source
Chandina	(Peta/3 × TN1) × TKM 6	Bangladesh
BG 66-1	IR8-24-6 × Remadja	Sri Lanka
Cica 4	IR8 × (MCVA × I-geo-tze)	Colombia ^a
P738-97-3-1	IR8 × [(MCVA × I-geo-tze) × (IR8 × Tadukan)]	Colombia ^a
P753-40-3-1	IR8 × [(MCVA × I-geo-tze) × (IR8/2 × Pankhari 203)]	Colombia ^a
Jaya	TN1 × T 141	India
RP 79-23	IR8 × N 22	India
RP 4-14	T 90 × IR8	India
CR12-178	IR8 × CR 1014	India
Ratna	TKM 6 × IR8	India
IET 1039	T 90 × IR8	India
IET 1991	GEB 24 × TN1	India
Pelita I	IR5 × Syntha	Indonesia
Navolato A71	IR8 × Tadukan	Mexico
KT-29	Chianan 2 × Arulno	Nepal
IR269-26-3	Bluebelle/2 × TN1	Nigeria ^b
IR838-7-2	D.C. Wui × BPI-76	Nigeria ^b
IR578-95-1	IR8 × (Sigadis × TN1)	Nigeria ^b
IR630-27	IR8 × IR5	Nigeria ^b
IR841-36-2	(Peta/3 × TN1) × Khao Dawk Mali	Pakistan
Naylamp	IR8 × (MCVA × I-geo-tze)	Peru
Huallaga	Peta/2 - TN1 × Leb Mue Nahng	Peru
C4-63	Peta × BPI-76	Philippines ^c
IR1514A-E666	IR20 × TKM 6	Philippines ^d
IR1529-680-3	IR24 × (Sigadis/2 × TN1)	Philippines ^d
IR1541-76-3	IR24 × TKM 6	Philippines ^d
IR1561-228-3	(IR8 × Tadukan) × (TKM 6/2 × TN1)	Philippines ^d
IR1721-14-6	IR24/3 × <i>O. nivara</i>	Philippines ^d
Chianung-sen-yu No. 6	IR8 × TKM 6	Taiwan
BKN 6517-9-2	P.N. 16 × Sigadis	Thailand
BKN 6652-249-1	(Peta/3 × TN1) × P. N. 16	Thailand
BKN 6809-74-40	(CNT 3176 × W 1256) × RD 2	Thailand
IR8	Peta × Dee-geo-woo-gen	check
IR20	(Peta/3 × TN1) × TKM 6	check

^aCentro Internacional Agricultura Tropical. ^bInternational Institute of Tropical Agriculture. ^cUniversity of the Philippines College of Agriculture. ^dInternational Rice Research Institute.

New sources of cold tolerance from Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Australia were crossed with high-yielding dwarfs this year. The F₁ generation was grown during the wet season. The F₂ generation will be grown at an elevation of 2,000 m in the Mountain Province, Philippines. This location has cool ambient temperatures throughout the year.

International cooperation. We continued to cooperate with breeding programs throughout the world. The International Rice Yield Nursery was established to provide cooperating programs with basic information on yield and disease and insect resistance of their best varieties and breeding lines under varied environmental conditions. This nursery will also facilitate the exchange of breeding material.

The nursery is composed of about 30 entries and two check varieties (Table 11). After multi-

plication at IRRI during the 1973 dry season, seed will be distributed to cooperators. Brazil, Cuba, Sierra Leone, and Vietnam will participate without contributing varieties.

During 1972, IRRI sent 6,865 seed packages of breeding lines to research workers in 69 countries and territories. These lines are tested for adaptability to local conditions and some become named varieties. Others are used as parents in national breeding programs. Nineteen breeding lines developed at IRRI have been released as commercial varieties by other countries (Table 12). Four of these lines were named during 1972. In Fiji, IR480-5-9 was named Ajral, in Peru, IR930-31-10 was named Chancay and IR442-2-50 was named Huallaga, and in Bangladesh IR272-4-1-2 was named Mala.

The variety Tongil (IR667-98), an indica-japonica hybrid developed by Korean scientists

in collaboration with IRRI, was grown on more than 200,000 hectares in 1972—about 17 percent of Korea's rice land. The average yield of Tongil was reported to be over 4 t/ha of milled rice, compared with the national average of 3.2 t/ha. This indicates the superiority of the dwarf indica plant type over the japonica type which has been traditionally grown in regions such as Korea.

IR579-48-1, a sister selection of IR22, is early maturing and has excellent grain quality. It was earlier named Nilo 11 in El Salvador and Palman 579 in India. It is yielding well in extensive tests in Egypt.

Many IRRI breeding lines were tested by Vietnamese scientists in replicated and observational yield trials in 1971 and 1972 in a cooperative project. Two promising selections, IR1529-680-3 and IR1561-228-3, are being evaluated on farmers' fields.

Varieties named at IRRI continued their impact throughout the world. IR20 is widely grown in the Philippines, Vietnam, Bangladesh, and India. IR22 is a recommended variety in several Latin American countries, in the Philippines, and in Vietnam. A reselection was named Navolato A71 in Mexico. IR22 is being tested on a large scale in Egypt. IR24 was named Mum Mai and approved for general cultivation in Fiji.

Upland-lowland crosses. Comparative studies of upland and lowland varieties during 1970 and 1971 showed the need to combine desirable features from both to improve upland rice. The breeding objectives are early vegetative vigor, moderately long and slightly droopy leaves, intermediate plant height, a vigorous root system with many long and thick roots, high tillering capacity, early maturity, tolerance to drought, quick recovery from water stress, tolerance to problem soils, resistance to major diseases and insects, good grain quality, and stable, potentially high yields.

We continued to search for promising parents among upland and lowland materials. In the dry season we tested 46 upland types from Malaysia and 39 varieties from Laos. We retested the promising ones in the wet season. During the wet season, we tested 201 upland varieties, mostly from West Africa, Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam. We included deep-water types from Bangladesh and Thailand that

can survive variable soil moisture during the early growth period. Breeding lines from IRRI and from Thailand were also tested under upland conditions at two seeding dates.

Among the traditional upland types, Kantong, Osog, 63-83, and Khao Lo were resistant to both drought and to bacterial leaf blight. Khao Lo was early maturing but produced few tillers. The IRRI breeding lines IR1480-190-3, IR1487-194-3, IR1541-121-2, and IR1529-680-3 showed promise.

We made 39 crosses between upland and lowland varieties in 1972 to bring together features essential for upland rice improvement. As upland parents we used the varieties OS4, OS6, E425, Rikuto Norin 21, M1-48, C22-51, and Bluebonnet 50. Lowland varieties repeatedly used as parents were Pelita I/2, Sigadis, PTB 28, IR272-4-1, IR442-2-58, IR1364-37-3, IR1529-680-3, and IR1541-76-3. Some F_1 hybrids will be crossed with another parent or another F_1 hybrid to develop three-way or double crosses.

Intensive selection for characteristics essential for upland culture was continued in bulk populations. Recognizable features continued to segregate distinctly through the F_5 generation. Selected F_4 plants were grown as F_5 lines in both upland and lowland culture to provide comparative data on tillering capacity, straw strength, and maturity. We grew about 160 F_5 plants from the wet season upland planting for seed propagation.

F_2 progenies from four three-way crosses were grown for selection in the wet season. Because either IR5 or an upland variety from Africa or Japan was included as a parent in each cross, the F_2 plants were generally more drought tolerant than either of the semidwarf parents, IR8 or IR841-67-1.

Bulk samples selected from the single crosses were sent to Nigeria and Indonesia for selection under local conditions.

Upland yield trials. Thirty-one lowland and 11 upland rice types were tested in the dry season under three cultural methods: upland, drill-flood, and transplant-flood. The upland plants were periodically surface-flooded assuring only enough water to maintain plant growth to maturity. This upland cultural system also permitted us to identify drought resistance by

Table 12. Varieties named from IRRI lines by other agencies.

Name	IRRI line	Cross	Country where line was named
Pankaj	IR5-114-3	Peta × Tangkai Rotan	India
Bahagia	IR5-278	Peta × Tangkai Rotan	Malaysia
Mehran 69	IR6-156-2	Siam 29 × Dee-geo-woo-gen	Pakistan
CS 2	IR160-25-1	Nahng Mon S-4 × TN1	Ivory Coast
Sinaloa A68	IR160-27-4	Nahng Mon S-4 × TN1	Mexico
RD 2	IR253-4	Gam Pai 15/2 × TN1	Thailand
CS 3	IR253-16-1	Gam Pai 15/2 × TN1	Ivory Coast
CS 1	IR262-7-1	Peta/3 × TN1	Ivory Coast
IR262	IR262-43-8	Peta/3 × TN1	Sri Lanka
Mala	IR272-4-1	(CP 231 × SLO-17)/2 × Sigadis	Bangladesh
Huallaga	IR442-2-50	(Peta/2 × TN1) × Leb Mue Nahng	Peru
Ajral	IR480-5-9	Nahng Mon S-4/2 × TN1	Fiji
IR532	IR532-1-18	IR262-24-3 × TKM 6	Sri Lanka
Chandina	IR532-1-176	IR262-24-3 × TKM 6	Bangladesh
Nilo 11	IR579-48-1	IR8 × Tadukan	El Salvador
Palman 579	IR579-48-1	IR8 × Tadukan	India
Tongil	IR667-98	IR8 × (Yukara × TN1)	Korea
Naylamp	IR930-2-6	IR8 × IR12-178	Peru
Cica 4	IR930-31	IR8 × IR12-178	Colombia
Chancay	IR930-31-10	IR8 × IR12-178	Peru

observing water-stress symptoms and root system development. The upland trial was fertilized with 90 kg/ha N.

The grain yields of both upland and lowland types were generally low under the restricted water supply of the upland cultural system. The lowland varieties Hashikalmi, Lal Nakanda, PTB 10, and PTB 28 which are tall and early maturing (from 100 to 120 days) produced the highest yields, from 1.1 to 1.6 t/ha. C 12 was the only late-maturing (157 days) entry to produce more than 1 t/ha. Most IRRI semidwarf varieties or lines produced under 1 t/ha. IR5 had no yield because it was late maturing and the plants were severely damaged by bacterial blight and sheath blight. No upland varieties yielded well. Rikuto Norin 21 produced 0.7 t/ha while OS4 and M1-48 yielded between 0.3 and 0.5 t/ha.

In the drill-flood and transplant-flood tests, the upland types yielded from 2.2 to 5.2 t/ha. C 22-51 yielded better than any other upland type, partly because of its high panicle number. The semidwarfs yielded from 3.1 to 5.6 t/ha while the Hashikalmi, Lal Nakanda, and PTB lines yielded from 2.3 to 4.7 t/ha. C 12 produced over 5 t/ha.

In the wet season, upland yield trials were planted on June 20, July 14, and August 11. They were fertilized with 90 kg/ha N, but were not

irrigated. The June 20 planting grew through an unusually wet period. Although the seven upland and 13 lowland varieties differed in maturity, none suffered from water stress. Both types yielded well, except for varieties that had poor seedling stand or severe leaf diseases (Table 13). IR1541-102-3 and IR442-2-58 produced the top yields, about 4.1 t/ha, and IR5 had 3.9 t/ha. Among the upland varieties, C 22-51 yielded 3.4 t/ha while OS4, M1-48, and Palawan yielded from 2.1 to 2.4 t/ha.

In the July 14 upland planting, a 17-day dry spell in October caused extreme leaf rolling, leaf wilting, and spikelet sterility among drought susceptible entries such as C 22-51, IR272-4-1, IR442-2-50, IR442-2-58, IR1541-102-3, and C 12. Neither wilting nor panicle sterility was a problem among the drought-resistant entries such as OS4, M1-48, and IR5. As a result, IR5 and M1-48 produced more than 2 t/ha, while most drought-susceptible varieties produced less than 1 t/ha. The yield of C 12, 1.6 t/ha, was lower than that of IR8 or the early maturing Rikuto Norin 21. IR442-2-50 and IR442-2-58 were affected by sheath blight and neck blast as well as by drought.

In the drill-flood planting sown on July 24 and fertilized with 60 kg/ha N, most upland types yielded from 1.7 to 3.0 t/ha while the semidwarf

Table 13. Grain yield of upland and lowland varieties in three upland experiments and one drill-flood trial. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)			Drill-flood ^d
	Upland			
	June 20 ^a	July 14 ^b	Aug. 11 ^c	
<i>Upland varieties</i>				
Rikuto Norin 21	0.3	1.78	0.46	2.8
OS4	2.1	1.48	0.78	2.4
Moroberekan	1.4	1.52	1.10	1.7
M1-48	2.4	2.36	1.11	1.9
Palawan	2.3	1.06	1.14	3.7
C 22-51	3.4	0.60	1.77	4.3
Bluebonnet 50	2.2	1.32	1.11	3.1
<i>Lowland varieties</i>				
TN1	2.8	0.55	1.41	3.7
IR5	3.9	2.51	2.37	5.0
IR8	2.7	1.82	1.68	3.7
IR272-4-1	3.4	0.56	1.12	2.88
IR442-2-58	4.1	0.48	1.20	2.3
IR442-2-50	—	0.25	0.81	1.3
IR661-1-170	2.1	0.58	—	2.4
IR841-67-1	3.8	0.36	2.22	4.5
IR1541-102-3	4.2	0.75	1.45	4.2
BG34-11	0.9	0.97	0.50	3.7
Hashikalmi	0.7	1.58	1.14	4.2
C 12	2.9	1.58	1.29	2.8
IR1541-102-6	3.2	0.51	1.09	4.4

^aNon-replicated, 1806 mm rainfall during growing period.

^bReplicated, 1534 mm rainfall during growing period.

^cNon-replicated, 935 mm rainfall during growing period.

^dNon-replicated, planted July 24.

lowland types yielded from 3.7 to 4.5 t/ha, except those heavily infected by bacterial blight or neck blast.

Rainy weather in July delayed the third upland planting to August 11. The shortening daylength reduced the height of many varieties. Low precipitation in October and November also affected drought-susceptible entries. IR5 and IR841-67-1 had the highest yields, slightly over 2 t/ha. Most other lowland types yielded slightly more than 1 t/ha. Upland entries produced from 1.1 to 1.7 t/ha, except for Rikuto Norin 21 and OS4, which were infected by bacterial blight.

The 1972 results verify the findings of two preceding years that in upland culture the drought-tolerant upland varieties produce low yields that are rather stable even when droughts occur. The semidwarfs and lowland types with intermediate stature, on the other hand, can produce higher yields with good soil moisture

and little disease. But during droughts, only those short-statured selections with drought tolerance and disease resistance can yield as well as the upland types. IR5 performs well during the wet season because its growth duration is elastic, allowing it to use late rains. But it is not suited for the dry season because it is susceptible to sheath blight and bacterial blight, which generally strike during the late dry season. The subsistence upland rice farmers prefer the traditional upland types because they produce a lower—but more dependable—yield than do the more variable improved varieties.

DROUGHT TOLERANCE AND UPLAND YIELD

We continued to search for drought-tolerant material from the IRRI germ plasm collection to use as parents. We measured root and shoot characteristics of materials grown in the replicated and observational trials to identify component characters related to drought resistance and to yield performance in upland culture.

Water stress at different growth stages. Symptoms of water stress vary in drought-susceptible varieties according to growth stages. Water stress during tillering is indicated by extreme rolling of the leaf blade, reduced leaf size, dark-green foliage, and accelerated death of the lower leaves. Under extreme water stress at flowering the leaf blades, or the glumes on the panicle, may lose chlorophyll and die. Stress during later vegetative growth reduces plant height and delays heading. Stress at heading often protracts the period of panicle exertion. The lower spikelets of panicles finally exerted are smaller than the apical ones. Water stress during panicle development or during grain ripening often causes degeneration of apical spikelets on the panicle, high spikelet sterility, and low grain weight.

These yield-reducing manifestations seem to be symptoms of water stress in a susceptible genotype rather than factors that cause drought susceptibility. The drought-resistant varieties, such as Rikuto Norin 21, OS4, and M1-48, continue to grow and develop normally during stress. They retain leaf sizes, heading dates, plant

Table 14. Heading dates and 100-grain weights of drought-tolerant and drought-susceptible varieties. The upland planting was sown on August 11 and the drill-flood planting was sown on July 24. IRRI, 1972.

Designation	Reaction to drought ^a	Upland vs. drill-flood	
		Difference in heading dates	100-grain-wt ratio
<i>Upland varieties</i>			
Rikuto Norin 21	R	0	0.84
OS4	R	12 ^b	0.56
M1-48	R	1	1.04
Palawan	R	10 ^b	0.75
C 22-51	MS	9	0.80
<i>Lowland varieties</i>			
IR5	R	12 ^b	0.85
IR8	MR	10	0.88
IR442-2-50	MS	10	0.78
IR442-2-58	MS	12	0.84
IR1541-102-3	S	14	0.78
C 12	MS	10	0.85
TN1	S	15	0.79

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bA difference of 2 to 3 days is a more comparable difference between upland and transplant-flood plantings because over several seasons this variety headed earlier than others when grown in drill-flood cultures.

heights, grain weights, and percentage panicle fertility corresponding with those under no stress conditions.

Leaf canopy and reaction to drought. The long, droopy leaves of many upland varieties might contribute to drought tolerance because they form a leaf canopy, reducing evaporation of soil moisture. Light transmission ratios measured at 60 days after seeding were low for IR5, C22-51, IR272-4-1, IR442-2-50, and IR841-67-1. Of these varieties, however, only IR5 did not show severe water stress symptoms during the height of a drought at 68 days after seeding. The low tillering varieties Rikuto Norin 21, OS4, and Palawan, on the other hand, had high light transmission ratios but showed no severe water stress. Thus a spreading leaf canopy does not appear to contribute much to drought tolerance.

Leaf structure and drought resistance. Thick leaf blades in wheat have been reported to indicate drought resistance. We estimated rice leaf thickness by determining dry weight of whole leaf blades per square centimeter 60 days after seeding under upland conditions. Drought-tolerant upland varieties, such as Palawan and M1-48, had the highest values. But the drought-

susceptible lowland types such as IR1531-186-1, IR1541-102-3, and IR661-1-170, had almost equally high values. On the other hand, IR5, Taichung Native 1, IR442-2-50, IR442-2-58, and C 12 had low values.

The varietal differences in leaf dry weight were much smaller in the drill-flood planting. We could not relate the varietal differences in leaf dry weight to the known differences in drought tolerance.

Water stress and reproductive processes. By comparing the August 11 upland planting (which suffered drought around mid-October and late November) and the July 24 drill-flood planting, we obtained information on how water stress affects heading. The late November dry period occurred during flowering and grain ripening. In the drought-susceptible types, such as Taichung Native 1, C 22-51, and IR1541-102-3, water stress delayed heading dates and lowered 100-grain weights (Table 14).

Root system and drought tolerance. By weighing dried root samples taken from the upland planting in the dry season, we found that the drought-tolerant upland varieties produced more roots per unit area than susceptible varieties. Drought-tolerant varieties tended to have deep roots, large numbers of roots, large diameter of the roots, and high proportion of thick roots.

Abundant rain fell on the wet season experiments during vegetative growth, so varietal differences in root characteristics were small. Nevertheless, Rikuto Norin 21 had the longest and most dense roots. The roots of OS4, M1-48, Palawan, and IR5 were among the thickest of 21 varieties sampled. The drought-susceptible Taichung Native 1, IR272-4-1, and IR1541-102-6 had few and rather thin roots. IR8, IR442-2-58, and IR841-67-1 had roots intermediate between those of the other two groups.

RICE GERM PLASM BANK

During 1972, IRRI received 4,186 seed samples, mainly from India, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Nepal, Senegal, and Thailand.

Special grants from several agencies permitted field collection in several countries of Southeast Asia by IRRI staff and local workers. The teams

1. Distribution of parents and F_2 grains by brown rice protein content in two low $\times$ high crosses. Horizontal lines show the range of the parent samples about the means (dotted circles).

collected 400 samples in Ceylon, 1,400 in Indonesia, 700 in the Khmer Republic, 200 in South Vietnam, and 125 in the Philippines. The IRRI collection now has 23,000 cultivars.

We responded to 83 foreign requests and sent abroad 2,500 seed packages of cultivars. From the collection of wild species and genetic testers, we supplied 610 seed packages to 15 institutions in eight countries.

We sent duplicate samples from recently harvested seeds of 2,000 accessions to the U.S. National Seed Storage Laboratory for safe-keeping.

We supplied 2,700 seed packages to various research departments of the institute for experimental use.

During the year 5,700 plots were planted for seed multiplication, description, or rejuvenation. We completed the characterization of over 2,000 accessions, bringing the number of recorded varieties to 14,242.

Twice this year we checked the seed viability of control varieties in the cold storage room (3 to 4°C, 25 to 40% relative humidity). The germination of 10-year-old Peta and Siam 29 seeds re-

mained over 90 percent, while that of Chianan 8 seeds was about 50 percent. In an experiment we found that viability of seeds of PI 215936 (Tainan Yu 487) stored for 3 years in an air-conditioned room with no dehydrating agent dropped to 44 percent, while seeds stored with silica gel in air-tight jars in the cold room retained 95 percent viability. This indicates the need to periodically rejuvenate the seeds of japonica varieties sooner than those of indica varieties.

GENETICS AND CYTOGENETICS

Inheritance of protein content. We determined single-grain protein content of F_2 seeds from six crosses of high-protein and low-protein selections in reciprocal combinations. The protein content of brown rice kernels was continuously distributed in the F_2 generations of all crosses, indicating multiple gene action expressed as metaxenia. In most crosses the majority of F_2 kernels ranged between the two parental means of protein content, with more at the low end of the distribution. Few F_2 kernels had higher protein content than that of the high-protein parent in each cross, but some had lower protein content than that of the low-protein parent (fig. 1).

We found no marked difference in F_2 distribution patterns between reciprocal combinations of the same crosses. But five crosses of high-protein female $\times$ low-protein male produced a few extreme segregates with higher protein content than the extreme segregates of the corresponding reciprocal cross. These distributions suggest that several pairs of dominant alleles control low protein content and that the cumulative action of recessive genes causes high protein content. When different recessive genes are recombined in one F_2 seed, its protein content may be as high as that of the high-protein parent or higher.

Tillering rate. We studied genetic control of tillering in two crosses involving parents with contrasting tiller numbers, maturities, heights, and panicle features. The crosses were T56-1-6 $\times$ IR747B2-6-3 and IR127-80-1 $\times$ IR747B2-6-3. Both T56 and IR127 lines were medium tall, medium maturing, and lower in tiller number

2. Range of variations in four parents, F_2 plants of six single crosses, and F_2 plants of three double crosses. The circle or dot represents population mean; the horizontal line, the range of variation. $P_1 = \text{IR332-2-10}$; $P_2 = \text{IR127-80-1}$; $P_3 = \text{IR781-184-2}$; $P_4 = \text{IR747B2-6-3}$.

than the early maturing IR747B line. Genetic analysis was based on populations of the two parents, F_1 hybrids, two backcrosses, and F_2 plants grown in the dry season.

Variability in tiller number was most marked at 48 days after seeding. Tiller number changed most between 48 and 62 days after seeding. The number of panicles varied more than the number of tillers at other stages of vegetative growth, however. At 48 days after seeding, the F_2 variance in tiller number was largely additive in $\text{IR127} \times \text{IR747}$ and mostly non-additive in $\text{T56} \times \text{IR747}$. The non-additive variance comprised dominance effects and dominance $\times$ dominance effects.

The rate of tiller number change in both crosses between 48 and 62 days after seeding appeared to be controlled mainly by non-additive effects. Dominance and non-allelic interaction caused the bulk of the genetic variation.

Panicle number appeared to be controlled largely by additive effects in both crosses. In $\text{T56} \times \text{IR747}$, the rate of change in panicle number between 48 and 62 days after seeding was negatively correlated with grain yield and positively correlated with the period from seeding to heading.

Heritability estimates for tiller number and rate of change also differed for the two crosses, even though the IR747 line was a common parent. The estimated heritability for panicle number ranged from 31 to 40 percent for the two crosses.

Intercrossing F_1 hybrids. Last year, to assess the relative range of segregation in different cross combinations and to identify useful segregates with both extremely early maturity and high tillering ability, we intercrossed four selections that differ markedly in tillering ability, plant height, maturity, panicle length, and spikelet features to produce six single-cross and three double-cross F_1 hybrids. Their performance compared with that of the four parents was described in the 1971 annual report.

Variability in F_2 populations. In the 1972 dry season, we grew the F_2 progeny and found that tiller number was most variable at 60 days after seeding in the $\text{IR332} \times \text{IR747}$ single cross and next most variable in the double cross of $(\text{IR332} \times \text{IR127}) \times (\text{IR781} \times \text{IR747})$. On the average, we found more transgressive segregates with tillering number exceeding that of IR747 in the double crosses than in the single crosses (fig. 2). We observed transgressive segregation for extremely early plants in all three double crosses but in only three of the six single crosses. All crosses, however, took only 60 days from seeding to heading—2 weeks less than the early maturing IR747 parent. An upper limit of 125 days was common to all double crosses, although we found segregates exceeding 135 days in two single crosses (fig. 2). Similarly, in our 1966 study on the basic vegetative phase, we found that the cumulative effect of several dominant *Ef* genes results in short growth duration.

The lowest limit of plant height in all crosses

was 50 cm—less than the IR747 line, the extreme parent. The upper height limit ranged from 160 to 180 cm in the three double crosses. Only one single cross (IR332 × IR127) reached 170 cm. We found an excess of tall segregates in all double crosses and in four single crosses. This segregation confirmed previous findings from diallel analysis that most height genes are additive in effect and some also are dominant for tallness.

From 29,900 F_2 plants, we selected ones that mature as early as IR747B2-6-3 or IR781-184-2, or earlier, and that have tiller number, erect culms, attractive grains, and slow senescence. Selections were also made for IR127-type progenies that, compared with the IR127 parent, have higher tiller number, more slender grains, darker foliage, and more erect flag leaves.

Performance of F_3 progenies. Over 1,100 F_3 lines, as well as the four parents, were grown in the wet season. Two hundred lines produced offspring that matured at least as early as IR747B2-6-3. The early maturing segregates came mostly from the three double crosses and the single cross of two early parents, IR747B × IR781. In many segregates, one or two panicles exerted extremely early, but the remaining panicles did not emerge until 2 weeks later. Few F_3 plants matured as early as IR747B2-6-3 or tillered as profusely.

We selected about 150 segregates that were early maturing, medium-to-high tillering, and slender grained. Another 250 lines were intermediate in maturity between the IR781 and IR127 parents. About 50 lines of plants that were intermediate in height, low tillering, and long leaved were selected for observation under upland conditions. Most were from the cross IR127 × IR747 and (IR332 × IR747) × (IR127 × IR781).

Cytology of sterility in F_2 hybrids. We continued investigating the cytology of hybrid sterility in F_2 plants in indica × indica and indica × javanica crosses, in cooperation with cytogeneticists of the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Sporocytes of sterile F_2 plants from four cross-combinations were examined, taking into consideration the chromosome behavior during meiosis I. The four crosses

were IR8 × Boegi Imba, IR8 × Pankhari 203, Basmati 370 × TN1, and Basmati 370 × Pankhari 203. The rate of pollen sterility ranged from 54 percent in Basmati × Pankhari to 73 percent in IR8 × Pankhari.

At the pachytene stage, the IR8 × Boegi Imba progeny had the lowest percentage of normal cells (63.4%) while Basmati × Pankhari progeny had the highest (87.5%). Loose pairing, reciprocal translocations, and duplication-deficiency loops were found in all crosses. The major nucleolus was absent in all crosses except Basmati × Pankhari. Inversion loops were found in both IR8 × Boegi Imba and Basmati × TN1. Unequal bivalents were observed in IR8 × Pankhari and Basmati × TN1. We also found fragmented chromosomes in IR8 × Boegi Imba and IR8 × Pankhari. We observed a high percentage of incomplete pairing (46.2%) in IR8 × Boegi Imba.

At diakinesis and metaphase I, 62 to 85 percent of the cells were normal. One plant of the IR8 × Boegi Imba cross showed 24 univalents in 13.5 percent of the cells. Some univalents split early at metaphase I, producing half-univalents. As many as 16 half-univalents per cell were found at metaphase I. The IR8 × Boegi Imba cross also exhibited hexavalents (0.68%). Two plants of the same cross showed precocious disjunction, forming a bridge (0.78%). From 3 to 5 percent of the cells in IR8 × Boegi Imba, IR8 × Pankhari, and Basmati × TN1 possessed quadrivalents and aneuploid chromosome numbers as low as 20 ($2n - 4$) and as high as 28 ($2n + 4$). Several nucleolus bodies were found in four crosses at diakinesis.

At anaphase I and telophase I, we observed unequal segregation, unsplit bivalents, laggards, and bridges in all crosses. Bridges and fragments were found only in IR8 × Boegi Imba and Basmati × TN1 crosses. From two to eight half-univalents were associated with the normal chromosomes. A persistent nucleolus was observed in IR8 × Boegi Imba and IR8 × Pankhari. Ninety percent of the cells were normal in Basmati × TN1 and Basmati × Pankhari, 84 percent in IR8 × Pankhari, and 76 percent in IR8 × Boegi Imba.

Entomology

A major advance in insect control was the development of the concept of inserting insecticide about 2.5 cm below the soil surface near the roots of transplanted seedlings. This treatment can protect the plants throughout the crop season, a degree of control normally obtained only by applying granular insecticides every 20 days. The prolonged effect is apparently due to minimizing exposure of the pesticides to heat, sunshine, aerobic bacteria, and volatilization. □ We found that insecticides usually are not needed to protect a resistant variety such as IR20 from the tungro virus disease. Foliar sprays to control the brown planthopper are best applied soon after a hatch of nymphs. Methyl parathion apparently caused an increase in the abundance of brown planthoppers because it killed some predators. □ We continued to search for diverse sources of varietal resistance to insect pests and to incorporate resistance to several insects into rice lines. Some progeny of IR20 × TKM 6 have shown resistance to the insect pests and diseases common at IRRI and also have high yield potential. □ The duration of infestation is important in determining the density of sucking insects that causes economic yield loss. The major environmental factors that influenced the field population of *Nephotettix virescens* were season or weather, plant resistance, and predation. Growth of the *Nilaparvata lugens* population was encouraged by keeping paddies flooded and by using close plant spacing. Populations of both brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers were influenced by dispersal. The pests competed in the absence of predators. *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and spiders were important predators, but did not appear to control the pests efficiently.

VARIETAL RESISTANCE TO INSECTS

Striped borer. In greenhouse studies of varietal resistance to the striped borer, *Chilo suppressalis* Walker, we infested potted plants with a uniform number of first-instar borer larvae, then measured larval damage, rate of larval survival, and larval weights. Most lines evaluated were progeny of the variety Eswarakora or TKM 6. Eswarakora has been reported in India as resistant to the yellow borer and the rice gall midge. TKM 6 is resistant to several pests and diseases. Ratna and Taitung 16 had the fewest dead hearts and lowest rate of larval survival (Table 1). The larvae reared on these varieties were smaller and weighed less than those raised on the other lines. On some test lines which had few dead hearts, larval survival and weights were similar to those on susceptible check varieties. These lines appear tolerant to striped borer damage. The Eswarakora progeny, even though resistant to the yellow borer, were susceptible to the striped borer.

In another experiment, progenies of crosses of TKM 6 with various varieties were evaluated for resistance to striped borer (Table 2). Several lines appeared to be almost as resistant as the resistant check, Taitung 16.

This year we standardized a simple mass screening technique which may greatly ad-

vance our studies on varietal resistance to the stem borer. The screening is conducted in a screen cage measuring 15 × 20 × 2 m. Striped borers are maintained on a susceptible variety planted in nursery beds covering about one-third of the area. The remaining area is planted with the test varieties. Each variety is planted in a 1.5-m row of about 20 hills. Every tenth row is either a susceptible or a resistant check variety. The moths that emerge from the susceptible variety in the adjoining nursery beds oviposit on the test varieties. Periodically, egg masses and dead hearts on each variety are counted. The same borer population can be used in successive experiments, but it should be supplemented with field-collected eggs every five to seven generations to avoid inbreeding.

Using this screening technique, we evaluated three batches of test lines consisting of 90 to 225 entries. In each test all rows of susceptible check varieties were severely damaged or killed—an ideal condition for evaluating varietal resistance (fig. 1). In an experiment, we evaluated IR1514A lines and reselected lines from IR20 (IR532E576). There were distinct differences in the ovipositional preference of the moths for some lines (Table 3). The number of eggs laid on a line, however, was not correlated with the number of dead hearts later found in that line. This finding indicates either larval non-preference or

Table 1. Reaction of selected lines to the striped rice borer in the greenhouse^a IIRI, 1972.

Designation	Cross	Dead hearts (no./five larvae)	White heads ^b (no./five larvae)	Larval survival (%)	Avg wt (mg/larvae)
CPA 6805-2	[(17-1 LT × IR8) × EK 1252] × RD-2	2	1	87	57
-7		2	—	71	44
-22		2	1	92	43 ^c
-23		4	—	92	52
PAN 6806-16	[(17-1 LT × IR8) × EK 1259] × RD-2	3	—	74	42
CPA 6806-18	[(17-1 LT × IR8) × EK 1259] × RD-2	5	—	90	51
-34		4	—	92	40
-36		4	—	92	50 ^c
-46		5	—	90	46
-56		4	—	95	41
-58		5	—	66	40
Ratna	TKM 6 × IR8	1	1	54	29
Cauvery	TKM 6 × TN1	4	3	88	44 ^c
CR57-49	Ptb 18 × IR8	3	—	80	37
CR52-3	IR8 × (Chinsura boro × TKM 6)	4	—	65	37
Rexoro ^d		3	—	80	56
Taitung 16 ^e		2	—	44	32

^a40-day-old potted plants of each variety were infested with five first-instar larvae per hill. ^bObservations were made at 22 days after infestation. Lines for which no data are given had not flowered at the time of observation. ^cSome larvae had already pupated.

^dSusceptible check. ^eResistant check.

Table 2. Striped borer damage and survival^a on progeny of crosses involving TKM 6 in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1972.

Designation	Dead hearts (no./five larvae)	White heads ^b (no./five larvae)	Survival (%)		Total wt of larvae and pupae (g)
			Larvae	Pupae	
IR747B ₂ -12-1	7	—	17	13	0.77
IR532E184-615-2	6	—	35	15	0.91
IR532E384-1122-2	5	—	15	18	0.97
IR532PK56-C5	8	—	20	17	0.98
IR532-1-176	3	4	0	33	1.07
IR532-1-18-2	8	0	22	28	1.46
IR532E425-1214-2	2	3	7	40	1.44
IR580-25-3	8	—	43	22	1.47
IR532-1-215	6	—	42	22	1.58
IR747B ₂ -6-3	3	4	30	30	1.59
IR710-17-1	6	0	32	42	2.23
IR532E458-1334-1	7	—	22	42	2.39
Rexoro (susceptible check)	3	—	30	43	3.16
Taitung 16 (resistant check)	3	0	8	23	0.92

^a40-day-old potted plants of each variety were infested with five first-instar larvae per hill. Observations made 22 days after infestation. ^bLines for which no data are given had not flowered at time of observation.

plant antibiosis to the larvae. The IR1514A lines were more resistant than the IR532 lines and all lines were more resistant than TKM 6.

Yellow borer. The yellow borer, *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker, is the predominant species of the rice stem borer in tropical Asia. Studies on varietal resistance to yellow borer have been hindered because the larvae are difficult to rear in large numbers and they are extremely sensitive to handling. As a result controlled infestations have not been tried previously.

In an attempt to use controlled infestations this year we avoided the problems of mass rearing by collecting egg masses from moths at

night in the field. After the eggs hatched in the laboratory, one larva was placed near the auricle of the youngest leaf of each tiller in test plants 65 days after seeding in pots. The tests were conducted on 57 varieties which are resistant to certain insect pests and diseases. The plants were thinned so that each pot contained a uniform number of primary tillers. After the tillers were dissected and the larvae counted, the larvae were discarded. They were not used for subsequent tests because the increased mortality from handling might have raised the level of experimental error.

The final data on dead hearts, larval survival,

1. In an experiment in a 15- × 20- × 2-m screen house that simulates natural field conditions, IR1514A selections suffered little damage from the striped borer while Rexoro and TKM 6 (center) were killed.

Table 3. Resistance of IR1514A (IR20 × TKM 6) F₁ lines and IR20 selections (IR532E576) to the striped borer 7 to 21 days after oviposition^a in a screenhouse experiment. IIRI, 1972.

Designation	Egg masses ^a (no./row)	Dead hearts ^b (%)			White heads ^c (%)
		7 days	14 days	21 days	
IR1514A-E582-2	5	21	24	20	3
-E588-3	1	15	17	15	2
-E597-6	3	11	15	20	4
-E661-3	0	16	17	15	2
-E661-4	1	16	17	17	1
-E661-5	3	21	21	19	3
-E661-8	0	18	19	20	1
-E666-2	1	15	18	15	1
-E666-3	2	18	21	18	2
IR532E576-21-6	1	20	21	20	5
-21-11	3	19	20	19	7
-23-3	1	26	28	25	5
-47-2	2	32	36	36	5
TKM 6	9	24	61	100	—
Rexoro ^d	13	57	77	83	—
Taitung 16 ^e	6	38	45	52	1

^aOviposition occurred when the plants were 58 days old.
^bEach row was 2.4 m long and contained about 23 hills.
^c21 days after oviposition varieties for which no data are given had not flowered at the time of observation. ^dSusceptible check.
^eResistant check.

and larval weights were taken 20 days after infestation. Two of the 57 varieties were identified as resistant—WC 1251 and WC 1253—and four were identified as moderately resistant—IR20, Kipusa, Taitung 16, and TKM 6 (Table 4). The larvae that infested resistant varieties caused fewer dead hearts, suffered higher mortality, and were smaller than those that infested the susceptible plants.

Table 4. Effect of caging first-instar larvae of yellow borers on different test varieties for 20 days. IIRI, 1972.

Variety	Dead hearts ^a (no./ 100 larvae)	Larval survival (%)	Avg larval wt (mg)	Total larval wt ^b (g)
WC 1251	31	21	28	0.59
WC 1253	27	19	31	0.59
IR20	34	26	34	0.88
Kipusa	41	24	37	0.89
Taitung 16	61	28	36	1.01
TKM 6	40	38	40	1.52
IR8	75	49	48	2.35

^aAverage of three to four different experiments. In each experiment, 60 to 80 tillers of each variety were infested with one larva per tiller. ^bNo. of surviving larvae × average larval weight.

Our test for varietal resistance to the yellow borer was improved when we learned to separate individual eggs from egg masses without impairing hatchability. Soaking and occasionally shaking the egg masses at the blackhead stage of development in a 5-percent sodium hydroxide solution for 2.5 hours separates the eggs. Then the eggs are rinsed in distilled water and placed on a moist filter paper for hatching. From 60 to 80 percent of the eggs separated in this way have hatched.

Leafhoppers and planthoppers. During 1972, 2,000 to 3,000 varieties or selections were tested in a continuation of our screening for resistance to the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix virescens* Distant, the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål, and the white backed planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath. Many were identi-

Table 5. Reaction (R = Resistant, I = Intermediate, S = Susceptible) of selected varieties and lines to *Nephotettix nigropictus* and other leafhoppers and planthoppers. IIRI, 1972.

Designation	Origin	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>
H5	Sri Lanka	R	R	R	R
Hashikam	Surinam	R	R	I	S
Ptb 18	India	R	R	R	S
Ptb 19	India	R	R	R	—
Ptb 21	India	R	R	R	S
ASD 7	India	R	R	R	I
D-204-1	India	R	R	S	R
Baguamon	Pakistan	R	R	I	—
DNJ 9	Pakistan	R	R	S	S
ARC 6049	India	R	S	S	S
ARC 6230	India	R	S	I	S
CR 94-13	IIRI	R	MS	R	I
IR833-62	IIRI	R	R	S	—
IR944-102-2	IIRI	R	R	S	S
BW-173	Sri Lanka	R	R	S	—
IR8	IIRI	S	R	S	S
TN1	Taiwan	S	S	S	S

fied as highly resistant. A few examples are ARC 10229, Ptb 21, DV 139, ASD 8, and Su-yai 20, resistant to green leafhopper; H 105, Ptb 18, Ptb 21, Murungakayan 3, and M.I. 329, resistant to brown planthopper; and C 5-17, SLO 12, Colombo, 3-Month Variety, and Ratu Hinatee, resistant to white backed planthopper.

Screening of varieties for resistance to *Nephotettix nigropictus* Stål, was begun this year. *N. nigropictus* is found in large numbers throughout South and Southeast Asia. It is a vector of tungro virus, although not as efficient as *N. virescens*. The techniques of mass rearing and evaluation of varietal resistance are similar to those for *N. virescens*. We found, however, that mass rearing was more efficient when we used a mixture of rice and the grassy weed *Echinochloa crusgalli* Beauv. than when rice alone was used as host plant. Of the 323 varieties tested, 15 were resistant and 45 moderately resistant. Resistance to *N. nigropictus* appears quite specific and independent of other insects, even though certain varieties, such as H5, Ptb 19, Ptb 21 and ASD 7, have a broad range of resistance to insects (Table 5).

Combining resistance to several pests. Of the various crosses investigated for resistance to more than one insect, the line IR1514A (IR20 × TKM 6) appears the most promising. Its spectrum of insect and disease resistance is like IR20's, but it is also resistant to the brown planthopper (fig. 2). It has shown field resistance to grassy stunt virus, probably because it is resistant to the vector, the brown planthopper. Selected lines of this cross have the same general plant type as IR20, but are about 10 cm shorter, which makes them less likely to lodge.

In trials this year, F₆ lines of IR1514A were transplanted as pedigree rows in two sets of plots with six 5-m rows per plot. One set was treated with 2 kg/ha a.i. of diazinon every 20 days, starting 5 days after transplanting. The other set received no insecticide. The stem borer incidence was low during the experiment but incidence of virus diseases (grassy stunt and tungro) was high. IR8, the check variety, was severely damaged by grassy stunt and tungro and produced low yields. All test lines, however, had low incidence of virus diseases and produced high yields (Table 6).

2. Several progeny of IR20 × TKM 6 (IR1514A) are highly resistant to the brown planthopper even though both parents are susceptible.

Although diazinon was applied to encourage brown planthoppers to build up (1970 and 1971 Annual Reports), a high population did not develop. In greenhouse experiments, however, we found these lines to be highly resistant to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper.

The F₇ seeds of the promising lines from the experiment were bulked and grown in plots 2 m × 5 m. Three replications were partially protected from insect damage by application of lindane to the paddy water 5, 25, and 45 days after transplanting. Another three replications received no insecticidal treatments.

Table 6. Reaction of IR1514A (IR20 × TKM 6) F₆ lines to insect pests and virus diseases in a field experiment. IRRI 1972 dry season.

Selection	Dead hearts (%) 67 DT ^a	White heads (%) 102 DT	Virus ^b (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
			60 DT	102 DT	
IR1514A-E588-1	1	3	2	10	4.36
-E588-3	2	1	2	0	4.84
-E597-2	5	2	2	0	5.29
-E597-4	3	0	2	0	5.09
-E597-6	1	2	2	0	5.13
-E597-7	1	1	2	0	5.59
-E661-1	2	4	1	0	4.59
-E661-4	0	5	3	5	5.40
-E663-2	0	3	2	0	5.10
-E666-7	0	3	0	0	5.18
-E666-8	0	4	0	0	5.08
-E666-9	1	2	1	0	5.22
-E670-1	0	3	3	0	5.04
-E670-4	2	2	2	5	5.53
-E670-5	1	4	2	0	5.21
-E685-1	3	3	2	0	5.15
IR8 (Check)	1	3	16	56	1.49

^aDays after transplanting. ^bMixture of grassy stunt and tungro.

3. An IR1514A line (centre) remained unaffected while Taichung Native 1 (right) was severely damaged by tungro virus and bacterial blight. Rexoro (left) was damaged by stem borers.

Severe incidence of rice whorl maggot, stem borers, tungro virus, and grassy stunt virus occurred. Plots without insecticides (Table 7) showed that the IR1514A lines were highly resistant to tungro virus, grassy stunt virus, and stem borers. Although tungro virus infected 28 percent of the IR8 hills and 40 percent of the TN1 hills, most test lines had less than 1 percent infected hills. Similarly, the check varieties were severely infected by the grassy stunt virus, while the test lines had low incidence. Rexoro, the check variety susceptible to stem borer, had

70 percent white heads, but the test lines were relatively unaffected (fig. 3).

Because of multiple resistance, the IR1514A lines gave high yields while many other varieties yielded poorly. Outstanding evidence of these lines' resistance was that even under heavy insect and virus incidence, most IR1514A lines yielded the same whether or not they were protected with insecticides. Some are also resistant to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, and blast. IR1514A-E597 showed field resistance to cercospora leaf spot disease during

Table 7. Reaction of IR1514A (IR20 × TKM 6) F₂ selections to insect pests and virus diseases. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Whorl maggot damage ^a	Tungro virus (%) 74 DT	Grassy stunt (%) 74 DT	Dead hearts (%) 40 DT	White heads (%) 90 DT	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR1514A-E583-1	3.0	0.4	3	4.0	3.0	4.31
-E588-3	3.5	0.4	3	2.1	2.9	4.23
-E597-2	4.0	0.6	3	1.4	1.6	5.08
-E597-3	4.0	0.8	2	1.5	2.4	4.95
-E666-3	4.0	1.0	5	0.4	1.3	4.00
-E666-7	4.0	2.0	5	2.0	4.8	4.26
-E666-9	4.0	1.2	5	0.4	4.1	4.22
-E570-11	4.0	0.6	3	2.3	1.6	4.52
-E570-12	4.0	0.0	4	1.0	1.1	4.33
IR442-2-58	5.0	3.6	3	4.9	2.4	2.14
IR20	4.0	2.2	5	1.9	1.8	4.12
IR8	5.0	28.0	22	4.4	1.4	0.52
IR22	5.0	9.3	9	2.8	4.5	2.48
IR24	5.0	12.1	9	3.2	6.1	2.36
Rexoro	5.0	12.1	4	9.4	70.7	0.00
TKM 6	5.0	0.0	3	1.0	4.6	2.31
TN1	5.0	40.3	18	7.2	1.6	0.26

^aAverage of five weekly observations. Higher number indicates higher degree of damage on a scale of 0 to 5.

both F₆ and F₇ evaluations. *Cercospora* is not currently considered a major disease of rice. Nevertheless, IR20 and most of the IR20 × TKM 6 selections are susceptible to the disease.

Causes of resistance. In cooperation with IRR1 chemists, we are studying the biochemical basis of resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers in rice varieties. Using a bioassay (1971 Annual Report), we investigated the efficiency of different solvents for extracting the resistance factor from the plants. In general, the brown planthoppers that fed on ethanol, methanol, petroleum ether, or chloroform extracts of resistant plants died sooner than those that fed on similar extracts of susceptible plants. Green leafhoppers fed at a faster rate and died sooner on the extracts of resistant plants than the brown planthoppers. In repeated experiments the green leafhoppers consumed all the bioassay materials in the sachet within 24 hours after caging; the same amount lasted for more than 48 hours for the brown planthoppers.

Results of one bioassay are shown in Table 8. The brown planthoppers feeding on petroleum ether or chloroform extracts of Mudgo × IR8 plants (resistant to the insect) suffered greater mortality than those feeding on similar extracts of IR8 plants (susceptible). But differences in the mortality of the insects feeding on the benzene extracts of IR8 and Mudgo × IR8 plants were not so distinct. This finding indicated that the petroleum ether and the chloroform extracts of Mudgo × IR8 contained factors that render the plant resistant to the brown planthopper.

In another experiment with the brown planthopper, the aqueous extracts of resistant and susceptible plants, as well as various fractions of these extracts, were bioassayed (Table 9). The insects that fed on any extract of the resistant plants suffered higher mortality than insects that fed on similar extracts of susceptible plants. In general, insects lived longer on distilled water alone than on extracts. Except for the protein-free fraction minus the basic fraction, insect survival on the extracts of resistant and susceptible plants was not significantly different if the extracts were in a 5-percent sucrose solution. The sucrose solution apparently made

the extracts more acceptable to the insects. Therefore, more brown planthoppers caged on the extracts of the resistant plants died because the extract was not acceptable for feeding rather than because it contained toxic materials. Previous experiments also suggested that plants were resistant to the brown planthopper because they were not palatable to the insect (1970 and 1971 Annual Reports).

Cooperative variety trials. Varieties and selections were tested without application of insecticides for field resistance to insect pests at three stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry, the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station. Although the insect infestation was usually too low for adequate screening of new selections, yield differences were evident, partly because of infection by tungro virus.

In the dry season, the yields at Bicol were generally low. The only selections that produced more than 3 t/ha were IR1330-240-1, IR1529-53-2, and IR1541-102-6. At other locations, the selections that gave yields greater than IR20, that is, over 5 t/ha, were IR1402-415 at Maligaya, and IR1402-38, IR1529-53-2, and IR1541-102-6

Table 8. Survival of adult brown planthoppers fed on extracts of 2-month-old IR8 (susceptible) and Mudgo × IR8 (resistant) plants 3 to 24 hours after caging IRR1, 1972.

Source of extract	Survival* (%)			
	3 h	6 h	21 h	24 h
<i>Petroleum ether extract</i>				
IR8	87	82	30	22
Mudgo × IR8	82	65	5	5
Control ^b	88	82	30	25
<i>Benzene extract</i>				
IR8	95	92	58	50
Mudgo × IR8	90	87	45	32
Control ^b	92	87	35	27
<i>Chloroform extract</i>				
IR8	83	73	30	28
Mudgo × IR8	78	70	10	7
Control ^b	92	88	38	35
Distilled water	83	82	37	23
5% sucrose	97	97	90	90

*Average of six replications each consisting of 10 adult insects.

^bThe container was first filled with the solvent used for extracting the plant. Then the solvent was evaporated and the container was filled with water.

Table 9. Survival of brown planthopper adults 3 to 48 hours after caging in three experiments with extracts of IR8 (susceptible) and Mudgo × IR8 (resistant) sampled at flowering. IIRI, 1972.

Treatment	Survival* (%)				
	3 h	6 h	24 h	30 h	48 h
<i>Aqueous extract</i>					
IR8					
Extract alone	97 b	79 b	34 b	24 b	16 ab
Extract + 5% sucrose	99 b	97 d	77 c	74 c	59 c
Mudgo × IR8					
Extract alone	84 a	51 a	14 a	11 a	4 a
Extract + 5% sucrose	98 b	97 d	69 c	65 c	61 c
Distilled water	96 b	89 c	41 b	34 b	19 b
5% sucrose	99 b	98 d	76 c	74 c	67 c
<i>Protein-free fraction</i>					
IR8					
Extract alone	95 a	60 a	28 b	20 a	8 a
Extract + 5% sucrose	97 a	90 b	71 cd	68 b	66 bc
Mudgo × IR8					
Extract alone	93 a	59 a	10 a	12 a	8 a
Extract + 5% sucrose	96 a	91 b	61 c	59 b	59 b
Distilled water	99 a	97 b	74 cd	65 bc	52 b
5% sucrose	99 a	98 b	87 d	85 c	82 c
<i>Protein-free fraction minus basic fraction</i>					
IR8					
Extract alone	48 a	5 a	—	—	—
Extract + 5% sucrose	73 b	29 b	0 a	—	—
Mudgo × IR8					
Extract alone	40 a	2 a	—	—	—
Extract + 5% sucrose	64 b	25 b	10 b	0 a	—
Distilled water	94 c	91 c	41 c	34 b	5 a
5% sucrose	100 d	96 c	72 d	69 c	51 b

*For each experiment values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

at Visayas. The yield of IR8 was 2.2 t/ha at Maligaya and 4.6 t/ha at Visayas.

In the wet season the yields of IR442-2-58, IR1487-194-5, several IR1514A lines, IR1541-102-3, Fortuna × MA-3-26, and BE3 (Mutant) were statistically equal to or greater than the yield of IR20.

INSECTICIDES

Laboratory and greenhouse screening. Fifty-three insecticides were evaluated for control of the green leafhopper, the brown planthopper, and the striped borer in laboratory and greenhouse experiments.

Most compounds tested had high contact toxicity for the green leafhopper in a Potter's spray tower experiment. But only a few such as AC 92,100, Ciba-Geigy 13,608, Mobam, and Monitor were toxic to both green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers. Most of these compounds were effective as 0.04 percent sprays on

potted plants, but had residual durations of only 5 to 10 days. Only a few effectively controlled the striped borer larvae. Carbofuran was most toxic to the striped borer and had the longest residual period—when first-instar borer larvae were caged on plants 1 day after spraying with carbofuran, 63 percent of the larvae died; at 5 days after spraying, 100 percent died; and at 10 days after spraying, 27 percent died.

When broadcast as granules on the soil surface of potted plants, carbofuran, Paddigard, AC 92,100, and AC 64,475 were highly effective against the green leafhopper, the brown planthopper, and the striped borer (Table 10). Several other chemicals were toxic to one or two test species but not to the third.

As seedling root-soak treatments, many of these insecticides were effective against the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper. Except for carbofuran, however, residual durations were short against the brown planthopper (Table 11). Because residual effectiveness is

Table 10. Systemic effects (1 to 15 days after treatment) of granular insecticides applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. to the water of potted plants (TN1). IRRI, 1972.

Insecticide	Mortality ^a (%)											
	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>				<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>				<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> ^b			
	1 day	5 days	10 days	15 days	1 day	5 days	10 days	15 days	5 days	10 days	15 days	
Carbofuran	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	87	47	63	
Paddigard	100	100	100	100	97	100	68	59	—	74	100	
AC 92, 100	100	100	100	100	100	97	84	90	10	3	51	
AC 64, 475	95	98	100	100	65	84	92	93	70	52	100	
Phorate	95	100	100	100	89	92	76	46	0	0	10	
Promecarb + chlorphenamide	70	100	100	95	76	81	95	51	12	13	23	
Fenitrothion + meobal	100	100	100	60	100	56	22	8	9	0	—	
Meobal ^c	100	100	89	15	95	38	10	5	0	5	—	
Fenitrothion ^c + metacrate ^c	100	100	89	12	98	49	5	5	10	3	—	
S 300	98	100	81	12	8	5	5	2	0	0	—	
MC 2420	90	70	80	31	16	14	0	3	0	2	20	
Endrin-MIPC urea	100	100	5	0	98	0	2	0	8	8	—	
Endrin-MIPC-ammophos	100	100	3	5	80	3	5	0	12	0	—	

^a48 h after infestation; adjusted using Abbott's formula. ^bFreshly hatched larvae. Data for carbofuran obtained from a separate experiment. ^cMicrogranules.

longer against the green leafhopper, many of these insecticides may be effective in minimizing the spread of tungro virus.

Several compounds were highly effective against the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper when placed in short paper straws

and inserted about 2.5 cm below the soil surface in the root zone of potted plants. These compounds killed nearly 100 percent of the test insects up to 25 days after treatment (Table 12). Several other compounds which were highly effective when applied to the soil surface, such

Table 11. Effect of soaking roots of TN1 seedlings in insecticide solutions for 24 hours before transplanting on insects caged on the seedlings 5 to 20 days after transplanting (DT) in an insectary. IRRI, 1972.

Insecticide ^a	Mortality ^b (%)							
	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>				<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>			
	5 DT	10 DT	15 DT	20 DT	5 DT	10 DT	15 DT	20 DT
Carbofuran ^c G	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	100
Carbaryl WP	100	88	72	50	89	68	38	18
Fenitrothion + meobal MG	100	68	22	15	97	72	32	10
Fenitrothion + metacrate MG	100	95	12	15	100	—	—	—
Folimat EC	100	90	72	60	66	12	5	0
Meobal MG	100	88	22	2	100	65	22	8
MIPC WP	100	95	79	62	97	92	55	32
Mobam WP	100	100	100	92	87	95	52	36
Monitor EC	100	98	95	92	34	18	40	20
Re 15223-4 WP	100	65	18	13	92	35	5	0
Tamaron EC	100	95	85	72	60	62	25	15
EMD 7051 ^c G	98	18	0	5	3	5	0	8
S 300 G	98	88	58	12	37	25	22	10
C 10015 A 3861 WP	95	92	23	28	53	75	42	38
Orthene	95	55	41	12	89	35	15	5
LS 69-1123 EC	88	45	25	0	74	—	—	—
C 8514 A 4072	45	20	5	10	97	100	92	60

^aApplied at 400 ppm for *N. virescens* and at 1000 ppm for *N. lugens* unless otherwise indicated. G = granular, WP = wettable powder, MG = microgranules, EC = emulsified concentrate. ^b48 hours after caging; adjusted using Abbott's formula. ^cApplied at 400 ppm for both *N. virescens* and *N. lugens*.

Table 12. Effect of granular insecticides inserted^a (2 kg/ha a.i.) in the root zone about 2.5 cm beneath soil surface of potted TN1 plants in an insectary. IRRI, 1972.

Insecticide	Mortality ^b (%)									
	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>					<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>				
	5 DT	10 DT	15 DT	20 DT	25 DT	5 DT	10 DT	15 DT	20 DT	25 DT
Carbofuran G	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
AC 64,475 ^c G	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Fenitrothion + metacrate MG	100	100	100	100	87	100	100	100	80	20
Meobal MG	100	100	100	100	100	91	98	100	100	98
Fenitrothion + meobal MG	100	100	100	100	100	79	100	90	85	88
MC2420 G	78	97	100	97	100	78	82	100	44	60
Phorate G	38	38	37	30	—	13	15	8	0	—
Paddigard G	33	33	37	12	—	8	0	10	0	—
AC 92,100 G	5	23	50	5	—	0	10	2	0	—

^aInsecticide was placed in capsules made from sections of paper straw. ^b48 h after caging. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula. ^cSome phytotoxic effects manifested as burning of leaf tips.

as phorate, Paddigard, and AC 92,100, were not effective when inserted in the rice root zone.

Field comparisons. Promising insecticides were compared in the field when applied as granules to paddy water or as foliar sprays during the

4. Effect of carbofuran on grassy stunt infection. Insecticide was applied at 2 kg/ha at 1 and 10 days after seeding in the nursery bed and at 2, 22, 42, and 62 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

1972 dry season. All treatments except methyl parathion spray were highly effective against the rice whorl maggot and the stem borer (Table 13). Carbofuran was the only treatment that protected against grassy stunt virus, although the disease level was too low to properly evaluate treatments. A large population of brown planthoppers developed as the crop neared maturity. The plots treated with diazinon, lindane + carbaryl, or methyl parathion suffered complete hopperburn and produced no grain. Hopperburn occurred in other plots after the grain ripened, but this did not reduce yields. Although hopperburn was lightest in the plot treated with carbofuran (it affected only the borders), this plot did not produce the highest yields.

The untreated control plot did not have hopperburn, yet it yielded significantly less than most treated plots. This yield loss was chiefly due to cumulative damage by whorl maggots, stem borers, and grassy stunt virus. We are investigating why plots treated with insecticides that do not effectively control brown planthoppers suffer hopperburn, while the untreated control plots generally remain free from such damage. Possibly the thick growth of the treated plots and the killing of parasites and predators encourage rapid increase in the brown planthopper population.

Prevention of virus infection. Tungro virus has become such a problem in tropical Asia that the development of a simple method of preventing virus infections is essential. Seed, seedbed, and root-soak treatments which are all relatively

Table 13. Comparison of selected insecticides applied to paddy water (2 kg/ha a.i. every 20 days) and as foliar sprays (1325 liters) containing 0.04% a.i. every 15 days). Variety IR22. IRR1, 1972 dry season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a		Dead hearts ^b (%) 61 DT	Grassy stunt virus ^{bc} (%) 61 DT	Hopperburned area (%) 109 DT	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
	21 DT	30 DT				
Lindane + unden G	0.0	2.0	0.4 ab	4 ab	55	7.62 a
S 6626 + unden G	0.5	2.0	0.0 a	5 ab	15	7.07 ab
Lindane + BPMC G	0.5	3.0	1.1 bc	3 ab	25	6.81 ab
Carbofuran G	1.5	2.0	0.2 ab	2 a	3	6.78 ab
Monocrotophos EC	1.5	1.5	0.4 ab	5 ab	48	6.47 ab
Lindane + MIPC G	1.0	3.0	0.3 ab	4 ab	55	6.01 b
Diazinon G	0.0	2.5	1.1 bc	8 ab	98	0.00 d
Lindane + carbaryl G	1.0	2.0	0.2 ab	7 ab	98	0.00 d
Methyl parathion EC	4.0	2.5	2.1 c	9 b	100	0.00 d
Control	4.5	4.0	4.6 d	9 b	0	4.04 c

^aGrade of damage on a range of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cIncidence was low and statistically identical in all treatments at 20 and 40 days after transplanting.

inexpensive prophylactic measures sometimes protect crops from tungro. We tested carbofuran, dursban, terracur, unden, and lindane + MIPC as granules and monocrotophos, Bux 300, and MIPC as sprays. Each treatment was replicated three times and the experiment was repeated twice. The varieties used were IR20 and IR22.

Grassy stunt virus was predominant in both experiments. In general, the insecticides did not adequately protect the plants from this virus. Although at 13 days after transplanting many of the treated plots had lower virus incidence

than the untreated control plots, the differences with both IR20 and IR22, became obscure in later observations (Table 14). Overall, the seedbed and the seedbed plus seedling root-soak treatments had significantly less virus than the other treatments, indicating that virus infection started in the seedbed. Varietal resistance seems more important than insecticide treatments in virus control. Although the insecticide treatments were at first equally ineffective on both IR20 and IR22, they were more effective on IR20 in later observations (fig. 4). The older

Table 14. Control of virus infection (mostly grassy stunt) on IR20 and IR22 plants with treatments involving carbofuran and other chemicals. IRR1, 1972.

Treatment ^a	Chemical	Virus (%)							
		Dry season					Wet season		
		13 DT	31 DT	51 DT	76 DT	95 DT	40 DT	51 DT	64 DT
<i>IR20</i>									
Seedbed 1X	Carbofuran	0.4	2	4	6	5	4	30	29
Seedbed 2X ^b	MIPC	0.4	2	5	7	4	8	27	29
Root soak	Dursban	0.7	4	6	6	6	6	28	29
Seedbed 1X & root soak	Carbofuran & carbofuran	0.6	3	6	6	6	5	31	34
Seedbed 1X & root soak	Unden & unden	1.0	3	5	8	7	8	29	31
Seedbed 2X ^b & root soak	MIPC spray & carbofuran	1.1	3	5	7	6	7	30	35
Field applied ^c	Carbofuran	0.7	3	6	5	6	4	20	25
Field applied ^d	MIPC spray	0.3	3	6	7	7	8	25	32
Seedbed 2X ^e & field applied ^c	Carbofuran & carbofuran	0.3	1	4	5	3	6	17	23
Control	—	1.4	4	7	9	8	12	22	29
<i>IR22</i>									
Seedbed 1X	Carbofuran	1.0	6	14	17	19	27	54	62
Root soak	Carbofuran	2.1	7	15	15	19	23	58	75
Seedbed 1X & root soak	Carbofuran & carbofuran	1.2	5	13	14	18	20	48	58
Seedbed 2X ^e & field applied ^c	Carbofuran & carbofuran	0.3	4	11	12	13	17	43	56
Control	—	2.2	7	12	15	16	25	50	68

^aSeedbed 1X = applied in seedbed 6 days after seeding. ^bApplied in seedbed 6 and 14 days after seeding. ^cApplied in field every 20 days after transplanting starting 2 days after transplanting. ^dApplied in field every 10 days after transplanting. ^eApplied in seedbed 1 and 10 days after seeding.

Table 15. Effect of root-coat treatment of seedlings with selected insecticides on rice insect pest control. IRRI, 1972.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (ppm)	Whorl maggot damage ^b			Virus (%)					
		TN1	IR20	IR22	TN1		IR20		IR22	
					58 DT	93 DT	58 DT	93 DT	58 DT	93 DT
Carbofuran	500	1.2	1.0	1.5	16	20	4	5	10	11
	1000	0.6	0.9	1.1	9	22	2	3	9	13
	2000	0.5	0.3	0.4	15	17	4	3	10	7
Diazinon	500	1.5	1.1	1.5	31	51	5	6	16	38
	1000	1.4	0.9	1.5	21	33	5	10	10	21
	2000	0.9	0.6	1.1	32	50	2	5	15	28
Carbaryl	500	1.9	1.3	1.7	16	50	5	7	11	19
	1000	1.6	1.2	1.7	18	48	2	7	12	20
	2000	1.7	1.3	1.8	20	38	2	4	11	17
TBPMC	500	1.8	1.4	1.6	11	34	4	6	13	18
	1000	1.6	1.4	1.7	16	62	3	6	8	18
	2000	1.9	1.3	1.7	26	63	3	5	13	27
Uden	500	1.9	1.2	1.7	23	40	5	6	13	18
	1000	1.5	1.2	1.5	18	34	4	6	18	28
	2000	1.2	1.0	1.3	14	28	4	5	15	14
Mobam	500	1.7	1.4	1.8	19	35	3	11	12	19
	1000	1.7	1.5	1.7	17	40	2	7	15	18
	2000	1.7	1.1	1.7	15	31	3	11	11	18
MIPC	500	1.8	1.4	1.6	19	40	5	6	11	18
	1000	1.9	1.4	1.7	23	51	3	5	16	24
	2000	1.5	1.1	1.6	11	27	3	5	14	14
Control		1.8	1.2	1.7	33	71	3	6	14	20

^aThe insecticides cartap, dursban, lindane, Monitor, S 6626, and Taron were less effective and their data have been excluded. ^b20DT. Scale: 0 to 3, larger number indicates greater damage.

IR20 plants develop resistance to the grassy stunt virus while IR22 plants remain susceptible.

In another study, root-soak treatments of 13 selected insecticides at 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm concentrations were tested for prevention of virus. The varieties used were Taichung Native 1 (highly susceptible), IR22 (moderately susceptible), and IR20 (field resistant).

At 20 days after transplanting, seedlings treated with 2,000 ppm carbofuran, lindane,

diazinon, dursban, uden, or S 6626 had significantly lower whorl maggot damage than the other plots (Table 15). Carbofuran was also effective at 500 and 1,000 ppm and dursban at 1,000 ppm. No treatment, however, was effective against whorl maggots at 35 days after transplanting.

IR20 was the least infected by tungro virus and Taichung Native 1 was the worst infected. No treatment gave significantly lower virus

Table 16. Effect of seedling root-soak treatment in 1000 ppm of carbofuran for 24 hours on insect mortality 5 to 45 days after treatment in comparison with root-coat treatment in 1000 ppm carbofuran and 2% methyl cellulose for 30 minutes. Variety Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Treatment	Mortality ^a (%)										Dead hearts ^b (%)
	Green leafhoppers				Brown planthoppers			Virus (%)			
	5 days	10 days	15 days	20 days	5 days	10 days	15 days	15 days	30 days	45 days	
Root-soak	75	48	1	0	44	29	0	11	15	25	4.7
Root-soak, then roots washed in water	52	18	1	0	30	27	0	8	19	35	4.5
Root-coat	100	70	16	0	78	40	0	3	12	23	4.4
Root-soak then root-coat	100	50	2	0	71	25	0	5	14	29	3.8
Control	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5	28	51	6.3

^aAdjusted using Abbott's formula. Data are for 48-h periods at indicated days after caging on plants. ^b65 DT.

infection in IR20 or IR22 compared with the control but significant differences occurred in Taichung Native 1. The carbofuran, carbaryl, MIPC, and unden treatments were most effective against virus infection, with some protection evident at 93 days after transplanting.

No treatment significantly reduced dead hearts or white heads.

Seedling root treatments. Soaking the roots of rice seedlings (root-soak treatment) for 12 to 24 hours in 1,000 ppm of carbofuran can control the rice whorl maggot, the green leafhopper, and the brown planthopper for 15 to 20 days after transplanting (1971 Annual Report). It sometimes minimizes virus infection as well.

This year we compared residual insecticide durations on seedlings whose roots were washed in water after the root-soak treatment with residual durations on seedlings whose roots were unwashed. Both treatments caused high insect mortality at 5 days after transplanting. In later cagings, however, the insect mortality was lower on the seedlings whose roots had been washed. This indicated that the insecticide adsorbed on the root surface contributed more to the duration of effectiveness than the quantity absorbed by the plants. We tried an alternative method—soaking seedling roots for 30 minutes in 1,000 ppm carbofuran mixed with 2 percent methyl cellulose as an adhesive—and found that residual toxicity improved (Table 16). This “root-coat treatment” protected the crop from virus infection better than root-soak treatment. We saw no apparent difference between seedlings which received only the root-coat treatment and those which received both the root-soak and root-coat treatments.

The root-soak and the root-coat treatments were evaluated using 1,200 ppm of carbofuran. Both methods were highly effective during the first 10 days after transplanting. Beyond this period, however, the root-soak treatment was only half as effective or less (Table 17). Apparently, plants given the root-soak treatment absorb the insecticide only to a certain level. The root-coat treatment provides an added supply of insecticide that remains in the root zone for future absorption by the plants.

Because methyl cellulose is expensive, we evaluated cheaper, locally available materials

Table 17. Effect of seedling root-coat and root-soak treatments in carbofuran (1200 ppm) 3G or 75% WP on *Nephotettix virescens* caged for 8 or 48 h on a transplanted crop in the field. Variety Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Plant age (DT)	Mortality ^a (%)			Control
	Root soak ^b in 3G	Root coat ^c		
		In 3G	In WP	
	<i>Insects caged for 8 h</i>			
1	100	100	100	1
5	98	100	100	2
10	94	96	97	2
15	22	62	62	0
20	6	55	31	0
30	2	35	27	0
	<i>Insects caged for 48 h</i>			
15	56	100	100	3
20	10	95	97	3
30	38	65	60	0

^aAvg of 10 replications, consisting of 10 insects caged on a plant.

^bFor 24 h. ^cFor 30 min. Includes 2% methyl cellulose sticker.

as adhesives. We found that flour from wheat, corn, or cassava, at 6 to 8 percent concentrations, worked as well as 2 percent methyl cellulose (Table 18).

We further evaluated the root-coat treatment with higher concentrations of carbofuran. All treatments except the root-soak treatment of 600 ppm carbofuran effectively controlled the rice whorl maggot (Table 19). The root-coat treatments with 1,200 or 2,500 ppm of carbofuran were the most effective. It appears that as the quantity of carbofuran used increases, residual effect lengthens. Diazinon was initially effective, but had a short residual period.

Root-zone application of insecticides. The success of the root-coat treatment led to the concept of placing insecticides in the rice root zone. We sealed several insecticides inside “capsules” made from small sections of paper straw. Minute holes were punched in the straw and 5 days after transplanting the capsules were pushed by hand about 2.5 cm into the soil, near roots of rice seedlings. We hoped that capsule application would permit the use of less insecticide because the chemical is concentrated in the root zone and it is shielded from sunshine, heat, and volatilization and is less likely to wash away. Furthermore, it was expected to be less hazardous to the parasites and predators of rice pests.

Several compounds applied in this manner

5. One application of cartap at 2 kg/ha a.i., in the root-zone of newly transplanted rice plants effectively controlled whorl maggot and stem borers.

at a rate equivalent to 2 kg/ha a.i. gave good control of the whorl maggot (Table 20) up to 43 days after transplanting (at which time whorl maggot incidence declines naturally). Carbofuran and lindane + unden gave outstanding protection from tungro virus up to 54 days after transplanting. With these two chemicals only 10 percent of the treated plants had tungro while more than 90 percent of the plants in the untreated control plots were infected.

In a subsequent test of selected compounds, incidence of whorl maggots, stem borers, and tungro virus was high, providing a valuable opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of various compounds when inserted in the rice root zone of variety Taichung Native 1. All insecticides controlled the rice whorl maggot up to 44 days after transplanting (Table 21). Carbofuran, unden, and diazinon were most

effective. But plots treated with unden, diazinon, and MIPC were heavily damaged by stem borers by 49 days after transplanting. Diazinon is effective against borers, and the diazinon-treated plots initially looked vigorous. The high incidence of dead hearts at 49 days indicates that diazinon had shorter residual effect than some of the other insecticides. MIPC and unden are ineffective against the borer.

Several compounds gave outstanding crop protection from common insect pests and the tungro virus (fig. 5). At 83 days after transplanting the plots treated with carbofuran, MIPC, or unden, had fewer than 10 percent infected hills, while 76 percent in the untreated control plot were infected (Table 21). The plots treated with carbofuran, cartap, or MIPC yielded most—about five times as much as the untreated control plots.

Table 18. Effect of different materials used as stickers for the root-coat treatment with 1000 ppm carbofuran. Variety Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Sticker	Concn. of sticker (%)	Missing hills (%)	Whorl maggot damage ^a			Dead hearts (%)		Virus ^b (%)	
			15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	30 DT	50 DT	30 DT	50 DT
Methyl Cellulose A	2	3	0.9	1.7	1.7	1.2	7.6	3	25
Methyl Cellulose B	2	4	1.3	2.0	1.8	2.0	7.2	3	42
Wheat flour	6	3	0.8	1.8	1.6	1.9	9.2	4	34
Wheat flour	8	3	0.8	1.8	1.8	1.2	8.2	2	19
Corn starch	4	6	1.0	2.0	1.6	1.4	8.7	3	36
Corn starch	6	5	0.8	2.0	1.6	1.5	6.3	3	28
Cassava flour	6	5	1.2	1.9	1.6	1.4	7.3	3	31
Cassava flour	5	2	1.4	1.9	1.8	1.7	7.2	3	36
Glutinous rice flour	4	17	1.1	1.9	1.9	2.0	7.5	3	33
Molasses	70	54	0.5	1.1	0.8	1.1	4.8	2	13
None ^c	—	2	1.2	1.9	1.7	2.0	10.4	4	29
Control ^d	—	4	1.9	2.1	1.5	3.4	2.7	4	39

^aGrade of damage on a scale of 0 to 3. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bMostly tungro. ^cSoaked in carbofuran alone for 24 h. ^dNo insecticide.

A single placement of insecticide in the rice root area may be as effective as repeated applications in the paddy water.

With the same chemicals used in the root-zone experiment, but with variety IR22, we made

applications at 2 kg/ha a.i. to the paddy water every 20 days. Surprisingly, unden, cartap, and MIPC, when applied to paddy water, did not control the rice whorl maggot (Table 22) although they were effective when applied in

Table 19. Effect of root-soak and root-coat treatments with carbofuran on control of whorl maggots on transplanted IR22 seedlings. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Treatment	Chemical	Rate (ppm)	Whorl maggot damage ^a		
			25 DT	35 DT	45 DT
Root-coat	Carbofuran	2500	0.2 a	0.7 a	1.4 a
Root-soak + root-coat	Carbofuran	600 + 1200	0.3 a	1.4 ab	1.7 ab
Root-coat	Carbofuran	1200	0.5 ab	1.5 b	1.8 bc
Root-coat	Diazinon	2500	1.1 bc	2.0 b	2.0 cd
Root-soak	Carbofuran	600	1.5 cd	1.9 b	2.1 d
Control	—	—	2.0 d	1.8 b	2.2 d

^aGrade of damage on the youngest leaf on a scale of 0 to 3. Larger number indicates greater damage.

Table 20. Effect of placement of insecticides, in straws, at 2 kg/ha a.i. (12.5 mg/hill) in the root zone of Taichung Native 1 seedlings at 8 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1972.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a		Tungro-infected hills (%)			
	33 DT	43 DT	33 DT	43 DT	54 DT	68 DT
Carbofuran	0.0 a	0.0 a	3 a	8 a	9 a	43 a
Lindane + unden	0.0 a	0.5 ab	10 ab	10 a	13 a	71 ab
Terracur	1.0 b	1.0 bc	14 ab	29 ab	60 abc	88 b
Lindane + MIPC	1.0 bc	1.5 cd	7 ab	25 ab	20 ab	80 ab
Diazinon	1.0 bc	1.0 bc	18 b	36 ab	62 abc	91 b
Cartap	1.0 bc	2.0 de	5 ab	22 ab	46 abc	83 ab
Chlorphenamidine	1.5 cd	1.5 cd	11 ab	26 ab	61 abc	81 ab
Lindane + BPMC	2.0 de	2.0 de	9 ab	24 ab	43 abc	90 ab
Phorate	2.0 de	2.0 de	9 ab	32 ab	53 abc	70 ab
Disulfoton	2.0 ef	2.0 de	11 ab	29 ab	56 abc	92 b
Dursban	2.5 ef	2.5 e	15 ab	52 ab	78 bc	99 b
S 6626	2.5 ef	2.5 e	9 ab	37 ab	51 abc	96 b
Lindane	3.0 f	3.0 e	11 ab	38 ab	78 bc	100 b
Control	3.0 f	3.0 e	17 ab	53 b	92 c	98 b

^aGrade of damage on youngest leaves on a scale of 0 to 3. Larger number indicates greater damage.

Table 21. Effect of inserting insecticides (2 kg/ha a.i.) in the root zone of TN1 seedlings at 5 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a			Dead hearts (%)		Virus (%)			Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
	20 DT	32 DT	44 DT	49 DT	49 DT	69 DT	83 DT		
Cartap	1.5 d	1.0 e	1.0 d	0.5 a	7 ab	11 b	14 ab	3.30 a	
Carbofuran	0.1 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.3 a	2 a	1 a	2 a	3.29 a	
MIPC	1.3 d	1.7 f	1.7 e	12.3 d	3 ab	9 b	7 ab	2.85 ab	
Unden	0.2 a	0.1 b	0.5 b	20.8 e	2 a	6 b	6 ab	2.62 b	
Chlorphenamidine	0.6 bc	0.9 d	1.0 d	2.0 b	7 ab	12 b	19 bc	2.26 bc	
Diazinon	0.4 ab	0.5 c	0.7 c	12.2 d	9 b	26 c	30 c	1.83 cd	
S-6626	0.8 c	1.6 f	1.6 e	7.1 c	32 c	65 d	75 d	1.29 d	
Control	2.3 e	2.1 g	1.9 f	6.9 c	24 c	68 d	76 d	0.60 e	

^aGrade of damage based on the youngest leaf of the main tillers on a scale of 0 to 3. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bYields of all plots were lowered by a severe bacterial leaf blight infection towards crop maturity. The carbofuran-treated plots suffered from lodging.

Table 22. Paddy water application of selected insecticides (2 kg/ha a.i. every 20 days) for insect control in IR22. IIRRI, 1972 wet season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a			Virus-infected hills ^b (%)			Dead hearts (%) 61 DT	Grain yield (t/ha)
	22 DT	33 DT	45 DT	61 DT	73 DT	96 DT		
Carbofuran	1.1	0.9	0.0	1	1	1	0.2	4.58
Unden	2.0	1.5	1.1	6	10	9	2.8	4.21
Cartap	2.0	1.7	1.7	8	14	14	0.3	4.07
MIPC	2.3	1.6	1.6	5	8	6	4.2	4.06
S 6626	0.5	1.6	0.9	11	15	12	0.4	3.93
Diazinon	0.3	1.6	0.9	3	5	5	0.6	3.85
Chlorphenamidine	1.8	1.5	1.3	12	18	18	0.7	3.79
Control	2.1	1.7	1.9	7	16	22	2.8	3.25

^aGrade of damage based on the youngest leaf of the main tillers on a scale of 0 to 3. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bMostly tungro but including some grassy stunt.

the root zone (Table 21). As in the root-zone experiment, neither unden nor MIPC protected against stem borer regardless of the method of application. Tungro virus incidence was not as high as in the experiment on root-zone placement of insecticides, possibly because IR22 is less susceptible than Taichung Native 1, but it was adequate to show differences among various

treatments. Carbofuran, diazinon, MIPC, and unden protected the plants from virus infection.

In another study, we compared different rates of carbofuran, chlorphenamidine, diazinon, unden, and cartap inserted in the root zone. All treatments protected the crop from the rice whorl maggot up to 41 days after transplanting. But at 0.5 or 1 kg/ha, carbofuran and unden were

Table 23. Effect of insecticides in straws placed in the root-zone of Taichung Native 1 at 7 days after transplanting.^a IIRRI, 1972 wet season.

Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Whorl maggot damage ^b			Virus (%)			Stem borers ^c	
	21 DT	32 DT	41 DT	29 DT	50 DT	73 DT	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)
<i>Carbofuran</i>								
0.5	0.4 abcd	0.6 bcd	0.6 abcd	3 a	14 abc	23 ab	9.3 de	6.0 bcdef
1.0	0.2 abc	0.3 ab	0.4 abcd	7 ab	13 abc	18 ab	6.3 bcd	5.4 bcde
2.0	0.1 ab	0.1 ab	0.1 ab	8 ab	11 ab	12 a	1.8 ab	4.9 bcde
4.0	0.1 ab	0.0 a	0.0 a	4 ab	9 a	12 a	0.7 a	3.9 abcd
<i>Chlorphenamidine</i>								
0.5	0.6 bcd	1.1 e	1.4 efg	10 ab	41 efg	70 de	3.2 b	3.9 abcd
1.0	0.6 bcd	1.0 de	1.0 def	11 ab	28 bcdefg	46 bcd	3.3 bc	2.2 abc
2.0	0.2 abc	0.5 abc	0.7 bcd	8 ab	22 abcdef	31 ab	1.6 ab	0.8 ab
4.0	0.2 abc	0.4 ab	0.3 abc	7 ab	21 abcde	35 ab	3.5 bc	0.9 ab
<i>Diazinon</i>								
0.5	0.5 abcd	1.0 de	1.6 g	12 ab	46 gh	81 e	8.8 d	18.2 f
1.0	0.4 abcd	0.6 bcd	0.8 cd	8 ab	35 defg	68 cde	10.8 de	11.5 def
2.0	0.1 ab	0.2 ab	0.4 abcd	13 b	38 defg	64 cde	7.1 d	18.2 f
4.0	0.1 ab	0.2 ab	0.4 abcd	11 ab	42 fgh	71 de	7.3 d	16.4 ef
<i>Unden</i>								
0.5	0.2 abc	0.5 abc	0.9 cde	6 ab	20 abcd	45 bcd	14.1 ef	3.2 abcd
1.0	0.0 a	0.2 ab	0.5 abcd	9 ab	16 abc	29 ab	16.4 f	4.6 bcd
2.0	0.0 a	0.1 ab	0.3 abc	6 ab	14 abc	25 ab	13.8 ef	5.8 bcdef
4.0	0.1 ab	0.1 ab	0.1 ab	8 ab	13 abc	23 ab	10.0 de	5.8 bcdef
<i>Cartap</i>								
0.5	0.8 d	1.2 e	1.5 fg	7 ab	29 cdefg	41 bc	0.4 a	1.3 ab
1.0	0.7 cd	0.9 cde	0.8 cd	11 ab	27 bcdefg	31 ab	0.5 a	0.7 ab
2.0	0.6 bcd	0.6 bcd	0.9 cde	7 ab	19 abcd	27 ab	0.6 a	0.1 a
4.0	0.4 abcd	0.3 ab	0.6 abcd	14 b	32 cdefg	36 ab	0.6 a	0.1 a
<i>Control</i>								
—	2.3 e	2.2 f	2.3 h	4 ab	60 h	85 e	8.9 de	11.0 cdef

^aValues followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level. ^bAverage grade of the damaged leaves. On a scale of 0 to 3, larger number means greater damage. ^cDead hearts counted at 50 DT and white heads at 79 DT.

Table 24. Evaluation of different insecticide combinations on IR24. Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station (B), Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (M), and Visayas Rice Experiment Station (V), 1972 dry season.

Treatment (no. of applications)				Whorl maggot damage ^d (%)			Tungro virus hills ^e (%)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
Carbofuran	Lindane ^a	MIPC ^b	Spray ^c	B	M	V	B	M	V	B	M	V
2 ^f	4	4	—	4*	2*	29*	1*	0	5	4.1	6.8*	5.1*
1 ^g	4	4	—	7*	2*	26*	0*	1	4	4.5*	7.0*	5.1*
Root coat ^h	4	4	—	32	7	44	2*	1	5	4.1	6.6*	5.2*
—	5	5	—	15*	1*	16*	2*	1	4	4.4	7.0*	4.9*
—	2	—	Bux 300	27*	3*	47	4*	1	3	4.0	6.2*	4.7*
—	2	—	MIPC	36	8	40*	4*	1	5	4.2	6.2*	4.9*
—	2	—	TBPMC	48	8	43	3*	1	3	3.8	6.3*	4.9*
—	2	—	Monocrotophos	31	2*	45	5*	1	4	4.0	6.6*	4.6*
—	2	—	—	46	5	52	7*	2	7	3.5	4.8	4.4*
Control	—	—	—	48	7	52	23	1	9	3.5	5.3	2.9

^a2 kg/ha a.i. ^b1.3 kg/ha a.i. applied with lindane. ^c0.04% applied six times. ^dDamaged tillers 20 DT. ^e75 DT. ^fOn seedbed, 7 days after seeding (0.1 kg a.i. per 50 kg seed) and 1.5 kg/ha a.i. in field 1 DT. ^g1.5 kg/ha a.i. in field 1 DT. ^hSeedling roots coated with solution of 1200 ppm insecticide and 2% methyl cellulose before transplanting.

significantly more effective than other chemicals (Table 23). Carbofuran and unden also gave more protection against tungro virus and grassy stunt virus than did the other chemicals. At 50 days after transplanting, all treated plots except one had significantly less virus infection than the untreated control plots. Cartap and chlorphenamide gave the best protection from stem borers. Diazinon and unden did not control stem borers at any rate tested.

Cooperative insecticide trials. Different combinations and formulations of insecticides representing various systems of pest control were tested on IR24 during the dry season at three locations in the Philippines.

Only application of carbofuran or lindane granules soon after transplanting provided control of the whorl maggot at all locations (Table 24). Leafhopper and planthopper incidence generally was low, but tungro was a moderate problem at the Bicol station where all treatments protected the crop. Stem borer damage as shown by white heads was low, especially at the Bicol station, but all treatments reduced the formation of white heads. Except at Bicol, most treatments significantly raised the yield above that of the control. At Bicol the pest problems evidently were not severe because only one pest control system was advantageous for IR24.

In the wet season we tested the concept of coating the seedling roots of IR20 and IR22 with a solution of insecticide and a sticker at

the Bicol and Maligaya stations and at the Visayas Agricultural College.

Up to 45 percent of the tillers were damaged by whorl maggots. No treatment effectively controlled the insect on either IR20 or IR22. The tungro infection in IR20 was low at all locations and no effect of the treatments was detected (Table 25). As a result, except for mobam at Bicol, no treatment significantly improved the yield of IR20. IR22 however became severely infected with tungro by 70 days after transplanting. The effect of the treatments varied with the location: all treatments provided some protection at the Visayas station, a few provided some protection at the Bicol station, but none were effective at Maligaya. In two locations the yield of IR22 was higher than the control due to root coating with carbofuran, carbaryl, or MIPC. Therefore root coating appears to have some promise for use on IR22 because of IR22's susceptibility to tungro, even though similar results were not achieved in all locations.

INTEGRATED CONTROL OF INSECTS

Integrated pest control means using all compatible techniques to reduce and hold pest populations below the levels that cause economic injury. Only two major control methods can now be used in tropical rice production: chemical control and plant resistance. For integrated control narrow-spectrum pesticides

should be used minimally and should not destroy beneficial organisms which aid in biological control.

Insecticides and plant resistance. In the dry season we tested several combinations of

prophylactic applications (Table 26) with IR8, IR20, and C4-63(G) at Bicol, Maligaya, and Visayas. These varieties differ in response to attacks of insects and virus diseases. Table 27 shows representative results at one station.

Table 25. Effect of coating seedling roots of IR20 and IR22 with various insecticides, using methyl cellulose as a sticker, on hills with tungro virus and grain yield. Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station (B), Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (M), and Visayas Agricultural College (VAC), 1972 wet season.

Insecticide (1000 ppm)	Tungro virus ^a (%)						Yield (t/ha)					
	IR20			IR22			IR20			IR22		
	B	M	VAC	B	M	VAC	B	M	VAC	B	M	VAC
Carbofuran	3	4	0	10*	26	11*	4.1	2.7	3.0	3.5*	1.9	3.1*
Carbaryl	3	3	0	8*	25	38*	4.4	2.7	3.1	3.3*	1.8	2.3*
MIPC	1	3	0	13*	33	40*	3.6	3.1	3.1	3.7*	1.9	2.4*
Mobam	2	6	0	33	32	24*	4.6*	2.7	3.0	2.8	2.0	1.9
Methomyl	2	3	0	30	34	41*	4.4	2.9	2.8	2.8	1.9	1.4
Diazinon	3	4	0	22	39	33*	4.4	3.0	2.3	2.1	1.5	1.3
Cartap	5	6	0	44	26	39*	4.2	2.6	2.5	2.2	2.0	2.0
Lindane ^b + Unden	2	5	0	8*	38	33*	4.1	2.6	2.3	3.2	1.5	2.2*
Lindane ^b + TBPMC	2	3	0	26	32	33*	4.1	2.8	2.6	3.0	1.8	2.1
Control	2	4	1	43	35	79	3.3	2.9	2.8	2.2	1.8	1.3

^a70 DT. ^bApplied at 500 ppm.

Table 26. Treatments for testing integrated control practices using both foliar sprays (S) at 0.04% concentration and granules (G) applied to the paddy water. Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, 1972 dry season.

Treatment	Seedbed	Carbofuran root coat	Field application			Cost ^a (P/ha)
			Chemical	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Number	
A	Carbofuran (G)	—	Carbofuran (G)	1.5	5	1231
B	MIPC (S)	✓	Lindane (G)	2	2	844
			Monocrotophos (S)	—	2	
C	—	✓	Lindane (G)	2	1	645
			Ureadrin (G)	2	2	
D	MIPC (S)	✓	Ethyl and methyl parathion (S)	—	2	1256
			Terracur (G)	2 & 3	2	
E	MIPC (S)	—	Azinphosmethyl (S)	—	2	539
			—	—	—	
Control	—	—	—	—	—	0

^aOf insecticide and application.

Table 27. Value of prophylactic treatments on varieties differing in insect and disease resistance. Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, 1972 dry season.

Treatment	Whorl maggot ^a (%)	Tungro virus hills ^b			Grain yield (t/ha)			Net return ^c (P/ha)		
		IR8	IR20	C4-63(G)	IR8	IR20	C4-63(G)	IR8	IR20	C4-63(G)
A	0*	2*	0	1	5.8*	5.1*	3.2	2721*	2242	1086*
B	28	18*	2	3	2.5*	4.5	3.1	878	2204	1439*
C	23	26*	5	5	2.6*	4.6	3.4	1108	2478	1859
D	23	23*	3	5	2.3*	4.4	3.6	305*	1719*	1362*
E	7*	11*	3	4	4.9*	4.1	3.7	2801*	2238	2153
Control	28	73	6	5	1.5	3.8	3.0	1007	2574	2152

^aDamaged tillers 20DT; avg of three varieties. ^b75 DT. ^cValue of rough rice minus cost of insecticide and its application. Rice price: P682/t for IR8 and IR20, P727/t for C4-63(G).

In general, carbofuran and Terracur granules applied to the paddy water soon after transplanting controlled the whorl maggot. The tungro-resistant varieties IR20 and C4-63(G) showed very little infection, and therefore did not benefit from treatment. However where susceptible IR8 became infected it benefited from insecticide application, especially from treatment A which provided continuous protection. As a result of this protection, treated IR8 outyielded the control. Only one treatment for IR20 at one location caused a yield increase which demonstrates the general insect and virus disease resistance of this variety. C4-63(G) also did not usually benefit from pesticide use except at Visayas where several treatments improved the yield. For IR20 and C4-63(G) applications of pesticides usually did not raise the net returns, at least under conditions of relatively low insect infestation. On the other hand several treatments were profitable with IR8, even with these expensive insecticide applications. Therefore it is important to integrate varietal resistance into a pest control program. Sometimes no pesticide is needed to achieve good yields with IR20 and C4-63(G).

In the same season we protected IR20 at IRRI with varying amounts of pesticides. Here again none of the treatments increased the yield above that of the control.

In the wet season at Bicol, Maligaya, Visayas, and IRRI we tried to find a simple integrated system for controlling tungro and insects by combining varietal resistance, pesticides, and cultural practices (Table 28).

Roguing of infected plants did not lower the percentage of hills infected. In these experiments IR20 responded to the maximum pesticide treatment at all locations. This was largely due to the control of stem borers. At two stations there was an unexpected yield response from early protection as well, and the reason for this is not known. The performance of IR22 was the same as that of IR20 at three locations, but at IRRI, IR22 also benefited from early protection because the insecticide prevented the tungro virus from infecting the plants severely. These experiments again demonstrated that there is a variety-insecticide interaction that should be used in an integrated program. Varietal resistance can sometimes replace a pesticide treatment.

Predation. An improved predator-prey balance to complement insect resistance of plants would mean better pest control. We appraised the indirect influence of insect resistance on the density of natural enemies.

In an unreplicated preliminary trial we grew IR8 (resistant to the green leafhopper), IR1561-228-3 (resistant to the brown planthopper), IR1514A-E666 (resistant to both insects), and IR22 (susceptible to both). Unfortunately both green leafhoppers and spiders were scarce in all plots. The density of brown planthoppers was low on resistant plants, but high on susceptible plants (fig. 6). We often found more predators, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter, than brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers combined, especially in the plots with plants resistant to brown planthoppers. So, low numbers of brown

Table 28. Grain yield as affected by simple integrated pest control practices. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Visayas Rice Experiment Station, and IRRI, 1972 wet season.

Treatment				Yield (t/ha)							
Seedbed treated ^a	Root coat ^b	Roguing ^c	Paddy water application	Maligaya		Bicol		IRRI		Visayas	
				IR20	IR22	IR20	IR22	IR20	IR22	IR20	IR22
✓	✓	✓	✓ ^d	3.5*	1.9*	4.6*	4.5*	4.8*	5.2*	6.0*	4.9*
✓	✓	✓	✓ ^e	3.4*	2.0*	4.2*	3.6*	4.2	4.6*	4.9	3.8
✓	✓	✓	—	3.5*	2.1*	4.2*	3.9*	4.1	4.2*	5.0	3.4
✓	✓	—	—	3.4*	1.9*	4.1*	3.6*	—	—	4.6	3.7
—	—	✓	—	2.7	1.2	3.7	2.1	—	3.3	4.7	3.7
—	—	—	—	2.6	1.0	3.2	2.5	4.0	3.3	5.0	3.7

^aCarbofuran granules applied to seedbed at 3 and 13 days after seeding at 2 kg/ha a.i. of seedbed area. ^bSeedling roots coated with solution of carbofuran (1000 ppm) and methyl cellulose (2%). ^cHills showing virus symptoms were rogued and replaced with healthy seedlings at 10, 20, and 30 DT. ^dCarbofuran granules applied at 1 kg/ha a.i. at 40 and 65 DT. ^eLindane granules applied at booting at 1 kg/ha a.i.

6. Density of *Nilaparvata lugens* and of the predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on IR8 (susceptible to brown planthopper) and IR1514A-E666 (resistant). IRRI, 1972 wet season.

planthoppers on resistant plants do not necessarily mean few predators.

Predators are natural biological control agents which should be conserved if possible. We need chemical pesticides that kill pests but not predators. Commonly used chemicals however, may kill predators as well as pests. We noticed previously (1971 Annual Report) that diazinon probably kills *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. This year we observed the predator and the pest densities in plots treated with lindane or carbosulfan granules every 20 days, or with MIPC, CPMC, or methyl parathion sprayed every 10 days. The densities of spiders and *C. lividipennis* were at the levels expected except where methyl parathion had been sprayed. Despite a high density of brown planthoppers (hopperburn resulted), incidence of this predator remained low (fig. 7). The methyl parathion probably

Table 29. Damage by different populations of *Nephotettix virescens* caged on plants of IR22 (susceptible) and IR20 (resistant) in the greenhouse 40 days after seeding. IRRI, 1972.

Population pressure	IR22 ^a		IR20 ^a	
	Tillers ^b (no./plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Tillers ^b (no./plant)	Panicles (no./plant)
High ^c	4 d	0 d	22 b	18 b
Moderate ^d	20 c	17 c	28 ab	23 a
Low ^e	26 b	22 b	28 a	23 a
No insects	28 a	24 a	30 a	27 a

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bSixty days after infestation. ^cPopulation growth was not limited. ^dMaximum of one pair of adults and 50 nymphs per plant. ^eMaximum of one pair of adults and 10 nymphs per plant.

killed many predators which allowed the high pest density to build up. Thus methyl parathion should not be used repeatedly where brown planthoppers are a problem.

Timing of pesticide application. For maximum effectiveness and to eliminate unnecessary pesticide treatments, timing of application must be optimal. If an insect population has distinct generations, a pesticide may be applied to interrupt its life cycle. We applied MIPC foliar spray (0.04%), which causes rapid mortality of brown planthoppers, when the nymphal density was rapidly increasing (after a hatch began), or at the peak nymphal density in each generation (about when third-instar nymphs dominated), or when the nymphal density was rapidly decreasing. Only the application at peak nymphal density in each generation adequately controlled the pest population (fig. 8). So one treatment per generation of a planthopper population large enough to cause an economic yield loss should prevent direct damage. But a pesticide applied at an inappropriate time may have little effect.

The concept of an economic injury level or economic threshold—the lowest pest density that will cause economic damage—is critical to the minimal but effective use of pesticides. Applying a quick-acting pesticide at the economic threshold level puts pest control on a sound economic basis. In the greenhouse we tried to determine the economic threshold for *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix virescens* in relation to the number of insects and the length of infestation. We allowed the insect populations

caged on the plants to increase to certain levels to simulate population pressures that could occur in the field over time.

Damage to IR22 by *N. virescens* (Table 29) was significant even at the low population pressure (maximum of 12 insects for 60 days), but damage to resistant IR20 was significant only at the high population pressure. IR20 had little damage because insect mortality was higher and, consequently, the population never reached the anticipated levels. Thus plant resistance must be considered when establishing threshold levels.

Yield loss in IR22 due to *N. lugens*, measured by the reduction in filled grains (Table 30), was noticeable at all population pressures. More panicles per plant were produced under the fluctuating density of the moderate insect pressure than under the constant density of the low pressure. Since populations continually fluctuate in the field, the damage threshold must be defined in number of insects per unit time.

Most yield loss probably occurs during the peak density of a generation. In the MIPC experiment (fig. 8), spraying at the peak density of a generation increased the yield by more than 0.5 t/ha above that of the untreated control. Another experiment showed that a crop can tolerate some planthoppers, perhaps one to five per hill, for short periods without yield loss.

INSECT ECOLOGY

Fluctuations in density of rice pests. Light trap collections at IRRI showed that green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers were generally as abundant in 1972 as they were in 1971, but

Table 30. Damage by different populations of *Nilaparvata lugens* caged on plants of IR22 in the greenhouse 70 days after seeding. IRRI, 1972.

Population pressure	Panicles (no./plant)	Filled grains (no./plant)
High ^a	4	14
Moderate ^b	18	208
Low ^c	7	203
No insects	18	373

^aMaximum of 100 insects/plant. ^bWhen population reached 50 insects/plant, it was reduced to five insects/plant. ^cMaximum of 10 insects/plant.

the peak numbers often occurred at different times from last year.

In cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry we set gas light traps and made field collections in 16 provinces. We measured field densities and related these to control procedures, damage, and forecasting potential. Insect infestations were localized or regional, and no widespread outbreak occurred. The techniques employed could be adapted to a simple surveillance system useful for supervised pest control.

Population dynamics of *N. virescens*. Under ideal conditions an insect population should increase with each generation until some density-dependent factor such as competition for space

7. Density of *Nilaparvata lugens* (brown planthopper) nymphs and of the predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on IR22 treated with methyl parathion (0.05% every 10 days) or left untreated. IRRI, 1972 wet season.

limits population growth. The rate of reproduction of an insect population is not always optimal, however.

To determine if plant age affects reproduction rate, we raised *Nephotettix virescens* on plants of various ages. After three generations the largest population was on plants 70 to 90 days old (fig. 9). In another test, plants were allowed to mature normally and peak insect populations occurred on 70-day-old plants. So a peak

8. Density of nymphs of *Nilaparvata lugens* on IR20 in relation to timing of insecticide application (MIPC at 0.04%). IRRI, 1972 wet season.

population should occur in the field about 50 days after transplanting. But other factors such as dispersal and season also influence populations (1971 Annual Report). Studies this year indicate that frequent fluctuations related to distinct generations also exist in the field.

To observe how seasonal conditions influence population density, we planted a crop each month and counted leafhoppers periodically. By comparing leafhopper densities at the same stage of crop maturity over time, we determined that a warm, moderately wet season facilitates population growth.

In another experiment we attempted to determine how host resistance affects a leafhopper population in the optimal environment of an insectary. We caged five pairs of newly emerged adults on the susceptible variety Taichung Native 1 and on the resistant varieties IR8, Pankhari 203, and IR20. On Taichung Native 1, a large leafhopper population built

9. Density of the third generation of *Nephotettix virescens* on IR22 plants of different age ranges in an insectary experiment.

up rapidly. On IR8 and Pankhari 203 the five pairs of insects died soon, so we introduced another five pairs. The second set also died quickly. On IR20 the introduced insects survived but both the first and second generations of insects were small. Thus, under these conditions, the resistance level of IR20 was between that of IR8 and that of Taichung Native 1.

Leafhopper incidence was also compared in the field on IR22, IR8, and IR20 during the dry season. In contrast with our findings last year (1971 Annual Report), the infestation on IR8 was almost identical to that on IR20, but the IR22 infestation was often three times higher.

In dispersal studies using sticky boards most flying leafhoppers caught were males and most were trapped within the first 70 days after transplanting.

Last year we reported that in the field, green leafhoppers appeared to prefer plants infected with tungro virus. In a study this year we introduced five pairs of adult green leafhoppers on both healthy and diseased plants in insectary cages. We found that on healthy plants the insects laid more eggs and many more nymphs hatched (fig. 10). We concluded that infected hills were not optimal for population growth. The apparent field preference may simply be a temporary behavioral response. In another field study we found that green leafhoppers did not seem to prefer hills infected with grassy stunt.

Population dynamics of *N. lugens*. We monitored the incidence of *Nilaparvata lugens* in a monthly planting experiment comparing insect numbers over time at the same crop age. Brown planthopper density was high from February to May and again from August to December, the two main cropping seasons at IRRI. This suggests that the presence of a host crop in neighboring fields contributes to higher populations.

Host resistance was studied in a manner similar to that used in the green leafhopper investigations. The four varieties were Taichung Native 1 and IR20 (both susceptible), and ASD 7 and Mudgo (both resistant). A few nymphs hatched on Mudgo, but soon died. A small population persisted on ASD 7. The insects multiplied on Taichung Native 1 and

IR20, but the population on Taichung Native 1 was larger. After two generations both varieties were about equally infested at a low level. Considering the pest's entire life cycle for several generations, the resistance of Mudgo and ASD 7 was confirmed, and IR20 was not as susceptible as Taichung Native 1.

We studied the relationship between field density and movement into and out of a plot as measured by insects caught on sticky boards. Macropterous adults were on the plants within a week after transplanting (fig. 11). Three major peaks in adult density occurred which coincided with peak sticky board catches: the first was mostly macropterous insects, the second mostly brachypterous insects, and the last mostly macropterous insects. Females were dominant in each peak. The adults of the first peak were immigrants, but later adults must have hatched and matured in the crop. The second adult peak produced the largest nymphal hatch. The last peak soon moved out of the field, usually flying at night, probably because the crop matured.

Some insects were caught on the sticky boards at 7 m above the ground, but more insects were caught nearer the ground.

10. Density of *Nephotettix virescens* in an insectary on IR22 plants infected with tungro virus and on healthy plants 50 to 70 days after seeding.

11. Change in density and composition of a field population of *Nilaparvata lugens* during a crop period. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

In another experiment we caged part of a field plot at 35 days after transplanting to trap the natural pest population. At harvest the population in the caged area was much larger (hopperburn occurred) than the population in the surrounding area. Assuming that the mortality rate was similar for caged and noncaged insects, the insects apparently flew out of the field when the crop matured.

Brown planthoppers often seem more numerous on hills infected with grassy stunt virus than on healthy hills. We checked this by inspecting pairs of hills (one healthy hill and an adjacent infected hill) for 12 days and removing all insects daily. We found significantly more nymphs on infected hills than on healthy hills. But a rearing test in the insectary suggested that healthy plants are slightly better hosts for population growth than plants infected with grassy stunt. Field preference for diseased hills may therefore be a behavioral phenomenon.

In the dry season we investigated how water management affects population density. When

12. Density of nymphs of *Nilaparvata lugens* on short Peta transplanted at spacings of 10 x 10 cm and 50 x 50 cm. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

the plots were continuously flooded, at least two large population peaks developed. Only one moderate peak developed when the field was kept saturated but not flooded. The population was negligible on rainfed plots in which the surface soil dried out. These findings reinforce the common belief that good agronomic practices often increase pest problems. Periodically draining the paddy might be a way to control brown planthoppers if the crop can tolerate it without losing yield.

To determine if high-tillering dwarf varieties with dense foliage encourage the growth of a brown planthopper population more than other varieties, we planted short Peta (an IR262 line) and tall Peta at spacings of 10 x 10 cm and 50 x 50 cm, and also planted IR20 at 10 x 10 cm, 25 x 25 cm, 50 x 50 cm, and 100 x 100 cm. We found no effect due to plant height. At the times of peak insect density, however, the 10-cm x 10-cm spacings of both tall and short Peta had significantly more brown planthopper nymphs per tiller than 50 x 50 cm (fig. 12). In

IR20, however, the populations were not significantly different. Preliminary measurements of the temperature and relative humidity showed that plants spaced closely provide a slightly cooler and more humid environment for planthoppers during the day than widely spaced plants. Thus high-tillering varieties may magnify a brown planthopper problem.

Competition between leafhoppers and planthoppers. To measure competition between *Nephotettix virescens* (green leafhopper) and *Nilaparvata lugens* (brown planthopper) we excluded or removed by hand certain segments of the fauna from field plots. Leafhopper density increased more when both brown planthoppers and predators were removed than when predators alone were removed (fig. 13). Predators lowered pest densities, apparently reducing or eliminating competition between leafhoppers and planthoppers.

When brown planthopper nymphs were at peak density, removing leafhoppers or predators did not raise the number of planthoppers, but when both leafhoppers and predators were removed, the planthopper density increased. Thus there seems to be competition between the two species. Planthoppers appear dominant because the brown planthopper population was

much larger than the green leafhopper population. Also, the feeding habits of the two species suggest that leafhoppers should suffer first in competition.

Predation and parasitism. *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* is a predator of green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers (1971 Annual Report). To determine what capacity the predator had to kill prey, this year we caged one to 20 adult predators with 20 green leafhopper nymphs (*Nephotettix virescens*). At a 1:1 predator-prey ratio, 100 percent of the nymphs were killed in 1 day, and from 65 to 80 percent were killed at other ratios.

In a similar test with brown planthopper nymphs (*Nilaparvata lugens*), predation was lower. At a 1:1 ratio, only 79 percent of the planthopper nymphs died in 1 day, while 23 percent died at the 1:20 ratio. But in some treatments, particularly where the predator-prey ratio was 1:4, mortality increased with time over a 7-day period. Thus *C. lividipennis* appears to be an effective predator, but more harmful to leafhoppers than to planthoppers.

The effectiveness of predators in controlling green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers was measured by observing the density of the prey populations in field plots. In some plots predators were either excluded or removed by

13. Density of green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens*) nymphs and adults in relation to brown planthopper competition and to predation. IIRRI, 1972 dry season.

14. Density of brown planthopper nymphs and of predators, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and spiders, in field plots where green leafhoppers were removed. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

hand, and in other plots the predators were left alone. Potential predators were *C. lividipennis*, spiders, coccinellid beetles, dragonflies, damselflies, birds, lizards, and toads.

We found that the green leafhopper population was suppressed by predators. But the brown planthopper population did not significantly increase in plots where predators were removed compared with control plots. When predators and green leafhoppers were both removed, however, the brown planthopper population significantly increased to maximum nymphal density. Based on predator numbers, the important predators seem to be *C. lividipennis* and spiders (mainly *Lycosa pseudoannulata* and *Theridion* spp.). When brown planthoppers were removed, *C. lividipennis* outnumbered green leafhopper nymphs, and the spider density approached that of the leafhoppers. When we removed green leafhoppers, the *C. lividi-*

pennis population at times became high compared with the number of brown planthopper nymphs, but the number of spiders was generally low (fig. 14).

It appears that leafhoppers and planthoppers, especially leafhoppers, might be substantially controlled under natural conditions by *C. lividipennis*, and, to a lesser degree, by spiders. Predator fluctuations, however, follow prey fluctuations, rather than coinciding with them. The predator populations apparently respond to increased pest density too late to prevent a pest from building up. So these predators are unlikely to be highly effective in suppressing outbreaks of nymphs.

The predatory activity of adult *C. lividipennis* against stem borer eggs was demonstrated by placing the predators in small cages with freshly laid egg masses of *Chilo suppressalis*. The eggs were almost always destroyed.

Population dynamics of stem borers. Techniques for predicting damage from stem borers would make pest control more economical. To monitor seasonal fluctuations in stem borer density and damage, we made monthly plantings of Malagkit Songsong, a variety susceptible to stem borers. We observed more egg masses and borers (about 10 to 25 borers per 100 tillers) in the wet season than in the dry season. In both seasons, dead hearts were more common (up to 40%) at 100 days after transplanting than at 50 days. White heads were as high as 15 percent.

IDENTIFICATION OF RICE INSECTS

Rice insects have not been thoroughly collected and identified anywhere in tropical Asia. We have begun an intensive insect collection from both rice fields and light traps at several locations in the Philippines.

More than 10,000 insects have been collected, mounted, labelled, and identified at least to the family level. The collection appears to contain about 630 species. So far, we have identified 240 species, including 50 species of leafhoppers and 20 species of planthoppers. We have sent 860 specimens representing about 40 species to various specialists for identification.

Soil chemistry

Studies of the chemical kinetics of some problem soils revealed the following yield-limiting factors: iron deficiency in a neutral aerobic soil; manganese and aluminum toxicities in an acid aerobic soil; excess electrolyte, excess sodium, and calcium and potassium deficiency in an alkali soil; excess electrolyte, excess sodium, and incipient K deficiency in a saline soil; iron toxicity in an acid latosolic soil; excess electrolyte and toxicity of aluminum and iron in one acid sulfate soil and toxicity of aluminum, iron, and H₂S in another; iron and zinc deficiency in a calcareous soil; and excess reduction products in a problem soil from Taiwan.

□ Striking varietal differences in resistance to injurious soils were observed. IR22, IR24, M1-48, and IR1008-14-1 tolerated iron deficiency on neutral aerobic soils and resisted manganese and aluminum toxicities on acid aerobic soils. Pokkali, MI 273, IR712-23-2, and IR1008-14-1 survived and produced grain on an alkali soil on which 77 varieties perished. SR 26 B, CAS 209, BG 79, Pelita I/1, and Pokkali showed strong resistance to salinity, while Pokkali, IR20, IR442-2-58, and IR441-20-3 manifested marked resistance to iron toxicity. SR 26 B, CAS 209, and Pokkali also showed resistance to excessive soil reduction. Among the varieties that yielded well in spite of phosphorus deficiency were CAS 209, BG 79, Doc Phung Lun A R-16, IR5, Pelita I/1, and Pelita I/2. □ The major yield-limiting factor on over 100,000 hectares of alluvial rice soils, well supplied with the major nutrients and with water, in Agusan del Norte and Agusan del Sur, Philippines was identified as zinc deficiency and corrected by applying zinc oxide. Rice farmers of these provinces can expect a return of 4 to 5 t/ha of rice per season for an additional P6 to P7 spent on zinc oxide, even in the absence of N, P, K fertilizers.

CHEMICAL KINETICS OF PROBLEM SOILS

Flooding or moistening a soil sets in motion a series of chemical and physicochemical changes. These changes influence the rate and magnitude of nutrient release or removal and the generation of substances that can harm the rice plant. Thus the chemical kinetics of soils profoundly influences the growth and yield of rice. Combined with soil and plant analysis and with plant observations, chemical kinetics is a valuable diagnostic tool in the study of problem rice soils.

In 1972, we compared the chemical kinetics of 10 problem soils with that of Maahas clay, a highly productive soil. Figure 1 shows how IR8 reacted to some of the soil conditions.

Maahas clay. Maahas clay (Table 1) is a nearly neutral montmorillonitic clay well supplied with available phosphorus and potassium and buffered against excessive reduction by Fe (III) and Mn(IV) oxides. Examination of the chemical kinetics of submerged Maahas clay (fig. 2) revealed that peak specific conductance was less than 4 mmhos/cm, the threshold for salt injury; that pH attained a fairly constant value of about 6.8, 2 weeks after submergence; that redox potential (Eh) was positive throughout submergence; that the concentrations of phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, and manganese in the soil solution were adequate for healthy growth of rice; that the manganese-to-iron ratio in the soil solution was less than 1; that high concentrations of reducing substances

and organic acids in the soil solution were shortlived; and that the partial pressure of CO₂ never exceeded 0.2 atm.

IR8 grew and yielded well on this soil (Table 2). Chemical analyses of the straw revealed adequate levels of mineral elements and an excess of none.

Aerobic soils. The yield of rice on aerobic soils rarely exceeds 60 percent of the yield on the same soil rendered anaerobic by submergence. If the growth-limiting factors are identified, it may be possible to reduce their severity by soil management and thereby increase the yield of rice on nonflooded soils.

We studied the chemical kinetics of three aerobic soils: Luisiana clay, pH 4.6; Maahas clay, pH 6.6; and Pila clay loam, pH 7.5 (fig. 3). All three had redox potentials well above 0.2 v, the level below which iron becomes available and the concentration of iron in the soil solutions was less than 1 ppm. In the acid soil, the pH decreased sharply 8 weeks after planting causing an increase in concentration of manganese, an increase in the manganese-to-iron ratio to over 500, and a rise in the concentration of aluminum to 1 ppm.

The chemical kinetics suggested that the yield-limiting factors were iron deficiency in all three soils, and, in addition, manganese and aluminum toxicities in the acid soil. Plant symptoms agreed with these observations: plants on the Maahas clay and Pila clay loam showed clear symptoms of iron deficiency, while those on Luisiana clay

1. IR8 on Maahas clay (middle pot) and on some problem soils.

Table 1. Chemical properties of Maahas clay and 10 problem soils.

Soil	pH	Organic matter (%)	N (%)	Fe (%)	Mn (%)	CEC ^a (meq/100 g)	Exch. K (meq/100 g)	Available P (ppm)	Available Zn (ppm)
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	0.13	2.18	0.16	39.2	1.21	30	3.2
Luisiana clay	4.8	3.2	.19	3.30	.05	25.3	0.50	7	11.4
Pila clay loam	7.5	1.5	.09	0.95	.08	30.0	0.36	18	8.6
Lateritic clay	4.8	1.5	.09	2.10	.01	9.4	0.19	5	1.2
Acid sulfate clay (A)	4.3	2.9	.17	1.12	.01	30.1	0.57	5	3.3
Acid sulfate clay (B)	3.6	9.5	.27	0.08	.00	23.0	0.04	4	1.4
Acid sulfate clay (C)	3.4	8.3	.18	1.91	.04	30.3	0.04	58	6.1
Cotabato clay loam	8.7	2.2	.07	0.63	.07	35.6	3.19	30	3.6
Bani clay	7.1	2.8	.09	0.59	.01	35.1	2.21	11	1.8
Tungshan silt loam	5.8	3.4	.20	1.30	.02	11.0	0.35	31	2.2
San Manuel clay	7.3	1.9	.11	1.80	.11	35.2	0.34	24	0.6

^aCation exchange capacity.

showed symptoms of manganese toxicity and later signs of severe aluminum toxicity. Plant analyses revealed a low content of iron in all three soils as well as a high content of manganese and a low content of phosphorus in the acid soil (Table 2).

An alkali soil. The poor growth of rice on submerged alkali soils is attributed to high pH and to iron and zinc deficiencies. But the chemical kinetics of Cotabato clay loam (fig. 4) suggested that excess electrolyte, calcium and magnesium deficiency, and excess reducing substances limit growth. Plants grown in this soil showed symptoms of calcium deficiency and of water stress. The straw at harvest contained adequate amounts of iron, manganese, and zinc, low concentrations of calcium and potassium, and a very high concentration of sodium.

To ascertain whether the observed effects of the Cotabato soil were due to the presence of Na_2CO_3 or to some other peculiarity of this soil, we studied the kinetics of Maahas clay treated with Na_2CO_3 (1.5%) to raise its aerobic pH to 8.5. Addition of Na_2CO_3 made the pH and concentrations of electrolyte, sodium, calcium, magnesium, potassium, iron, and manganese comparable to those in the Cotabato soil (fig. 5). Plant symptoms and plant analyses (Tables 2 and 3) were similar to those on the naturally alkali soil.

The limiting factors in the alkali soil were calcium and potassium deficiency. Excess reducing substances may have been another retarding factor.

A saline soil. The chemical kinetics of Bani clay, a nearly neutral saline soil (fig. 6), indicated that the sodium concentration was high and the

Table 2. Yield and straw analysis of IR8 on nine submerged and three aerobic soils.

Soil	Yield (g/pot)		Straw composition (%)							Straw composition (ppm)			Problem	
	Straw	Grain	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	Na	Si	Fe	Mn	Zn	Def.	Tox.
Maahas clay	196	161	0.7	0.13	2.6	0.18	0.27	0.2	7.9	191	665	27	—	—
Maahas clay (aerobic)	105	65	0.5	.08	2.8	.19	.26	0.1	7.0	36	252	—	Fe	—
Luisiana clay (aerobic)	149	36	1.8	.04	2.3	—	—	—	5.3	57	2660	—	Fe, P	Mn, Al
Pila clay loam (aerobic)	55	20	0.7	.06	3.2	—	—	—	5.9	25	34	—	Fe	—
Latosolic clay	24	18	—	.12	2.1	.30	.26	—	2.8	3080	922	51	—	Fe
Acid sulfate clay (A)	82	69	1.2	.04	2.6	—	—	—	3.6	150	115	53	P	—
Acid sulfate clay (B)	24	21	2.1	.04	2.3	—	—	—	4.1	1705	321	62	—	Al, Fe
Acid sulfate clay (C)	0	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Al, Fe, H_2S
Cotabato clay loam	9	1	1.5	.27	0.1	.07	.27	3.8	9.9	131	248	—	K, Ca	Salt, red. subs.
Bani clay	26	27	1.8	.18	1.6	.19	.36	1.1	6.3	148	336	29	—	Salt
Tungshan silt loam	53	29	2.1	.13	3.1	—	—	—	3.3	207	452	—	—	Red. subs.
San Manuel clay	58	51	0.7	.08	2.8	—	—	—	7.1	89	1220	7	Zn, Fe	—

VARIETAL RESISTANCE TO INJURIOUS SOILS

In 1972 we tested 85 varieties and selections provided by the varietal improvement department and overseas collaborators for resistance to adverse soil conditions, and found many striking differences (fig. 11).

Aerobic soil conditions. IR22, IR24, M1-48, and IR1008-14-1 tolerated iron deficiency on

neutral aerobic soils and resisted manganese and aluminum toxicities on acid aerobic soils. These varieties are better adapted to aerobic soils than other improved varieties. Peta and IR878B4-220-3, by the same criteria, are utterly unsuited to aerobic soils, acid or neutral.

A previous study (1971 Annual Report) suggested that M1-48, IR127-80-1, IR577-11-2, and IR661-1-170 were adapted to acid aerobic soils. In the 1972 wet season we sought con-

5. Kinetics of Maahas clay treated with NaCl or Na₂CO₃.

3. Chemical kinetics of three aerobic soils.

and a low redox potential. Apparently, consumption of oxygen in the rhizosphere by these substances impaired root activity and retarded growth. Some of the organic metabolites may also have poisoned the plants and produced the purplish-brown spots and blotches characteristic of "suffocation disease."

A calcareous soil. At Luna, Agusan del Norte, Philippines, rice appeared to be suffering from severe iron deficiency on San Manuel clay although the soil was submerged. The chemical

4. Chemical kinetics of a submerged alkali soil (Cotabato clay loam).

analysis of the soil (Table 1) revealed no abnormality except zinc deficiency. But when we studied the kinetics of this soil other unusual features came to light. It had a redox potential exceeding 0.2 v (fig. 10), and low concentrations of iron and manganese during the first weeks of submergence and zinc deficiency later (Table 6). Plant analyses revealed a very low content of zinc and a low content of iron (Table 2).

The growth-limiting factors were iron and zinc deficiencies.

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5. Kinetics of Maahas clay treated with NaCl or Na₂CO₃.

Table 3. Mean mineral composition of the straw of 50 varieties grown under eight soil conditions in the greenhouse, IIRRI, 1972.

Soil treatment	Composition (ppm)			Composition (%)					
	Fe	Mn	Zn	K	Na	Ca	Mg	P	Si
Maahas clay									
aerobic	59	309	22	2.31	0.01	0.17	0.26	0.14	6.8
submerged	145	507	26	2.51	0.10	.17	.28	.17	7.6
plus 1% CaCO ₃ , submerged	141	512	27	2.48	0.11	.18	.28	.16	7.1
plus 1.5% Na ₂ CO ₃ , submerged	114	264	28	0.30	2.56	.07	.26	.17	5.8
plus 0.5% NaCl, submerged	174	814	25	1.17	0.95	.24	.29	.12	6.1
Acid latosolic clay, submerged	2654	971	49	1.94	0.36	.27	.20	.14	2.9
Luisiana clay									
submerged	471	1136	25	1.49	0.32	.17	.20	.05	6.3
plus P, submerged	544	1027	24	1.58	0.35	.21	.24	.10	6.4

6. Chemical kinetics of a saline soil (Bani clay).

firmation of this finding in a replicated experiment on a sloping acid latosolic soil in Luisiana, Laguna, Philippines. We included IR442-2-58 and IR20 for comparison. Because phosphorus deficiency limits the yield of rice on acid aerobic soils, we studied the performance of these varieties with and without 50 kg/ha P as superphosphate. All plots received 50 kg/ha N at planting and 50 kg/ha N at panicle primordia initiation. The plots were row seeded at 80 kg/ha and hand weeded. IR577-11-2 gave the highest yield of grain with and without phosphorus fertilizer; M1-48, the lowest (Table 7). The mean response to phosphorus was 1.0 t/ha.

In a later experiment in the 1972 wet season on two similar soils in Luisiana we tested the effect of 50 kg/ha P on M1-48 after increasing the

7. Chemical kinetics of water-soluble iron in two submerged soils.

8. Chemical kinetics of three acid sulfate soils.

seeding rate to 120 kg/ha. In spite of lodging in the phosphorus-treated plots, phosphorus increased the yield from 1.8 to 4.3 t/ha on one

soil and from 2.9 to 4.0 t/ha on the other. It is remarkable that under the shade of coconut palms at the second location M1-48 yielded 4 t/ha in 4 months (fig. 12).

9. Chemical kinetics of a highly reduced soil (Tungshan silt loam).

Alkalinity. Eighty-five varieties and selections were grown in the greenhouse on submerged Maahas clay whose aerobic pH had been raised to 8.5 by adding Na₂CO₃ at the rate of 1.5 percent by weight of the soil. The chemical kinetics of this artificial alkali soil resembled that of the natural alkali soil, Cotabato clay loam (cf fig. 4 and 5).

Pokkali, MI 273, IR1008-14-1, IR626-1-112, IR712-23-2, IR1006-28-6, CICA 4, and IR24 survived and produced grain on this soil, while 77 varieties perished within a few weeks of planting. Pokkali was by far the most resistant.

Salinity. Saline soils vary widely in salt content, composition of salts, pH, organic matter content, and content of available plant nutrients. Thus the effects of excess salt on the growth of rice are often confounded with those of other soil properties. To study the direct effect of excess electrolyte, we made Maahas clay, a productive soil, saline by adding NaCl at the rate of 0.5 percent by weight of the soil. The chemical kinetic pattern of this soil was very similar to that of Bani clay, a nearly neutral natural saline soil (cf fig. 5 and 6). So the performance of rice varieties on saline Maahas

10. Chemical kinetics of pH and Eh in San Manuel clay.

clay may be taken as a measure of their resistance to salt (NaCl) on an otherwise productive soil.

Of the 85 varieties tested in the greenhouse during the dry and wet seasons SR 26B, CAS 209, BG 79, Pelita I/1, Pokkali, and Doc Phung Lun A R-16 showed strong resistance to salt. IR24, IR712-23-2, IR1006-28-6, and IR442-2-58 were moderately resistant. Among the least resistant were M1-48, SML Apani, SML Acorni, and T 26.

Iron toxicity. The nutritional disorder of rice known as "bronzing," which occurs on strongly acid latosolic soils and on acid sulfate soils, is due to excess iron in the soil solution. We previously noted varietal resistance to iron toxicity (1970 and 1971 Annual Reports). In 1972 we screened 85 varieties including some varieties from earlier tests.

Using a combination of absolute grain yield, grain yield relative to that on Maahas clay, and symptoms, we were able to group the typical varieties: resistant—Pokkali, Pelita I/2, Mahsuri, Cadung Go Gung 1601, Cadung Phen R-92, Engkatek, CAS 209, RD1, LD66, IR20, IR442-2-58, IR441-20-3, and IR1154-223-2; moderately resistant—IR22, IR24, IR790-28-2, IR712-23-2, IR4-11, and CICA 4; and susceptible—IR8, IR5, Jaganath, BG11-11, BG34-8, CP 231 × SLO 17, ICA 10, T 141, M1-48, and IR424-21-PK2.

Of the varieties which were tested more than once, Pokkali and IR20 were consistently among the most resistant; M1-48 and IR424-21-PK2 were by far the most susceptible.

Excessive soil reduction. Excess of reduction products retards the growth of rice on certain

Table 4. Kinetics of water-soluble aluminum in three acid sulfate clays.

Weeks submerged	Al (ppm)		
	Acid sulfate clay (A)	Acid sulfate clay (B)	Acid sulfate clay (C)
0	0.6	156	437.0
2	.1	25	0.9
4	.1	9	0.4
6	.1	5	0.2
8	.1	6	0.2
10	.1	6	0.2

Table 5. Kinetics of water-soluble H₂S in two submerged soils.

Weeks submerged	H ₂ S (ppb)	
	Maahas clay	Acid sulfate clay (C)
1	1	964
2	1	237
4	4	124
6	1	18
8	3	16
10	1	1

Table 6. Kinetics of water-soluble iron, manganese, and zinc in a submerged calcareous soil (San Manuel clay).

Weeks submerged	Fe (ppm) Mn (ppm) Zn (ppm)		
	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Zn (ppm)
0	0.09	0.02	0.10
2	.07	0.10	.05
4	.08	0.23	.03
6	.83	4.4	.08
8	.95	15	.05
10	.71	15	.05
12	.70	12	.04

Table 7. Response of six varieties to 50 kg/ha P on an aerobic acid soil in a farmer's field, 1972 wet season.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	No P	P
IR20	3.3	4.0
IR127-80-1	3.2	4.7
IR442-2-58	3.2	4.0
IR577-11-2	3.9	5.4
IR661-1-170	3.4	4.1
M1-48	2.4	3.1

soils. Since the obvious remedy of draining and aerating the soil is often not feasible, varietal resistance to this soil condition that we first reported in 1970 (1970 Annual Report) was further explored.

11. Varietal resistance to injurious soil conditions.

Of the 50 varieties tested in the greenhouse, the most resistant were Pokkali, CAS 209, SR 26B, BG 79, Doc Phung Lun A R-16, and Doc Phung R-37. IR712-23-2, IR20, IR8, and IR24 were moderately resistant. The most susceptible variety was the upland variety M1-48.

Phosphorus deficiency. Because phosphorus deficiency is widespread in tropical rice soils and may require heavy fertilization to correct, screening of varieties for capacity to yield well on phosphorus-deficient soils, begun in 1970, was continued.

The most resistant varieties in the 1972 tests were Pelita 1/1, Pelita 1/2, CAS 209, Engkatek, Doc Phung Lun A R-16, Cadung Go Gung 1601 and BG 79. The moderately resistant varieties included IR5, IR8, IR20, and IR24. Among the least resistant varieties were Pokkali, M1-48, SML Acorni, T 26, CP 231 × SLO 17, and IR712-23-2.

The field resistance to phosphorus deficiency of 40 varieties used in the 1971 greenhouse tests was studied in the 1972 dry season on a phosphorus-deficient latosolic clay in an irrigated farmer's field at Luisiana, Laguna, Philippines, with and without 50 kg/ha P, over a basal dressing of 100 kg/ha N and 50 kg/ha K. All varieties responded to phosphorus as measured by increase in the mean number of tillers per hill 5 weeks after transplanting (from 13.8 to 21.5) and in the mean of phosphorus content of the plant (from 0.14 to 0.21%). But the increase in grain yield varied from 0 to 51 percent. Using a combination of absolute grain yield and grain yield relative to that on the phosphorus-treated soil, the varieties were divided into three groups: resistant—IR20, H4, RDI, IR506-1-36, IR626-1-112, IR790-5-1, IR790-28-6, IR878B2-83-3, IR879-183-3, IR937-76-2, IR1163-142-3, IR1170-261-3, and IR1168-21-3; moderately resistant—IR5, IR8, IR22, IR24, IR262-43-8, IR665-58-2, IR751-595, IR790-28-1, IR790-28-5, and IR937-55-3; and susceptible—IR790-54-1, IR878B4-220-3, and IR1163-152-1.

Overall resistance to soil injury. Rice varieties vary widely in their resistance to injurious soils. Table 8 and figure 13 show that some varieties are better adapted than others to one or more of the adverse soil factors. The varieties suited

12. Response of M1-48 to P fertilizer on an acid aerobic soil.

to the widest range of soil conditions are Pokkali, CAS 209, Doc Phung Lun A R-16, BG79, and IR24; among the least adapted are T26, M1-48, RP5-3, BG34-8, Bala, IR747B2-6-3, and the three IR1561 lines.

Pokkali shows promise as a source of resistance to alkalinity, salinity, iron toxicity, and reduction products. CAS 209 and SR 26B may confer salt resistance on their progeny, and Pelita 1/1 and Pelita 1/2, resistance to phosphorus deficiency.

ZINC DEFICIENCY

Zinc deficiency is the most important reason for low yields of rice on 80,000 hectares of flat, wet, alluvial soils in Agusan del Norte, Philippines (1971 Annual Report).

N, P, K experiments. At the time we identified a widespread nutritional disorder of rice in Agusan del Norte as zinc deficiency, farmers told us that its incidence and severity had increased with the use of N, P, K fertilizers and the new improved varieties. But the single experiment we conducted to test this assertion (1971 Annual Report) gave a negative result. Because theoretical considerations suggested that N and P fertilizers should aggravate zinc deficiency by immobilizing zinc as zinc ammonium phosphate, a highly insoluble compound, we installed a factorial experiment involving nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and zinc at 11 locations in Agusan del Norte in the 1972 dry season. The variety was C4-63G and

13. Varietal reaction to injurious soil conditions: Pokkali is resistant, except to phosphorus deficiency; M1-48 is susceptible, except to iron deficiency.

we used 0 and 60 kg/ha each of N, P, and K. The zinc treatments were no zinc and dipping the seedlings in a 2-percent suspension of zinc oxide in water just before transplanting. The plots at five locations were damaged by rats. Table 9 summarizes the data for the other locations.

In the absence of zinc, N, P, K fertilizers depressed the yield of grain at three locations, confirming the observation of some farmers. While the responses to nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the presence of zinc ranged from 0.4 to 1.2 t/ha, the response to zinc averaged for all levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium was as high as 4.2 t/ha. The mean yield for the "zinc only" treatment for the six locations was 4.47 t/ha.

These experiments were carried out on established rice farms. But there are thousands of hectares of abandoned rice land topographically well suited to rice cultivation. To ascertain

Table 8. Varietal reactions^a to injurious soil conditions.

Designation	Fe def. (aerobic)	Alkalinity	Salinity	Fe toxicity	Reduction products	P deficiency
IR5	MR	S	MR	S	MS	MR
IR8	MR	S	MR	S	MR	MR
IR20	MR	MS	MR	R	MR	MR
IR22	MR	S	S	MR	MR	MR
IR24	R	MR	MR	MR	MS	MR
IR4-11	MS	S	MR	MR	—	R
IR4-93-2	S	S	MR	S	—	MR
IR424-21-PK2	MS	S	MR	S	—	MR
IR441-20-3	S	S	S	R	—	S
IR442-2-58	MR	MR	MR	R	MS	MS
IR579-48-1	MR	S	MR	MS	—	S
IR579-48-2	MR	S	MS	S	—	S
IR580E420-1-1	MR	S	MR	S	—	MR
IR626-1-112	MR	MR	MR	—	MR	MR
IR661-1-170-1	MR	MS	MR	MR	—	MR
IR712-23-2	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	S
IR747B2-6-3	MS	S	S	S	—	S
IR878B4-220-3	S	MS	S	MS	—	S
IR1006-28-6	MR	MR	MR	MS	—	MR
IR1008-14-1	MR	MR	S	MS	S	MS
IR1154-223-2	MS	S	MR	R	—	MS
IR1154-681-2	MS	S	MR	S	—	MR
IR1561-43-2-2	S	S	S	MS	MR	S
IR1561-243-5-6	MS	S	MS	S	—	S
IR1561-250-2-2	MS	S	MS	S	—	S
Bahagia	S	S	MR	MR	MR	R
Bala	MS	S	S	S	MR	S
BG 11-11	S	S	MS	S	—	MR
BG 34-8	MR	S	MS	S	—	S
BG 34-11	MR	S	S	MS	—	S
BG 79	MR	S	R	MR	R	R
BKN 6806-18	MS	S	MR	S	MR	MR
C 12	MR	MR	MR	MS	R	MR
C 22	MR	S	MR	S	S	S
Cadung Go Gung 1601	S	S	MR	R	MR	R
Cadung Phen R-92	S	S	MS	R	MS	R
CAS 209	MR	S	R	R	R	R
CICA 4	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR
CO 34	—	S	MS	S	MS	S
Columbia 1	S	—	S	S	S	S
CP 231 × SLO 17	MS	S	MR	MS	—	S
CR 94-13	MS	S	MR	MR	MR	MR
DB 4	MR	MR	MR	MS	MS	MS
Doc Phung Lun A R-16	MR	S	R	MR	R	R
Doc Phung R-37	MR	S	R	MS	R	MR
Engkatek	MS	S	MR	R	MR	R
ICA 10	S	MR	MR	S	S	S
Jaganath	MR	S	R	S	MR	MR
LD 66	MR	S	MR	R	—	MS
M1-48	MR	S	S	S	S	S
Mahsuri	MR	S	MR	R	MS	MR
Mehran 69	MR	S	MR	MS	—	MR
MI 273	S	R	S	S	—	S
OS 4	MR	MR	S	S	—	S
Pelita I/1	MS	S	R	MS	—	R
Pelita I/2	MS	S	S	R	—	R
Peta	S	S	MR	S	—	MR
Pokkali	MR	R	R	R	R	S
RD 1	S	MR	S	R	—	R
RP5-3	S	S	S	S	MR	S

continued next page

Table 8. Continued

Designation	Fe def. (aerobic)	Alkalinity	Salinity	Fe toxicity	Reduction products	P deficiency
SML Acorni	S	MR	S	S	MR	S
SR 26 B	MS	S	R	MS	R	R
T 26	S	S	S	S	S	S
T 442-35	MR	S	S	MS	MS	MR
Taichung Native 1	MR	S	MR	MR	—	MS
TKM 5	MR	S	MS	S	—	MS

*R = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; S = susceptible; MS = moderately susceptible.

whether these lands carrying a dense growth of marsh plants could be made productive by the application of zinc, we installed, in cooperation with the Northern Mindanao National Agricultural College, a replicated experiment on an abandoned rice field. Zinc alone increased the yield of IR20 to 5.4 t/ha and that of C4-63G to 4.0 t/ha, while N, P, K fertilizers depressed yield (Table 10).

Although farmers were impressed by the dramatic response to zinc in experimental plots in their fields, they were skeptical about similar responses over large areas. To demonstrate that high yields are possible on a large scale, in the 1972 wet season we planted 1 hectare in a rice field which had been abandoned for the past 14 years. We plowed in the weeds, levelled the land, constructed bunds, and planted half of a hectare to IR20 and the other half to IR24. The only treatment was dipping the seedlings in a 2 percent suspension of zinc oxide before transplanting. No fertilizers were applied. Standard pest control measures were used.

IR20 produced 2.18 t of sun-dried grain (about 14% moisture) and IR24, 2.02 t, giving a total yield of 4.2 t/ha. But for some unevenness in the lower part of the field due to insufficient land preparation, the total yield might

have been 5 t/ha. Thus rice farmers in Agusan del Norte can expect a return of 4 to 5 t/ha of rice for P6 to P7 spent on zinc oxide, even without N, P, K fertilizers.

Residual effects. Table 11 shows that seedling treatment does not bring about a significant accumulation of available zinc in the soil but because this treatment was repeated each season, the average yield was not significantly different from those in which an accumulation of zinc occurred. The application of spent flashlight batteries brought about the highest accumulation of available zinc.

Varietal resistance to zinc deficiency. Last year we observed striking varietal differences in resistance to zinc deficiency (1971 Annual Report). Since the farmers in Agusan believed that the traditional varieties were not as susceptible to zinc deficiency as the modern ones, the performance of three locally grown varieties (Doce-doce, Bengawan, and Peta—all tall indica type varieties) was compared with that of five other varieties in the presence and absence of zinc.

Three to four weeks after transplanting, all varieties showed symptoms of zinc deficiency—brown spots on the older leaves, poor tillering, and stunting. But the severity of the symptoms,

Table 9. Response of C4-63G to N, P, K fertilizer with and without zinc in six farmers' fields in Agusan del Norte, 1972 dry season.

Soil type	pH	Organic matter (%)	Avail. Zn (ppm)	Response to N, P, K (t/ha)		Mean response to Zn (t/ha)
				No Zn	With Zn	
San Manuel clay loam	7.7	3.2	0.52	-1.6	1.2	4.0
Butuan clay	6.7	5.5	0.72	-0.8	1.0	2.8
Butuan clay	6.9	5.7	0.80	0.8	1.3	4.2
San Manuel clay loam	6.9	7.7	2.80	-0.2	0.4	1.0
San Manuel clay loam	7.7	5.1	1.34	1.7	1.0	0.4
Butuan clay	7.3	7.0	0.64	1.2	0.9	1.2

Table 10. Effect of zinc application on the grain yield of IR20 and C4-63G in the presence and absence of N, P, K fertilizer. Ampayon, Butuan, Philippines, 1972 wet season.

Treatment		Yield (t/ha)	
Zn	NPK	IR20	C4-63G
No	No	2.4	2.9
Yes	No	5.4	4.0
No	Yes	1.9	0.9
Yes	Yes	5.0	3.6

the zinc content of the plant, the rate of recovery, and the response to zinc varied. The symptoms were mildest, recovery was fastest, and zinc content of the plant was highest in IR20 and IR5 (Table 12). IR20 gave the highest yield in the no-zinc treatment and responded least to applied zinc. The tall indica varieties lodged and gave low yields whether zinc was applied or not.

Soil tests for available zinc. Soil samples collected from experimental plots in farmers' fields in Agusan del Norte were assayed for available zinc by the method of Lindsay and Trierweiler. A high correlation was observed between the content of available zinc in the soil on the one hand and plant performance and analysis on the other (Table 13).

Although the method is a good soil test for available zinc, it has some theoretical and practical disadvantages. So we modified an HCl extraction procedure that had been used widely earlier: we reduced the concentration of the acid to 0.05 N and the extraction time to 5 minutes. We found that available zinc by this method correlated well ($r = +0.963^{**}$) with available zinc by the method of Lindsay and

Trierweiler and with the zinc content of the plant ($r = +0.738^{**}$).

Since the new method is rapid, inexpensive, and convenient, we use it routinely in our laboratory as the soil test for available zinc. By this method deficient soils have less than 1 ppm Zn.

NITROGEN LOSSES IN FLOODED SOILS

Large amounts of nitrate are lost when air-dry soils are flooded (1964 and 1965 Annual Reports). Continuous submergence prevents these losses and leads to a substantial accumulation of nitrogen (1969 Annual Report). Because we suspected that considerable amounts of nitrate are lost during alternate drying and flooding of rice fields we surveyed these losses, and studied the kinetics of denitrification.

Nitrogen losses. Soil samples collected from 280 lowland rice fields in the Philippines shortly after harvest (when the soils are usually dry) were assayed for total nitrogen, available nitrogen, exchangeable NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- . Other soil characteristics were recorded to ascertain whether the NO_3^- content could be related to them. Since most of the NO_3^- present in a dry soil is denitrified when the soil is submerged, the nitrate content of a soil may be taken as a measure of the loss of nitrogen when it is flooded.

The NO_3^- content of a rice soil at harvest depends on total and available nitrogen content, cropping history, moisture regime, and weed growth. The NO_3^- content of cropped rice fields varied from 5 to 39 ppm, with a mean

Table 11. Residual available zinc after three successive crops as affected by form and method of zinc application. Ampayon, Butuan, Philippines 1971-72.

Treatment	Rate	Residual available Zn (ppm)			Avg grain yield ^b (t/ha)
		After 1st crop	After 2nd crop	After 3rd crop	
Seedlings dipped	2% ZnO ^a	1.6	2.0	2.2	5.0
Seedlings dipped	2% ZnCl ₂ ^a	1.4	1.8	2.0	4.8
ZnO	10 ppm Zn ^b	8.5	7.6	6.4	4.9
ZnCl ₂	10 ppm Zn ^b	8.6	7.4	5.2	4.8
ZnSO ₄	10 ppm Zn ^b	7.4	6.4	6.2	5.0
Flashlight battery	one/sq m ^b	22.4	47.5	19.7	4.9
Flashlight battery	two/sq m ^b	37.2	100.0	36.1	5.3
Control	—	1.0	1.0	1.4	4.4

^aThese treatments were repeated each season. ^bFor the three crops.

of 12.9 ppm. Since about 2 million hectares of land in the Philippines are flooded for rice cultivation annually, the country loses about 26,000 tons of nitrogen a year. Based on the price of ammonium sulfate this loss amounts to P56 million.

Kinetics of denitrification. The NO_3^- content and temperature strongly influence the rate of denitrification in flooded soils (1965 and 1969 Annual Reports). This year, we attempted to quantify these effects. We incubated three soils, Louisiana clay (pH, 4.6; organic matter, 3.2%), Tungshan silt loam (pH, 5.8; organic matter, 3.4%), and Keelung silt loam (pH, 7.7; organic matter, 6.8%) anaerobically at 15, 25, 35, and 45°C, and assayed NO_3^- at regular intervals.

The kinetics of NO_3^- showed roughly exponential trends in all three soils at all four temperatures. This suggested that denitrification followed first-order kinetics ($-dc/dt = kc$). To test this observation quantitatively, we plotted $\log(\text{NO}_3^-)$, where (NO_3^-) denotes concentration in moles per liter, against the period of incubation. The rectilinear regressions of $\log(\text{NO}_3^-)$ on time (fig. 14) reveal first-order kinetics for denitrification in each soil at each temperature and also temperature-dependent velocity constants for each soil.

Although soil is a complex heterogeneous system and denitrification is largely a bacterial process, the marked variation of the velocity constants with temperature suggested that the Arrhenius equation $k_T = Ae^{-E/RT}$ where k_T is the velocity constant at T° Kelvin, A is a constant, E is the activation energy, and R is the molar gas constant, might apply (strictly, the Arrhenius equation applies only to homogeneous systems). The rectilinear plots of $\log k_T$ on $1/T$ (fig. 15) indicate that the Arrhenius equation describes quantitatively the influence of temperature on the kinetics of denitrification in soils.

Table 13. Correlation between available zinc in the soil and plant performance.

Available zinc (ppm)	Zinc deficiency	Yield reduction	Zinc content of plant (ppm)
1.5 to 1.0	mild, transitory	moderate	12 to 14
1.0 to 0.6	severe, transitory	severe	10 to 12
< 0.6	very severe	very severe	< 10

Table 12. Grain yield and zinc content of eight rice varieties with and without zinc on Butuan clay (December 1971 to April 1972).

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		Yield increase with Zn (%)	Zn content (ppm) ^a	
	No Zn	Zn		No Zn	Zn
IR8	2.5	3.6	44	10.0	14.6
IR20	3.6	3.8	6	12.5	18.4
IR5	3.2	4.6	44	11.8	15.4
C4-63G ^b	2.4	2.9	21	9.7	14.3
Bengawan	1.9	1.9	0	9.0	13.7
Doce-doce	1.6	1.8	12	9.5	14.5
H 4	1.8	1.8	0	9.6	12.8
Peta	1.4	2.1	50	9.4	14.6

^aIn the plant 30 days after transplanting. ^bSuffered from a severe attack of bacterial leaf blight.

14. Relationship between $\log(\text{NO}_3^-)$ and time of anaerobic incubation at four temperatures in Louisiana clay, Tungshan silt loam, and Keelung silt loam.

KINETICS OF HYDROGEN SULFIDE

Although H_2S is a plant poison and has been blamed for some nutritional disorders of rice, there is little reliable data on the concentration of free H_2S in flooded soils. This dearth of information was due to the absence of a precise and sensitive method of measuring the concentration of H_2S . With the advent of the specific sulfide ion electrode, however, concentrations as low as $10^{-19} M S^{2-}$ can be measured and the H_2S concentration can be derived from the equation $\log H_2S = pK_1 + pK_2 + \log S^{2-} - 2 pH$. The sulfide ion electrode confers another advantage: the measurement can be made in the electrometric cell used for the simultaneous measurement of pH, Eh, and specific conductance (1964 Annual Report). Using the sulfide ion electrode we studied the kinetics of hydrogen sulfide in 10 soils.

The concentration of water-soluble H_2S increased on flooding, reached a peak 1 to 3 weeks later, and then decreased to a very low level (Table 14). Peak values were lowest (30 to 60 ppb) in neutral soils high in iron and manganese; they were moderately high (500 to 800 ppb) in soils low in iron or high in organic matter; and the values were highest in the acid sulfate soil low in iron.

Harmful concentrations of H_2S may be present in acid sulfate soils and acid soils low in iron during the first few weeks after flooding, but not later as generally supposed. The concentration in acid sulfate soils can be drastically

15. Relationship between $\log K_T$ and $1/T$ in Luisiana clay, Tungshan silt loam, and Keelung silt loam.

Table 14. Kinetics of H_2S in the solutions of 10 soils, 1 to 10 weeks after submergence.

Soil	pH	O.M. ^a (%)	Fe (%)	Mn (%)	H_2S (ppb)							
					1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk	8 wk	10 wk
Calbon clay	7.0	1.8	1.0	0.15	40	29	4	9	6	1	3	1
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	2.2	.16	1	1	18	4	6	1	3	1
Luisiana clay	4.6	2.8	2.1	.06	11	9	150	26	24	3	3	1
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	0.3	.06	106	192	451	542	192	42	32	3
Keelung silt loam	7.9	6.9	2.3	.07	1	4	506	46	58	27	3	1
Silt loam (Korea)	4.8	3.2	0.5	.06	139	542	1600	327	146	42	17	2
Acid sulfate clay (C)	3.4	6.6	2.6	.01	964	237	461	124	54	18	16	1
Acid sulfate clay (C) (limed)	5.5	6.6	2.6	.01	9	9	4	3	4	1	2	2
Acid sulfate clay (B)	3.6	6.3	0.08	.00	242	13000	30000	10000	3700	1400	1800	100
Acid sulfate clay (B) (limed)	5.5	6.3	0.08	.00	61	136	171	90	23	5	2	2

^aOrganic matter.

Table 15. Mean values of the ionic products of FeS (pK_{FeS}) and ZnS (pK_{ZnS}) in the solution of 10 submerged soils from the H_2S peak to 10 weeks after submergence.

Soil	pH	Organic matter (%)	Fe (%)	Mn (%)	H_2S peak (wk)	pK_{FeS}	pK_{ZnS}
Calbon clay	7.0	1.8	1.0	0.15	1	18.6	21.8
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	2.2	.16	1	18.5	21.5
Luisiana clay	4.6	2.8	2.1	.06	3	18.0	21.6
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	0.3	.06	4	18.1	21.1
Keelung silt loam	7.9	6.9	2.3	.07	3	17.9	20.7
Silt loam (Korea)	4.8	3.2	0.5	.06	3	18.1	21.4
Acid sulfate clay (C)	3.4	6.6	2.6	.01	1	16.9	21.3
Acid sulfate clay (C) (limed)	5.5	6.6	2.6	.01	1	17.2	21.4
Acid sulfate clay (B)	3.6	6.3	0.1	.00	3	17.9	21.2
Acid sulfate clay (B) (limed)	5.5	6.3	0.1	.00	3	18.1	21.9

lowered by liming (Table 14).

The rapid decline in H_2S concentrations coincided with the build-up of high concentrations of Fe and Mn in the soil solutions. This suggested that H_2S is being inactivated as insoluble FeS and MnS. A criterion for the presence of FeS is the constancy of the function $p\text{Fe}^{2+} + p\text{S}^{2-}$ and its approximation to 18.4

(the pK_s value of FeS) in spite of variations in the activities of Fe^{2+} and S^{2-} . Table 15 shows that FeS with a pK_s value of about 18.4 was present in six soils. The relative constancy of the value of $p\text{Zn}^{2+} + p\text{S}^{2-}$ at a value near 22.8, the pK_s of ZnS, suggests that ZnS was present in all the soils. Similar tests failed to reveal the presence of either MnS or CuS.

Plant physiology

Experiments with CO₂ enrichment proved that sink size (grain number) limits grain yield more than does source activity during ripening. The time from neck-node differentiation to spikelet differentiation was identified as the most important period for increasing sink size. □ In controlled-environment studies, high temperatures were required for active growth at early stages, but relatively low temperatures appeared favorable for high spikelet production. Large differences in photosynthetic rate among varieties of *Oryza sativa* and among different species of *Oryza* genus were found. Preliminary tests of heat tolerance and stomatal control of 12 varieties gave promising results for screening varieties for resistance to drought. □ Tests of varieties developed by other cooperating agencies from IRRI lines and of promising new IRRI lines showed that all were insensitive to photoperiod. □ Cold water treatment (12°C) of seedlings was found sufficient to produce differences in cold tolerance of rice varieties at the vegetative stage. □ A research project was started on the biology of *Scirpus maritimus*, a sedge which is resistant to most commercial herbicides and which is rapidly spreading in rice fields. Preliminary results indicate that mechanical control may be possible.

EFFECT OF CO₂ ON SPIKELET FORMATION

Carbon dioxide enrichment for 30 days before or after flowering significantly increases grain yield through either increased spikelet number or improved grain filling (1971 Annual Report). This year we attempted to determine the response of the rice plant to CO₂ enrichment at different stages of panicle development—from neck-node differentiation to rachis-branch differentiation, during spikelet differentiation, from the reduction-division stage to flowering, from neck-node differentiation to flowering, and from flowering to maturity.

Carbon dioxide enrichment before flowering increased grain yield by 30 percent over the control (Table 1), largely because of an increase in both grain number and grain weight. Enrichment for 9 to 10 days at the rachis-branch differentiation stage or at the spikelet differentiation stage raised grain yield by 10 percent, mostly by increasing the number of grains. On the other hand, CO₂ enrichment for 2 weeks from the reduction-division stage to flowering (when the plant is most sensitive to such stresses as low temperature and shading) did not affect grain yield. Enrichment for 30 days after flowering increased grain yield by 10 percent over the control, because of higher filled grain percentage and increased grain weight.

The number of differentiated spikelets minus those that later degenerated gives the number of developed spikelets (grains). The failure of CO₂ enrichment from the reduction-division stage to flowering to increase the grain number

suggests that spikelet degeneration is negligible in the dry season at Los Baños. So the critical time for determining the number of grains is from neck-node differentiation to spikelet differentiation—about 33 to 14 days before flowering. Carbon dioxide enrichment at early stages of panicle development therefore increased grain number, which, in turn, increased grain yield.

These experiments confirm earlier research (1971 Annual Report) which indicated that sink size (grain number) limits grain yield more than does source activity during ripening. More emphasis should be placed on panicle development before flowering because this determines sink size.

Several scientists claim that certain grain numbers are optimum for maximum yield under given climatic environments and that yield decreases if the number of grains increases beyond the optimum because fewer grains will be filled. We have found, however, that the filled grain percentage of IR8 is a nearly constant 85 percent over a wide range of grain numbers (1969 Annual Report). On the other hand, the filled grain percentage of the line IR667-98, an indica-japonica cross, decreased from 90 to 60 percent as grain number increased. The filled grain percentage of IR667-98 when $0 < N \leq 30$ can be expressed as $F = 0.85$ (constant), where F is the filled grain percentage and N is the grain number $\times 10^{-3}$ per square meter, but when $N \geq 30$, $F = 0.85 - 0.011(N - 30)$. Some scientists believe that excessive mutual shading causes a decrease in filled grains as grain number increases. That does not, however, explain the

Table 1. Effects of CO₂ enrichment before and after flowering on grain yield and yield components of IR8. IRRI, 1972 dry season.

Time of CO ₂ enrichment		Yield ^b (t/ha)	Grain no. ^b (10 ³ /sq m)	Filled grains ^b (%)	Grain wt ^{bc} (mg)
In relation to flowering (days)	Developmental stage ^a				
Control ^d	—	10.2 c	40.4 c	85.4 b	27.5 d
-33 to -24	I	11.3 b	45.0 ab	84.2 b	27.7 d
-24 to -14	II	11.4 b	43.4 bc	86.2 b	28.7 c
-14 to 0	III	10.2 c	38.9 c	85.8 b	29.1 bc
-33 to 0	I-III	13.3 a	48.2 a	87.6 b	29.9 ab
0 to 30	IV	11.5 b	38.9 c	92.4 a	30.2 a

^aI: Neck-node differentiation to differentiation of secondary rachis-branch, II: Differentiation of spikelets, III: Differentiation of pollen mother cell, reduction division stage to flowering, IV: Flowering to harvest. ^bAny means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cPanicles dried at 75° C for 48 hours, threshed, then grains were placed at 50° C for 12 hours and weighed. ^dNone.

difference between IR8 and IR667-98 in our study, because both varieties have erect leaves and IR8 usually develops a larger leaf area index by flowering time. Instead, this negative correlation appears to be a varietal characteristic of IR667-98. Varieties in which the filled grain percentage remains high as grain number increases should be selected to further increase grain yield.

TEMPERATURE AND GROWTH

In the tropics, excessive vegetative growth tends to depress grain yield, so agronomists do not generally emphasize early growth. But for rice varieties to be grown in relatively high altitudes, or for early maturing varieties, early growth should become an important plant characteristic, even in the tropics.

We studied how various temperatures in a controlled environment (Plant Physiology Division, Department of Scientific and Industrial Research, Palmerston North, New Zealand) affect the early growth of varieties IR8, Taichung Native 1, Jinheung, and Calrose. Mean air temperature in this experiment ranged from 22 to 31°C, with day and night temperatures differing by 8°C (22°C, for instance, was the mean of a 26°C daytime temperature and an 18°C nighttime temperature). Temperature variations within the selected range have little effect on rice photosynthesis. The selected range covered seasonal variations of temperature at Los Baños and many other low-altitude areas in the tropics. Light was supplied with Philips quartz halogen lamps and Sylvania metal arc lamps, giving 29 klx at trolley height with a balanced spectral composition.

Early growth. The rate of leaf emergence accelerated as temperatures rose; at 22°C, one leaf emerged every 5.4 days, but at 31°C, one leaf emerged every 3.5 days. Temperature influenced dry weight much more than did varietal difference, so only the mean values of the four varieties at each temperature are given in Table 2. After 4 weeks, dry weights differed widely between the temperature treatments. We computed mean relative growth rates and found that temperature affected growth much more in the first 3 weeks than in the fourth week.

To more closely examine the effect of temperature on early growth, we grew IR8 in the same environment for 3 weeks. Growth was divided into growth from seed reserve (G_s) and photosynthetic growth (G_p). Growth from seed reserve can be measured as $G_s = 0.6(S_1 - S_2)$ or $G_s = 0.6 \times \Delta S$, where S_1 and S_2 are weight of seed at time t_1 and t_2 , and 0.6 is growth efficiency.

In the first week after sowing, less than 30 percent of growth was from photosynthesis; the seed reserve supported most plant growth (Table 3). In the second week, 84 percent of the plant's growth was photosynthetic and by the third week growth depended totally on photosynthesis. We estimate that photosynthesis supports 95 percent of total growth at the 2.7-leaf stage.

We studied the effect of temperature on later growth by growing IR8 plants at 28°C for 3 weeks, then subjecting them to different temperatures for 2 weeks. Except at 22°C, plant growth was about the same for all temperatures (Table 4).

Temperature affected growth rate considerably in the first week. The temperature quotient (Q_{10}) was almost equal to 2, indicating that chemical reactions dominated growth. This result was expected because more than 70 percent of growth was supported by the seed's reserve, which is broken down by enzymatic action.

Relative growth rates ranged from a low of $1.16 \text{ g} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{wk}^{-1}$ at 22°C from 1 to 2 weeks to a high of $1.62 \text{ g} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{wk}^{-1}$ at 28°C and 31°C from 3 to 5 weeks (Table 5). Relative growth rates were far lower at 22°C than at higher temperatures. Growth did not differ much between 25°C and 31°C. Temperature affected

Table 2. Mean dry weights and mean relative growth rates of four varieties at different temperatures.

Mean temperature (°C)	Dry weight (g/plant) ^a		Relative growth rate (g · g ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)	
	3 wk	4 wk	0 to 3 wk	3 to 4 wk
22	0.09	0.29	0.45	1.15
25	0.23	0.74	0.75	1.18
28	0.26	0.89	0.78	1.25
31	0.30	1.08	0.83	1.28
Mean	0.22	0.75	0.70	1.21

^aInitial grain weight was 0.024 g.

Table 3. Growth of IR8 seedlings at different temperatures.

Mean temperature (°C)	Endosperm wt (mg/grain) ^a	Growth (mg/plant)			
		Total ^b	From seed reserve	From photosynthesis	Ratio (photosynthesis/total)
			<i>First week</i>		
22	9.2	8.1	7.3	0.8	0.10
25	6.9	10.7	8.7	2.0	0.19
28	4.3	13.7	10.3	3.4	0.25
31	3.1	15.7	11.0	4.7	0.30
			<i>Second week</i>		
22	2.6	25.7	4.0	21.7	0.84
25	1.3	49.6	3.4	46.2	0.93
28	1.2	62.0	1.9	60.1	0.97
31	1.0	71.4	1.3	70.1	0.98
			<i>Third week</i>		
22	1.1	81.9	0.3	80.7	1.00
25	1.0	201.8	0.2	201.4	1.00
28	1.2	239.2	0.0	239.2	1.00
31	1.1	286.4	0.0	286.4	1.00

^aInitial weight of endosperm was 21.4 mg per grain. ^bLSD (5%): First wk, 1.8; second wk, 8.5; third wk, 32.5.

growth most markedly in the first week after sowing; its effect decreased with time. For early growth of IR8, 22°C can be considered sub-normal.

Tillering. Varieties IR8 (indica) and Jinheung (japonica) were grown for 6 weeks at different temperatures in a controlled environment and their rates of tillering were measured. Higher temperatures increased the rate of tillering in both IR8 and Jinheung (Table 6), but IR8 seems to have a much higher tillering capacity than Jinheung.

The number of tillers counted weekly included not only the tillers formed during that week but also the tillers already present when the week began. To better determine how temperature affects tillering, we grew plants in the same environment for 3 weeks, then transferred them to separate rooms with different temperatures where they grew for another 2

weeks. Tiller increase was highest at 28°C and at 31°C, and lowest at 22°C. It is clear that high temperatures encourage vigorous tillering.

Spikelet number. IR8 was grown at four temperatures in a controlled environment until about 10 days after flowering. Time to flowering varied from 118 days at 28°C to 140 days at 22°C.

At 31°C, as leaves advanced in age to about the 20-leaf stage, the color of the leaf tips changed to brown and leaf tissues became brittle, suggesting internal moisture stress. Furthermore, flag leaves of 20 percent of the plants failed to develop midribs. As a result, these flag leaves drooped. At 22°C leaves turned orange-yellow around flowering time. Otherwise, the general appearance and specific plant characteristics, such as culm length and flag leaf size, were normal at all temperatures.

As temperatures increased, spikelet number decreased (Table 7). Although degenerated spikelets were not counted, they seemed more numerous at high temperatures, particularly at 31°C. Harvest indices would have been approximately 0.58 at 22°C, 0.56 at 25°C, 0.55 at 28°C, and 0.51 at 31°C, with assumptions of 85 percent filled grains, 29 g per 1,000 grains, and no loss in straw weight. These harvest indices are within the range encountered for IR8 in field experiments.

Because grain number is the major limiting

Table 4. Tiller number, dry weight, and relative growth rate of IR8 at different temperatures from 3 to 5 weeks after sowing.

Mean temperature (°C)	Tiller no. ^a	Dry wt (g) ^b	Mean relative growth rate (g · g ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)
22	7.0	3.73	1.40
25	8.4	5.21	1.56
28	9.4	5.91	1.62
31	9.2	5.87	1.62

^aInitial tiller number: 2.6. ^bInitial dry weight: 0.24 g.

Table 5. Growth rate of IR8 at different temperatures up to 5 weeks after sowing.

Mean temperature (°C)	Growth rate			
	0 to 1 wk (mg · plant ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)	1 to 2 wk (g · g ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)	2 to 3 wk (g · g ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)	3 to 5 wk (g · g ⁻¹ · wk ⁻¹)
22	8.1	1.16	1.16	1.40
25	10.7	1.53	1.40	1.50
28	13.7	1.51	1.35	1.62
31	15.7	1.52	1.39	1.62

factor of grain yield in the tropics, persons evaluating the climatic potential of a region for production should carefully consider the effect of low temperature on spikelet number.

Temperature effect on growth. Figure 1 summarizes the effect of temperature on rice growth until flowering. High temperatures are required for active growth at early stages. The effect of temperature then decreases with growth. At the reproductive stage, the optimum temperature for the rice plant shifts from high to low because lower temperatures appear to favor higher spikelet production.

PHOTOSYNTHESIS

Improved measurement technique. We improved the technique for measuring a plant's CO₂ exchange rate. To increase the precision of measurement, we replaced the integral type of infrared gas analyzer with a differential type. We also began using an air-sealed leaf chamber which allows us to measure the photosynthetic rate of a single intact leaf more accurately than using cut leaves. Measurements on cut leaves sometimes reflect ability to endure moisture stress caused by cutting in addition to photosynthetic ability.

To compare our measurements of rice photosynthesis with those of other laboratories, we determined the photosynthetic rates of two rice varieties and one sorghum variety using our improved technique. At a light intensity of 60 klx, the rice varieties produced about 50 to 60 mg CO₂ · dm⁻² · h⁻¹ and sorghum about 90 mg CO₂ · dm⁻² · h⁻¹ (fig. 2). These photosynthetic values for both rice and sorghum agreed with our previous measurements, but they were higher than values reported by other sources.

Leaf nitrogen and photosynthetic rate. In nine rice varieties grown in culture solution at four nitrogen levels photosynthetic rate was linearly related to nitrogen content (on a leaf area basis) (fig. 3). Photosynthetic rate and specific leaf weight were not closely correlated within samples, however. To further examine the relationship between photosynthesis and leaf nitrogen, we grew 23 varieties in pots at two nitrogen levels. The photosynthetic rate, specific leaf weight, nitrogen content, and nitrogen percentage were measured and correlated. The highest correlation was between nitrogen content and photosynthetic rate (Table 8). Specific leaf weight and nitrogen percentage were less correlated with photosynthetic rate.

We analyzed the second leaf from the top because it is one of the most active leaves. To examine the relationship between photosynthetic rate and nitrogen in leaves at different positions, IR8 was grown at seven levels of nitrogen in pots. The photosynthetic rate of leaves was closely correlated with leaf nitrogen content regardless of leaf position (fig. 4). The photosynthetic rate of leaves with high nitrogen

Table 6. Number of tillers produced by IR8, an indica variety, and Jinheung, a japonica variety, at different temperatures.

Mean temperature (°C)	Tillers (no.)				
	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
	<i>IR8</i>				
22	1.0	1.0	3.8	7.2	11.8
25	1.0	2.4	4.2	11.0	22.0
28	1.0	2.6	4.8	12.2	23.2
31	1.0	3.0	7.2	17.4	28.6
	<i>Jinheung</i>				
22	1.0	1.0	3.6	4.6	9.8
25	1.0	2.0	3.2	6.4	11.2
28	1.0	2.8	4.0	8.8	12.0
31	1.0	2.8	4.0	9.6	13.8

Table 7. Growth characteristics and spikelet number of IR8 grown at different temperatures.

Mean air temperature (°C)	Days to flowering	Leaves developed (no./main culm)	Spikelets (no./panicle) ^a	Spikelets (relative no.)
22	140	19.5	272	100
25	127	20.2	227	83
28	118	20.5	207	76
31	131	21.7	157	58

^aLSD (5%) = 16.

levels varied, however. The third leaf seemed to have higher photosynthetic activity than other leaves with the same nitrogen content. Figure 4 strongly suggests, however, that leaf nitrogen content is the primary determinant of photosynthetic activity of rice leaves.

Photosynthesis of the most active rice leaf has been reported to reach a saturation point at about 50 klx. The nitrogen content of the leaf may also affect the light-photosynthesis curve.

In our studies, when leaf nitrogen was low, photosynthesis of rice leaves became light-saturated at 50 to 60 klx, but when nitrogen content was high the photosynthesis of rice leaves did not reach a saturation point even at 83 klx (fig. 5).

Species differences. In a screening of 137 varieties of 13 species of *Oryza*, photosynthetic rate varied from about 30 to 58 mg CO₂ · dm⁻² · h⁻¹ (Table 9). These primitive species of rice, unlike primitive species of wheat, did not always have high rates of photosynthesis. Two cultivated species, *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima*, have the highest rates of leaf photosynthesis of the genus *Oryza*.

Varietal differences. We screened 313 varieties for high photosynthetic rate by calculating the net assimilation rate from growth analysis during the four-leaf to seven-leaf stage. Eight varieties seemed to have high net assimilation rates: JBS 377B, Kaluheenati, MLY VI 283, Molaga Samba G18, Radin Eboss 33, Siam, M 302, and White China. Comparing 44 varieties, in one experiment, we found that the net assimilation rate varied from 88 to 161 mg · dm⁻² · day⁻¹. The net assimilation rate was positively correlated with relative growth rate and leaf photosynthetic rate, and negatively correlated with leaf area ratio. Net assimilation rate was also closely correlated with specific leaf weight and nitrogen content.

1. Effects of temperature on growth of IR8 in a controlled environment.

SCREENING TEST FOR DROUGHT RESISTANCE

We studied plant-water relationships to better understand growth under moisture stress and to help determine physiological methods of screening for drought resistance. Combined measurements of stomatal behavior, desiccation tolerance, and leaf water potential should permit

Table 8. Correlation coefficients between photosynthetic rate (P_n), nitrogen content per unit leaf area (N_{LA}), percentage nitrogen, and specific leaf weight (SLW).

	P_n	N_{LA}	SLW
<i>Low nitrogen level</i>			
N_{LA}	0.881**		
SLW	0.621**	0.686**	
%N	0.671**	0.797**	0.118 ^{ns}
<i>High nitrogen level</i>			
N_{LA}	0.556**		
SLW	0.495**	0.887**	
%N	0.353 ^{ns}	0.481*	0.023 ^{ns}
<i>Combination of low and high nitrogen levels</i>			
N_{LA}	0.880**		
SLW	0.482**	0.607**	
%N	0.796**	0.862**	0.130 ^{ns}

a sound evaluation of the plant's ability to endure moisture stress. In a preliminary study, we examined stomatal behavior and tolerance to desiccation of several varieties.

Stomatal response to moisture stress. Quick closure of stomates in response to moisture stress conserves water, helping the plant to survive a drought. Measurement of the stomatal aperture of rice leaves, however, is time consuming and does not quantitatively measure transpiration loss from leaves.

2. Photosynthetic rates of single leaves of rice (IR667-98 and Hung) and of sorghum (IS9290) at different light intensities. Vertical lines represent standard error.

Table 9. Photosynthetic rates of different species of *Oryza* at 60 klx.

Species	Strains (no.)	Photosynthetic rate (mg CO ₂ · dm ⁻² · h ⁻¹)		
		Min	Max	Mean
<i>O. alta</i>	4	32.2	34.9	33.1
<i>O. australiensis</i>	4	39.6	45.8	42.8
<i>O. barthii</i>	8	30.6	41.2	35.1
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	4	40.2	50.7	46.7
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	39	29.8	54.3	41.6
<i>O. latifolia</i>	17	37.7	53.9	47.6
<i>O. minuta</i>	10	34.3	44.6	40.6
<i>O. officinalis</i>	13	31.0	44.5	41.2
<i>O. perennis</i>	2	41.4	49.7	45.6
<i>O. punctata</i>	10	40.7	43.5	42.0
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	4	45.3	57.9	49.2
<i>O. sativa</i>	19	41.4	54.9	48.2
<i>O. spontanea</i>	3	36.5	43.5	38.9

Transpiration of a leaf under a given environment can be expressed $T = K(e_i - e_a)/(r_l + r_a)$, where T is transpiration, K is a constant, e_i is vapor pressure at the evaporating surface within the leaf, e_a is vapor pressure in the bulk air, r_l is the diffusive resistance inside the leaf, and r_a is the resistance of the surface boundary layer encountered by diffusing molecules.

The leaf resistance to water vapor (r_l) is composed of cuticular resistance (r_c) and stomatal resistance (r_s), and the relationship of the

3. Relationship between photosynthetic rate of second leaves of nine rice varieties and nitrogen content of leaves (leaf area basis).

4. Effect of leaf position on relationship between nitrogen and net photosynthesis.

three is $1/r_t = 1/r_s + 1/r_c$. The cuticular resistance is generally much greater than the stomatal resistance and there is no control mechanism for it. The boundary layer resistance is primarily determined by leaf shape and wind speed, and is usually less than the stomatal resistance. Thus, stomatal resistance is the most important influence on transpiration loss from leaves under a given environment.

5. Light-photosynthesis curve of rice leaves at high and low nitrogen levels.

We measured stomatal resistance to water vapor of 12 varieties with a diffusion porometer. Under normal conditions, the stomatal resistance ranged from 3.5 to 3.9 s/cm (Table 10). Under moisture stress induced by the addition of polyethylene glycol (-6.5 bar) to the culture solution, stomatal resistance increased sharply, ranging from 6.9 to 12.4 s/cm.

Drought-resistant varieties such as M1-48, OS 4, and IR5 showed high values for stomatal resistance in response to moisture stress. On the other hand, the susceptible varieties such as IR20 and TN1 had low stomatal resistance values.

Heat tolerance. Under moisture stress, the stomatal resistance of the leaf increases, raising the leaf temperature. To demonstrate this, plants were subjected to moisture stress (-10.8 bar). The stomatal resistance of leaves increased from 2.2 to 29.3 s/cm. The leaf temperature varied depending on incoming radiation (fig. 6), but averaged about 5°C higher than that of control plants. The leaf temperature rose to a maximum of 48°C. Because leaf temperature rises under severe moisture stress, heat tolerance appears to be important to drought-resistant varieties of rice.

In sorghum, heat tolerance and, hence, drought resistance, have been successfully determined by the conductivity test: measuring the amount of electrolytes in cells destroyed by heat. Heat tolerance is expressed as percentage of extracted electrolytes at a specified temperature divided by total amount of electrolytes extracted when all the cells are destroyed by heat. This test measures the tolerance of protoplasm to heat and desiccation.

Destruction of rice tissue cells begins at about 48°C (fig. 7). We subjected rice tissue to 53°C, the temperature at which half of the cells are destroyed by heat. Tissue injury ranged from 32 to 75 percent when the plants were grown in culture solution without moisture stress (Table 11). When the plants were subjected to moisture stress (-12 bar) for a few days and again transferred to a normal culture solution, the heat tolerance of the plants increased. Tissue injury ranged from about 9 to 23 percent. Injury was low among the drought-resistant varieties such as OS 4, M1-48, Palawan, and

IR5. But drought-susceptible varieties such as IR20 and TN1 had high level of injury.

PHOTOPERIOD

Response to photoperiod. One objective of the IIRI breeding program is to develop varieties that are not sensitive to photoperiod. Such varieties can be planted during any season and their growth durations vary little when temperature is not critical to plant development.

IIRI lines which have been named as varieties by cooperating agencies were tested under different daylengths to determine how they respond to photoperiod. All lines flowered at photoperiods ranging from 10 to 16 hours (Table 12). Bahagia (IR5-278), however, flowered late and had the longest photoperiod-sensitive phase. This variety can be grown only during months that have short days. Its growth duration will not vary much in areas near the equator where daylength is short and constant. Chandina (IR532-1-176) flowered earliest, at around 80 days at 14 hours of daylength. This variety is planted during the cold season in Bangladesh so its growth duration may exceed 130 days under field conditions. Chandina can be planted at any season in the tropics and be expected to flower early. Cica 4 (IR930-31) was the least sensitive variety. One of its parents is IR12-178, which was previously reported as the least

6. Temperature of rice leaves under moisture stress and without moisture stress. IIRI, October 3, 1972.

sensitive IIRI line yet tested (1969 Annual Report).

Table 13 shows the response to photoperiod of recent IIRI lines and selected varieties which showed high yield potential in the varietal improvement trials. All IIRI lines were essentially insensitive to photoperiod; they flowered

Table 10. Stomatal resistance^a to water vapor of 12 varieties grown with or without moisture stress.

Variety	Stomatal resistance (s/cm)	
	Without moisture stress	With moisture stress
Jappeni Tungkungo	3.7	12.4
M1-48	3.8	10.8
IR5	3.6	10.1
OS 4	3.7	10.0
Tainan 3	3.7	10.0
Palawan	3.5	9.6
Dular	3.9	9.4
PI 215936	3.8	9.1
E 425	3.5	8.5
TN 1	3.9	8.3
T141	3.6	7.9
IR20	3.6	6.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3	2.5

^aMean value of upper and lower surface

7. Relation between temperature and tissue injury (variety IR20 at 50 days after sowing).

Table 11. Heat tolerance test of 12 varieties grown with or without moisture stress.

Variety	Injury at 53° C (%)	
	Without moisture stress	With moisture stress
Jappeni Tungkungo	31.8	14.1
M1-48	47.7	13.0
IR5	46.6	11.1
OS 4	52.1	9.1
Tainan 3	51.1	18.7
Palawan	38.6	12.0
Dular	75.0	19.3
PI 215936	61.2	17.9
E 425	56.2	9.8
TN1	55.0	18.6
T141	44.6	20.6
IR20	57.6	22.6
Mean	51.5	15.6

at each photoperiod treatment. The early-maturing lines, IR1561-149-5 and IR1561-228, have short photoperiod-sensitive phases.

Varieties C12 and C22, developed at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, are insensitive to daylength (that is, they will flower under any daylength) although a long daylength may delay flowering by more than a month.

T442-36 and T442-57 are deep-water selections from Thailand. Although both selections flowered at all photoperiods, they are weakly photoperiod sensitive; a long daylength delayed flowering by more than 60 days.

Reception of photoperiodic stimulus. The photoperiodic stimulus for flowering is generally received by the leaf blades of the plant, although

reports indicated that the leaf sheath can also receive the stimulus. To determine if BPI-76, a photoperiod-sensitive variety, can receive the stimulus through the leaf sheath, we clipped the leaf blades at the collar of 70-day-old plants grown under continuous photoperiod. The plants were then subjected to 15 photoinductive cycles (10 hours of light).

The panicle primordia (1 mm) of plants with intact leaf blades were visible 15 days after photoinduction began, while the primordia in plants without leaf blades were not visible until after 26 days. This difference was later intensified. The intact plants flowered 34 days after the start of photoinduction while the plants without leaf blades flowered in 58 days. Thus the leaf sheath without the blade can also receive the photoinductive stimulus.

SCREENING FOR LOW TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

We continued to work on a faster method of screening cultivars for tolerance to low water temperature at the seedling stage and the early tillering stage. Selecting cold-tolerant varieties after they are transplanted demands much work and field area. Selection in the nursery would reduce the laborious task of transplanting by eliminating the susceptible types.

We found that treating 10-day-old seedlings with cold water (12°C) for 10 days causes leaf discoloration in cold-susceptible rices. The degree of leaf yellowing indicates the ability of

Table 12. Response of varieties named from IRRI lines to photoperiods of 10, 14, and 16 hours.

Name	IRRI line	Country	Time to flowering (days)			Basic vegetative phase (days)	Photoperiod-sensitive phase (days)	Date sown
			10 h	14 h	16 h			
Pankaj	IR5-114-3	India	90	120	136	55	46	May 1971
Bahagia	IR5-278	Malaysia	81	122	146	46	65	May 1971
Mehran 69	IR6-156-2	Pakistan	104	108	126	69	22	May 1971
CS-2	IR160-25-1	Ivory Coast	91	91	104	56	13	May 1971
Sinaloa A68	IR160-27-4	Mexico	93	105	113	58	20	May 1971
RD-2	IR253-4	Thailand	79	94	105	44	26	May 1971
CS-3	IR253-16-1	Ivory Coast	79	97	104	44	25	July 1967
Huallaga	IR442-2-50	Peru	83	119	128	48	45	Oct. 1969
Chandina	IR532-1-176	Bangladesh	66	78	88	31	22	May 1971
Nilo 11	IR579-48-1 ^a	El Salvador	75	88	97	40	22	Oct. 1969
Mummai	IR661-1-140	Fiji	97	107	114	62	17	Oct. 1969
Tongil	IR667-98	Korea	77	84	96	42	19	May 1971
Cica 4	IR930-31 ^b	Colombia	90	92	90	55	2	March 1972

^aNamed Palman 579 in India. ^bNamed Chancay in Peru.

Table 13. Response of selected varieties and lines to photoperiods of 10 to 16 hours.

Designation	Time to flowering (days)				Basic vegetative phase (days)	Photoperiod-sensitive phase (days)
	10 h	12 h	14 h	16 h		
<i>Tested March 1972</i>						
BPI-121-407	80	106	100	108	45	28
C12	72	98	112	107	37	40
IR579-48-1	66	80	85	90	31	24
IR833-34-1	60	89	93	95	25	35
-62-1	62	80	80	86	27	24
Latisail	55	84	^a	^a	20	200+
Seraup Besar	69	102	129	129	34	60
T442-36	65	94	131	130	30	66
<i>Tested August 1972</i>						
C22	69	106	105	106	34	37
Fortuna	107	110	106	108	72	4
IR841-5-1	68	94	92	91	33	23
IR1480-116-3	74	102	100	106	39	32
-125-2	74	108	108	107	39	34
IR1529-72-5	88	106	107	106	53	19
-382-4	76	103	106	104	41	30
-430-3	78	104	105	103	43	27
-548-1	78	103	104	101	43	26
-677-2	87	106	107	105	52	20
-680-3	81	105	106	104	46	25
IR1541-76-3	84	96	101	100	49	17
-102-6	71	101	103	101	36	40
IR1561-149-5	68	87	91	92	33	24
-228	67	82	85	90	32	23
M1-48	77	109	115	147	42	70
Seraup Besar 15	50	136	^a	^a	15	200+
T442-57	73	117	140	142	38	69

^aNo panicle initiation after 200 days of growth.

rice seedlings to survive and recover rapidly from subnormal temperatures (fig. 8). About 97 percent of the green-leaved varieties had a seedling survival of 70 percent or higher, while only 60 percent of those with yellow leaves had higher than 70 percent survival. Thus selection of green seedlings will eliminate 88 percent of the cultivars that are not tolerant to low temperature.

Upland varieties seem to be tolerant to low water temperature at the seedling stage, as indicated by leaf discoloration, percentage of tillering after transplanting, and survival percentage (Table 14).

WIND DAMAGE TO LEAVES

Typhoons break and tear rice leaves and damage internal tissues. When exposed to sunlight, the leaf tips dry and the injured portions are sometimes infected with bacterial blight or bacterial leaf streak. Strong winds alone can also desiccate the leaf tips.

During the 1972 wet season, leaf damage was extensive in upland plots of the agronomy department in which both upland and lowland varieties were planted. From July 15 to 31,

Table 14. Relationship of leaf discoloration, seedling survival, and tiller number of upland rice varieties subjected to low temperature at seedling stage. IRRI, 1972.

Variety	Discoloration rating ^a	Seedling survival ^b (%)	Tillers (%)
Agbede	1.5	82	167
Azucena	1.5	72	118
Dinalaga	2.5	81	147
E425	0.5	87	153
Elliott	1.5	72	100
Hirayama	0.0	93	157
M1-48	0.5	72	130
Miltex	1.5	93	148
OS4	1.0	85	149
OS6	1.0	90	143
Palawan	1.5	79	123
Rikuto Norin-21	1.0	80	158
RT1095S26	2.5	89	164

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5 (0 = completely green, 5 = completely yellow). ^bObtained by comparing each treated variety with an untreated control of same variety.

8. Relation between degree of yellowing of seedlings grown at 12°C and plant survival when transplanted in the field.

winds lashed through the experimental field with a maximum velocity of 13 m/s at 1 m height. The mean wind speed was more than 2 m/s during 10 of the 17 days. We observed the 70 varieties on these plots to better understand varietal resistance to leaf damage by wind.

We rated wind damage on a scale of 1 to 4 by determining the percentage of affected leaves per plot. Leaf damage was severe and varietal differences were clear. The differences in wind damage among varieties accounted for 71 percent of the total variation. Upland varieties, which generally have longer leaf blades than lowland varieties, were all resistant to wind damage.

In 10 varieties planted under upland conditions in a greenhouse, leaf thickness was positively correlated with the extent of leaf damage in the field (Table 15). The wind damage to upland varieties that were grown under

9. Changes in leaf area, shoot number, and tuber number per pot during growth of *S. maritimus*.

upland conditions ranged from 1 to 2 and leaf thickness ranged from 3.1 to 3.6 mg/sq cm. The lowland varieties grown under upland conditions had much higher wind damage scores, ranging from 3 to 4 and leaf thicknesses of only 2.2 to 2.9 mg/sq cm. Leaf damage during the vegetative stage in the field was highly correlated with leaf thickness during the vegetative stage of plants grown under upland conditions in the greenhouse ($r = -0.777^{**}$).

Degree of resistance of varieties to leaf damage by wind when grown under upland field conditions was not correlated with differences in silica and nitrogen content.

When breeding and screening upland varieties, resistance to wind damage should be considered.

AUTECOLOGY OF *Scirpus maritimus* L.

Herbicides have greatly improved weed control, but they have also caused a shift in predominant weed populations from annuals to perennials.

Table 15. Leaf damage from strong winds and leaf thicknesses of plants, IRRI, 1972.

Variety	Leaf damage score ^a	Leaf thickness ^b (mg/sq cm)
<i>Upland varieties</i>		
Azmil	2.0	3.6
M1-48	1.0	3.1
OS 4	1.0	3.1
Palawan	2.0	3.4
Avg	1.5	3.3
<i>Lowland varieties</i>		
IR5	4.0	2.2
IR8	4.0	2.6
IR20	3.0	2.6
IR442-2-58	3.5	2.5
IR747B2-6-3	3.0	2.9
Taichung Native 1	4.0	2.6
Avg	3.6	2.6
LSD (5%)	—	0.8

^aScored under upland field conditions. 1 = 0 to 25% damage, 2 = 25 to 50% damage, 3 = 50 to 75% damage, 4 = 75% to 100% damage. ^bPlants grown under upland conditions in porcelain pots.

Herbicides can control most annual weeds but perennials are more difficult because many of them accumulate food reserves in underground rhizomes and tubers. Topgrowth is killed, but fresh shoots emerge from the protected vegetative parts deep underground.

One such weed, *S. maritimus* L., is rapidly spreading in rice fields in the Philippines. We began studying its ecology to determine how to control its growth and reproduction more effectively.

Growth stages. Growth in terms of dry matter production was relatively slow from sowing to about 40 days after sowing (fig. 9). The dry weight of the underground parts (roots, stolons, and tubers) was fairly constant. Only the green leaves and the culms contributed significantly to the total dry weight.

From 40 to 120 days after sowing, dry matter increased rapidly and metabolic products accumulated in the tubers. The highest number of shoots and maximum leaf area were reached during this stage, but some shoots and leaves began to die.

During the last growth stage (120 to 210 days after sowing) growth rate declined and leaves and shoots died. Almost 50 percent of the total dry weight was in the tubers.

The dry weights of the plant and the tubers throughout plant growth were significantly

10. Height of *S. maritimus* under different photoperiods.

correlated ($r = 0.9592^{**}$) indicating that most dry matter ultimately accumulates in the tubers.

The fast-growing *S. maritimus* is a highly competitive weed. The plant may grow more than 1 m high within 40 days after sowing and a single tuber can produce 35 shoots. *S. maritimus* competes with and shades the rice plants during this critical stage. It produces shoots and tubers simultaneously, insuring a good source of infestation for succeeding crops. In the limited space of the pots in this experiment, a single sown tuber produced 265 tubers in 7 months, an average of more than one tuber per day. *S. maritimus* did not flower during the 210-day growing period, indicating that tubers are probably the primary means of reproduction.

Table 16. Effect of photoperiod on the growth of *S. maritimus*.

Photoperiod (h)	Dry wt (g)			Tubers (no.)	Shoots (no.)
	Shoot	Tuber	Total		
10	50	29	86	119	70
12	57	18	81	66	50
16	72	14	93	41	29
24	76	16	99	35	26

Tubers are difficult to kill with herbicides. Without proper timing, mechanical control may only separate and disperse the tubers. Plowing a field 40 days after the first harrowing may prevent the initial rapid production of tubers and reduce the weed's density.

Response to photoperiod. We grew *S. maritimus* under different photoperiods. At 90 days, the plants turned yellow and were more than 2 m tall. No plants flowered and dissection of some shoots revealed no floral primordia. Photoperiod does not seem to influence the flowering of this species. In the field, we observed that the flowering shoots had a maximum of five leaves. In the greenhouse, more than 15 leaves per plant developed.

Photoperiod affected height even in early stages of growth. As photoperiod lengthened, the plants grew taller (fig. 10). At high latitudes or under long daylengths *S. maritimus* would shade most improved rice varieties.

Although the plant height at maturity became progressively less as photoperiods became shorter, the number of shoots and tubers increased (Table 16). Under field conditions, more tubers are formed during the main cropping season as the days become shorter. Increases in photoperiod affected dry weight little although it markedly decreased tuber formation and increased shoot weight. Tuber weight was lower at long photoperiods than at a photoperiod of 10 hours.

Rice production training and research

TRAINING PROGRAMS

Six-month course. The eighth annual 6-month rice production training course had 36 participants from 15 countries. Since 1964, 247 trainees from 27 countries have graduated.

The educational background of the 1972 class was diverse. Three were master's degree holders, 16 had B.S.A. degrees, five were engineers in agriculture, three were diploma holders, eight had senior certificates, and one was a high school student. Teaching a class with such varied educational background, experience, and interest was difficult. For the first time several trainees did not satisfactorily complete the course. Eleven were given certificates indicating they had participated in the course, rather than completed the course satisfactorily. Seven of them were B.S.A. degree holders, two were diploma holders, one was an engineer in agriculture, and one was a high school student.

The average score on the practical examination at the start of the course was 26 percent with a range of 4 to 83 percent. On the written test it was 34 percent with a range of 10 to 67 percent. The average on the final practical was 85 percent and on the written test, 87 percent.

Ten applied research plots, five production plots of the leading IRRI varieties, and three display plots were established and managed by the 6-month rice production trainees. Planning the applied research, preparing the materials, growing the crops, and performing all the operations in the plots under the supervision of trained instructors gave the trainees an opportunity to develop self-confidence and credibility in imparting new rice technology to farmers. They also acquired actual cultural skills and obtained decision-making experience by producing a rice crop.

As in previous 6-month courses, the trainees collected field data on factors relevant to the applied research. They harvested yield samples from several of the plots and analyzed the data. They performed analysis of variance and tests for significance of differences using their own

data. This training technique helps the trainees to gain important experience in organizing and managing applied research which will enable them to adjust the package of practices to suit local conditions.

Short courses. Five short courses in rice production were held during 1972. The first was a 3-day course in February for rural broadcasters from rice-producing provinces. It was held at the request of the broadcasters who wanted to improve their knowledge of rice and how it is grown. Twenty-five persons attended this course. The second was a 15-day course, conducted in March for 41 extension workers from Bulacan and Nueva Ecija provinces. It was designed to train personnel for the pilot extension projects being planned for these two provinces. The third was a 2-week course in July for five scientists enroute to assignments in Indonesia and South Vietnam. It was joined by three scholars from the varietal improvement department. The fourth course, held in November was organized and conducted by the 6-month rice production trainees. It gave the trainees experience in planning and conducting a short course in rice production. Forty persons attended, 28 of whom were Filipino extension workers. The fifth course, in December, had 48 trainees: 10 Filipino extension workers, four vocational agricultural teachers, five agro-business representatives, two IRRI scholars, five IRRI employees, seven farmers, three missionary nuns, four college students, one mayor, and seven individuals from outside the Philippines—three from Israel, and one each from Laos, Uganda, Japan, and Indonesia.

The growth-stage plot, where rice is planted every 2 weeks, enabled all the short-course trainees to perform all the steps in growing a rice crop. This method of training is becoming popular and there is an increasing demand for it from other countries as well as the Philippines.

APPLIED RESEARCH TRIALS

In cooperation with various Philippine agencies and IRRI departments we conducted applied

Table 1. Grain yield of 14 varieties or selections in 12 provinces in the Philippines, 1972 dry season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)												Mean
	Marin- duque	Panga- sinan	Isabela	Zamboanga del Sur	Pampanga	Leyte	Caga- yan	Sorso- gon	Kalinga- Apayao	Batangas	Tarlac	Laguna*	
PB76-TB188	2.0	5.8	2.0	2.8	4.6	6.8	3.9	2.8	4.2	4.9	4.8	5.7	4.2
BPI 121-407	0.7	5.8	1.9	4.3	5.0	6.8	5.5	2.5	6.0	4.3	3.1	7.1	4.4
C4-63 G	1.3	5.8	1.9	3.7	5.0	6.8	5.2	5.1	5.8	4.6	4.9	5.9	4.7
C4-137	1.6	5.8	2.1	3.9	4.5	6.3	3.3	4.9	4.6	4.5	5.2	6.7	4.5
C 12	1.6	5.8	2.2	2.7	4.1	6.3	1.8	5.7	5.3	4.5	4.5	4.9	4.1
IR8	0.9	5.9	2.2	4.7	3.6	7.1	4.3	2.1	5.3	2.8	3.5	6.8	4.1
IR20	2.2	4.6	2.1	4.2	4.2	6.0	3.2	6.0	5.3	4.7	4.4	7.1	4.5
Fortuna ×													
MA3-2b	1.5	5.8	2.1	2.9	4.7	6.1	4.0	5.7	5.2	4.3	4.9	4.9	4.3
IR1006-20-5	1.7	4.7	2.2	4.5	5.2	6.5	2.0	3.9	3.7	5.5	4.0	7.3	4.3
IR24	2.8	4.7	1.9	3.9	5.5	6.7	3.6	4.5	5.7	4.4	4.0	7.9	4.6
IR665-8-3	1.6	4.6	2.2	4.5	4.7	7.4	2.4	4.3	4.5	5.3	3.5	7.7	4.4
IR881-5-3	1.4	5.8	2.3	4.5	4.5	6.4	2.8	5.0	4.7	4.5	3.1	7.8	4.4
IR833-34	4.3	5.8	2.2	3.5	4.9	6.4	2.1	8.0	5.6	3.6	3.5	7.3	4.8
IR833-6-2	3.5	5.8	2.1	3.5	6.0	5.3	2.4	5.7	4.5	3.1	3.4	6.8	4.3

*IRRI.

research trials on two groups of promising rice selections, on integrated pest control, and on new herbicides. The results of the herbicide trial are reported by the agronomy department.

New selections. The 1972 Farmers Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial was

conducted in both the wet and dry seasons, but data are not yet available for the wet season trial. Among the 12 locations from which reports were received IRRI had the highest yields. IR833-34 gave the highest mean yield for the 12 locations, 4.8 t/ha, followed in order by C4-63 and IR24 (Table 1). The low yield levels obtained at several locations suggest inadequate management and limit the usefulness of these data in evaluating new selections.

In a similar trial, seven new IRRI selections and varieties IR8 and IR20 were tested for yield performance and resistance to pest and virus diseases at four locations. Their yields in protected and unprotected plots did not differ significantly (Table 2), except at the IRRI farm, where the yield of the protected plot was significantly higher than that of the unprotected plot. The insect and disease problem apparently is more serious at IRRI than in farmers' fields. Results from one location are not reported because all except one plot lodged due to excess nitrogen from an unknown source. IR1529-680-3 had the highest mean yield in both the protected and unprotected plots.

Integrated pest control. Some insecticides which can be applied to paddy water, when used in combination with the new seedling treatment technique and on varieties tolerant to insect pests, can drastically reduce losses caused by insect pests and virus diseases. During the wet

1. Soil map. Rainfed and upland applied research project sites. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija provinces, Philippines.

Table 2. Grain yield of promising selections grown with and without protection at three locations.* 1972 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)							
	IRRI		Santa Rosa		P. Garcia		Mean	
	Pro- tected	Unpro- tected	Pro- tected	Unpro- tected	Pro- tected	Unpro- tected	Pro- tected	Unpro- tected
IR8	4.64	3.74	4.74	3.88	5.08	5.18	4.82	4.26
IR20	4.67	3.85	4.67	4.15	4.42	4.92	4.59	4.30
E666	4.92	4.35	4.89	3.85	4.87	4.65	4.89	4.28
IR1364-37-3	4.14	2.64	4.10	3.93	3.68	3.91	3.97	3.49
IR1529-382-4	5.06	4.52	4.39	4.02	5.20	4.70	4.88	4.41
IR1529-680-3	5.36	4.53	5.41	4.29	5.62	4.71	5.52	4.51
IR1541-102-3	4.74	4.30	3.66	3.63	5.14	4.82	4.51	4.25
IR1541-76-3	—	—	4.49	3.92	4.62	4.59	4.55	4.25

*Unprotected — no insecticide applied. Protected — seeds and seedling roots soaked in carbofuran; lindane granule applied at 1 kg/ha a.i. 6 days after transplanting (DT), carbofuran applied at 0.5 kg/ha a.i. 20 and 40 DT, MIPC (0.05% toxicant) sprayed at 70 DT.

season, an integrated pest control scheme was formulated in cooperation with the entomology department, combining variety, insecticidal treatment, and cultural practices to eliminate virus-infected plants. Eleven trials were established in the provinces of Laguna, Pampanga, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pangasinan, Tarlac, and La Union. Although harvesting has not been completed, visual observations indicate that this study will yield some interesting findings.

RAINFED AND UPLAND RICE PROJECT

This is the second year of a 3-year cooperative applied research project with the National Food and Agriculture Council, the Bureau of Agricultural Extension, and other Philippine agencies on rainfed and upland rice in Bulacan and Nueva Ecija provinces (fig. 1). Trials are being conducted to field-test emerging technology, including new promising selections and varieties, herbicides, insecticides, rates and timing of fertilizer application, methods of stand establishment, and different management levels; to determine the economic feasibility of growing crops other than rice in rainfed and upland rice areas; and to train government technicians in conducting applied research trials.

This year we established 118 trials to obtain more quantitative data on rainfed and upland rice, and on the production of other crops before and after the rice crop in both upland and rainfed areas.

Twenty-one trials were cancelled because of the floods in July and August, which destroyed seedlings and prevented the application of chemicals as scheduled.

The results of this year's trials further support last year's findings (1971 Annual Report). Average yields of over 4.5 t/ha were obtained with the best performing varieties and selections that were planted early and were not seriously affected by the drought.

The rainfall distribution in 1972 was less favorable than last year's. It rained continuously from early July until mid-September after which there were only showers (fig. 2). Except for one rain of about 4 cm in early November, there was no effective rainfall after September 15 throughout the project area. Only a few trials planted in early July escaped the drought. All other plantings suffered from moisture stress. Some trials were exposed to moisture stress from flowering to harvest, some from booting to harvest, and others from panicle initiation to harvest.

Rainfed variety trial. Bacterial blight and time of planting greatly affected the performance of the 17 test varieties and selections planted on different dates in rainfed paddies (fig. 3).

Most test entries produced high yields in the early plantings (planted the first week of July). The crops were in the hard dough stage when the soil started to dry so they escaped the drought. The best yielders were IR20, IR1529-680-3, and IR577-24-1 (Table 3). All the test entries, except IR20, IR22, IR1529-680-3, and

2. Average monthly 1972 rainfall at project locations in Bulacan and Nueva Ecija. Long-term averages from Ipo Junction, Bulacan, and Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija.

IR1529-879, were severely damaged by bacterial leaf blight.

The yields were lower in the medium-late plantings (planted the second and third week of July). These crops were exposed to drought for about 30 days from flowering to harvest. The 30-day exposure to drought caused wilting of the leaves of most entries; some grains shrivelled and some spikelets were empty. Surprisingly, most entries yielded over 4.5 t/ha. The best yielders were IR1529-879, IR22, IR577-24-1, IR1529-680-3, and IR24 (Table 3).

The yields of all entries were reduced considerably in the late plantings (planted late July and early August). Drought affected these crops for about 40 days from booting to harvest. The yield of IR20 decreased by as much as 55 percent (fig. 4). IR20 plants started to wilt at the flowering stage and the leaves and straw dried before harvesting. Most IR20

3. Rainfall during four plantings of the rainfed variety trial, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

grains were shrivelled. It yielded only 2.6 t/ha. IR1529-879, IR1541-102-3, and IR1529-680-3 gave the best yields. The leaves of IR1529-680-3 were still green at harvest and most of its spikelets were filled.

None of the test entries produced economic yields in the late plantings (made during the second week of August). The crops were exposed to drought for more than 50 days from panicle initiation to harvest. By flowering time, the leaves of most of the entries had dried up. Only eight of the 17 entries produced some grain (Table 3).

Rainfed fertilizer trial. Significant responses to nitrogen occurred on Prensa clay loam, Buenavista sandy loam, and Bantog clay (Table 4). The maximum net returns were P229/ha, obtained at 120 kg/ha N on Prensa clay loam soils, and P385/ha, obtained with 90 kg/ha N on the Bantog clay soils (Table 5). No response to nitrogen was observed on Buenavista silt loam. The drought in September and October prevented topdressing of nitrogen at 45 days after transplanting.

Response to phosphorus occurred at all 17 test sites during the early vegetative stage. The plots without phosphorus had reduced tillering and delayed growth. But significant differences in yields due to phosphorus were observed in only two locations, on Bantog clay loam in

4. Grain yield of IR20, IR1529-680-3, and C4-63 as affected by time of transplanting under rainfed conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Gapan and on Prensa clay loam in Santa Maria (Table 6). The plots without phosphorus in the other locations were able to recover. Significant responses were observed up to 60 kg/ha P_2O_5 on Bantog clay loam soils. The application of 60 kg/ha P_2O_5 increased yields by 2.6 t/ha.

Significant response to potassium was observed at only one location, on Sibul clay soils (Table 7).

Rainfed insecticide trial. Whorl maggots, leaf rollers, caseworms, rice stem borers, and green leafhoppers were observed throughout the project area. To gather quantitative data on the yield losses caused by these pests and to determine the returns from five insecticidal combinations, nine trials were established in typical rainfed paddies. The treatments used are shown in Table 8.

The four treatments involving post-transplanting application effectively controlled whorl maggots, caseworms, leaf rollers, and rice stem borers. The spray of Thiodan at the rate of 0.05% concentration did not effectively control the late attack of leaf rollers and rice stem borers.

The unprotected plots were severely damaged. Caseworms, leaf rollers, and whorl maggots caused 50 to 100 percent damage on these plots. Rice stem borers caused up to 15 percent white heads at six locations.

Table 3. Grain yield of 17 varieties and selections as affected by time of planting under rainfed conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)			
	Early ^a	Medium late ^b	Late ^c	Very late ^a
IR5	—	3.6	3.0	0.0
IR20	5.8	4.5	2.6	.0
IR24	4.5	4.6	2.9	.0
IR22	4.5	4.8	3.0	.7
IR577-24-1	5.0	4.8	3.2	.7
C4-63 G	4.2	4.3	2.2	.4
BPI 76-1	—	4.0	2.8	.5
C4-137	—	4.4	3.0	.0
IR1006-20-5	3.4	3.8	2.6	1.2
IR1541-102-3	4.6	4.5	3.6	.0
IR1154-681-2	3.6	4.1	3.0	.0
IR1163-124-3	—	—	2.4	.4
IR1364-37-3	4.5	3.4	2.2	.0
IR1529-680-3	5.5	4.6	3.4	.4
IR1529-879	4.6	4.8	3.8	.0
IR790-28-6	4.3	3.2	—	—
C22	—	3.1	2.7	.7

^aMean of one location. ^bMean of five locations. ^cMean of seven locations.

Table 4. Nitrogen response of IR20 with 60 P_2O_5 and 60 K_2O under rainfed conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Soil type	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	0 kg/ha N	60 kg/ha N	90 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
Prensa clay loam ^a	4.5	4.8	5.1	5.2
Buenavista silt loam ^a	4.1	4.4	4.5	4.3
Buenavista sandy loam ^b	2.7	3.2	2.3	2.4
Sibul clay ^c	2.9	3.6	3.4	3.3
Bantog clay ^c	2.8	3.4	3.8	3.2
Mean	3.4	3.9	3.8	3.7

^aMean of four locations. ^bMean of two locations. ^cMean of one location.

Table 5. Returns above cost of cash inputs for nitrogen fertilizer applied at different rates on transplanted IR20 under rainfed conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Soil type	Return (P/ha)		
	Nitrogen level (kg/ha)		
	60	90	120
Prensa clay loam	86	215	229
Buenavista silt loam	86	101	-55
Buenavista sandy loam	200	-353	-339
Sibul clay loam	313	158	59
Bantog clay loam	257	385	2
Mean	188	101	-21

Table 6. Phosphorus response of IR20 with 90 kg/ha N and 60 kg/ha K₂O under rainfed conditions, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Locations (no.)	Soil type	Grain yield (t/ha)		
		0 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅	30 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅	60 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅
<i>Locations with yield response</i>				
1	Prensa clay	3.1	4.7	5.3
1	Bantog clay	0.8	3.4	3.8
<i>No response</i>				
4	Prensa clay	4.8	5.1	5.1
2	Buenavista silt loam	4.8	4.8	5.1
2	Buenavista sandy loam	2.1	2.7	2.4
1	Sibul clay	3.4	2.9	3.4

The seed and seedling treatment alone protected the crop from early whorl maggot damage. The plots were later severely damaged by leaf rollers, caseworms, and rice stem borers.

Yields obtained from seven locations (fig. 5) indicated an increase of about 1 t/ha for treatments 3, 4, 5, and 6.

Treatment 4 gave the highest net return per hectare (Table 9).

Rainfed herbicide trial. Some of the most important weed species observed in farmers' fields are *Cyperus difformis*, *Cyperus iria*, *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Echinochloa colonum*, *Echinochloa crusgalli*, and *Scirpus erectus*. These weeds become serious in rainfed paddies when rainfall is insufficient to keep the soil flooded and when land preparation is poor.

To determine the effectiveness of four granular herbicide treatments, 2,4-D, benthicarb/2, 4-D, butachlor, TCE-styrene/2, 4-D, and MCPA, in controlling weeds in rainfed areas, 10 trial plots were established in different loca-

tions. All of the herbicides were applied 3 to 5 days after transplanting.

All the plots, including the control, had no weeds. No significant differences in yield between the treatments were observed at any of the eight locations. The low weed population could be attributed to the continuous early flooding of the plots immediately after the application of herbicides. Thorough land preparation, and close spacing may also have helped control weeds.

Rainfed management levels. Herbicide, insecticide, and fertilizer trials have indicated that yields of rainfed rice can be increased. To determine the most profitable combinations of weed control, insect control, and fertilizer applications, trials of five management levels were established in typical rainfed paddies.

Table 10 shows the methods of weed control, insect control, and fertilizer application used in each level of management. Management level 2 represents the level of management of an average Filipino farmer; it costs P194/ha. Management level 5 represents a sophisticated level of management designed to assure high yields. Trials planted early gave high yields, up to 5.5 t/ha for management level 5 (Table 11).

Management level 5 gave the highest return above cash costs, P2,615/ha. Lindane granules applied 50 days after transplanting in management level 5 protected the crop against late attack of stem borers, increasing the yield by about 1 t/ha over that in management level 2. The insecticide applications in management levels 3 and 4 were not sufficient to adequately protect the crops.

Table 7. Potassium response of IR20 with 60 kg/ha N and 60 kg/ha P₂O₅ under rainfed conditions, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Soil type	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	0 kg/ha K ₂ O	30 kg/ha K ₂ O	60 kg/ha K ₂ O
Prensa clay loam ^a	5.0	4.9	5.1
Buenavista silt loam ^a	4.4	4.3	4.5
Buenavista sandy loam ^b	2.7	3.0	2.3
Sibul clay loam ^c	3.2	4.0	3.4
Bantog clay loam ^c	3.6	3.4	3.8
Mean	3.8	3.9	4.0

^aMean of four locations. ^bMean of two locations. ^cMean of one location.

Table 8. Treatments used in rainfed insecticide trials, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Treatment no.	Carbofuran seed and seedling treatment	20 DT ^a	35 DT	40 DT	70 DT
1	no	none	none	none	none
2	yes	none	none	none	none
3	yes	MIPC ^b and lindane ^c	MIPC	Lindane ^e	Folidol ^f
4	yes	Carbofuran ^d	none	Carbofuran ^d	Folidol ^f
5	yes	Carbofuran ^d	none	Thiodan ^b	Folidol ^f
6	yes	Lindane ^c	none	Lindane ^e	Folidol ^f

^aDays after transplanting. ^b0.05%. ^c1 kg/ha a.i. ^d0.5 kg/ha a.i. ^e1.5 kg/ha a.i. ^f0.04%.

Low yields were obtained in trials planted in August. The scheduled application of 20 kg/ha nitrogen in management levels 4 and 5 at 45 days after transplanting, and the application of lindane granules at 50 days after transplanting in management level 5, were not made as there was no water in the plots. Hence, no differences in yields were observed between management levels 3, 4, and 5 in the late plantings.

Seeding on unpuddled banded soil. When rainfall is insufficient to permit puddling of the soil, farmers must delay transplanting of rainfed rice. This is one cause of low yields. Yields we obtained with direct seeding trials last year were impressive in spite of relatively high weed populations and poor stands. To gain more experience with seeding on unpuddled banded soil, trials were established in five locations during the 1972 wet season. The soil was plowed and rotovated during the last week of April when enough rain had fallen to permit the soil to be worked. A *lithao* was used to make furrows. During the second week of June, varieties IR20 and IR1561-243-5 were broadcast uniformly over the field at 90 kg/ha. A comb harrow was then passed over the field to cover the seeds. We applied 60 kg/ha of P₂O₅ and K₂O during the last rotovation. The crops were topdressed with urea using 30 kg/ha N at 15, 35, and 55 days after seeding. To control weeds, Preforan was sprayed at 2 kg/ha a.i. from 3 to 5 days after seeding, when weed germination was observed.

Excellent stands were established in all locations and weeds were effectively controlled. Yields obtained from two locations indicate the potential of this method. IR1561-243-5 yielded 4.3 t/ha and IR20, 3.8 t/ha. Two plots

were destroyed by flood. The harvest data from the direct-seeded plots on puddled soil will be reported later.

Upland variety trial. Excellent yields were obtained in trial plots seeded the second week of June. IR577-24-1 performed best; its average yield was 4 t/ha. It was followed by IR24, IR790-28-6, and C4-63 G with average yields of 3.7, 3.3, and 3.3 t/ha respectively (Table 12). The drought did not affect these entries as much as it did the others since they were in the hard dough stage when the plants started to wilt. IR5 had an average yield of only 2.4 t/ha. It was affected by the drought beginning at early flowering. Many spikelets were unfilled.

Poor yields were obtained in plots seeded

5. Grain yield of IR20 and IR22 as protected by various insecticidal combinations under rainfed conditions. Treatment No. 1 is the control. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Table 9. Returns above cash costs for insecticides used under rainfed conditions (mean of eight locations; varieties IR20 and IR22). Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Treatment no.	Insecticide treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cash cost (P/ha)	Net return ^b (P/ha)	Benefit : cost ratio
1	Control	3.2	0	—	—
2	SST ^b	3.3	24	33	1.4
3	SST + MIPC + lindane + MIPC + lindane + Folidol	3.9	143	255	1.8
4	SST + carbofuran + carbofuran + Folidol	4.1	208	304	1.5
5	SST + Thiodan + Folidol + carbofuran	4.0	158	297	1.9
6	SST + lindane + lindane + Folidol	3.9	141	257	1.8

^aSST = seed and seedling soaked in carbofuran solution. ^bNet increase compared with the control.

during the fourth week of June. Most of the selections or varieties were flowering when the soil started to dry in late September. The highest yields were obtained with IR24, C22-51, and HBDA₂.

Upland fertilizer trial. Upland rice gave a significant response to nitrogen and phosphorus in four test locations. An application of 30 kg/ha P₂O₅ increased yields by 0.6 t/ha (Table 13). Response to phosphorus above 30 kg/ha was not significant.

Response to nitrogen up to 90 kg/ha was significant. Plots treated with 90 kg/ha N yielded twice as much as did the control plots and gave the highest net return, P837/ha (Table 14).

Response to potassium was observed only on

Table 10. Cultural practices for five levels of management.

Fertilizer (kg/ha) N	Fert. P ₂ O ₅ applied	Weed control ^a	Insect control ^b	
			Chemical	Applied
<i>Management level 1</i>				
20	—	25 DT	Handweeding	—
<i>Management level 2</i>				
20	—	basal	Handweeding	—
20	—	25 DT	MIPC	15 DT
<i>Management level 3</i>				
40	40	basal	2,4-D	Carbofuran
20	—	25 DT	Carbofuran	4 DT
<i>Management level 4</i>				
40	40	basal	2,4-D	Carbofuran
20	—	25 DT	Carbofuran	20 DT
20	—	45 DT	MIPC	45 DT
<i>Management level 5</i>				
60	40	basal	Butachlor	Carbofuran
20	—	25 DT	MIPC	35 DT
20	—	45 DT	Lindane	50 DT
			MIPC	75 DT

^aHandweeding done at 20 DT. Herbicides applied at 4 DT. 2,4-D: 0.8 kg/ha a.i. Butachlor: 1.5 kg/ha a.i. ^bSST = seed and seedling treatment. Rates (a.i.), except for SST: carbofuran, 0.05% kg/ha; MIPC, 0.05% concn; lindane, 3 kg/ha.

the Buenavista silt loam soils in one location. However, no yield data were obtained from this plot because of late planting and drought damage.

Upland herbicide trial. Five promising herbicides and handweeding were tested in four locations to determine their effectiveness in controlling the common weeds in upland rice. The chemicals were sprayed 4 to 6 days after seeding at 2 kg/ha a.i. Preforan and butachlor provided the best control of grasses, broad-leaved weeds, and sedges in all locations. Benthocarb also effectively controlled broad-leaved weeds and sedges, but it did not control grasses effectively at all locations. A-820 satisfactorily controlled broadleaved weeds, but gave only fair control of grasses and sedges. C-288 gave satisfactory control at two locations but performed poorly at the other locations.

All the plots in general gave low yields (Table 15) as a result of severe moisture stress starting at the booting stage. Butachlor and Preforan performed best.

Multiple cropping. Trial plantings of sorghum, sweet potato, soybean, cowpea, and mongo in the rainfed areas last year revealed that it is possible to grow these crops after harvesting the rice crop. To determine if these crops could be grown successfully in the rainfed and upland areas before the rice crop, we established several trial plantings in May and June 1972. The crops tested were mung bean, soybean, cowpea, sweet corn, peanut, and field corn.

A trial established in a rainfed paddy at Santa Maria was planted the last week of April. The trial plantings in San Rafael, San Ildefonso, San Miguel, and Gapan were established immediately after a 3-cm rainfall in the middle of May. Crops planted in Santa Maria and San

Table 11. Effects of five levels of management on the grain yield of IR20 and returns above cash costs, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Management level	Cash costs ^a (P)	Early planting ^b		Late planting ^d	
		Yield (t/ha)	Return above cash costs ^c (P/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Return above cash costs (P/ha)
1	88	3.6	1956	1.4	707
2	194	4.5	2362	1.8	828
3	297	4.6	2316	2.1	896
4	384	4.8	2342	2.2 ^e	922
5	510	5.5	2615	2.3 ^f	930

^aCost of fertilizer, insecticide, handweeding, and herbicide. ^bTwo locations. Plots established between the first and third week of July. ^cRice price: at P568/t. ^dFour locations. Plots established the first or second week of August. ^eCash costs of inputs, P328. Application of N at 45 DT omitted because of drought. ^fCash costs of inputs, P376. Application of N at 45 DT and of lindane at 50 DT omitted because of drought.

Ildefonso the first week of May had excellent stands, and excellent yields would have been obtained from these crops had they not been destroyed by the typhoon which hit the area in July. The plots established in the rainfed areas after the middle of June became water-logged, and the plants died before they flowered.

Weeds were a serious problem at all trial sites. Butachlor was sprayed at 2 kg/ha a.i. at seeding time. The plots were weed-free for about 2 to 3 weeks but became very weedy later. The weeds most common in the area were *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Echinochloa colonum*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptiura*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Paspalum flavidum*, *Portulaca oleracea*, *Mimosa pudica*, and *Cynodon dactylon*.

Table 12. Performance of 15 varieties and selections under upland conditions, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)		Maturity ^c (days)
	Early seeding ^a	Late seeding ^b	
IR577-24-1	4.0	0.8	121
IR24	3.7	1.9	118
IR790-28-6	3.3	0.8	120
C4-63 G	3.3	1.6	120
C22-51	3.2	1.7	120
IR8	3.1	^d	123
BPI 9-33	3.0	1.2	106
Palawan	2.9	1.4	120
MI-48	2.9	1.6	120
BPI 76-1	2.8	1.3	121
Kinandang Puti	2.7	1.4	108
Azmil 26	2.7	1.4	120
HBDA ₂	2.5	1.7	121
IR5	2.4	^d	138
Azucena	2.2	1.4	121

^aMean of four locations. ^bMean of one location. ^cSeeding to harvest. ^dNo data obtained. Harvested by cooperator.

PILOT EXTENSION PROGRAM

The applied research project on rainfed and upland rice was established to explore ways of increasing rice yields in the rainfed and upland areas and to develop strategies for spreading the new technology to farmers. The field testing program was planned for 3 years to develop a satisfactory package of cultural practices, but the high rice yields obtained in 1971 under conditions of rather severe drought and a serious outbreak of tungro virus convinced the research workers and the agriculturists of Bulacan province that the results could be safely recommended immediately for adoption by farmers.

In early 1972, the project management decided to launch a pilot extension program to determine the effects of the new technology when applied on a whole-farm basis. The program was designed to promote rapid widescale adoption of the package of cultural practices using a small number of skilled and highly motivated farm management technicians. The

Table 13. Phosphorus response of direct-seeded IR5 with 90 kg/ha N and 60 kg/ha K₂O under upland conditions, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Trial no.	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Phosphorus level (kg/ha P ₂ O ₅)		
	0	30	60
1	2.2	3.2	3.6
2	1.6	1.1	2.5
3	3.9	4.1	4.4
4	1.9	3.7	2.6
Mean	2.4	3.0	3.3

Table 14. Net returns from the application of nitrogen on direct-seeded IR5 under upland conditions (mean of seven locations). Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cash costs (P/ha)	Net return* (P/ha)
0	1.3	—	—
60	2.7	85	710
90	3.0	128	837
120	3.0	170	795

*Rice price: P568/t.

goal was to increase rice yields to an average of 4.5 t/ha over the entire project area within 3 years.

Food and agricultural councils were formed at the provincial, municipal, and barrio levels to serve as the coordinating and implementing bodies.

A detailed program of work was developed which included (1) Developing a sample work plan for a municipality, including selection of pilot barrios, organizing barrio seminars, and organizing field demonstrations and field days; (2) Developing cultural recommendations for growing rice based on the results of the 1971 applied research trials and previous trials conducted by the Bureau of Soils in the area; (3) Developing a sample farm plan and budget for a 1-hectare rice farm; (4) Outlining responsibilities of members of the food and agricultural councils in supporting the program.

Eleven farm management technicians from Bulacan were selected and trained at IIRRI for 3 weeks. Results of the pre-training evaluation of the technicians showed that without training they would have been poor advisers to farmers. The group had an average score of only 32

Table 15. Effects of herbicides (applied at 2 kg/ha a.i.) and handweeding on grain yield of IR5 under upland conditions, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1972 wet season.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	
Butachlor	2.1*	4.3*	1.1	3.2	2.7
Benthiocarb	1.7*	2.9	2.0	3.4	2.5
Preforan	2.3*	3.1	1.5	2.3	2.3
C-288	1.2	3.0	1.0	3.1	2.1
A-820	2.7*	3.0	1.6	3.1	2.6
Handweeding	2.4*	3.0	1.1	3.3	2.4
Control	1.1	2.5	0.8	2.6	1.7

percent. They would have been wrong seven out of 10 times in identifying the major field problems. Few had the necessary skill to effectively demonstrate the new technology to farmers. The technicians improved considerably during the 3 weeks of intensive classroom laboratory and field instruction.

Posters, banners, leaflets, newsletters, radio programs, signboards on model farms, and other means were used to create awareness in farmers of the new technology and to develop their interest in adopting it. Seminars and field demonstrations were held in all barrios within the program area. The technicians made continual field visits to guide farmers in the proper application of inputs and to maintain their interest. Field days were conducted for farmers, rural bank officials, and others.

A "flagging system" was adopted to inform farmers of problems in their fields and what they should do about them. The technician in cooperation with a member of the food and agricultural council of the barrio finds problems in the field and alerts the farmer by putting up a flag in his field. Instructions are written on the flag indicating what to do about the problem.

The technicians were assigned to five or six barrios selected from each municipality covered by the program. Barrios whose potential for development was great and whose farmers and barrio officials indicated an interest were selected. The plan is to make the first five or six barrios models for the municipality.

Incentives and transportation are provided each technician who is expected to work long and hard. The incentive pay is necessary in addition to regular monthly travelling expense to partially compensate the technicians for the extra work performed. A motorcycle, with gasoline, oil, maintenance, and insurance provided free, is made available to each technician so he can easily cover his assigned area.

Production loans are made to selected farmers through the Agriculture Loan Fund (ALF) of the rural banks to enable them to participate in the program. The loans have averaged P700/ha. Loans are released in three installments. All loans are given in kind except the amount allocated for land preparation and transplanting which is given in cash. Any deviation from the re-

commended package of practices was considered a risk so rural banks were encouraged to provide the full loan. The rural banks in the area cooperated in granting ALF loans to farmers, but only two banks lent more than P100,000. Other bankers were skeptical about granting loans to farmers because of the history of very low repayment. By November P1,425,000 had been released to farmers to finance the production of 2,600 hectares of rice.

Arrangements were made with pesticide and fertilizer companies to ensure the availability of sufficient stocks of all recommended inputs. Private industry gave unprecedented support in the form of printed information materials and motorcycles and other transportation facilities for use of the technicians. It has also provided immeasurable assistance in gaining the cooperation of different support services to the program.

It is difficult to assess the impact of the program with experience from only one cropping season. Evaluation is based mainly on the

reports of yields obtained by farmers who participated. For example, in Pandi, Bulacan, of the 100 hectares reported harvested, 90 hectares had yields of over 4 t/ha. Average yields of farmers who did not use the recommended package of practices ranged from 2 to 3 t/ha. Poor weed control, heavy insect damage, high incidence of diseases, and improper application of fertilizer contributed to low yields.

The results of the pilot program show that it is feasible to increase rice yields substantially. It has been demonstrated that well-trained and highly motivated technicians, with transportation and incentive pay, can effect a rapid adoption of new technology if farmers have sufficient capital with which to purchase the required inputs. For the farmers, the experience they have had in harvesting, for the first time, over 5 t/ha has created new confidence in their capacity to produce. With the cooperation of administrators, bankers, agro-business firms, and community leaders the same yield increases are possible in other areas.

Other activities

Training programs

One of the most important conditions for the successful implementation of national rice programs is the availability of properly trained and highly motivated researchers and extension workers. The institute is helping increase the number of such qualified individuals through its training programs.

Research-oriented rice workers are given the opportunity to work under the guidance of IRRI scientists in different research areas related to rice culture. Rice workers who participate in IRRI's research training program may undertake a degree or a non-degree program.

The degree program is carried out in cooperation with various universities, especially the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines (UPCA), and the post-graduate school of the Indian Agricultural Research Institute. The individual's course requirements are completed in the cooperating academic institution and he does his research at IRRI. Participants work for either an M.S. or a Ph.D. degree.

A non-degree participant gains valuable research experience by working on a specific project under the guidance of an IRRI staff member. The participant helps plan the project and assumes major responsibility for gathering and analyzing data and preparing a report of the work.

Two types of programs are available to extension workers—a 6-month course in rice production and a 2-week course. Participants in the 6-month course are taught how to conduct rice training programs in their own countries. The 2-week course attempts to impart the latest technology of growing rice.

During 1972 the institute had 65 research scholars and fellows (Table 1). Of the 37 research scholars, 25 were M.S. degree candidates at UPCA. Of 20 post-M.S. fellows 4 were degree candidates: one was working for a Ph.D. degree from UPCA and the others were working for a Ph.D. degree from the Indian Agricultural Research Institute. Forty-one research scholars and fellows completed their programs during the year and returned to their home countries.

Thirty-six trainees from 15 countries participated in the 6-month rice production course held from June to December. As part of their training, they planned and conducted a 2-week rice production course in November.

Forty-two persons participated in the November 2-week course; 38 of the participants were from the Philippines. Another 2-week course was conducted by the staff of the Rice Production Training and Research Office in December. It had 48 participants representing eight countries.

Sixteen rice scientists and administrators of agencies concerned with

rice either observed some phase of the institute work or participated in a short research project. Typical examples of the participants were the director of a major crop experiment station in Korea, who was briefed about and observed the implementation of the institute's breeding program, and an agricultural engineer from India who studied and observed machinery design, development, and testing for 2 months.

In 1972, 21 individuals were studying in the U.S., the U.K., and India under IRRI sponsorship through its different country programs. Eleven of the students are from Ceylon, six from Indonesia, three from Bangladesh, and one from the Philippines. Five of the Indonesians are only partially sponsored by IRRI. This means that IRRI, through its country program in Indonesia, supports the family of the scholar, who is under a study grant from USAID, to enable them to be with the scholar at his place of study. IRRI's resident adviser in Indonesia plays an important role in identifying and selecting the scholars to be awarded the USAID

Table 1. Distribution of different categories of scholars according to area of specialization.

Research area	Scholars (no.)			Total
	Research scholars	Post-M.S. fellows	Post-doctoral fellows	
Agr. economics	6	—	—	6
Agronomy	5	3	—	8
Entomology	5	—	2	7
Plant pathology	4	2	1	7
Soil chemistry	3	3	1	7
Statistics	2	—	—	2
Varietal improvement	8	3	2	13
Soil microbiology	3	2	1	6
Multiple cropping	1	—	—	1
Plant physiology	—	5	1	6
Agr. engineering	—	2	—	2
Total	37	20	8	65

TRAINEES

Names and home institutions of persons who completed their training during the year are given below. An asterisk (*) indicates individuals who completed the M.S. degree during the year.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS

Agricultural Economics

Jose Diaz III, Philippines. Comparison of mechanical and sun-drying for traditional and improved systems of harvesting and milling rice and the measurement of economic benefits of each in terms of the rice recovery and quality.

William Henry Meyers,* U.S.A. Alternative patterns of resource use for achieving self-sufficiency in rice in the 1970's: A linear programming analysis.

Agronomy

Ricardo Canet Pellicer, chief director, rice experiment station, Institute of Agricultural Science, Havana University, Cuba. Weed control in rainfed and irrigated rice. Evaluation of rice varieties bred at IRRI and elsewhere.

Rajeshwar Nath Mallick,* agronomist, Department of Agriculture Education and Research, Nepal. Interaction between soil moisture regime and nitrogen level in upland rice.

Tamoyuki Watanabe, fertilizers research department, Mitsubishi Chemical Industries Ltd., Tokyo. Effect of nitrogen sources on upland and lowland rice.

Entomology

Emmanuel Akinsola,* research officer (rice entomology), Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria. Yellow borer, *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker, resistance in rice varieties.

Chao-yen Hsieh,* junior entomologist, Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan. The ecology of rice green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant).

Ramon Rodriguez,* Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Agricolas, Mexico. Resistance to the whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in rice varieties.

Plant Pathology

Pethsri Chaipanich, second grade agricultural officer, technical division, Rice Department, Thailand. Some factors affecting the development of sheath blight of rice.

Mohamed Roushdy Mahmoud Aly Sehly, research assistant, plant pathology section, Sakha Research Station, Egypt. Identification of the races of *Pyricularia oryzae* from single lesions.

Soil Chemistry

Francisco Cotejo, Jr., Philippines. Nitrogen loss in dry fallowed paddy soils.

Statistics

Sridodo,* research assistant, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia. Sampling in broadcast rice.

Varietal improvement

J. E. Deus Reuteria, chief of genetics branch, rice experiment station, Institute of Agricultural Science, University of Havana. General rice breeding.

Moon Kap Joo, junior agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Breeding for cold tolerance.

Mansur Lande, department of agronomy, Maros Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia. Genetic analysis and the correlation of leaf and grain characters in a rice cross of IR127-80-1-10 × IR332-2-10-1-2-1-2.

Paul Peiris, agricultural instructor, plant breeding, Rice Research Station, Ceylon. Improvement of Ceylonese rice varieties against common diseases and pests.

Dil Rosh, research assistant, Agricultural Research Institute, Pakistan. Breeding for cold tolerance.

study grants. Except for five agricultural engineers from Ceylon, the rest are working for either the M.S. or Ph.D. degree. The Ceylonese agricultural engineers are participating in a 2-month non-degree program in rice process engineering at the Indian Institute of Technology.

During the year Mir Nazrul Islam obtained a Ph.D. in cereal chemistry from the Louisiana State University and Mohammed Abu Bakr, Bangladesh, completed an M.S. degree in plant pathology from the University of Hawaii.

With partial financial assistance from IRRI, a graduate student at the University of Wisconsin (USA) began a study of the effectiveness of the training programs. Since its founding IRRI has trained 743 individuals, including persons who completed their programs in 1972. The study will focus on how trainees have used the skills they developed at IRRI, what procedures were used to select the trainee and plan his program, what follow-up support reached the trainee, and what plans the former trainees have.

During 1972, 119 scholars, fellows, and other trainees were in residence at IRRI for all or part of the year.

International programs

Ties between the institute's core research program and national programs were further strengthened during 1972. Several new projects were undertaken. These include a contract with the U.S. Agency for International Development for research on rice and multiple cropping in Indonesia, a USAID contract to assist the Philippine government in its intensified crop production program, one agreement with the Ford Foundation to provide the services of a rice breeder to work with its Arid Lands Agricultural Development Program in Egypt,

and another to improve rice processing, marketing, and storage in Sri Lanka. A contract was signed with the government of Indonesia to assist with the development of the regional research station at Sukamandi, using a World Bank loan made to Indonesia. Under various projects, a total of 21 senior scientists on the institute staff were located in Bangladesh, Egypt, India, Indonesia, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam.

The institute continued to cooperate with countries with which it did not have formal agreements through exchange of staff visits and supply of technical information, and plant materials. In 1972, IRRI supplied more than 10,000 seed packages of breeding lines and varieties from the world collection to 69 countries.

The institute started a project for collecting and preserving germ plasm under a grant from The Rockefeller Foundation. The institute staff and scientists in Sri Lanka, Indonesia, and Khmer Republic collected more than 4,000 indigenous varieties which were added to the world collection.

Under cooperative testing programs agricultural machines developed at IRRI were evaluated in nine countries.

Country projects. Since IRRI scientists assigned to cooperative projects work as members of teams with local scientists engaged in national rice programs of host countries, detailed accounts of their work are included in local reports. A brief review of progress of national programs in which they are involved is given here.

IRRI continued to help the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute develop its research capabilities and coordinate research. Activities during the early part of the year were curtailed due to the aftermath of the war, but the project picked up new momentum in the latter part

RESEARCH FELLOWS

Post-M.S.

Kolawole Adeyemi Ayotade, research officer, Federal Rice Research Station, Nigeria. Soluble sulfide (S^{2-} , HS^- , H_2S) in soil solution of submerged soils—Method of quantitative estimation and sulfide equilibria studies.

Somkid Disthaporn, second grade researcher, Rice Department, Thailand. Testing resistance to tungro disease by mass screening method.

Leonardo Hernandez Aragon, rice breeding program, Centro de Investigaciones Agrícolas de Sinaloa, Mexico. Breeding for grain quality and disease and insect resistance.

Tsuguhiro Hoshino, graduate student, department of agronomy, faculty of agriculture, Tohoku University, Japan. Density effect in rice and sorghum. The difference of energy efficiency in rice and sorghum.

Ghulam Nabi Kalwar,* assistant agronomist (rice), Rice Research Station, Pakistan. Water use and moisture stress effects on transplanted rice.

Mohamed Samir Abdel Aziz Abdel Kerim, research worker, Agricultural Research Station, Sakha, Egypt. The performance of rice in puddled and nonpuddled soil under rainfed and irrigated flooded conditions.

Bonifacio Lapade, Philippines. Atmospheric nitrogen fixation in some edible aquatic plants.

Jeffrey Lessoff, U.S.A. Rotational cropping.

Yun Jin Oh, junior agronomist, Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Growth performance of IR667 in the Philippines and Korea.

Rumiati, L. P. P., Indonesia. Plant nutrition problems.

A. B. M. Salahuddin,* research assistant, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bangladesh. Cold tolerance of improved rice varieties at seedling stage and its effects on the yield component.

V. E. A. Wikramanayake, senior lecturer, University of Ceylon. The design of improved small-scale rice processing equipment.

Post-Doctoral

J. C. Katyal, soil scientist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. Zinc deficiency.

Antonio T. Perez, field advisor and visiting scientist, IRRI, Philippines. Inheritance of amylose content in rice. Inheritance of gelatinization temperature in rice. Chemical induction of artificial male sterility in rice by using Ethrel and RH-531. Endosperm dosage effect of waxy genes in rice.

S. S. Sajjan, entomologist (rice), Punjab Agricultural University, India. Varietal resistance of rice to the green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus*.

R. Sridhar, Annamalai University, India. Biochemistry of disease resistance mechanism in rice blast disease.

Yoshihiro Takano, Sanyu Consultants International Inc., Nagoya, Japan. Study of photosynthesis among rice varieties.

Sant Singh Virmani, department of plant breeding, Punjab Agricultural University, India. Investigations on cytoplasmic male sterility in rice. Studies on outcrossing mechanism in rice. Development of isogenic lines possessing genes for resistance to brown planthopper and green leafhopper.

RICE PRODUCTION TRAINEES

Dario Alfonso Morel, inspector de campo, Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería, Paraguay.

Carla Eudoxia Andaki, chief, extension division, Agricultural Extension Service, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Pulsawat Archalaka, second grade officer, technical division, Rice Department, Thailand.

Edilberto R. Ardieta, training officer, Department of Agrarian Reform, Philippines.

Prayoon Bailee, second grade officer, extension division, Rice Department, Thailand.

Samrej Chairatana, agricultural officer, Stule Province, Thailand.

Dharma, field extension worker, North Sumatra Agricultural Extension Service, Indonesia.

Abdurrazak Djafar, Agricultural Extension Service, South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia.

Pramono Djojodarmodjo, counterpart agronomist, Land and Water Resources Development Project, Indonesia.

Oloche Anebi Edache, agricultural officer, Federal Department of Agriculture, Nigeria.

K. A. C. Fernando, agricultural instructor, In-Service Training Institute, Ceylon.

Edward James Findley, agricultural country extension agent, Department of Agriculture, Liberia.

Abdur Rashid Gomosta, scientific officer, physiology division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Bangladesh.

Haeruddin, chief of second crop division, Agricultural Extension Service, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

James R. Hoopper III, graduate student, department of agronomy, University of Florida, U.S.A.

Andrew Joseph, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

Pisanai Krasaindra, second grade officer, Agriculture Extension Department, Thailand.

Khampheuy Luangpraseuth, rice technician, Rice Research Center, Laos.

U Nyunt Lwin, township manager, Department of Agriculture Corporation, Burma.

T. E. R. M'Bawa, farm demonstrator, department of agronomy, Njala University College, Sierra Leone.

Iliki Naikatini, extension officer, Irrigation Office, Fiji.

U Win Naing, township manager, Department of Agriculture Corporation, Burma.

Aurelio C. Ocampo, agriculture extension supervisor, Apalit/San Simon Agrarian Reform Team, Philippines.

Emmanuel Bassey Okoro, agricultural officer, Federal Department of Agriculture, Nigeria.

J. N. T. Paaris, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

A. M. S. Perera, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

Buluku Pomanto, head, information division, Agricultural Extension Service of South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

W. H. E. Premaratne, cultivation officer, River Valley Development Board, Ceylon.

Debabrata Sarkar, district agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture and Community Development, India.

Kanwar Phool Singh, deputy director of agriculture, Department of Agriculture, Haryana, India.

Raghibir Singh, extension officer, Department of Agriculture, Punjab, India.

Victor Situmorang, head, farm management section, Agriculture Extension Service, North Sumatra, Indonesia.

Pen Song, in-charge, rice experimental section, Agricultural Pilot Station of Bañan, Khmer Republic.

Thong Chanh Souvannarith, rice technician, Department of Agriculture, Laos.

Sedjati Sukatendel, staff, North Sumatra Agricultural Extension Service, Indonesia.

Enos Tambing, chief, Agriculture Extension Service, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

SHORT-TERM VISITORS

Buyyala C. Babu, agricultural engineer, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, studied and observed machinery design, development, and testing for 2 months.

Mohammed Abu Bakr, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, worked on disease resistance to bacterial diseases; observed the cooperative work on combining resistance to other major diseases and insects; and observed screening methods. He stayed for 2 months.

Ubol Chaimongkol, technical division, Rice Department, Thailand, conducted studies on strains of rice tungro virus for 2 months.

Hoo Sup Chung, college of agriculture, Seoul National University, Korea,

of the year. Negotiations were made with the Ford Foundation and the Bangladesh government to revitalize the training and research programs. The Bangladesh project is likely to be expanded in 1973. Lack of adequate numbers of qualified rice scientists is limiting the progress of the rice program in Bangladesh. A significant event during the year was the identification of many promising young scholars for training in different areas at IRRI and other institutions.

IR20 continued to spread, 800,000 hectares were planted to this variety in 1972. The new variety Chandina, which was grown only on a small area in 1971, was planted on about 60,000 hectares in the boro crop season of 1972.

Under a contract with the Ford Foundation, IRRI provided a rice breeder to work with the Arid Lands Agricultural Development Program in Egypt. The entire rice crop in Egypt is of japonica type. Evaluation of IRRI selections during the year demonstrated the tremendous potential of long and slender grain indica rices for large-scale commercial introduction. Egypt has no serious insect problem and the only disease of major significance is blast. The performance of IR22 and its sister selection, IR579-48-1-2, was very encouraging and the Egyptian government has decided to rapidly multiply these lines for commercial cultivation. Another IRRI variety, IR24, which has long, slender grains but cooks semi-sticky, has also shown promise of adaptability to Egyptian conditions. In addition, several advanced lines performed well. These lines will be advanced one generation at IRRI during the winter season to help the Egyptian program expedite the identification and multiplication of new superior lines.

The institute continued to cooperate with the All-India Co-

ordinated Rice Improvement Project. The major support came through a contract with the USAID which supplies five scientists to the project. The support is being gradually phased out and two of the scientists completed their assignment, bringing the staff down to three by the year end. In addition, the Ford Foundation provided funds for rice pathology and adaptive research. The joint coordinator of AICRIP is assigned to IRRI by The Rockefeller Foundation.

The Indian government strengthened the project by filling new positions created in agronomy, pathology, physiology, entomology, and breeding. A building program under way will provide office and laboratory facilities for scientists and greenhouse facilities for research on host-plant resistance. Evaluation and adaptive trials with new rice selections were expanded. A mini-kit program started in the dry season of 1972 with 4,000 farmers was extended to over 40,000 farmers with additional selections, including some with resistance to gall midge and to tungro virus.

As research programs in the various states of the country have intensified in activity, research is being extended to special localized problems such as salinity, deep water, and cold tolerance while varieties with wide adaptation are being developed with higher resistance to diseases and insects. With greater staff strength at the AICRIP headquarters in Hyderabad, additional support was provided to state programs through exchange visits and short courses for scientists.

The Indonesian project was greatly expanded during the year to cope with the many research problems requiring attention for a sustained increase in rice production in the country. IRRI signed a contract with USAID to strengthen

worked on reactions of some IRRI lines to *Pyricularia oryzae* in Korea and at IRRI for 1 month.

- Kyu Yong Chung, director, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea, observed the rice breeding program for 2 weeks.
- Young Soo Ham, director, Honam Crop Experiment Station, Korea, observed the rice breeding program for 2 weeks.
- Abdul Hamid, head, Agricultural Equipment Development Sub Division, Mekanisasi Pertanian, Indonesia, observed machinery design, development, and testing, and motor vehicles maintenance for 2 months.
- Chong Woon Hong, Institute of Plant Environment, Korea, observed soil chemistry program for 3 months.
- Shih-Pan-Yu Hsieh, Taiwan, made ecological studies of *Xanthomonas oryzae* for 5 months.
- Panya Lakanurak, Thailand, studied machinery design, development and testing, and made a Thai translation of instruction manuals for the table thresher, row seeder, and grain cleaner. He stayed for 2 months.
- Syed F. Quader, in-charge, service center, maintenance of farm equipment and support vehicles, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, studied and observed machinery design, development, and testing, and motor vehicle maintenance for 2 months.
- Jae Yong Rhee, director, research bureau, Office of Rural Development, Korea, observed the rice breeding program for 1 week.
- Jibril T. Rogun, agricultural officer, Government of Kwara State, Nigeria, observed the rice production course and applied research program for 1 week.
- D. W. Sirinayake, agricultural officer in-charge, In-Service Training Institute, Ceylon, observed training program and coordinated and managed a special course. He stayed for 3 months.
- I. W. Made Tantera, Indonesia, observed general rice pathology work for 3 days.
- Ching Piao Wu, senior specialist of agricultural engineering, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, studied machinery design, development, and testing for 2 weeks.

PUBLICATIONS AND SEMINARS

STAFF PUBLICATIONS

Administration

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- Crisostomo, C. M., W. H. Meyers, T. B. Paris, Jr., B. Duff, and R. Barker. 1971. The new rice technology and labor absorption in Philippine agriculture. Malay. Econ. Rev. 16(2): 117-158.

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- De Datta, S. K., W. N. Obcemea, and R. K. Jana. 1972. Protein content of rice grain as affected by nitrogen fertilizer and some triazines and substituted ureas. *Agron. J.* 64:785-788.
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- Palmiano, E. P., and B. O. Juliano. 1972. Physicochemical properties of Niigata waxy rices. *Agr. Biol. Chem.* 36:157-159.

research in rice breeding, agronomy, and multiple cropping. Four of the five scientists provided by this contract began working at the Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor.

The development of the Maros station in South Sulawesi continued under a grant made by the Netherlands government. One experiment station development engineer and a research administration specialist began work at Maros. The first phase of the building program is well under way.

The institute continued to coordinate foreign support of the National Rice Research Program. With IRRI's assistance, the Caltex prepared a plan for setting up a small branch station in the Riau province of Sumatra. The provincial government and Caltex signed an agreement to provide technical assistance and training for the establishment of this station.

The Ford Foundation renewed its grant to IRRI for another 2 years. This grant provides for the continuation of the services of a senior scientist as joint coordinator of NRRP, training of Indonesians, and purchase of equipment.

A contract was signed between the government of Indonesia and IRRI to provide six experts, to train Indonesian research staff, and to give technical support for strengthening research at a new research station at Sukamandi. This station is a branch of the Central Research Institute for Agriculture and funds for its development were furnished by a World Bank loan to the government of Indonesia.

In the Philippines under a contract with USAID, the institute assigned a crop production specialist to the National Food and Agriculture Council to help develop an intensified inter-agency extension and production program for rice and other crops. Working closely with NFAC and other

national agencies, the specialist helped prepare plans and informational material for rice production in flood-affected areas. Under NFAC sponsorship, 6,000 mung bean production kits, each for 500 sq m, were prepared by an inter-agency team and distributed free to farmers in areas of Central Luzon silted by the July floods.

IR20 has become the leading rice variety planted by Philippine rice farmers. IRRI supplied 18 tons of IR20 foundation seed to Philippine agencies for multiplication and distribution.

The rice program in Sri Lanka showed good progress and several new high-yielding varieties were released for commercial cultivation. The mini-kit program continued to accelerate the evaluation and spread of new rice selections on farmers' fields. The training program for extension workers was further strengthened. In 1972, over 10,000 man-days of training were provided in 1-week to 2-week rice production courses organized at two training centers manned by IRRI graduates. Thousands of farmers received informal rice training and small amounts of seed of new varieties at district extension centers throughout the country.

The Paddy Marketing Board, with assistance from the IRRI rice processing project, sent engineers abroad for training. A new facility for local training in storage and processing is being developed. This facility will be used to train operators, technicians, and managers for rice mills. The project is helping the Paddy Marketing Board to improve its paddy purchasing system, storage methods, and existing rice mills and to establish new modern complexes to store and process paddy.

Under a contract with USAID, IRRI assigned one agronomist and one rice breeder to assist Vietnam's Institute of Agricultural Research

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in improving the rice research program. Four research stations in Vietnam are engaged in rice research. The principal one is the National Crops Testing and Training Center at Mytho. One IRRI scientist worked full time at Mytho. The efforts of the IRRI team were focused on helping Vietnam's researchers evaluate IRRI lines and conduct fertility and herbicide experiments. Several new IRRI lines performed well in yield trials and may soon replace rice varieties now being used for commercial production in Vietnam. Unfortunately, poor security conditions interfered with the experimental work at Mytho and a major portion of the work has been moved to Long Xuyen in the Mekong delta.

International conferences. At the time of its 10th anniversary celebrations on April 20 and 21, IRRI held a symposium which was attended by about 200 scientists, administrators, and policy makers from 21 countries. Ten papers were presented during the symposium which reviewed IRRI's activities, rice research in different regions, the impact of new rice technology, and rice production trends. These papers have been printed in *Rice, science, and man*.

The agricultural economics department, in cooperation with the agricultural engineering and agricultural economics departments of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, conducted a 4-day workshop on water management in December. The program included 18 papers on rice response to water, economic analysis of irrigation, project operation, and case studies of organizational and institutional problems. The purpose of the workshop was to bring together recent results of research on water management and to provide an opportunity for interaction between agronomists, economists, engineers, and sociologists.

The papers will be printed in a single volume. Fifty-three scientists attended the workshop. Most of them were from the Philippines but 10 came from Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Singapore, Thailand, and Nigeria.

Experimental farm

In the dry season we planted 8.4 hectares for seed production and in the wet season, 8.9 hectares.

Tungro disease decreased yields in the dry season, including that of IR20, which was planted on 2 hectares outside the IRRI farm and received less insecticide than the other varieties planted inside the farm. The dry-season crop averaged 3.8 t/ha for IR20, 5.8 t/ha for IR833-6-2, 5.5 t/ha for IR1561-243-5, 6.1 t/ha for IR1561-250-2, 4.5 t/ha for IR1561-228-3 and for IR8, 4.2 t/ha for IR5, and 5.9 t/ha for IR1006-20-5.

The wet-season crop was also badly affected by tungro. Some of the average yields: 3.4 t/ha for IR1529-680-3, 3.8 t/ha for IR1529-382-4, 3.9 t/ha for IR1529-430-3, and 4.5 t/ha for IR24.

Ninety hectares were prepared and planted to rice this year compared with 79 hectares last year.

Leafhopper infestation contributed to the low yields of the seed production plots. In some heavily infested areas, insecticide was sprayed weekly instead of every 2 weeks. The most used insecticides were Furadan, Mipcin, and lindane.

As in previous years the plots were fertilized with ammonium sulfate, solophos, muriate of potash, and urea. Weeds were controlled with Machete, 2,4-D, and Saturn. Except in the upland rice fields, hand weeding was kept at a minimum. For the roadways and levees Gramoxone was used extensively.

The creek passing through one of the upland areas was straightened and the low spots were partially filled with soil, increasing the seed-

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- Loresto, G. C., and T. T. Chang. 1971. Root development of rice varieties under different soil moisture conditions. Pages 412-416 in Crop Science Society of the Philippines, Proceedings of the second annual scientific meeting, May 4-6, 1971. College, Laguna, Philippines.
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SEMINARS

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the institute during 1972. Unless otherwise stated the speakers were staff members.

- Developing research capabilities in the food crop production sector: an Indonesian experience. Dr. Go Ban Hong, visiting scientist, IRRI.
- Land and water use in Ceylon: modernization of an ancient tradition. Mr. V. E. A. Wikramanayake, research fellow, IRRI.
- The place of off-farm work in the economy of some Bulacan rice farmers. Mr. Brian Fegan, anthropologist, National Museum, Manila.
- Adoption of high yielding varieties of rice in the Philippines. Dr. Reeshon Feuer, visiting professor, UPCA (Cornell University), and Mr. Paulino Resma, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Diliman, Quezon City.
- Vegetable breeding in Hawaii. Dr. Richard W. Hartmann, associate professor of horticulture, University of Hawaii.
- Surveillance of pests and diseases of rice in India, with special reference to the occurrence of tungro virus, Dr. John A. Lowe, entomologist, Ford Foundation, India.
- Recent research on rice diseases in Korea. Prof. H. S. Chung, Seoul National University, Korea.
- New dimensions for international agricultural research. Dr. Cummings.
- Some thoughts on the green revolution and agricultural development in India. Dr. Chandler.
- The tungro disease. Dr. Ou.
- Highlights of the study and evaluation of the rice production intensification program of Indonesia. Dr. Orlando J. Sacay, vice president, International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, Silang, Cavite.
- Education for rural development: the case of the UPCA/BNE barrio development school project. Dr. Tito E. Contado, director of extension education, UPCA.
- Long distance migration of planthoppers. Dr. Ryoichi Kisimoto, chief, Third Laboratory of Entomology, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Japan.

The involvement of U.S. universities in international agricultural development. Dr. Kenneth L. Turk, director, International Agricultural Development, Cornell University.

The evolution of maize and its significance in breeding. Dr. E. J. Wellhausen, associate director, The Rockefeller Foundation.

Rice marketing and price stabilization. Mr. J. D. Drilon, Jr., director, Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture, College, Laguna.

Intensified pest management needs of developing nations. Dr. J. L. Apple, assistant director, Research and Academic Affairs, North Carolina State University, Raleigh.

Production of rice and wheat in Pakistan. Dr. Gordon W. McLean, agricultural adviser, Ford Foundation, Pakistan.

The problems and potentials of irrigation in the Philippines. Dr. Wickham. Irrigation objectives of the Upper Pampanga River Project. Mr. Cesar E. Gonzales, project manager, Upper Pampanga River Project.

Trends in Pakistan agriculture. Ambassador A. A. Farooq, Pakistan Embassy, Manila.

The impact of agricultural modernization on non-farm employment. Mr. Arthur Gibb, Jr., research associate, School of Economics, University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City.

Malariaology and malaria eradication. Dr. A. C. van der Gugten, epidemiologist, World Health Organization, International Malaria Eradication Training Center, and Dr. Cesar Valera, chief, Division of Epidemiology, Research and Training, Malaria Eradication Service, Manila.

The status and future of the fishing industry in the Philippines. Mr. Inocencio A. Ronquillo, chief, Marine Fisheries Biology Division, Philippine Fisheries Commission.

World demand for Philippine coconut products. Dr. Aida Librero, assistant professor, Department of Agricultural Economics, UPCA.

An anthropologist's view of rice and vegetable crop farming in Palawan. Mr. James Eder, research scholar, University of California, Santa Barbara.

Cooperative lowland rice trials in the Philippines. Dr. Pedro B. Escuro, professor, Department of Agronomy, UPCA.

Poverty and progress in Tondo. Mrs. Mary Hollensteiner, Institute of Philippine Culture, Ateneo de Manila University, Quezon City.

The IRRI rice program in Vietnam. Dr. Perry Bosshart, team leader, IRRI/USAID Rice Research Project in Vietnam.

Sorghum production in Thailand. Dr. Harwood.

Five tons of rice for five extra pesos of zinc oxide in Agusan del Norte. Dr. J. C. Katyal, research fellow, IRRI.

Leaching losses of nitrate nitrogen from a virgin organic soil profile. Dr. Jerry B. Fitts, agronomist, International Rice Program in Indonesia.

The international wheat testing program at CIMMYT. Dr. David MacKenzie, Asian Vegetable Research Development Center, Taiwan.

An attempt at the characterization of the physical environment of the Asian rice land. Dr. Hayao Fukui, Center for Southeast Asian Studies, Kyoto University, Bangkok Liaison Office.

The concepts of agricultural biology in tropical agriculture. Dr. T. A. Taylor, dean of agriculture, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Agrarian reform—the Philippine experience. Fr. Frank Lynch, Institute of Philippine Culture, Ateneo de Manila University, Quezon City.

Panel discussion on flood rehabilitation program. Dr. Domingo M. Lantican, vice president in charge, UPCA, Gov. F. T. San Luis, Laguna; Mr. Vicente C. Lavidés, Jr., general manager, Laguna Lake Development Authority, and Sen. Helena C. Benitez, Republic of the Philippines.

Conservative farm strategies in Hagonoy, Davao del Sur. Mr. James C. Stewart, soil sciences division, Ateneo de Davao Colleges, Davao City.

Agronomic aspects of the multiple cropping world. Dr. Harwood.

Relation of language behavior to economic behavior. Dr. Carol H. Molony, Stanford University.

Varietal differences in photosynthetic efficiency in the rice plant. Dr. Y. Ohno, visiting scientist, IRRI.

New directions in development economics research. Dr. Harry Oshima, visiting professor, School of Economics, University of the Philippines, Quezon City.

Supervised credit and compact farming. Mr. Mariano Gimenez, associate

bed area of the varietal improvement department and facilitating the flow of water during the rainy season. By next dry season, all the low spots will have been covered and leveled.

The seed processing plant is now in operation. Two steel tanks, each with a gravity-flow grain cleaner, were constructed and installed. Seed cleaning is now much faster and it requires a minimum number of laborers.

Zinc phosphide and Warfarin were used to control rats in addition to dusting rat burrows with Cyanogas and use of the electric fence. We also provided poisoned baits to the owners of neighboring farms and allowed them to use the foot duster during weekends to minimize the movement of rats to the IRRI farm.

Information services

During the year we distributed 55,000 publications to our mailing list in response to requests from individuals and agencies. The total includes 28,000 copies of *Field problems of tropical rice* in English and 7,000 copies in Vietnamese. The Bangladesh Rice Research Institute completed a Bengali translation of *Field problems* which we will publish with funds from the Bangladesh Ecumenical Relief and Rehabilitation Service. The All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project is publishing a Hindi edition. A Tagalog translation is in preparation.

A nontechnical account of some of IRRI's achievements, *IR8 and beyond*, was distributed to guests at IRRI's 10th anniversary celebration and to others. The booklet is entirely illustrated with color photographs. The papers presented at the anniversary celebration were published in *Rice, science, and man*.

Papers from the 1971 rice breeding conference were published in a 760-page book, *Rice breeding*. This

is the first major symposium to be published and distributed entirely by IRRI. Previous symposiums were published and distributed by the Johns Hopkins University Press for IRRI. We are now handling the distribution of the earlier volumes, too.

To help readers find subjects discussed in several different chapters of the annual report we added a subject index to the *Annual report for 1971*.

Other publications issued during the year: *Rice virus diseases*, a 134-page review of knowledge about virus diseases and their vectors; *Training manual for rice production*, a 141-page book intended for instructors conducting training courses for extension specialists; *Manual for field collectors of rice*, a 32-page booklet designed to help scientists collecting wild and primitive varieties of rice in the field; *Production of seedlings*, a 24-page booklet which is the first of a planned series of "how-to-do-it" booklets based on information in the *Training manual*. We also prepared several instruction manuals for machines designed by the agricultural engineering department.

Techniques for field experiments with rice: Layout/sampling/sources of error is in press.

Nearly 8,000 visitors received tours of IRRI facilities and our demonstration plot. The demonstration plot contains simple rice experiments that show obvious contrasts that laymen can easily grasp, such as a semi-dwarf variety growing side-by-side with a traditional variety, chemical control of weeds, and differences in varieties' resistance to insects.

Library and documentation center

Bibliographical services. The 1971 Supplement to *The International Bibliography of Rice Research* was

published in 1972 and the 5-year cumulative index to the 1966-1970 bibliography supplements was completed. The 1971 Supplement contains nearly 2,800 references to scientific rice literature selected from numerous sources, with the bulk taken from journals published in 1971. References left out in the 1966-1970 supplements were also included. The supplement includes literature written in 24 languages.

As in previous supplements, the citations in the 1971 supplement are arranged according to subject matter, and an author index and a manually produced keyword index are provided.

The 5-year index, which is divided into three sections—author, subject, and geographic—is a comprehensive guide to world literature on rice reported in the 1966 through 1970 supplements. It is the second cumulated index; the first covered the years 1961 to 1965.

Growth of the collection. Nearly 3,500 books and pamphlets were acquired from various sources, bringing the total collection of monographs to 31,300. In addition, 181 serial titles were added during the year. Maps, translations, and microfilms were also added to the collection.

Reference and circulation. There was a marked increase in the number of reference inquiries received, particularly from Malaysia, India, and Ceylon. Rice breeding and genetics outranked all other subject requests. Many of the requests were for Japanese literature.

director, Department of Rural Banks, Central Bank of the Philippines. Concepts of pest management. Dr. Dyck. Congress and economic development. Mr. Jose E. Romero, Jr., Congressional Economic Planning Office, Republic of the Philippines. The phytotron. Dr. Vergara. New promises and new dilemmas for the rice farmers of Klaten, Central Java. Mr. John Ihalauw, Research Institute in Social Sciences, Satja Wajana Christian University, Salatiga, Java. Population growth in Asia: the crucial challenge. Mr. Brent Ashabrenner, associate representative, Ford Foundation, Manila. Food grain crisis—1973. Dr. Barker.

Requests for short bibliographies on specific subjects, and for information on library problems dealing with organization, administration, and information retrieval were also received.

Within IRRI, 28,900 books and journals were borrowed. Use within the library is not measured.

Other library activities. To keep scientists abreast of current literature, the library continued to circulate photocopies of tables of contents of newly received journals. This service resulted in requests for loans of these journals, and photocopies of articles appearing in them.

The institute staff is notified of the availability of new information relative to their fields of specialization and interests through a monthly listing of books, translations, reprints, and new serial titles.

Copies of translations of foreign language rice literature were sent regularly to the National Agricultural Library, U.S. Department of Agriculture, where they are eventually listed in the *Bibliography of Agriculture* to make them known to rice scientists.

Index

- Acetylene reduction
 - effect of air on, 36
 - and nitrogen fixation, 37
- Amylose content. *See also* Eating quality
 - breeding for, 153
 - screening methods for, 16
 - survey of rice varieties, 16
- Anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay, 37
- Autecology of *Scirpus maritimus*, 218
- Bacteria
 - nitrogen-fixing, 38
- Bacterial blight disease
 - breeding program, 151
 - inoculation technique, 127
 - selective medium, 132
 - varietal resistance, 129, 130
 - virulence of Philippine isolates, 131
 - yield loss, 131
- Biochemistry
 - of plant hopper damage, 17
- Blast disease
 - breeding program, 151
 - new races, 123
 - stabilizing selection, 122
 - varietal resistance, 122
- Breeding program, 148
- Broadcast rice
 - sampling, 112
 - weed control in, 92
- Brown planthoppers
 - biochemistry of damage, 17
 - causes of resistance, 169
 - competition between, and leafhoppers, 187
 - varietal resistance to, 166
- Cold tolerance
 - breeding program for, 154
 - screening for, 216
- Corn borer, 31
- Crop management
 - and multiple cropping, 23
- Cropping intensification
 - interplanting, 27
 - relay planting with rice, 27
- Crosses
 - upland-lowland, 156
- Cultural practices
 - for irrigated rice, 90
 - for rainfed paddy, 98
- Diamond-back moth, 30
- Dormancy, grain, 18
- Drought tolerance
 - lowland rice, 104
 - screening test for, 212
 - upland rice, 105, 158
- Drying and processing
 - batch drier, 76
 - centrifugal huller, 76
 - heated sand and parboiling, 74
 - hull furnace, 77
- Eating quality
 - digestibility of cooked rice starch, 16
 - fermented rice cake, 15
 - parboiled rice flakes, 14
 - puffed rice, 14
 - rice noodles, 16
 - screening methods for amylose content, 16
 - survey of rice varieties, 16
- Economics, 48
 - grain loss, 81
 - rice processing systems, 82
 - credit programs, 83
- Enzymes
 - phytase, lipase, glucanase, 18
- Fertilizer. *See also* Nitrogen fertilization
 - N, P, K, 199
 - rainfed trials, 99, 224
 - upland trials, 228
- Genetics and cytogenetics, 160
- Germination, seed, 18
- Germ plasm bank, 159
- Glucanase, 18
- Grain
 - dormancy, 18
 - nitrogen translocation from leaves to, 13
 - quality, 14, 153 (*see also* Protein content)
- Grassy stunt disease
 - breeding program, 149
 - colony of transmitters, 133
 - screening for resistance to, 144
- Green leafhoppers. *See also* Tungro virus disease
 - causes of resistance to, 169
 - competition between, and planthoppers, 187
 - varietal resistance to, 166
- Growth and temperature, 209
- Growth duration
 - breeding program for, 154
 - and soil heterogeneity, 118
 - varietal comparisons and, 119
- Growth stages
 - and water stress, 158
- Herbicides
 - for broadcast rice, 92
 - for control of perennial sedge, 93

- effect on seedlings, 14
- rained trials, 100, 226
- residues, 45
- for transplanted rice, 92
- upland trials, 102, 228
- Hybrids
 - cytology of sterility in F_2 , 162
 - intercrossing F_1 , 161
 - performance of F_3 progenies, 162
 - variability in F_2 populations, 161
- Hydrogen sulfide
 - kinetics of, 204
- Insecticides
 - cooperative trials of, 179
 - field comparisons of, 172
 - laboratory and greenhouse screening of, 170
 - and plant resistance, 180
 - prevention of virus infection, 172
 - rained trials of, 225
 - residues of, 46
 - root-zone application of, 175
 - seedling root treatments, 175
 - timing of application, 182
- Insect resistance, 167, 169. *See also insect names*
- Insects
 - identification of, 188
 - integrated control of, 179
 - management of, in multiple cropping situations, 30
 - vectors of virus diseases, 132, 134
- Iron
 - reduction, 42
 - toxicity, 197
- Irrigation. *See* Water management
- Irrigated rice
 - control of perennial sedge in, 93
 - nitrogen response in, 86
 - nitrogen sources for, 90
 - rotational irrigation, 91
 - weed control, 92
- Kinetics
 - of denitrification, 203
 - of hydrogen sulfide, 204
 - of problem soils, 190
- Leaf area
 - sampling to determine, 113
- Leaves
 - and drought resistance, 159
 - nitrogen and photosynthetic rate in, 211
 - nitrogen translocation from, to grains, 13
 - wind damage to, 217
- Leafhoppers. *See* Green leafhoppers
- Legumes
 - nitrogen fixation in, 41
- Lesion formation
 - sheath blight, 123
- Lipase, 18
- Lysine, 11, 12
- Machinery
 - batch drier, 76
 - centrifugal huller, 76
 - 8-hp to 14-hp power tiller, 70
 - 5-hp to 7-hp power tiller, 70
 - 40-hp tractor, 71
 - for heated-sand drying and parboiling, 74
 - hull furnace, 77
 - low-lift bellows pump, 80
 - multicrop, axial-flow thresher, 72
 - multihopper seeder, 80
 - planters, 79
 - PTO thresher, 72
 - Savonius rotor windmill, 74
 - stripper harvester, 73
 - table thresher, 81
- Mechanization
 - economics of, 81
- Metabolism, protein, 12
- Mineral transformations, 42
- Mung bean, 22
- Multiple cropping, 22, 228
- Nephotettix virescens*, 183. *See also* Green leafhoppers; Tungro virus disease; Virus diseases
- Nilaparvata lugens*, 185. *See also* Brown planthoppers; Grassy stunt disease; Virus diseases
- Nitrogen
 - absorption, 12
 - leaf, and photosynthetic rate, 211
 - losses in flooded soils, 202
 - fertilizer sources, 90
 - residual effect of, 116
 - transformation, 41
 - translocation from leaves to grains, 13
- Nitrogen fertilization
 - economic analysis of, 48
 - farmers' fields, 87
 - in irrigated rice, 86
 - long-term fertility experiments, 87
 - and moisture stress, 58
 - in rained paddy, 95, 99, 224
 - and upland trials, 228
- Nitrogen fixation, 36
 - by aquatic plants, 40
 - in legumes, 41
- N, P, K, fertilization
 - and zinc deficiency, 199
- Organic matter
 - transformation of, 44
- Panicle
 - protein content variability in, 11
- Philippines
 - agriculture, 1948 to 1969, 68
 - barriers to higher yield and farm income, 55
 - rice production in Central Luzon, 1980, 67
- Phosphorus deficiency, 198
- Photoperiod, 215

- response of *S. maritimus* to, 220
- Photosynthesis, 211, 212
- Phytase, 18
- Planthoppers. *See* Brown planthoppers
- Population dynamics
 - of *Nephotettix virescens*, 183
 - of *Nilaparvata lugens*, 185
 - of stem borers, 188
- Protein
 - metabolism, 12
 - quality, 10
- Protein content
 - breeding program, 152
 - and grain properties, 12
 - inheritance of, 160
 - and lysine content of brown and milled rice, 11
 - variability within a panicle, 11
- Rainfed rice
 - cultural practices for broadcast-seeded, 98
 - fertilizers, 99, 224
 - herbicides, 100, 226
 - insecticides, 225
 - management levels, 226
 - and multiple cropping, 31, 228
 - nitrogen response, 95
 - seeding on unpuddled bunded soil, 227
 - varieties, 95, 223
 - water balance in farmers' fields, 96
 - water economy on puddled and nonpuddled soils, 96
- Resistance. *See also* Varietal resistance
 - biochemistry of brown planthopper damage, 17
- Root system
 - and drought tolerance, 159
- Scirpus maritimus*, 218–220
- Seed germination, 18
- Seedlings
 - effect of herbicides on, 14
- Sheath blight disease, 123, 124
 - chemical control of, 127
 - varietal resistance, 125–127
- Soils
 - aerobic, 190, 194
 - acid sulfate, 192
 - alkalinity, 191, 196
 - calcareous, 193
 - chemical kinetics of problem, 190
 - flooded, nitrogen losses in, 202
 - heterogeneity, 116
 - hydrogen sulfide in, 204
 - iron toxicity, 197
 - latosolic clay, 192
 - maahas clay, 190
 - molecular nitrogen in, 39
 - reduced, 192, 197
 - salinity, 191, 196
 - seeding on unpuddled bunded, 227
 - varietal resistance to injurious, 194
 - water economy on puddled and nonpuddled, 96
 - zinc deficiency, 199–202
- Soybeans, 23
- Spikelet formation
 - effect of CO₂ on, 208
- Spikelet number
 - and temperature, 210
- Starch
 - digestibility of cooked, 16
 - synthesis of, 17
- Statistical methods
 - determining yield in spacing trials, 115
 - estimating stem borer damage, 108
 - replanting dead hills, 115
 - sampling in broadcast plots, 112
 - sampling to determine leaf area, 113
- Stem borers
 - breeding program, 151
 - estimating damage of, 108
 - population dynamics of, 188
- Stomatal response to moisture stress, 213
- Striped borer
 - varietal resistance to, 164
- Sulfur transformation, 43
- Sweet potato, 23
- Temperature and growth, 209
- Tillering, 160, 210
- Transplanted rice
 - weed control in, 92
- Tungro virus disease. *See also* Green leafhoppers
 - breeding program, 148
 - epidemiology of, 133–139
 - new vector of, 132
 - screening for resistance to, 144
 - improved screening method, 139–144
- Upland rice
 - breeding program, 156
 - drought tolerance, 105, 158
 - fertilizer trial, 228
 - herbicide trials, 102, 228
 - and multiple cropping, 228
 - varieties, 101, 157, 227
 - weed competition, 102
- Varietal collection, 159
- Varietal resistance
 - to blast, 122
 - to bacterial blight, 129, 130
 - breeding program for multiple resistance, 152
 - combining disease resistance, 145
 - combining resistance to several pests, 167
 - to injurious soils, 194
 - causes of, to leafhoppers and planthoppers, 169
 - to leafhoppers, 166
 - to planthoppers, 166
 - to sheath blight, 125–127
 - to striped borers, 164
 - trials for resistance to insects, 169
 - to yellow borers, 165

- to zinc deficiency, 201
- Variety trials
 - rainfed, 95, 223
 - for resistance to insect pests, 169
 - upland rice, 101, 157, 227
- Virus diseases. *See also* Grassy stunt disease; Tungro virus disease; Yellow dwarf disease
 - vectors in the Philippines, 133, 134
- Water
 - varietal adaptation to different conditions, 105
- Water management, 57
 - balance in farmers' fields under rainfed conditions, 96
 - economy on puddled and nonpuddled soils, 96
 - economic performance of pumping systems, 58
 - performance of canal irrigation systems, 63
- Water stress
 - at different growth stages, 60, 158
 - and environment, 57
 - estimating yield loss with stress days, 61
 - and nitrogen response, 58
 - and reproductive processes, 159
 - stomatal response to, 213
- Weed control. *See also* Herbicides and multiple cropping, 30
- Wind
 - damage to leaves, 217
- World collection, 159
- Yellow borer
 - varietal resistance to, 165
- Yellow dwarf disease
 - new vector of, 132
- Zinc deficiency, 199, 201